

ŚRADDHĀ IN THE BHAGAVAD GĪTĀ

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By

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ABSTRACT

The *Bhagavadgītā* is an episode in the *Mahābhārata* when the climactic battle is about to begin. Here, Arjuna refuses to fight, and it is Kṛṣṇa's counsel that will finally convince him.

The issue of Arjuna's transformation has recently attracted some scholarly comment, but most scholars do not discuss the role of *śraddhā* (zeal, religious fervour, enthusiasm) in this transformation. Rao does discuss *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*, but one needs to question his conclusion that *śraddhā* is the same as *bhakti* (devotion).¹ Rao's conclusion contradicts, but does not refute, Hara's² earlier study showing that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* are different.

Given this scholarly indecision, this thesis is a theological effort to ask: What is the role of *śraddhā* in Arjuna's final acceptance of war as the necessary solution to his moral dilemma? It is my hypothesis that *śraddhā* differs from *bhakti*, and becomes the immediate cause that moves Arjuna to fight. When the *Gītā* starts, Arjuna is a devotee (*bhakta*) without *śraddhā*, and, when the *Gītā* ends, Arjuna is a devotee with *śraddhā*. That is to say, one can be dejected and still be a devotee. However, one cannot be depressed and full of *śraddhā* at the same time. This distinction between *śraddhā* and *bhakti* represents the first part of my argument. The second part is the sense I want to convey by translating *śraddhā* as 'zeal, religious fervour, soul force, or enthusiasm.' I argue that the standard translation as 'faith' hinders the effort to construct a comprehensive theology of Arjuna's transformation.

In conclusion, I intend to demonstrate that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* are different, and that when *śraddhā* is translated by a term that points to the right psychological and religious experience it explains Arjuna's decision to fight.

¹ See K. L. S. Rao, *The Concept of Śraddhā* (Patiala: Roy Publishers, 1971), and idem, "Sri Aurobindo on the Types of Sradha (Faith) in the Gita," (*Journal of Asian Literature*, V. 24, No. 1, E. Lansing, 1989).

² See Minoru Hara, "NOTE ON TWO SANSKRIT TERMS - *bhakti* and *śraddhā*" (*Indo-Iranian Journal*, VII, Hague: Mouton & Co. (1963-4), 124-145).

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The written code kills, but the Spirit gives life.

II Cor. 3:6

If you simply believe on this text, you are nothing but a fool.

Texts and scriptures are not meant to be believed, they

are meant to be *felt*. Only when you have similar

experiences, you will be able to relate to the

text, either proving or disproving it.

Ezequiel Ben Adam

To, and with, Hamsa Yogi; I hail Nārāyaṇa, Nara, Sarasvati, and Vyāsa

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I. INTRODUCTION

In this chapter I will introduce the general subject of *śraddhā* in the *Bhavavad Gītā* – a Scripture which consists of 700 verses and describes the moment of the *Mahābhārata* (constituted by approximately 100,000 verses) when the climactic battle is about to begin. In the *Gītā*, Arjuna, the foremost warrior of the *Pāṇḍavas*, the side of the family portrayed as righteous, refuses to fight. The sight of his *Kaurava* relatives and friends across the battlefield disheartens him. Ultimately, due to his dialogue in the form of a series of kind-hearted theological arguments with Kṛṣṇa, Arjuna is able to renounce his attachment to that convenient inactive state of *aśraddadhāna* (one without *śraddhā*) and fights on the battlefield.

The *Gītā* deals with this shift in Arjuna from an *aśraddadhāna* to a *śraddhāvanta* (one possessed of *śraddhā*). According to Hindu theologians, the *Gītā* synthesizes through its 18 *yogas* or chapters the different views on the science of being, or *ātmavidyā*, voicing through Arjuna the questions about human nature with its ordinary sentiments, and bringing forth from Kṛṣṇa the secrets of the ‘selfless’ self, or *ātman*. Arjuna first confesses his ignorance of the best course of action, and then expresses his desire to learn (BhG 2.7). Then, he is led to reflect on his phenomenological dissatisfaction related to the ‘*karmaṇi ghore*’ or ‘terrible deeds’ (BhG 3.1-2), and to inquire about the ‘best thing to do’ or ‘*śreyas*’ (BhG 5.1). Then, as a result of his will to fit into the divine *praxis*, or *yoga*, as well as his will to know about the divine (BhG 10.17-8), he reaches the

promised (BhG 9.5) revelation (BhG 11.9-34) of the universal form of the divine (*viśvarūpa-darśana-yoga*). Finally, he decides to adopt the practice known as *niṣkāmakarmayoga*, which represents engagement on the battlefield of righteousness for the sake of social welfare, unmindful of personal motives (BhG 18.73).

This account of Arjuna’s transformation in the *Gītā* has recently attracted some scholarly comment, but most of those scholars do not discuss the role of the term ‘*śraddhā*’ in this process.¹ K. L. S. Rao² discusses *śraddhā*, but dismisses its theological role by concluding that in the *Gītā* *śraddhā* is essentially the same as *bhakti* (devotion). In drawing this conclusion Rao contradicts Minoru Hara’s earlier study,³ which, after a careful review of a number of sources, concluded that the ritual atmosphere surrounding the concept *śraddhā* is “in striking contrast to the theistic aspect of *bhakti*” (Hara 1963-4, 140). We will come back to these two scholars shortly.

In the light of this unsatisfactory state of scholarship, this thesis asks: What is the role of *śraddhā* in Arjuna’s final acceptance of war as the necessary solution to his moral dilemma? It is my hypothesis that the concept of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* plays a central role in the process of Arjuna’s transformation from an inactive to an active person. It follows

¹ For instance, A. Sharma points out that “the *Bhagavadgītā* starts with Arjuna having certain doubts about pursuing a particular course of action – that of engaging in battle.” Moreover, he adds, the *Bhagavadgītā* “ends as soon as Arjuna indicates his willingness to pursue that course of action, namely, to engage in battle.” Arvind Sharma, “The *Bhagavadgītā*: a Mīmāṃsīc Approach” (*The Journal of Studies in the Bhagavadgītā* vol. X-XI, 1990-91), 46. Madeleine Biarreau, when she discusses Arjuna’s vision in Chapter 11 of the *Gītā*, suggests that they both, Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna, are using battle as a ritual of entry into *sannyāsa*. Madeleine Biarreau, “Etudes de mythologie hindoue,” (3, *Bulletin de l’Ecole Française d’Extrême-Orient*, LVIII, (1971), 17-89.

² See K. L. S. Rao, *The Concept of Śraddhā* (Patiala: Roy Publishers, 1971), and idem, “Sri Aurobindo on the Types of Sradha (Faith) in the Gita,” (*Journal of Asian Literature*, Vol. 24, No. 1, E. Lansing, 1989).

³ See Minoru Hara, “NOTE ON TWO SANSKRIT TERMS - *bhakti* and *śraddhā*” (*Indo-Iranian Journal*, VII, Hague: Mouton & Co. 1963-1964), 124-145.

that *śraddhā* differs from – and is more central in the argument than – *bhakti* (devotion, longing, faith), and represents the immediate cause that moves Arjuna to fight. When the *Gītā* starts, Arjuna is a devotee (*bhakta*) without *śraddhā*, and, when the *Gītā* ends, Arjuna is a devotee with *śraddhā*. That is to say, one can be dejected, like Arjuna, and still be a devotee. However, one cannot be said to be depressed and full of *śraddhā* at the same time. So, if the *Gītā* starts with Arjuna showing *bhakti*, but not *śraddhā*, and if the *Gītā* ends with Arjuna showing both, then *śraddhā* and *bhakti* are different.

I will argue that what moves Arjuna to decide to fight is the *śraddhā* (zeal, religious fervour, enthusiasm) that arises as a soul force in his own being (*ātman*). I will argue that devotion (*bhakti*) to Kṛṣṇa as a personal god plays only an instrumental and secondary role in this process. I recognize that in later devotional (*Purāṇic*) literature the term *śraddhā* sometimes fades in importance, and religious experience starts to be described by the more dogmatic term *bhakti*. In these contexts *bhakti* is sometimes set forth as the primary means to salvation, and the place of ‘action’ is reduced. Some scholars see this development as a widespread sectarian reform called Bhakti Hinduism. Whatever one might think of these post-*Gītā* sectarian developments, I will try to show that the *Gītā* is theologically closer to a ritual tradition coming out of the *Veda*.

In the following sections of this chapter, I will outline the set of questions raised by the text of the *Gītā*, present the plan for the establishment of my thesis, and discuss the methodology employed.

I.1. Research Questions and Mode of Procedure

My central questions are: (a) Considering the religious terminology of the *Vedic* and the Epic periods, how does the term *śraddhā* evolve? (b) What does the term seem to mean in the *Gṛā*? (c) How does *śraddhā* contribute to Arjuna’s final acceptance of war as the solution for his moral dilemma? (d) What are the other theological implications of Arjuna’s obtaining of *śraddhā*? and (e) How does *śraddhā* relate to other key concepts, like *saṃnyāsa* and *bhakti* in the *Gṛā*?

In order to answer the research question (a) “considering the *Vedic* and the Epic periods, how does the term *śraddhā* evolve?” Chapter II (THE EARLY TRADITIONS’ USE OF THE TERM *ŚRADDHĀ*) discusses the issue of continuity between the *Vedic* and Epic periods. Concrete cases of the early uses of *śraddhā* are cited, and the link between *śrāddha* and *śraddhā* is explored. The question on the continuity of meaning of the term ‘*śraddhā*’ is more complex than it might first appear. On one level it might be understood as a question of conceptual continuity, and we need only ask if the contexts in which the term is used have changed. There are, however, other issues about continuity within a religious tradition. What is the religious status of the different texts? Secondly, what does it mean that a *Smṛiti* text such as the *Gṛā*, is understood as only an interpretation of a *Śruti* text such as the *R̥g Veda*? What does it mean that a concept such as ‘*śraddhā*’ is linked with the ritual duty of *śrāddha* or funerary rite? Which would properly be interpreted in terms of the other? In order to address all these questions, the chapter is organized into four sections.

In section II.1 (Earliest References to the Term ‘*śraddhā*’) I examine some *Vedic* occurrences of the verbal forms of *śrad-dhā*, which can be translated as ‘to trust’. I also investigate occurrences of *śraddhā* as a noun, which can mean ‘trust or confidence’ – or in Köhler’s⁴ translations mean: ‘loyalty’ (*Treue*), ‘devotion, dedication’ (*Hingabe*), and ‘enthusiastic engagement’ (*Spendefreudigkeit*).

In section II.2 (The Hymn to *Śraddhā*) I discuss the Hymn to *Śraddhā*, which appears in *Rg Veda* X, 151, and is also found in *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* II, 8, 8, 6-8. In this unusual Hymn *śraddhā* is personified as a goddess *Śraddhā*. *Śraddhā* also appears in MBh 1.60.10-5, as one of the ten wives of *Dharma*. We will see why *śraddhā* or the attitude of ‘trust’ and ‘engagement’ is an essential component present in any righteous deed. For, “where there is no *Śraddhā* there is no *Dharma*” (Shastri, 1963, 369).

In Section II.3 (*Śrāddha* and *Śraddhā*) I discuss the rites of *śrāddha*. I explore the link between *śrāddha* and *śraddhā*, and show how this link points toward one issue present in every religion. Not only do funerary rites bring up theories related with the final destiny of the individual and the immortality of the soul, but they also raise the question of the individual’s relation to the whole universe. R. B. Pandey⁵ argues that among the factors that brought the *śrāddha* rites into existence is the idea that death represents the separation of the soul from the body. He then helps us to see how this idea

⁴ See Hans Werbin Köhler, “*Śraddhā in der vedischen und alt-buddhistischen Literatur*” (Ph.D. Diss., Göttingen, 1948). The Dissertation was finally published in 1973: *ŚRAD-DHĀ in der vedischen und alt-buddhistischen Literatur* (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner Verlag, 1973). Köhler makes an exhaustive study of the *Vedic* concept of *śraddhā*, and examines in detail the relation between the funeral rites or *śrāddha* and *śraddhā*. His view is that the rites of *śrāddha* are supposed to develop understanding in the living as well as to help the deceased reach the realm of the *pitṛs*.

⁵ Raj Bali Pandey, *Hindu Saṃskāras – Socio-Religious Study of the Hindu Sacraments* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 2nd ed., 1969).

provides a new meaning for the role of death ritual, in that it serves as an opportunity for the development of *śraddhā* in oneself. D. R. Shastri's⁶ studies show that the ritual of fire (*Agnaukaraṇa*) is as old as the *R̥g Veda*, and the ritual of *Piṇḍaḍāna* (offering of rice balls to the *manes*) is as old as the *Yajurveda*. Finally, in concluding this section I consider the work of D. Urquhart,⁷ who as early as the mid-nineteenth century reflected on the way these forms of ancestral worship differentiated Indian from Western thought.

In section II.4 (A Scholarly Dispute on Continuity) I have two central goals: to frame the controversy around the continuity argument in terms of the relation between the terms *bhakti* and *śraddhā*,⁸ and to highlight the continuity of meaning of the term *śraddhā* through the different periods. I discuss first those scholars who work with the traditional assumption of continuity. I start with Mrinal Das Gupta's 1930 essay on the terms *bhakti* and *śraddhā*,⁹ showing how it anticipates some of Minoru Hara's later findings. Next I consider how Minoru Hara started the contemporary controversy around the concept of *śraddhā* in 1963-4, when he published the innocently titled article "Note on Two Sanskrit Terms – *bhakti* and *śraddhā*." Then I compare these results with Hacker's¹⁰ discussion of Köhler's findings on *śraddhā*. Next I consider the works of

⁶ Dakshina Ranjan Shastri, *Origin and Development of the Rituals of Ancestor Worship in India* (Calcutta: Bookland Private Limited, 1963).

⁷ David Urquhart, *The Shraddha, The Keystone of The Brahminical, Buddhistic, and Arian Religions, As Illustrative of The Dogma and Duty of Adoption among the Princes and People of India* (London: Published by David Bryce, 1857).

⁸ See Das Gupta (1930, 315-333 and 487-513) and Hara (1963-4, 124-145).

⁹ Mrinal Das Gupta, "Śraddhā and Bhakti in Vedic Literature" (*Indian Quarterly* 6, 1930), 315-333 and 487-513.

¹⁰ P. Hacker, "Über den Glauben und der Religionsphilosophie des Hinduismus" (*Zeitschrift für Missionswissenschaft und Religionswissenschaft* 38, 1954), 51-66, and idem, "Śraddha" (*Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Sudasiens* 3, 1963), 151-189. *Paul Hacker Kleine Schriften* – Herausgegeben von Lambert Schmithausen Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner, 1978).

those who posit a radical discontinuity of meaning from one period to another: Rao and Bhattacharya. Finally, to sum up this scholarly dispute in relation to the state of scholarship on *śraddhā*, I draw on the findings of W. C. Smith,¹¹ who recognizes a sense of continuity in the tradition. In his *Faith and Belief*, he translates *śraddhā* as ‘faith’,¹² but he also uses Hara’s findings to support his view that *śraddhā* is more than ‘belief’. For him the term points out how a man of faith [*śraddhā*] is concerned with ceremonial works (1979, n. 51, 233). In this context I also revisit Hacker’s understanding that *Vedic śraddhā* is “the particularly religious element in all religious actions” (Hacker 1963, 188).

Chapter III (THE TERM *ŚRADDHĀ* IN THE *GĪTĀ*) is meant to answer the central research question (b) “what does the term seem to mean in the *Gītā*?” It deals with the twenty-one uses of the term *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*, and it focus on how *śraddhā* relates to the new religious questions raised in the *Gītā*. It also links these new questions with both the *Vedic* ideal of expressing oneself through external action, and the *Upaniṣadic* ideal of refraining from external activity.

In section III.1 (The Exegetical Plan) I introduce the issue of interpretation and point out some of the differences in the commentarial styles used in India and in the

¹¹ See Wilfred Cantwell Smith, *The Meaning and End of Religion; A New Approach to The Religious Traditions of Mankind* (New York: Macmillan, 1963); idem, *The Faith of Other Men* (New York: Harper & Row, 1972); idem, *Belief and History* (Charlottesville: University Press of Virginia, 1977); idem, *Faith and Belief* (Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 1979); idem, *Towards a World Theology: Faith and The Comparative History of Religion* (London: Macmillan, 1981), and idem, *What is scripture? A Comparative Approach* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1993).

¹² According to Smith, “*viśvāsa* was the term chosen by the Christian missionaries to render their concept of faith” (1979, n.57, 235).

West. In this context I introduce the argument of Krishna Sharma¹³ that the *Gītā* deals with a synthesis of what the West tends to divide into the two different categories of philosophy and religion. The section concludes with an analysis of what has sometimes been pejoratively called the ‘allegorical’ method.

In section III.2 (Exegesis of the Twenty-one Occurrences), I provide an exegesis of each verse where the term *śraddhā* occurs. I show how these occurrences are scattered through the text, and I consider the meaning of *śraddhā* in each verse, asking whether ‘enthusiasm’, ‘soul force’, or something else, is the better translation there.

In section III.3 (*Śraddhā* as ‘zealous soul force’ or ‘religious enthusiasm’) in the light of the results of the previous sections, I discuss my translation of *śraddhā* as ‘zeal, soul force, and religious enthusiasm’, and I distinguish between the contexts that use *śraddhā* and those that use *bhakti* in the *Gītā*. I also show how the uses of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* represents that ‘particular religious element in all religious actions’ discussed by Hacker. I make the case that when Arjuna uses the second person pronoun to refer to Kṛṣṇa, especially after his experience with the universal form in chapter 11, he is not intending the person of Kṛṣṇa, but the Universal within, the *Ātman*.

Chapter IV (A BRIEF HISTORY OF INTERPRETATION ON THE *Gītā*) is meant to answer the central research question (c) “how does *śraddhā* contribute to Arjuna’s final acceptance of war as the solution for his moral dilemma?” It discusses why Western scholarship has sometimes struggled to identify the theology of the *Gītā*,

¹³ See Krishna Sharma, *Bhakti and the Bhakti Movement – A New Perspective* (New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal, 1987).

and what problems in interpretation have come from an insistence on ignoring the transcendental¹⁴ characteristics of the text, pointed out in the classical commentaries, as well as in the modern Eastern approach to the text.

In section IV.I (Śaṅkara's *kevalajñāna* and Rāmānuja's *bhaktikarmasamuccaya*) I discuss in the light of my findings how Śaṅkara's and Rāmānuja's commentaries (*bhāṣyas*) are, in one way or another, reacting to the ancient *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*. I examine the implications of Rāmānuja's (1056 – 1137 C.E.) argument that the *Gītā* teaches that action without knowledge, or knowledge without action, cannot secure anything. Rāmānuja holds that the *Gītā* teaches the *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*¹⁵ theory, and he explains that argument with the doctrine of *Bhedabheda-vada* – or the doctrine that stresses the difference as well as the identity between *ātman* and *Brahman*. Rāmānuja radically disagrees with Śaṅkara (c. 788 to 820 C.E.) on the importance of this theory, which postulates one's deeds together with knowledge as a means to *mokṣa*.

In section IV.2 (The Western Interpretations) I review that part of the Western scholarship on the *Gītā* that has not been fully considered in the previous chapters. This review is meant as a preparation for understanding how my findings fit within more

¹⁴ I explain how I use the term 'transcendentalism' in the section I.2. Partially because missionaries mocked Theosophists intensely, 'transcendentalism' in any form has been considered suspect in Western thought.

¹⁵ This point will be made clear after we have exegeted the '*me matam*' (my teaching, understanding, thought) in BhG 3.31 which is followed by a *śraddhāvān* (one who is possessed with fervour) and disregarded by an *aśraddadhāna* (one without fervour). In the *Gītā*, both *niṣkāmakarma* (altruistic action) and *niyatam karma* (obligatory work) depend equally on *śraddhā*. The *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada* theory affirms that one cannot rely either on *jñāna* or *karma* alone for the attainment of salvation. Besides Rāmānuja, the Vedantins Bhāskara, Keśava, and Abhinavagupta, and also the Mīmāṃsakas in general hold the same view. Śaṅkara tries to refute this doctrine in his *Gītābhāṣya*, but without much success.

traditional scholarship on the *Gṛ̥ā*. This section surveys some English translations of the *Gṛ̥ā*, and shows how they have improved our understanding of the text.

In section IV.3 (The Eastern Approach: Tilak, Gandhi, and Aurobindo) I introduce the Eastern approach to the text of the *Gṛ̥ā* and discuss the modern commentaries of Tilak (1856-1920), Gandhi (1869-1948), and Aurobindo (1872 – 1950) in the light of my findings on *śraddhā*. This discussion goes on to introduce a new dimension of the meaning of *śraddhā* by demonstrating how the ritual categories of *yajñā*, *tapas*, *dāna*, etc., are in harmony with *śraddhā*.

In sum Chapters III and IV show that the basic structure of the *Gṛ̥ā* supports the argument for distinguishing *bhakti* and *śraddhā*, and therefore for clearly translating *śraddhā* differently from *bhakti*. Arising from the vital stimuli received from the soul (*ātman*) through its representative (i.e., *buddhi*, the power of forming and retaining conceptions; intellect, reason, discernment, and so on), *śraddhā* is a ‘material’ phenomenon manifested as energy in our body. This energy works through the modulations (*guṇas*) of *prakṛti*. The consequence is that in the *Gṛ̥ā śraddhā* in its *tamasic* and *rajasic* stages is acknowledged as forming part of the process leading to the ultimate salvation into which all beings are drawn. Yet, without *sattvic śraddhā*, any heroic deed (*vīrya*) becomes deaf and tyrannical. Without proper motivation, *śraddhā* becomes either *rajasic*, or *tamasic*, representing merely blind faith and dogmatism. The *Gṛ̥ā* in its chapter 16 (which deals mostly with the distinction between *daiva* and *asura* values) speaks of two classes of people – those born with *sattvic* or *daivic* endowments

(BhG 16.1-6) and those born with *asuric* (demoniac; either *rajasic* or *tamasic*) qualities (BhG 16.7-20). This dual understanding based on the distinction between *daiva* (divine) and *asura* (demonic) is relativized in chapter 17, where the context of the three *guṇas* (qualities) allows Kṛṣṇa to present the convergent path which leads from an evil (*asat*) existence to a truthful (*sat*) one.

After having finished the exegesis of all occurrences of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* and substantiated the arguments for my proposed translation, in Chapter V (THE *GĪTĀ* IN THE *MAHĀBHĀRATA*) I discuss further the theological implications of Arjuna's obtaining *śraddhā*. Here I present the core discussion about *śraddhā* and Arjuna's final decision to fight in the context of the *Mahābhārata*, and provide a comprehensive theology of Arjuna's transformation through four main sections.

In the section V.1 (A Polyphonic Perception) I evaluate the context of the *Gītā* in terms of Mikhail Bakhtin's (1895-1975) definition of polyphony and philosophy of action. Mikhail Bakhtin has brought to the literary field the concept of polyphony, in order to designate the effect of two or more concurrent and harmonizing voices. He defines the work of Dostoievski, for instance, as a new genre, where the different voices appear in the narrative with the same authority, in an interesting display of democratic thinking, where there is no space for a central ideology with its last word. The idea behind his conception is that in any statement there are at least two voices, which make the narrative dialogic, even when there is no dialogue. Seeing the characters of *Mahābhārata* in terms of the Bakhtian concepts, therefore, helps the understanding of the *Gītā*'s philosophy of the act. For, the *Mahābhārata* gives equal voice to the *Pāṇḍavas*

and *Kauravas*, despite all their antagonism.¹⁶ This strategy comes to a climax with the events that lead to the war, which is about to start. At this point Kṛṣṇa talks to Arjuna in the *Gītā* about human activity in terms of a philosophy of action. Hence, the Bakhtian concepts are of help in explaining Kṛṣṇa’s evaluation of the two paths of going out (*pravṛtti*) and return (*nivṛtti*): although they seem to be separate and opposite, representing ‘the paths of action’ and that of ‘non-action’, they constitute in reality the two aspects of that one path based on *ātman*.

In the section V.2 (Death and Dying) I show how Arjuna’s transformation in the *Gītā* is set within the general structure of the *Mahābhārata*. Central to the structure of the *Mahābhārata* is the link one recognizes between Arjuna’s discovery of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* – a subsection of the *Bhīṣmaparvan* (The Book of Bhīṣma) – and the heroic ancestor Bhīṣma’s *śrāddha* rites (death rituals) that follow in the *Aṃuśāsanaparvan* (The Book of Instructions). The *śrāddha* rite involves a ritual which bonds people to the deceased by *śraddhā*, or religious trust.¹⁷ What the epic is about is how this bond defines the relation of Arjuna and Bhīṣma. As a form of ancestor-worship, which involves the trustful casting of sacrificial materials into the fire, *śrāddha* rites are meant to define the multi-generational household. Performed at the death of a relative and thereafter for a time, these rites are believed to help the ancestral spirit in its progress in the different worlds, but also to help the younger generation have the faith to carry on. In the *Gītā* Arjuna

¹⁶ Bhīṣma, for instance, is described as having at least as much value as any of the *Pāṇḍavas*.

¹⁷ I do not want to decide at the outset which English term for *śraddhā* is the best – fervour, soul force, or enthusiasm. I just want to point out that these terms can translate *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*. As for myself, I prefer to treat *śraddhā* as that most fundamental category that should not even be translated. As we will see, in the *Gītā* *śraddhā* arises with the negating of the *ahaṃkāra* and the awakening of *ātman*.

refers to this practice in BhG 1.42, where he complains to Kṛṣṇa that deprived of rites of rice (*piṇḍa*) and water (*udaka*) the ancestors (*pitaras* or *manes*) indeed would fall. And we know that at that point without recovering *śraddhā* he would have failed in his duty. The common Hindu statement, quoted by Shastri, “*Śraddhā* is the basis of *Śrāddha*—*śraddhā śrāddhe yato mūlam*” (1963, 390), provides the underlying theological frame for structuring the story that links the *Gītā* with the larger structure of the *Mahābhārata*.

In the section V.3 (A Gender and Caste Theological Perspective) I discuss how the understanding of the role of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* reveals Vyāsa’s (the author and the character) theological perspective on caste and gender in the *Gītā* as well as in the *Mahābhārata*. For, the tension of the epic is built over issues related to gender and caste, whereas the solutions proposed in the *Gītā* are all related to the way we deal with such issues. Caste and gender represent qualities that belong to our material structure, and go with the class named ‘*ahaṅkāra*’. That is to say, on the one side, the *Mahābhārata* is about the conflicts of interest arising from everyone’s *ahaṅkāra* or ego, involving their gender and caste biased views. On the other side, the *Gītā* discusses how *ātmic* detachment and altruism are triggered through *śraddhā*, which enables one to take the righteous deeds to the heart (*ātman*). This section, therefore, shows how these topics are related through *śraddhā*. In the *Mahābhārata* characters learn how ethical values become possible in those who place gender and caste values second to the main goal of attaining *Brahman*. In the *Gītā* Kṛṣṇa (perhaps as Vyāsa’s alterego) shows how all kinds of prejudice belong to that which dies – the material body, and not to the *ātman*, which is

neither male nor female, and does not recognize any *varṇāśrama* hierarchical classification.

Finally, in the section V.4 (The Role of *Śraddhā* in Solving Moral Dilemmas) I discuss the role of *śraddhā* in solving Arjuna's moral dilemma. Here I make use of two other important characters of the *Mahābhārata* – Yudhiṣṭira and Karṇa. *Śraddhā* is essential to understanding Yudhiṣṭira, the *Dharma* King. The display of *śraddhā* is what differentiates Arjuna and Yudhiṣṭira from their brother Karṇa, who stubbornly refuses to move from his *ahaṃkāric* considerations. Yudhiṣṭira's one-pointed focus on *dharma* enables him to endure, out of his *śraddhā*, even the *śrāddha* rites of thousands of slain kings. Karṇa, on the other side, is unable to change his mind, because he does not want to do anything unpleasant to Duryodhana, not even when he knows that position to be wrong. The scene of the fight between Arjuna and Karṇa brings the contrast to light. The pair constituted by Arjuna and Kṛṣṇa is based on a mutual trusting relation, while the relation of Karṇa with his charioteer, Śālya, is one of total lack of *śraddhā*.

In chapter VI, I present my conclusions. This final chapter also reflects on the wider implications of my findings. The chapter is structured to show the logical steps involved in establishing the centrality of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*.

In the section VI.1 (*Ātma-Yoga Mārga: the Gītā in the Light of Śraddhā*) I present a reinterpretation of the *Gītā* in the light of *śraddhā*. I also show the way *śraddhā* is linked with other related concepts such as *saṃnyāsa* (renouncing). The discussion of *saṃnyāsa* (renouncing) in chapter 18 of the *Gītā* is directly linked with the development

of the concept of *śraddhā* in chapter 17. I argue that *śraddhā* and *saṁnyāsa*, as defined in the *Gītā*, are two parts of the same process. While *śraddhā* characterizes the subjective side of the spiritual path that occurs within human experience, *saṁnyāsa* characterizes the objective response of that person to life in the world. The first is the soul force to reach beyond the mundane, while the second is the decision to renounce one's ties with that world. Furthermore, I make it clear that if *śraddhā* were understood as a synonym of *bhakti*, or as a simple act of faith and devotion, it would not move Arjuna to decide to fight. What does move him is *śraddhā* as something beyond faith and devotion – something like 'self-motivated joy *when in the line of an authentic duty*'.

Precisely how *śraddhā* works as a key factor in Arjuna's final decision to fight is fully explained in terms of his specific religious experience, through the perfect balance of his 'spirituality' and 'materiality'. I then demonstrate this process in terms of the five step argument (*avayava-s*)¹⁸ of Indian logic: In section VI.2 (*Pratijñā*, or the hypotheses to be proved) I deal with my working hypotheses – that *śraddhā* is responsible for moving Arjuna from non-action to action, and means 'soul force' or that religious enthusiasm capable of putting love in action. In section VI.3 (*Hetu*, or the logical arguments) I present the reasons I have to believe so; that is to say, because the *Gītā* starts with Arjuna in the state of an *aśraddadhāna*, and ends with Arjuna's display of the

¹⁸ I am following the complete syllogistic expression (*nyāya-prayoga*), called inference for others (*parārthānumāna*), which consists of the five members (*avayava-s*) shown below:

1. *pratijñā*: statement of the proposition to be proved; e.g. the mountain has fire.
2. *hetu*: statement of the reason; e.g. because it has smoke.
3. *udāharaṇa*: the exemplification or statement of the universal proposition along with the instance; e.g. wherever there is smoke there is fire, as in the hearth.
4. *upanaya*: statement of the presence of the mark; e.g. there is smoke on the mountain.
5. *nigamana*: conclusion proved; e.g. therefore, this mountain is fiery.

highest form of *śraddhā*. In section VI.4 (*Udāharaṇa*, or some concrete examples) I provide textual evidence that wherever the term *śraddhā* is discussed in the main *Śruti* and *Smṛiti* texts, it appears with the same essential meaning. In the section VI.5 (*Upanaya*, or the bringing near to the master-conclusion) I show that the mark of *śraddhā* is decisively present in Arjuna's final choice to undertake his ritual duty. And in section VI.6 (*Nigamana*, or the final summing up) I conclude that *śraddhā* is the main category for the understanding of the *Gṛ̥ā*'s theology.

Throughout the final chapter I reaffirm the distinction between *śraddhā* and *bhakti*, and justify the sense I want to convey by my translation of *śraddhā* as soul force or enthusiasm. I also deal with the moral question about war.¹⁹ Although in the context of the *Mahābhārata* Kṛṣṇa appears as the *Pāṇḍavas*' ambassador of peace, at the moment of the *Gṛ̥ā* he is the one who reminds Arjuna that war had already been declared and that the fighting is, therefore, imminent and inevitable. He consoles Arjuna and reminds him that he would be morally justified in participating in that war²⁰ if he managed to fight out of *sattvic śraddhā*. In that spirit his participation would be an act of *saṅḡyāsa* (renunciation) involving a sense of self-sacrifice, performed for the sake of God,²¹ and for the welfare of the world. The point Kṛṣṇa makes is meant to distinguish between the *Kauravas*' and the *Pāṇḍavas*' attitudes toward war.

¹⁹ See K. N. Upadhyaya, "The *Bhagavad Gṛ̥ā* on War and Peace" (Phil. of East and West, vol. XIX, No. 2, April 1969). Upadhyaya poses the following question: "Should we then say that the *Gṛ̥ā* preaches war and violence without compunction, and shows no respect or regard for life?" (161)

²⁰ This is an important point, and it has confused many scholars. At the moment of the *Gṛ̥ā* the issue of just war (Latin: *bellum justum*) is not at stake anymore. Not even the justification for going to war (Latin: *jus in bello*) is in discussion, for war has already been declared. The point Kṛṣṇa is trying to make to Arjuna in the *Gṛ̥ā* is perhaps more of what Westerners would identify as *Jus in Bello* (Justification in War).

²¹ I expect to relate the concepts of *śraddhā* and *saṅḡyāsa* in the *Gṛ̥ā* with the moral dilemmas of war.

When the motivation for war is disguised as well intentioned or, recognized as for crude self-interest (*svārtha*), *śraddhā* is said to be, respectively, *rajasic* and *tamasic*. Religious disguises such as ‘war on evil’, ‘holy war’, ‘Crusades’, and so on, might really be a disguise to act exclusively in one’s own self-interest.²² As Arjuna eventually saw, action can, however, also arise from *sattvic śraddhā*.

I.2. The *Gītā* as a Scripture on *Niṣkāmakarmayoga*

This section develops my argument that the *Gītā* reveals itself as a Scriptural text on *niṣkāmakarmayoga*. This argument involves four controversial issues: (a) are Gandhi and the others who use allegory to interpret the *Gītā* completely wrong? (b) should one approach the *Gītā* as a Scripture? (c) is the *Gītā* a single text? and (d) is the *Gītā* a treatise on theism where *śraddhā* means faith?

Gandhi has shown that a life based on the *Gītā*’s *niṣkāmakarmayoga* is possible. Furthermore, the West, as stated by Sharpe,²³ has been persuaded by Gandhi’s ethical personality that the *Gītā* is the scripture that stands closest to the Sermon on the Mount (52). However, when it comes to Gandhi’s interpretation of the *Gītā*, some scholars are

²² I do not think that the *Gītā* is a naive expression of an ethics of intentions. The *Gītā* does not enforce any reward-punishment mechanism to develop or improve one’s ‘intentions’, but it rather casts some light on the issue of human nature to help one to improve one’s own motivation, or motives for acting. And that is why the *Gītā* is also said to introduce the theological *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada* argument, which is directly related to the ethical question of how to act. For, ‘intentional’ means done on purpose, especially a selfish one. ‘Motive’, however, as the reason for acting’, represents that motivation or enthusiasm which urges a person to act in a certain way. In the *Gītā*, Kṛṣṇa provides strong reasons for Arjuna becoming himself motivated, despite Arjuna’s good intentions when considering not fighting.

²³ Eric J. Sharpe, “Western Images of the Bhagavadgita, 1885-1985” (JSAL 23, 2, 1991), 47-57.

quick to point out that his relationship to the *Gītā* was feeble, for he was not even a scholar. Sanskritists in general have disregarded those, like Gandhi,²⁴ who, not only addressed the *Gītā* as a Scripture, but also accepted it as a sacred guide. That is to say, two hundred years after Wilkins²⁵ first translation of the *Gītā* into English there is still no agreement among scholars about how to read this text and evaluate those, like Gandhi, who represented a living *Gītā*.

Remembering that the West has created many mistaken images of the *Gītā* due to the influence of its missionaries, who have especially condemned the allegorical interpretation of the Theosophists,²⁶ perhaps, we should ask the narrower question in what sense is Gandhi's understanding a *sensus allegoricus*.²⁷ For, the *Gītā* does seem to

²⁴ See J. I. Bakker, *Gandhi and the Gita* (Toronto: Canadian Scholar's Press Inc., 1993). As he puts it, "Sanskritists have not seen any particular reason to turn to Gandhi's work on the *Gītā*, since it is assumed that professional Sanskrit scholars have done much better work" (289).

²⁵ Charles Wilkins, a merchant employed by the East India Company, which was in operation in Calcutta since 1765, produced the first English translation of the *Gītā* in 1785. Then followed the translations of Sir William Jones, the founder of the Asiatic Society in Bengal in 1784, H. T. Colebrooke, and H. H. Wilson.

²⁶ In Sharpe's words, "[For Theosophists,] Behind the world's sacred writings there is one single message concerning the relationship of soul and body, and the powers available to the soul when set free from bodily limitations and constraints. Before 1900, almost everything published on the *Gītā* under the Theosophical auspices was written by Hindus – T. Subba Row, whose influential book *The Philosophy of the Bhagavad Gītā* was delivered as lectures in 1886, Mohini Mohun Chatterjee's translations of 1887, and Annie Besant's translation (1904), now canonical in Theosophical circles" (49). The allegorical method reveals the *Gītā* to be the perfect allegory of the inner struggle going on in human nature. In the words of Sharpe, "All the *dramatis personae* of the BG represent human characteristics." Dhṛtarāṣṭra is "that part of man, which, containing the principle of thirst for existence, holds the material life." Arjuna is everyman, fighting a battle "raging on the sacred plane of our body." Kṛṣṇa is the "charioteer of the body," as well as being "the inner guide." When we read the BG, "we are face to face with ourselves." That is precisely what A. Besant in her *Hints on the Study of the Bhagavad Gītā* (1906) has shown. She worked with two levels of interpretation, an outer and an inner meaning, the one historical and the other allegorical.

²⁷ Gandhi made one major criticism of the *Gītā*, and his objection is very similar to that of the transcendentalist Thoreau: they both disliked the justification of violence. Thus Gandhi's insistence that for him the symbolic level of the *Gītā* was more alluring and important in the text than its representation of physical violence and the justification of killing. Contemplation, therefore, is what is really at stake.

possess some allegorical meaning, with Kṛṣṇa somehow symbolizing the divine and Arjuna the human.

The *Gītā* uses allegories and metaphors to relate the concrete forms of the divine with the realm of the Absolute.²⁸ In the whole of chapter 11 Arjuna’s experience of the One in the Many (BhG 11.13) is a kind of metaphor for the human relation to the divine. Even the theory of *avatar* (the theory of God’s descent to the mundane world) is part of the *Gītā*’s message. Furthermore, Arjuna’s reliance on his charioteer is an allegory explaining how *śraddhā* works in relation to the *Īśvara*,²⁹ as section V.4 will discuss thoroughly. Through its 18 *yogas* or chapters, the *Gītā* deals with Arjuna’s gradual shift from a state in which he is initially disheartened (*aśraddadhāna*), to that in which he learns how ‘to set his heart on’ (*śraddhāvanta*) an action.³⁰ Perhaps not by coincidence the

²⁸ Because spiritual discipline is a progression from the physical to the spiritual, action (*karma*) is a means to exercise religious values such as detachment, and detachment is the means for developing an ear for what is from God’s realm. See, for instance, BhG 5.29, which even seems to suggest the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* theory.

²⁹ BhG 7.19, 9.29, 13.27, 14.27, 15.12-5, and 18.61.

³⁰ With my own suggestion of translation, they are:

1. *Arjuna-Viśāda-Yoga* (The Mode of Arjuna’s Despondency)
2. *Sāṅkhya-Yoga* (The Mode of Reasoning, where Kṛṣṇa diagnoses Arjuna)
3. *Karma-Yoga* (The Mode of Action, where Kṛṣṇa starts his prescription by defining ‘*karma-yoga*’)
4. *Jñāna-Yoga* (The Mode of Knowledge)
5. *Karma-Samnyāsa-Yoga* (The Way of Renunciation in Action)
6. *Ātma-Saṁyama-Yoga* (The Way of Self-control, or the Way of Meditation)
7. *Jñāna-Vijñāna-Yoga* (The Way of Theoretical and Experiential Wisdom)
8. *Akṣara-Parabrahma-Yoga* (The Way Toward the Imperishable Brahman)
9. *Rājavidyā-Rājaguhya-Yoga* (The Discipline of Royal Science and Royal Mystery)
10. *Vibhūti-Yoga* (The Discipline of Sovereign Power)
11. *Viśvarūpa-Darśana-Yoga* (The Mystical Revelation of the Universal Form of God)
12. *Bhakti-Yoga* (The *Yoga* of Devotion)
13. *Kṣetra-Kṣetrajñā-Yoga* (The Mystical Distinction between the Field and the Field-Knower)
14. *Guṇatraya-Vibhāga-Yoga* (The Mystical Apportionment of the Three Strands)
15. *Puruṣottama-Prāpti-Yoga* (The Mystical Approach to the Supreme Being)
16. *Daivāsura-Sampad-Vibhāga-Yoga* (The Mystical Discrimination between Divine and Demonic Conditions)

first and the last occurrences (BhG 3.31 and 18.71) of the term *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* deal with this contrast between whining and *śraddhā*. Whining reflects an ill-will, as opposed to rejoicing and standing firm against everything that is threatening. They are the core elements in the definition of *śraddhā*, as taught by Kṛṣṇa. For, a *yogin* is one who is content in oneself, who is not disturbed by the events of *saṃsāra* (BhG 2.55-6), and whose joy dwells in the performance of unselfish actions alone (BhG 2.51 and 17.17).

In other words, Kṛṣṇa contrasts *śraddhā* with Arjuna's whining behavior by introducing Arjuna to the discipline of *niṣkāmakarmayoga* (also known as the practice of desireless action) – one should put one's heart on the performance of one's mission, without any ulterior motive or interest. For, to do anything because of what one may get out of it only leads to that specific object of attachment; it does not lead to *mokṣa*. On the other side, detachment from selfish-interest (the 'fruits') leads to detachment from *saṃsāra* and to the yogic realization of *ātman* (the selfless-self) (BhG 2.47-8). *Niṣkāmakarmayoga*, then, by severing the connection to the fruits of actions, helps one to free oneself from the *triguṇic* influences of *saṃsāra*.³¹ For, once one places 'one's heart on' *ātman*, the mind is kept still, and the senses are withdrawn from the objects and its delights, as a tortoise withdraws its limbs into its shell (BhG 2.58 and 2.61).

17. *Śraddhātraya-Vibhāga-Yoga* (The Mystical Recognition of the Threefold Religious Fervour)

18. *Mokṣa-Samnyāsa-Yoga* (The Mystical Liberation by Renunciation).

³¹ We should be careful in order not to be fooled by the word 'desire'. It is not to be taken in the general sense, as used for instance by Herbert Marcuse in his *One Dimensional Man* (Ark Paperbacks, 1964). For, of course, desire can never be fully eradicated from oneself. 'Non-desire', or *niṣkāma*, is only what is required from our actions, from the viewpoint of our interest or desire to profit from their outcome. One should act for the sake of the goodness of the action in itself, and not for any other particular reason. For, being disciplined and learning to detach oneself from the consequences or rewards of one's actions separate those who are ready for salvation from those who are not ready yet. This is clearly stated in BhG 17.17. We will have the opportunity to come back to this issue during the exegesis of the referred verse.

In the Indian Tradition, the *Gṝh̄ā* has always been considered as both *Śruti* and *Smṛti*, even when *Smṛti* is believed to depend on *Śruti* as inference depends on perception. As *Śruti* (Revealed Scripture) the *Gṝh̄ā* is recognized as self-evident knowledge revealed to the *ṝṣis* (seers); it represents non-mediated, or direct, knowledge manifest as *pratyakṣa* (intuitive perception). As *Smṛti* (mediated, or indirect knowledge), it is dependent on some human basis or ground and includes the second *pramāṇa* or *anumāna*, reasoning, or inference.

In this context, the assumption that the *Gṝh̄ā* is a Scripture and includes both *pramāṇas* (intuitive perception and inference) is essential to understanding that it reflects the duality of a revealed knowledge which is also recognized in the experience of the warrior Arjuna, and, as a consequence, of anyone who listens the divine song of *ātman* as

Arjuna had done.³² For, the *Gītā* is understood best as sung, with the adjective ‘*Srimad*’ or ‘sublime’ added to the title to make it the ‘sublime song of the Lord’.³³

The view of the German Romantics and American Transcendentalists are in many ways similar to that of Gandhi, inasmuch as they all accept the *Gītā* as a unified and mystical text. For, the truth is that no matter if ‘*revealed*’ or not, the *Gītā* does work as if it were revealed – which means that it functions also as a Scripture. The German Romantics and American Transcendentalists, who were thinking about a general symbolic realm and how it affects everyman, have acknowledged the *Gītā* as a coherent text, capable of triggering the highest sentiments of the soul. This means they were

³² As it is well known, the *Gītā* had a special appeal for the American Transcendentalists Emerson and Thoreau, for instance. See George Hendrick in his Introduction to Jagdish Chander Kapoor’s *BHAGAVAD-GĪTĀ – An International Bibliography of 1785 – 1979 Imprints* (New York & London: Garland Publishing, 1983). Thoreau’s praise of the *Gītā* is famous: “the reader is nowhere raised into and sustained in a higher, purer, or *rarer* region of thought than in the Bhagvat-Geeta” (xxiv). Further, Kapoor quotes Thoreau again: “Beside the vast and cosmogonical philosophy of the Bhagavat-Geeta, even our Shakespeare seems sometimes youthfully green and practical merely” (xxiv). Thoreau even dedicated some time to study the *Mahābhārata*. As a result he published his own English version of Langolis’ translation of the Harivamsa – the appendix of the *Mahābhārata*, dedicated to Kṛṣṇa.

Emerson first heard about the *Gītā* when attending Victor Cousin’s course of philosophy (Hendrick, in Kapoor 1983, xxiii). Later he had the opportunity to read it in full and even to buy his own volume of Wilkins’s translation, about which he wrote in 1848: “I owed – my friend and I owed – a magnificent day to the *Bhagavad Geeta*. It was the first of books; it was as if an empire spoke to us, nothing small or unworthy, but large, serene, consistent, the voice of an old intelligence which in another age and climate had pondered and thus disposed of the same questions which exercise us” (xxiii). Twenty years later, when writing to Emma Lazarus, he would still show the same excitement about the *Gītā*: “And of books there is another which, when you have read, you shall sit for a while & then write a poem – the ‘Bhagvat-Geeta,’ but read it in Charles Wilkins’s translation.”

³³ The title ‘*Bhagavad Gītā*’ also implies that text which being studied with *śraddhā* confers, according to BhG 18.71, salvation. In the *Gītā*, the knowledge of *ātman* comes to Arjuna in chapter 11 in the form of intuitive, or direct, knowledge, a realisation that reveals the cause of the world, despite the fact that this cause is ultimately imperceptible and unthinkable. This knowledge, which according to the *Upaniṣads* is expressed in the identity judgement *tat tvam asi* or *aham brahmā smi*, is expressed in its negative aspect as ‘*Brahman* is neither this, nor this’, and is expressed in its positive aspect as the realisation of the true nature of *ātman* in its relation of identity with any of Its representatives, in the case of the *Gītā*, Kṛṣṇa. Furthermore, the sound of the *Gītā* also is considered sacred. Indeed, similarly to the *Vedas*, or the Chants called *Śruti* “that which is heard,” the *Gītā* is *chanted*. The English word “chant,” used mostly in a context of religious fervour, is perhaps derived from the Sanskrit term *chandas* (metre), denoting the rhythm according to which *Vedic* Hymns should be recited.

aware of the place intuition plays in these teachings. For, they did not read the *Gṝā* only to ‘understand’ it; nor to understand its historical and cultural context, or to simply apprehend how it influences others. We might say they read the *Gṝā* to be enraptured by its Scriptural symbolism, to share with Arjuna what he had experienced in his craving for the transcendent.

Assessing the *Gṝā* as a Scripture, however, does not necessarily mean it falls into the category of ‘romantic rhetoric’. How we *feel* the text is still supposed to stay within some sort of logical regulation. In other words, when listening to a song, for instance, we might say that more important than our reasoning, more important than our understanding, is how we *feel* the song. When we listen with our soul, the sentiments that music and poetry instill are of more value than the ‘rational’ truths we may think they convey. But these sentiments also teach us how, when, and why to trust our own thoughts, or what we may consider as constituting a new revelation, arising as a higher voice talking what is privately true in our hearts, but also containing something of that which is universally true. That is to say, the *Gṝā* has been acknowledged as a Scripture with many theologically coherent messages and degrees of universality.

Aldous Huxley, the English novelist with an eye for science,³⁴ for instance, argues that the *Gṝā*’s values and ideas are relevant to contemporary life. Once we understand that religion and philosophy are part of the same human realm, it is not difficult to acknowledge that the *Gṝā* is pragmatic and operational, where the operations are also

³⁴ See his Introduction to *The Song of God: Bhagavad-Gṝā*, trans. by Christopher Isherwood and Swami Prabhavanda (New York: Mentor Books, 1944), and also his many essays and fictional works.

psychological, and aim to lead us toward revealing experiences similar to those bestowed upon on Arjuna. Huxley had no problem acknowledging the *Gītā* as a consistent treatise advocating a higher form of *praxis*, rather than a theistic creed. This is also one of the topics of his *The Perennial Philosophy* (New York: Harper Colophon Books, 1944). He even states that the *Gītā* is “one of the clearest and most comprehensive summaries of the Perennial Philosophy ever to be made,” hence its universality (Isherwood 1944, 16). He reads the *Gītā* as a treatise suggesting detachment and socialization of spirituality, where a kind of holy indifference becomes also loving wholeness.

The general concern for humanity, which Huxley sees in the text fits nicely with our thesis that the *Gītā* is a Scripture on *orthopraxis* (*niṣkāmakarmayoga*).³⁵ ‘*Orthopraxis*’ is the theological term for ‘correct practice’, and is not to be taken as ‘inflexible practice of rituals and *dharma*’, which the translation of *śraddhā* as ‘faith’ in the *Gītā* strongly suggests. On the contrary, *orthopraxis* is to be considered the result of one being motivated and full of religious enthusiasm (*sattvic śraddhā*). Resulting from *sattvic śraddhā*, it represents something deeper than the Christian understanding of it as ‘lifestyle’. For the *Gītā* reminds us that the idea of ‘*doxa*’ is something of provisional and of relative value; something that should be constantly re-evaluated under the light and higher authority of *ātman*. This is shown in the *Gītā* through Arjuna’s legitimate and honest process of doubting.

³⁵ See Gouriswar Bhattacharya, “Studies in the Concept of *śraddhā* in Post-Vedic Hinduism” (Ph.D. diss., University of Basle, 1971), where Bhattacharya introduces P. Masson-Oursel’s statement that the *Gītā* “calls for *orthopraxy* rather than *orthodoxy*” (76).

When a doubt is exposed, it can be addressed and dispelled through the process of acquiring new knowledge (BhG 4.41-2). In the case of Arjuna, he, out of plain devotion (*bhakti*), asks Kṛṣṇa to remove his doubt (*saṁśaya*) (BhG 6.39), then, out of *sattvic śraddhā*, he acknowledges that, through Kṛṣṇa’s clear (*prasāda*) exposition, he was able to solve his doubts (BhG 18.73). Therefore, what allowed Arjuna to recover his inner strength (*śraddhā*) was his awareness that he was free to have religious doubts (*saṁśaya*) and also free to question his own orthodox faith, without being stigmatized, or called a heretic, by Kṛṣṇa.

The logical arguments used by Arjuna to reveal Kṛṣṇa’s apparent contradictory statements (BhG 3.1 and BhG 4.4), were simply met with Kṛṣṇa’s deliverance of a deeper understanding on those subjects. In Kṛṣṇa’s words, “a man is wise who sees nonaction in action and action in nonaction.” (BhG 4.18). When the heart motivates one’s actions, one’s mind learns to rest in one’s heart. When one rests his mind in the heart, one rests in *āman*, from where, possessed of *sattvic śraddhā*, one acts as if one were not acting and vice-versa (BhG 4.20-2). This helps to explain, first, the universality of *śraddhā*, once we recognize that it represents that which is found in all religious paths. Secondly, seeing *śraddhā* as religious actions it becomes clear why it is improper to translate it as ‘faith’, for *śraddhā* is not an exclusive religious path pointing to a personal attachment to deity so much as a way in which any religious system is to be practised.

Taking *śraddhā* as if it were one path in the “Hindu systems” is what misled several scholars, who had interpreted it as if it were restating theistic *bhakti*. This

position is held by the majority of Western scholars who say that the message of the *Gṛ̥ā* is one of theistic devotion,³⁶ where the term ‘*śraddhā*’ means ‘faith’. Their interpretation, being an outcome of the widely accepted Biblical studies idea of a ‘documentary hypothesis’, has turned the *Gṛ̥ā* into a simple collage of different texts, containing many contradictions. The ‘documentary hypothesis’, although developed for the special circumstances of Biblical studies, still influences how Western scholars approach the *Gṛ̥ā*.³⁷ This pattern can be seen in a number of scholars who have adhered to the idea that interpolations and additions explain the many contradictory doctrines the *Gṛ̥ā* presents. Whereas the classic Rudolph Otto’s *The Original Gṛ̥ā* (1939) guesses that the original *Gṛ̥ā* would have little more than a hundred verses, the more recent study of Angelika Malinar on the royal knowledge about reign and renunciation in the *Gṛ̥ā*³⁸ still emphasizes that the text does not involve a single argument.³⁹

³⁶ See T. G. Mainkar, *A Comparative Study of the Commentaries on the Bhagavadgṛ̥ā* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1969).

³⁷ For more details, see Mircea Eliade, Editor in Chief, *The Encyclopedia of Religion* (New York: Macmillan Publishing Company, 1987) Vol.I, p.14; Vol. II, pp. 147, 158-159; Vol. 10, pp. 116-119 and Vol. 14, pp. 557, 558.

³⁸ Angelika Malinar, *Rājavidyā: Das königliche Wissen um Herrschaft und Verzicht – Studien zur Bhagavadgṛ̥ā* (Harrassowitz Verlag – Wiesbaden, 1996).

³⁹ In her section “5.17 Bhavavadgītā 17: Ritualvorschrift und śraddhā” (5.17 Bhavavadgītā 17: ritual-rule and śraddhā), for instance, she argues that perhaps chapter 17 belongs among the recent insertions into the *Gṛ̥ā* text – “Beide Möglichkeiten sprechen dafür, daß dieses Kapitel zu den jüngsten Einfügungen in die BG gehört” (1996, 366). Her argument is that differently from chapter 9, in chapter 17 Kṛ̥ṣṇa does not refer to his own divinity anymore. He only mentions Himself *en passant* in BhG 17.6. She also says: Die in 9.23 gennant Kombination von *avidhipūrvakam* und *śraddhā* wird vom Autor von BhG 17 nicht akzeptiert (364, end of note 6). Her comparison of chapter 17 with chapter 9, however, ignores Kṛ̥ṣṇa’s classification of forms of worship, where even demonic entities have a place. As such, her conclusion that the combination of *avidhipūrvakam* (not according to rule) with *śraddhā* in BhG 9.23 is no longer acceptable to the author of chapter 17 cannot be taken in absolute terms. Her argument, therefore, that chapter 17 does not belong to the *Gṛ̥ā*, does not seem to hold. Yet, the question Malinar is bringing here is of interest to our current discussion because it is in BhG 9.23 that Kṛ̥ṣṇa suggests how we all, in a sense, are in an asymptotic convergence to the final goal. For, he stresses, no matter one’s faith, as long as one

It is my understanding, however, that the overall characterization of the Indian philosophical systems is that they consist of a series of footnotes⁴⁰ to the *Gītā*, where Kṛṣṇa explains to Arjuna that one can have no greater mastery than the mastery of this mystery of *ātman* in oneself. Thus, I will take up the study of the *Gītā*, accepting the text in its present form as both a ‘scripture’ of the Indian Tradition and as a text on religious practice that any universal religious discourse has access to.

In taking this approach, I will follow in certain ways the arguments of Krishna Sharma. In her important study she starts with a critique of Western scholars. She argues that Westerners have taken for granted two principles: one, the belief in an essential difference between religion and philosophy; and the other, the association of ‘true’ religion with the idea of monotheism. Together, these two principles have led to a reading of the *Gītā* where *bhakti*, to use Krishna Sharma’s words, is understood as only *saguṇa* (possessed of personal qualities) *bhakti*. Yet, she argues, *nirguṇa* (beyond personal qualities) *bhakti* also finds a place in the *Gītā* (1987, 109). If *saguṇa bhakti* gives support to the reading of the *Gītā* as a theistic text, *nirguṇa bhakti* gives support to its deeper monist understanding.

Sharma’s argument is well supported in the *Gītā* itself. The distinguishing feature of the theory of the *guṇas* as described in the *Gītā* seems to be Kṛṣṇa’s assertion about the existence and reality of *prakṛti* as the lower nature (BhG 7.4-7) of the Supreme Being

has *śraddhā*, his or her worship, though not conforming to the ancient rule (*avidhipūrvakam*), will ultimately be directed toward him, and, therefore, toward the *ātman*.

⁴⁰ The reader should recognize here the paraphrase of Whitehead’s wellknown statement somewhere in his *Process and Reality* that “The safest general characterization of the European philosophical tradition is that it consists of a series of footnotes to Plato.”

(*Puruṣottama*). For, it is this assertion that also establishes the reality of the three constituents (*guṇas*) of matter (BhG 7.12-5). When *sattva* (illumination) predominates over *rajas* (energy) and *tamas* (inertia), there arises spiritual knowledge.⁴¹ But even *sattva* should be seen as something to be transcended. This is the point that Kṛṣṇa Sharma is considering when she says, “The *Gṝā* does not connect bhakti with these forms [of *śraddhā*]; it connects it only with parā-śraddhā or supreme faith which is beyond the three categories of *guṇas*” (113). That is to say, Sharma is of the opinion that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* are different in the *Gṝā*, but she sees *nirguṇa bhakti* as something higher and beyond the *triguṇic śraddhā*, or, as she puts it, “simple loving faith” (112).

Although I will propose a slightly different use of the terms *śraddhā* and *bhakti* I agree with her central argument that the central teaching of the *Gṝā* is the experience of *ātman*, rather than the worship of Kṛṣṇa. For, what she calls *parā-śraddhā* is the

⁴¹ The classic text known as *The Sāṃkhya Kārikā* of Iśvarakṛṣṇa (3rd century C.E.) with the *Tattva-kaumudī* (Vācaspatimiśra’s commentary – 850 C.E.) talks about the *guṇas* when discussing the complete discrimination of *puruṣa* and *prakṛti* as the best mean for overcoming suffering and achieving *mokṣa* (salvation). It defines and explains the manifested (*vyakta*) reality as evolving from the original matter (*prakṛti*), with the transcendent (*avyakta*) being expressed by the universal being (*paramātman*). *Prakṛti* (*pra + kṛ*), according to its etymological sense, means that which is primary, that which precedes what is made. However, this *prakṛti* is further understood as double folded: *mūlaprakṛti*, or that uncreated matter which is the primary root and substance of all things, except the *puruṣa*, and the relative *prakṛti*, or that created matter of which every substance is secondarily composed. The broad term used for the potencies of *mūlaprakṛti* is *vyakta* – that which is evident or manifest, from ‘vi,’ and ‘anja,’ ‘to make clear or distinct.’ *Paramātman* is the opposite; it is *avyakta*, ‘transcendent, and non-separated’. The manifest (*vyakta*) is with the three attributes (*triguṇas*); the *Paramātman* (*puruṣa*) is free from their influence. The soul does not have the *triguṇas*. By this assertion are set aside all those theories that attribute pleasure or pain to the Spirit. The material beings are the ones who experience the influence of the *triguṇas* – *sattva*, *rajas* and *tamas*. *Sattva* (intelligibility constituent) is illuminating (*prakāśaka*); it provides the intellectual clarity. *Rajas* (activity constituent) is stimulating (*upaśtambhaka*) and moving (*cala*), providing the capacity for change. *Tamas* (inertia constituent) is heavy (*guru*), providing the substance. In the *Sāṃkhyakārikā* these three are said to function together for a purpose just as the wick, oil, and flame of a lamp, though different in their makeup, nevertheless function for the purpose of illumination. In other words, the *triguṇas* exist and operate for the sake of the Spirit: the wick and the oil and the flame are substances, which are opposed in nature; and yet they cooperate in the lamp in giving light. So, the phenomenological world exists controlled by the *triguṇas* for the sake of the *puruṣa*, whose ontological existence permeates the *prakṛti*.

impersonal worship of *Brahman*, beyond the three *guṇas*, where *parā-śraddhā*, which is also *nirguṇa* in character, appears connected with *nirguṇa bhakti*.⁴²

This thesis discusses the *Gṝā*, then, in the context of the twenty-one occurrences of *śraddhā* in the text. It shows that Kṛṣṇa not only proposes *sattvic śraddhā* (BhG 17.17) as a means to salvation, but also condemns its absence as responsible for one's failure (BhG 4.40 and BhG 9.3). It shows, therefore, that Kṛṣṇa presents *śraddhā* as the means of *jñāna yoga* (BhG 4.39), *bhakti yoga* (BhG 12.2 and BhG 12.20), and *karma yoga* (BhG 3.31) and as such, that not only *bhakti*, but also *jñāna* and *karma yoga* are outcomes of this synthesizing and pure (*sattvic*) *śraddhā* (BhG 6.47).

⁴² The term *bhakti* per se appears for the first time in the *Śvetāśvatara Upaniṣad* 6.23 (Das Gupta 1930, 496), which is said to be older than the *Gṝā*. Since then, it is related to an emotional devotion to a personal god. As a consequence it slowly overshadows the impersonal *śraddhā* in the texts of the new *Upaniṣadic* sects due to their proximity of meaning. However, what the *Upaniṣads* generally stress is that meditation on the 'impersonal' symbol OM is the most important aspect of the religious discipline – a fact that the *Gṝā* also acknowledges in BhG 8.13; 9.17, and 17.23-4. In the *Gṝā* the object of Arjuna's devotion goes beyond Kṛṣṇa, who is only a means, as shown in BhG 7.23, for the positive approach, out of love and religious fervor, toward the Absolute.

II. THE EARLY TRADITIONS' USE OF THE TERM ŚRADDHĀ

The goal of this chapter is twofold: (a) to discuss the early uses of *śraddhā*, and (b) to link *śrāddha* to *śraddhā*. Because these two issues are important for the understanding of the ritual activity and theology of the *Mahābhārata* and of the context of the *Gṛ̥ā*, it is not easy to decide which topic one should address first. As we can infer from the following passage of Kane's *History of Dharmaśāstra*⁴³, both sequences seem to work:

In *śrāddha* one entertains the firm faith or conviction that what is given up to the brāhmaṇas for the benefit of the departed man or the Fathers will reach him or them in some way. The Skandapurāna VI.218.3 says that *śrāddha* is so called because *śraddhā* is the root (or main spring) of that rite. This means that there is not only the conviction stated above but that there is a firm belief that a person is under an obligation to offer it. Śraddhā is deified and addressed as deity in R̥g.⁷⁹³X.151.1-5, the first verse of which is explained in the Nirukta (IX.31). The word also occurs in R̥g.II.26.3, VII.32.14, VIII.1.31, IX.113.4. In some verses the two components of the word 'śraddhā' (viz. 'śrat' and 'dhā') are separated without any change in meaning. For example in R̥g.II.12.5 (= A.V.20.34.5) it is said 'Have faith in him: O people! he is *Indra*'. In R̥g.X.147.1, addressed to *Indra*, we have 'I have faith in that high wrath of yours &c.' (1973, vol. 4, 351)

⁷⁹³ śraddhayāgniḥ samydhate śraddhayā [. . .] x.151.1.

The passage makes it very clear that '*śrāddha*' is derived from '*śraddhā*'. Perhaps, then, we should leave the link between *śrāddha* and *śraddhā* for later, and start with early uses of *śraddhā*. The *śrāddha* discussion, then, should lead into the *Gṛ̥ā* nicely. In the Indian view death is an issue which links common peoples' everyday feelings of wonder

⁴³ Pandurang Vaman Kane, *History of Dharmaśāstra*, 2nd ed., Government Oriental Series Class B, No. 6, 5 vols. (Poona: Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, 1968-1977). Professor Kane's study of the term *dharma*, concluded by 1962 with the fifth Volume of his series, which he had started in 1930, help us understand the metaphysics of the *Gṛ̥ā* – a text whose very first word of the first verse (*śloka*) is *dharma*.

and terror with mystical and philosophical understanding. Death is feared but is also considered a blessed occasion for freeing the soul from the *triguṇic* influences of the material body. The ancient rites for departed ancestors⁴⁴ named *piṇḍapitṛyajña* (or the offering of balls of rice to the fathers, grandfathers, and great-grandfathers), or simply *śrāddha*, are meant to wash the *pitṛs* pure.⁴⁵

The structure of the first subsection, then, is in terms of my readings of *Vedic* material and the secondary sources used to interpret it. When discussing the *Ṛgvedic* texts, I put verses from books II-VIII first, as it seems there is a fair agreement that these ‘family’ books represent what is called the ‘early’ *Ṛg Veda*. Book IX, on *Soma*, is of uncertain period, and books I and X are considered ‘later’.

II.1. Earliest References to the Term ‘śraddhā’

In the *Ṛg Veda* the term *śraddhā* appears in 16 hymns.⁴⁶ The single occurrence where *śraddhā* appears with the meaning of ‘[on you] trusting’ in the nominative is:⁴⁷

1. *Ṛg Veda* VII, 32, 14 (similar to *Sāmaveda Saṃhitā* I, 280):⁴⁸

⁴⁴ When only one deceased person is intended, the *śrāddha* rite is named *ekoddiṣṭa*. It is to be performed on the 11th day after death, at the end of each month for a year, and every year on the day of death. Also, performed after a year of the date of death, the rite named *Sapiṇḍikaraṇa* or *Sapiṇḍana*, is meant as the reception of the deceased, or *preta*, into the community of *pitṛs* to whom *piṇḍas* are offered (1973, 517-20).

⁴⁵ See *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* II.4.2, *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* I.3.10 and II.6.16, *Āśvalāyana Gṛhya Sūtra* II.6-7, *Āpastamba Dharma Sūtra* I.7-10, *Kātyāyana Śrauta Sūtra* IV.1.1-30, *Satyāśāḍha Śrauta Sūtra* II.7, and *Baudhāyana Dharma Sūtra* III.10-1 (1974, Vol. II, 1086).

⁴⁶ Curiously, R. Minor states in his *Bhagavad-Gītā – An Exegetical Commentary* (New Delhi: Heritage Publishers, 1982), “the term *śraddhā* is not found in the *Ṛg Veda*” (181).

⁴⁷ Köhler suggests that the construction with *śrat-kr-* (‘to assure’) is similar to that of *śrad-dhā*, and in Classic Sanskrit means ‘to trust, to have confidence in, to confide in’ (*vertrauen*) (1973, 12-21).

⁴⁸ “Which mortal, O *Indra*, will attack the one whose wealth is you? O Maghvan, the one trusting in you will be the hero who wins victory on the decisive day.” See H. Grassmann, *Wörterbuch Zum Rig Veda* (Wiesbaden: Otto Hanssowitz, 1964), 1418-9: “*śrad-dhā* = *śrath-dhā*, und zwar nur in den unpersönlichen

*kas tam indra tvāvasum ā martyo dadharṣati /
śraddhā it te maghvan pārye divi vājī vājāṃ siṣāti //*

Which mortal, O Indra, can touch the treasure that you are? Through *the trust* on you, O Offering-rich, the hero strives for victory on the decisive day.

The ‘religious’ tone here is unlike the other occurrences in the ‘family’ books, where the heroic tone is central and *śraddhā* usually refers to human virtues such as ‘loyalty’ and ‘enthusiasm’. The next passages provide more examples of how the noun *śraddhā* is being formed in the *Vedic* context. In the first passage *śraddhā* appears in the instrumental form *śraddhayā*:

2. *Ṛg Veda* VIII, 1, 31:⁴⁹

*ā yad aśvān vananvataḥ śraddhayāhaṃ rathe ruham /
uta vāmasya vasunaś ciketati yo asti yādvaḥ paśuḥ //*

When I get up in the chariot of the fiery horses *with enthusiasm*, even the bull of the Yadus notices the handsome driver, whoever he might be.

3. *Ṛg Veda* VI, 26, 6a:

tvaṃ śraddhābhīr mandasānaḥ somair dabhītaye cumurin indra siṣvap /

You, Indra, pleased by means of *Soma* and the sense of *loyalty* have put the demon Cumuri to sleep in order to please Dabhīti.

This last passage addresses the myth of Dabhīti,⁵⁰ whose friendship with Indra is based on this *śraddhā* (trust), which appears also as loyalty. The concept of *śraddhā* in these early *Ṛg Veda* hymns of heroism seems to fluctuate around the idea of ‘trust’, understood

Formen, in denen *śrath* mit *dhā* verschmilzt (vgl. lat. credo), und dabei in Bezug auf die Betonung nach Art eines Richtungswortes behandelt wird. *śrad-dhā* f. Vertrauen, Glauben, auch als Gottheit angerufen” – *śrad-dhā* = *śrath-dhā*, and it refers only to impersonal forms, where *śrath* coalesces with *dhā* (cf. lat. credo). The composed term is, then, accentuated like simple words, in a single syllable. *śrad-dhā* f. trust, believe, and also a divine call.

⁴⁹ Köhler and Oldenberg translate *śraddhā* here as ‘trust’. Oldenberg had stressed *śraddhā* as the trust shown through the generosity of giving gifts.

⁵⁰ According to Köhler, in this myth *śraddhā* appears in a compound with *manas* for the first time (19). This myth also appears in relation to *śraddhā* in *Ṛg Veda* X, 113, 9: *bhūri dakṣebhīr vacanebhīr ṛkvabhiḥ sakhyebhiḥ sakhyāni pra vocata / indro dhuniṃ ca cumuriṃ ca dambhayaṃ chraddhāmanasyā śṛṇute dabhītaye //* Often proclaimed is the friendship (of Indra) with his skilled, eloquent, and praised friends. Indra is famous for outwitting the Dhuni and Cumuri for Dabhīti, who was loyally devoted at heart.

as ‘loyalty’, and the idea of ‘enthusiastic engagement’. The next passage exemplifies *śraddhā* as the basis of all virtuous actions.

4. *Ṛg Veda* II, 26, 3 (similar to *Māitrāyaṇi Saṃhitā* IV, 14, 10; *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* II, 3, 14, 3, and *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* II, 8, 5, 3):

sa ij janena sa viśā sa janmanā sa putrair vājam bharate dhanā nṛbhiḥ / devānām yaḥ pitaram āvivāsati śraddhāmanā haviṣā brahmaṇas patim //

He, with his people, with his household, with his family, with his sons gets the victory and gains the booty with his men. He, serves *Brāhmaṇaspati*, the father of the gods, with a loyal heart and with sacrifice.

The next passage shows that the absence of *śraddhā*, or *aśraddhā* is a characteristic of the enemy hordes.

5. *Ṛg Veda* VII, 6, 3:

ny akraṭūn grathino mṛdhravācaḥ pañūr aśraddhāṇ avṛddhān ayajñān / pra-pra tān dasyūr agnir vivāya pūrvas cakārāparāṇ ayajyūn //

They are without loyalty, without proper speech, proper action or sacrifices. These Dasyus Agni chased from the east but they did not even sacrifice in the west.

Moving on from heroic ‘family books’ we find *śraddhā* is used in somewhat more mystical contexts in the *Soma* hymns of the 9th book.

6. *Ṛg Veda* IX, 113, 2b-3a:

*ṛtavākena satyena śraddhayā tapasā sutaḥ . . . //2//
parjanyaavṛddham mahiṣam taṃ sūryasya duhitābharat /
taṃ gandharvāḥ praty agṛbhṇan taṃ some rasam ādadhuḥ . . . //3//*

With a sincere true-speech, with dedication, and squeezed with fervor.

[The *Soma*] is squeezed out with righteous words, with truth, with enthusiasm, and with self sacrifice. The buffalo raised by Parjanya was brought by the daughter of the Sun.

As Köhler argues, the ‘daughter of the sun (Sūrya, Prajāpati)’ is *śraddhā*. She is the one with whom *Soma*, represented as a king, is said to be in love in the *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa*

II, 3, 10, 1f. *Ṛg Veda* IX, 1, 6,⁵¹ *Vājasaneyi Saṃhitā* XIX, 4, and *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* XII, 7, 3, 11,⁵² also refer to the fact that *Śraddhā* is the daughter of the sun (1973, 22).

Another passage from Book 9 refers to enthusiastic engagement of the Lord of the sacrifice who brings the *Soma* plant to be pressed.

7. *Ṛg Veda* IX, 113,4

*ṛtaṃ vadann ṛtadyumna satyaṃ vadant satyakarman /
śraddhāṃ vadant soma rājan dhātrā soma pariskṛtaḥ . . . //4//*

Speaking righteously, acting righteously, speaking truth and acting truthfully;
Speak in trust, King Soma, O Soma properly prepared.

The links with ritual that one sees in these *Soma* hymns is common by the time of the *Brāhmaṇas*. Here *śraddhā* is an essential part of each ritual, and as a byproduct of this understanding, it is also used by the *Brāhmin* priests to refer to ‘trust’ that one should have in their services. For, to be endowed with *śraddhā* is a crucially important part of the ritual action (*yajña*). Every *yajña* starts with vows to promote *śraddhā*, and Köhler argues that a proper *yajña* or sacrifice could not exist in the absence of *śraddhā* (29). The following passage exemplifies this point.

8. *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* III, 7, 4, 1 (similar to the *Śrauta Sūtra* of *Āpastamba* IV, 4, 4; *Baudhāyana Śrauta Sūtra* II, 1; *Bhāradvāja Śrauta Sūtra* IV, 5,5, and *Satyāśāḍhviracitaṃ Śrauta Sūtram* I, 4):

*yāḥ purastāt prasrvanty upariṣṭāt sarvatas ca yāḥ /
tābhī raśmipavitrābhiḥ śraddhāṃ yajñam ārabhe //*

The water streams forth in the front, from above, and from all sides.
Through the sprinkles of this water, I achieve a faithfilled sacrifice.

⁵¹ *punāti te pariśrutam somam sūryasya duhitā* – Soma, flowing around from one to another vessel, purifies the daughter of the sun.

⁵² *śraddhā vai sūryasya duhitā, śraddhayaīṣa somo bhavati, śraddhayaivainam somam karoti* -- the daughter of the sun is *Śraddhā* indeed. Through *śraddhā*, this (*sutaḥ* = liquor) will become *Soma*; through *śraddhā*, he turns it into *Soma*.

As Köhler argues, when the sacrificer is not himself filled with devotion (*Hingabe*), the hymns and rituals that the priest directs to him are meaningless (29). That is to say, more powerful than the power of the speech and the sacrifice-formula is such an attitude of *śraddhā*: it is not only an ethical ideal, as it might be understood today, but something of mystic power, which should be regarded also as a kind of *tapas* (30):

9. *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* I, 6, 8, 1 (similar to *Māitrāyaṇi Saṃhitā* IV, 1, 4; *Kāṭhakaṃ* XXXI, 3, and *Kapiṣṭhala Kaṭha Saṃhitā* XLVII, 3):

yo vai śraddhām anārabhya yajñena yajate nāsyēṣṭāya śrad dadhate. 'paḥ pra ṇayati, śraddhā vā āpaḥ, śraddhām evārabhya yajñena yajata, ubhaye 'sya devamunuṣya iṣṭāya śrad dadhate.

One cannot *trust* the sacrifices of whoever performs them *without dedication*. One is supposed to lead the waters first: water is *dedication*; when one undertakes the sacrifice *with dedication*, both, the gods and the humans, can *trust* that sacrifice.

Here we see how an attitude of dedication to the *yajña* and a trust in its efficacy are related meanings of *śraddhā*. Gradually, then, we get the idea that the proper performance of a sacrifice necessarily leads to its results. So, here, *śraddhā* is not trust in the gods, but a part of the power of the sacrifice itself (31). The next passage exemplifies this point.

10. *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* VII, 5, 2, 2 (similar to *Kāṭhakaṃ* XXXIII, 1):

tās āṃ dvādaśe māsi śṛṅgāṇi prāvartanta śraddhayā vāśraddhayā vā, tā imā yās tūparāḥ.

These cows will win horns in the twelfth month as a result of their *dedication*. The result of *lack of dedication* is the absence of horns.

Köhler uses the expression *yajño vai devānām āśīr yajamānasya* (to the gods, the sacrifice; to the patron of the sacrificer, the blessings) from the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* II, 3, 4, 5 to illustrate the need for the patron of the sacrifice to be filled with *śraddhā*. The

consequence of lacking *śraddhā* is shown in the passage below, where Śaṃyu, the son of Bṛhaspati, and not the patron of the sacrifice, receives the blessings (32).

11. *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* II, 6, 10, 1:

yad abrahmaṇokto 'śraddadhāno yajate śaṃyumu eva tasya bārhaspatyaṃ yajñasyāśīr gacchati.

That which is offered *without dedication*, in a non-Brahmanic manner, only favors Śaṃyu Bārhaspatya.

In the 'late' hymns of Book I the activism of *Indra* is more evident than ever, and the term seems to mean a mix of 'trust', 'devotion', and 'enthusiasm' that links the human writer's visions with the sight of the gods' activity:

12. *Ṛg Veda* I, 102, 2 (similar to *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* II, 8, 9,2):

asya śravo nadyaḥ sapta bibhrati dyavākṣāmā pṛthivī darśataṃ vapuḥ / asme sūryācandramasābhicakṣe śraddhe kam indra carato vitarturam //

The seven rivers, heavens and earth, carry his (Indra's) fame, and the distant country his beautiful shape. So that we may see and have *confidence* (trust), O Indra, the sun and the moon wander in a regular switching pattern.

13. *Ṛg Veda* I, 103, 5:

tad asyedam pasyatā bhūri puṣṭam śrad indrasya dhattana vīryāya / sa gā avindat so avindat aśvān sa oṣadhīḥ so apaḥ sa vanāni //

See his riches; *trust* Indra's heroic virtues. He found the cows; he found the horses; he, the herbs; he, the waters; he, the forests.

In both these verses, Köhler points out, *śrad-dhā* is related to seeing: The sight of divine activity links directly with the 'trust'.⁵³ Köhler emphasizes that in the *Ṛg Veda* the stress is in the certainty about the often-experienced divine force.⁵⁴

The passage *Ṛg Veda* I, 103, 3 exemplifies this point, with *śrad-dhā* implying self-confidence. It relates 'to trust, to confide in' and 'to constitute, to base'. The

⁵³ In Das Gupta's view these passages stress the meaning of 'high regard' (*bahumāna; ādarāśīya*) (317).

⁵⁴ See J. Gonda, *The Vision of the Vedic Poets*, Disputationes Rheno-Trajectinae, VIII. (The Hague: Mouton, 1963). He links the visions (*dhī*) of the *Ṛṣis* to the cosmic order or *ṛta*.

passage *Ṛg Veda* I, 104, 6, again exemplifies *śrad-dhā* with the meaning of ‘to trust’, in this case, in Indra.

14 *Ṛg Veda* I, 103, 3a:

sa jātūbharmā śraddadhāna ojaḥ purovibhindann acarad vi dāsīh/

He (Indra) who is armed with the thunderbolt and who is full of self *confidence* approaches the forts of the Dasyus.

15. *Ṛg Veda* I, 104, 6:

māntarām bhujam ā rīriṣo naḥ śraddhitam te mahata indriyāya //

adhā manye śrat te asmā adhāyi vṛṣā codasva mahate dhanāya /

Do not destroy our next joy. One has put *trust* in the power of Indra.

Therefore, I think, one has *entrusted* oneself to you, like a bull which goes to a great competition.

This same meaning, ‘to trust’, appears in *Ṛg Veda* I, 55, 5; *Ṛg Veda* II, 12, 5 (which is similar to *Atharva Veda* XX, 34, 5); *Ṛg Veda* X, 39, 5, and *Ṛg Veda* X, 147, 1 (which is similar to *Sāmaveda Saṃhitā* I, 371).

16. *Ṛg Veda* I, 108, 6:

yad abravam prathamam vām vṛṇāno ‘yam somo asurair no vibhavyaḥ/

tām satyām śraddhām abhy ā hi yātam athā somasya pibatam sutasya //

When I had first chosen you I said “we must challenge the Asuras [demons] for this *Soma*. So, now come with true *enthusiasm* and drink this pressed *Soma*.”

Śraddhā here means something that happens during an action: the singer of these verses is expressing his *śraddhā* through his active devotion, which realizes itself during the ritual practice in which *Soma* is offered to the gods. That is to say, although a noun, *śraddhā* still carries its verbal meanings – a fact which implies a gradual development from the verbal *śrad-dhā* and its suggestion of a kind of force of the heart, or trust, towards the noun *śraddhā*, with the meaning of ‘enthusiastic engagement’.

In conclusion *śraddhā* is not a theological credo in the *Ṛgveda*. It starts as a usual word for ‘trust’ (*Vertrauen*), especially, trust in *Indra*. In the *Brāhmaṇas* *śraddhā* surpasses the gods in importance, and represents the confidence which determines the effectiveness of the sacrifice. Without *śraddhā* any sacrifice becomes worthless in this realm as well as in the beyond. As a consequence, it evolves to mean ‘faithfulness, devotion, and enthusiastic engagement’ (*Treue, Hingabe, Spendefreudigkeit*). This movement, as we will see in the next section, leads to the *personification* of *śraddhā* as the goddess *Śraddhā*. The later Hymns to *Śraddhā*, which we will also see, demand from the patrons *śraddhā* as this joy in donation as well as the attitude of trust in the *Purohita* and his knowledge. This mythologization of the concept puts it closer to the center of religious thought. At the same time ritual developments link it with the actions of sacrifice and the communion with the ancestors in the *śrāddha* rituals. In the *Gṛ̥ā*, as we will see further on, a final movement, turning *śraddhā* into an ethical/theological notion that defines *every person*, will place *śraddhā* at the very core of human experience.

II.2. The Hymn to *Śraddhā*

With the late-*Vedic* hymn to *Śraddhā*, personified as a goddess, *śraddhā* with the meaning of ‘to trust, to confide’ is placed at the center of religious thought. The *Śraddhā* Hymn from *Ṛg Veda* X, 151, which also appears in the *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* II, 8, 8, 6-8, is as follows:

śraddhayāgniḥ sam idhyate śraddhayā hūyate haviḥ/

śraddhām bhagasya mūrdhani vacasā vedayāmasi //1//

By *Śraddhā* is Agni kindled; through *Śraddhā* is oblation offered.⁵⁵

We celebrate *Śraddhā* with praises, as the highest bliss.

priyaṃ śraddhe dadataḥ priyaṃ śraddhe didāsataḥ /

priyaṃ bhojeṣu yajvasv idam ma uditam kṛdhi //2//

Bless, O *Śraddhā*, the offering; Bless O *Śraddhā*, this donation offered with good intention; Bless the generous Lord of the sacrifices; make this my prayer.

yathā devā asureṣu śraddhām ugreṣu cakrire /

evam bhojeṣu yajvasv asmākam uditam kṛdhi //3//

Even as the gods make the *śraddhā* for the powerful Asuras, so make our prayer the sacrifice for those who participate in it.

śraddhām devā yajamānā vāyugopā upāsate /

śraddhām hṛdayayākūtyā śraddhayā vindate vasu //4//

Guarded by Vāyu both gods and sacrificers approach *Śraddhā*.

Through good intention of the heart *Śraddhā* is achieved; and through *Śraddhā*, wealth.

śraddhām prātar havāmahe śraddhām madhyamdinam pari /

śraddhām sūryasya nimruci śraddhe śrad dhāpayeha naḥ //

We call *Śraddhā* in the dawn; and *Śraddhā* about midday; *Śraddhā* at the setting of the sun. O *Śraddhā* allow us here to develop *śraddhā* (*Spendefreudigkeit*).

The sense of fundamental courage and inner strength, which appears in the *Upaniṣads* as the sentiment of conviction and right intention in the performance of any deed, appears personified here as a deity called *Śraddhā*. As a deity, *Śraddhā* is said to reside in the heart of every living being as an innate quality. In *Ṛgveda* X.113 and in the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* III.117 *Śraddhā* is depicted as the daughter of Sūrya, the sun, a symbol of illumination and revealer of truth. In these contexts she is said to bring the state of *ānanda* (joy). The special *Sūkta* (*Vedic Hymn*; song of praise) *Ṛgveda* X.151 praising

⁵⁵ My translation follows closely the German version of Köhler.

Śraddhā as a goddess pictures her as the right intention abiding in the heart,⁵⁶ and as the basis of the whole sacrifice. It praises *Śraddhā* as responsible for the kindling of Agni (Fire). *Śraddhā* plays, then, a decisive part in this sphere of one's mental attitude during the rituals in general, and the death ritual in particular. Shastri, for instance, says:

In the Ṛgveda¹³ a lady named Śraddhā¹⁴ of the family of Kanva praises the divinity Śraddhā (faith) in the following lines: – Agni is kindled by Śraddhā, by Śraddhā is the oblation offered; with our praise we glorify Śraddhā, who is seated on Bhaga's head. O Śraddhā, grant the desire of the doner of the oblation; . . . grant this boon, which I have mentioned to my sacrificers who solicit happiness. (1963, 369-70)

¹³ R. V. X. 151. 1-5.

¹⁴ The wife of the sage Atri and the daughter of Devahūti who was, again, the daughter of the self born Manu and the sister of Uttānapāda, the father of Dhruva.

Köhler's interpretation of this Hymn to *śraddhā* links it with ritual in a somewhat different way; as an expression of joyous greed on the part of the *Brāhmin* priests who feel happy when receiving their donations. Even he, however, recognizes that the term *śraddhā* refers to the enthusiasm and happiness that is the natural consequence of the true engagement with the other. As the personification of what is a pre-requirement for the sacrifice, *Śraddhā* or the joyous enthusiasm of the action acts as a purifying entity,

⁵⁶ In *Ṛg Veda* 10.123.3 also it is said that when the *Ṛṣis* drink *Soma*, they perceive the symbolism of the visionary insights with their hearts (*hṛda*) and ascend to the height of *ṛta*. For, according to *Ṛg Veda* 6.9.5, the mind is like a bird (birds symbolize in the *Ṛg Veda* the heart's mediation of the visionary process), and can fly. The *Ṛṣis*, then, were those who could rise in the path of *ṛta* through the vision of the sacred speeches (*vāc*) that would describe it. *Ṛg Veda* 10.71 describes the *Ṛṣis* as being those capable of distinguishing between the speeches that were in conformity with reality (*ṛta*) from those which were empty. This heart, then, represented as a bird, bears sacred speech (*vāc*) and represents what in the *Upaniṣads* and the *Gītā* is inner light of *ātman*. In the *Gītā*, as in the *Ṛg Veda* 10.5, Agni in the role of the inner bird speaks from the heart (*hṛda*). Both texts agree, then, that when the seeker is prepared, with his or her inner ears and eyes receptive and purified, the manifestation of some aspect of *ṛta* occur as a transforming revelation. Furthermore, when receiving such a revelation one reaffirms the cosmic order and grows in enthusiasm.

capable of freeing one from the consequences of any mistakes in the performance of the sacrifice. The passage below will help us to show this point.

Śrauta Sūtra of *Āpastamba* III, 12, 1 (similar to *Baudhāyana Śrauta Sūtra* XXVII, 6):
yad vidvāṃso yad avidvāṃso mugddhāḥ kurvanty ṛtvijaḥ /
agnir mā tasmād enasaḥ śraddhā devī ca muñcatām //

From any disturbance that the sacrifice-priest, consciously or not, may cause, let Agni and the goddess *Śraddhā* free me from this blame.

Köhler argues that this passage helps us to understand the passage *Aitareya Brāhmaṇa* VII, 3, 4, where *śraddhāyai* (in the dative case) should be translated as ‘to *Śraddhā*’ – the deity which represents the joy resulting from virtuous practices prescribed in the *Śruti* and *Smṛti* literature (33).

The act of making an offering or payment [to the priest] or *dakṣiṇā* is an expression of *śraddhā*. In *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* III, 9, 21 *dakṣiṇā* is said to be *śraddhā* (36). When one has *śraddhā* in the sacrifice, one gives *dakṣiṇā*. The *Atharvaveda Saṃhitā* XII, 2, 51 places *aśraddhā* on the same level with greed (37, n. 68). In other words, the goddess *Śraddhā* is the opposite of the demon of greed (*Arāti*), as suggested in the passage of the Hymn to *Śraddhā* of the *Atharvaveda Saṃhitā*:

Atharvaveda Saṃhitā V, 7, 1:
ā no bhara mā pari ṣṭhā arāte mā no rakṣir dakṣiṇāṃ nīyamānām /
namo vīrtsāyā asamṛddhaye namo astv arātaye //

Bring here to us, do not stand in the way, *Arāti*, do not deprive us of the sacrifice-prize, which is now offered. Homage to (the demon of) balk-desire and failure; homage to *Arāti*!

The enemy power is calmed down through euphemistic veneration, which uproots *Arāti* and creates room for *Śraddhā* in one’s heart, so that *dakṣiṇā* can take place. If in the *Rg Veda* *śraddhā* is the trust in the gods and their help, as well as trust in the sacrifice, in the

later tradition *śraddhā* is presented as trust in the gods’ representatives – the *Brāhmins*, who, once hired to perform a sacrifice, deserve the *dakṣiṇā* (39).

Śraddhā is sometimes fully personified and sometimes just an attitude of enthusiasm linked to ritual duties. In the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* XII.7.3.1, *śraddhā* expresses this experience as the daughter of the Sun. In the *Vājasaneyi Saṃhitā* IX.77, *śraddhā* expresses truth as opposed to the falsehood of *aśraddhā*. In the *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* II.3.10.1 *śraddhā* represents the experience of the daughter of Prajāpati. In each of these *Brāhmaṇas* *śraddhā* expresses the human desire for a higher mode of existence, a way of being that arises from the ritual ceremony, a religious virtue not necessarily attached to any particular moral system. It is an attitude of the mind based on truth. To use a later philosophical category *śraddhā* is *āstikyabuddhi*, or a mental attitude of trust in that which is.

The central ritual act in the early Indian tradition was the *dīkṣā* or consecration. Here again this ritual is dependent on one’s *śraddhā*. In the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* XII.1.2.1, the offering is understood as a sacrifice to the goddess *Śraddhā* (27): *śraddhāyā vai devā dīkṣāṃ niramimata* – ‘from *Śraddhā*, indeed, have the gods achieved their consecration’. The *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* XII, 8, 2, 4 strongly exemplifies this point: *etad dīkṣāyai (rūpaṃ) yac chraddhā* – ‘dedication [*śraddhā*] is (the form to) consecration (*dīkṣā*)’. Arguing that *śraddhā* is ‘the asceticism of the soul’, Köhler points out that *śraddhā* is closely related to *tapas* (fervor, ardor), and that both constitute the essential

motifs of *dīkṣā* (27-8).⁵⁷ Köhler also shows how ‘sacrifice’ (*Opfer*) and ‘enthusiastic engagement’ (*Spendefreudigkeit*) come out of the understanding of *śraddhā* as ‘dedication, devotion’ (*Hingabe*), and are meanings represented mythologically in the goddess *Śraddhā*. This understanding continued on in the domestic sacrificial fire, which still represents the will power of the heart that compels one to sacrifice or link oneself with the divine (34).

The goddess *Śraddhā* might be said to possess those who perform the sacrifice with respect. She is their form of joy and enthusiasm, and prepares them for heroic deeds. In the sacrifice the gods are said to dress themselves with *Śraddhā*. As the *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa*: II, 8, 8, 8 (from the Hymn to *Śraddhā*) says: *śraddhā devān adhivaste* – ‘the gods dress *Śraddhā* as their clothes’, and III, 12, 3, 1: *śraddhayā devo devatvam aśnute* – ‘a god achieves divinity through *Śraddhā*’ (35).

In conclusion, when one is possessed by *śraddhā*, one’s whole soul and heart are engaged in the sacrifice, as exemplified in the two passages below:

Gopatha Brāhmaṇa I, 2, 14 (similar to *Vaitāna Sūtra* V, 3):

yadaiva kadācid ādadhyaċ chraddhā tv evainaṃ nātīyāt

Whenever somebody wants to kindle the fire, the attitude of *enthusiastic engagement* should never leave.

Baudhāyana Dharma Sūtra 1.c. 6:

aśraddhā paramaḥ pāpmā śraddhā hi paramaṃ tapaḥ /

tasmād aśraddhayā dataṃ havir nāśnanti devatāḥ //

⁵⁷ The *Baudhāyana Śrauta Sūtra* XXIX, 8 exemplifies this point:

śraddhayā śudhyate buddhiḥ śraddhayā matiḥ / śraddhayā prāpyate brahma śraddhā pāpaprāṇāśnī //

Through devotion the intellect is purified; through devotion the mind is purified. Through devotion one attains *Brahman*; devotion destroys evil.

Lack of enthusiastic engagement (*Spendefreudigkeit*) is the highest evil, because *enthusiastic engagement* is the highest *tapas*.⁵⁸

That is why the gods don't eat the offering which is given without *enthusiasm* (*Spendefreudigkeit*).

II.3. Śrāddha and Śraddhā

Overall this section develops the point that a faithful attention to *śrāddha* rites already takes one on to the understanding of *śraddhā* in terms of soul force and religious enthusiasm. Implicit in the performance of the *śrāddha* (funeral) rites is the belief in the after-death survival of the deceased ancestors. Furthermore, the emotional bond that these rituals entail is known as *śraddhā*, and is considered the main constituent of the *śrāddha* rites themselves. In this section, therefore, I make clear how *Vedic* death rituals, including the fire (*Agni*) that burns the deceased, play a role in triggering 'fervent' emotions, emotions capable of giving rise to philosophical inquiries about the afterlife and the realm of the divine.

According to Köhler (50), the following explanation quoted in the O. Böhtlingk-Roth Sanskrit Dictionary already indicates that the rites of *śrāddha* are meant to develop understanding in the living and to help the deceased reach the realm of the *pitṛs*:

*pretaṃ pitṛṃś ca nirdiśya bhojyaṃ yat priyam ātmanaḥ /
śraddhayā dīyate yatra tac chrāddhaṃ parikīrtitam //*

[The sacrifice] is named *Śrāddha* insofar as it is so considered by those (the youngest) who attend the father's dinner, which is dear to them, and in which *śraddhā* is donated.

⁵⁸ As we will see, this statement is in harmony with the discussion of *tapas* and *śraddhā* in BhG 17.13-7.

Śraddhā is what guarantees immortality, and is also present in the ritual act (*śrāddha*) to establish a bond with the deceased in the world of the Fathers. In this sense, affection and esteem shown toward the ancestors, combined with the attitude of respect toward death, then, are at the very core of those rites, which have fed the Indian belief in a life to come, as well as the possibility of some interaction between these two different realms. For, it is close to death and its rituals that we all are led to reflect upon the possibility of some kind of existence after death. Being at the same time both, motivation or will to sacrifice and the sacrifice-prize, *śraddhā* also represents, what Köhler has termed the human sense of “religious fervour” (*religiösen Eifer*) (53) about the imperishable nature of the good deeds.

Kane also explores the rites after death (*Antyeṣṭi*) and rites of death (*Śrāddha*) in detail in the fourth volume of his series.⁵⁹ Eschatology, he says there, is the word we commonly use to address issues such as what happens after death. He sees these issues as universal and present in every religion. They involve in his view not only theories related with the final destiny of the individual and the immortality of the soul, but also the individual’s relation to the whole universe (1973, Vol. IV, 179).

Death rites play a central role in both *Śruti* and *Smṛti* literature. In the *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* III.14.1 and in the *Praśna Upaniṣad* III.10, for instance, we find the idea that one’s last thoughts correlate with what happens to the soul after death, and have a role in determining how the self transmigrates. The importance of death in ritual terms is central to the plot of the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad*, where Naciketas is shown requesting Yama, the god of

⁵⁹ We have already mentioned his *History of Dharmaśāstra*, 2nd ed. (1968-1977).

death, that he clarify whether there is survival after death or not (*Kaṭha Upaniṣad* I.1.20). In the story of the *Mahābhārata*, the centrality of the death rites is easily seen. There, a large portion of the text – four whole *parvans*, from six to nine –, are taken up with the issues leading to the deaths of Bhīṣma, Droṇa, Karṇa, and Śālyā. In the *Mahābhārata* we also have full descriptions of the rites of cremation for Pāṇḍu in the *Ādiparvan* (MBh 1.127), Droṇa in the *Strīparvan* (MBh 11.23.38-42), Bhīṣma (who waits to die during the period of *Uttarāyana*, when the sun goes North and favours final release) in the *Aṇuśāsanaparvan* (MBh 13.169.10-9), Kuntī, Dhṛtarāṣṭra, and Gāndhārī in the *Āśramavāsikaparvan* (MBh 15.39), and Kṛṣṇa in the *Mausalaparvan* (MBh 16.7.19-25) (Kane, 1973, vol. 4, 223). Theoretical discussions on the causes of premature death and long life, as well as theories about transmigration are also discussed at length in the *Mahābhārata*. In the *Gītā* also these issues are discussed, and reference is made to the doctrine of *punarjanma*, or of how the self transmigrates (BhG 2.22), and to the question as to how the self should approach the imperishable (BhG 8.5-6 and 8.23-5). Reference is made to the two paths (one leading to the world of the *devas* and the other to the world of the *pitṛs*) (BhG 9.25) and to what brings about final release from *saṃsāra* (BhG 7.29).

According to R. B. Pandey,⁶⁰ the earliest literary mention of the funeral ceremonies are found in the *R̥gveda* and *Atharvaveda*.⁶¹ *R̥gveda* X. 14-19 and

⁶⁰ For a further study on the link between *śrāddha* and *śraddhā* see his *Hindu Saṃskāras – Socio-Religious Study of the Hindu Sacraments* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass. 2nd ed., 1969).

⁶¹ The funeral hymns are a direct descendent of the *Vedic* Hymns, although it is only in the *Atharvaveda* XVIII.1-4 that they become elaborated (Pandey, 1969, 2-3). In the *Taittirīya Āraṇyaka* we find in its sixth chapter the *Mantras* of the *Pitṛmedha* (burning of the deceased), while the first systematic treatment of the *Vedic* sacrifices and domestic rites is found in the *Śrautasūtras* (5). The discussion of the *Saṃskāras* first appears in some of the *Gṛhyasūtras*, or in their addenda (*Pariśiṣṭas*), the *Pitṛmedhasūtras*, (Rules for the

Atharvaveda XVIII 2-34, along with other brief references, address the funeral rites (Pandey, 1969, 237-244). We also find a description of these ceremonies in the *Taittirīya Āraṇyaka* VI, under the title of *Pitṛmedha*, or rites for the welfare of the *manes* (1969, 245). Although the term *śraddhā* already appears in the *Ṛgveda* (2,500 – 1,000 BCE), the term *śrāddha* is not used there to name the funeral rites. The first occurrence of the term *śrāddha* seems to be that of the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad* (600 BCE), where it expresses the sentiment of ancestor worship. Shastri refers to this fact in the following terms:

The word *śrāddha* as noted before, is unknown to the Vedic *saṃhitās* and the ancient *Brāhmaṇas*; we meet with the word for the first time in a passage of the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad*.² (1963, 128)

² Adhyāya I. Valli 3. Verse 17. – ‘And he who repeats this greatest mystery in an assembly of *Brāhmaṇas*, or, full of devotion, at the time of *Śrāddha* sacrifice, obtains thereby infinite rewards’.

The term *śrāddha* appears, then to be an adjective derived from the noun *śraddhā* in accordance to the rule provided by Pāṇini in *Aṣṭādhyāyī* V.1.109. Pāṇini himself uses the word in his *Aṣṭādhyāyī* V.2.85.⁶² If the term ‘*śrāddha*’ is not used in the *Vedic saṃhitās* and ancient *Brāhmaṇas*, it becomes common in later *Vedic* literature. The passage *Manusmṛti* III.275-86, for instance, describes *śraddhā* as the essential component in the performance of the *śrāddha* rites and the gratification of the *pitṛs*, and the *Mārkaṇḍeya*

Burning of the Deceased) or in the related *Kalpas* (ceremonial rules), such as the *Śrāddhakalpas* (Rules for Funeral Ceremonies) (6-7). The *Dharmasūtras*, which is perhaps a continuation of the *Gṛhyasūtras*, adapts the domestic and private rules to the social realm, but without describing rituals of any kind (7-8). Dealing with the *Varṇāśramadharmas* (rules for the castes and stages of life), the *Dharmasūtras* also contain rules about the *Śrāddhas*, developing its social aspects (8). Marking the transition to the *Paurāṇika Hinduism*, the *Smṛtis* build upon the *Dharmasūtras* and discuss, many issues, such as the *Pāñcamahāyajñas*, the funeral ceremonies, and sacrifices to the dead (8). The *Purāṇas* have influenced the *Dharmasāstra* literature, and even the *Dharmasūtras* quote the *Purāṇas* (9). The *Śrāddhakalpa* of the *Yajñavalkya Smṛti* is the same as given in the *Agni* and the *Garuḍa Purāṇas* (10).

⁶² Pāṇini brings in here the terms ‘*śrāddhin*’ and ‘*śrāddhika*’. The passage reads: “The affixes ‘*ini*’ and ‘*ika*’ come after the word *śrāddha* in the sense of ‘this is eaten by him’.” The reference is to the food one eats on the day the ceremony of *śrāddha* takes place.

Purāna 29.27 explicitly relates *śrāddha* to *śraddhā* and to the doctrine of *karma* and *punarjanma* (Kane, 1973, vol. 4, 351-2). And Kane shows how the explicit link of *śrāddha* and *śraddhā* continues when he refers to the later *Brahmapurāṇa* passage: ‘whatever is given with faith [*śraddhā*] to *brāhmaṇas* intending it to be for the (benefit of) *pitṛs* at a proper time, in a proper place, to deserving persons and in accordance with the prescribed procedure is called *śrāddha*’ (1973, 335).

D. R. Shastri⁶³ provides a theological frame which shows why *śraddhā* appears as the basis of the *śrāddha* rites. Shastri divides the rites for the dead into three stages: *Pūrva Kriyā* (Preliminary Rites), *Madhyama Kriyā* (Intermediate Rites), and *Uttara Kriyā* (Subsequent Rites) (1963, i). The rites of burning, offering of *pūraka* lumps, and touching of water are the preliminary rites that take the soul from its bodily life. Those from the first *ekoddiṣṭa* rite on the eleventh day up to the *sapiṇḍī karaṇa* rite at one year are the intermediate ones during the period when the soul is in the form of a *preta*. The rites to be performed for a *pitṛ* are the subsequent ones. The idea is that the deceased does not enter at once into the world of the *pitṛs*, but wanders for a while as a *preta*. It is through the *ekoddiṣṭa* and *sapiṇḍī karaṇa śrāddhas* that the *preta* is carefully delivered to the *pitṛs*. As Shastri explains, “the full number of *śrāddhas* necessary for the *sapiṇḍī karaṇa* is ordinarily sixteen – the first one, then one in each of the twelve months, then two semestral and lastly the *sapiṇḍana*” (63). Some texts suggest a variation, as for instance the *Brahmapurāṇa*, which argues that the sixteen *śrāddhas* are to be performed

⁶³ We have already mentioned his *Origin and Development of the Rituals of Ancestor Worship in India* (Calcutta: Bookland Private Limited, 1963).

within a year – on the fourth, fifth, ninth, and eleventh days, after which it is to be performed once a month for a year (65).

In the Vedic period, Shastri says, the belief was that the deceased would become a *pitṛ* (ancestor) immediately after the disposal of the corpse. During the period when the *gṛhya* (domestic) *sūtras* were written, the idea was introduced that they would remain a *preta* (ghost) until some rituals were performed for the release from the *preta* stage (1). Still later, the conception of the *ātivāhika* (*ati-vāha* = ‘fleeter than wind’, the *liṅgaśarīra*) or subtle body was introduced, and it was said that as soon as the gross body is burnt the self takes refuge in the subtle body. The *pūraka* offering of a meal helps in the creation of the *preta śarīra*, and the monthly rites from the *ekoddiṣṭa śrāddha* to the *sapiṅḍī karaṇa* help destroy the *preta śarīra*, and allow the departed to become a *pitṛ*. It is after becoming a *pitṛ* that the spirit of a deceased person takes part in the so-called *piṅḍapitṛ yajña*.

As a *pitṛ*, the deceased is worshipped in accordance with the rite of *Pārvaṇa* (oblations offered at new and full moon), which “owes its origin to the Vedic rites of *pitṛ yajña* and *piṅḍapitṛ yajña*,” as discussed in the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* II.4.2 (99). Generally speaking, the *piṅḍapitṛyajña* is to be performed after midday on the day of the new moon, with the sacrifice taking place in the fireplace to the south or the direction of death. Shastri argues that the feeding of *Brāhmaṇas* was not part of the ritual in the *Brāhmaṇas* and the *Śrauta sūtras*, and was probably introduced during the *Gṛhya* period (103). The *pitṛ yajña* is explained in the *Taittirīya saṃhita* of the Black *Yajurveda* as

well as in the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* II. 6.1. Both *yajñas* use the term ‘*svadhā*’, which also designates a blessing or benediction, to refer to the portion offered to the *pitṛs*.

The motive in a *pitṛ yajña* is to establish a relation “with the *pitṛs*, the gods, the animal world, the human world and with *Brahman*” (110). That is to say, those rituals help one to understand that no one is alone, and that we all are interconnected with the whole universe. It is not very different in the case of the *piṇḍapitṛ yajña*, where one is led to develop confidence in the existence of the cosmic power through the contemplation of the regular course of nature with its coming and going.

The important thing to stress is that the death of a family member represents the occasion for the development of something like ancestor worship, or at least ancestral ritual activity. Shastri stresses this point when he says that Manu revealed these *śrāddha* ceremonies as a way to help mankind toward salvation (126). According to him, even though the term ‘*śrāddha*’ is not found in the *Vedic Saṃhitās*, the ceremonies later designated by the term are taught in the *Vedic* ritual texts. As we have already seen, references to the *pitṛ yajña* goes back even to the *Ṛg Veda*, as in X.14. In the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* it appears as one of the five⁶⁴ daily *yajñas* performed by the husband on behalf of the household. For, no matter what one does in a day, it should include this *pañcasamṣkāra*⁶⁵ in which one feels oneself in relation with the entire universe.

⁶⁴ According to the *Manusamhitā*, the five are: *brahma-yajña* (sacrifice for *Brahman*), which means the study and teaching of theology; *pitṛ yajña* (sacrifice to the fathers), which is performed in the form of water offering to the ancestors; *deva-yajña* (sacrifice for the deities), which is the offering of oblations to the deities; *bhūta-yajña* (sacrifice for the beings of nature), which means the providing of living creatures needs, and *manuṣya-yajña* (sacrifice for the social), which is expressed in terms of hospitality.

⁶⁵ Shastri explains that the *samṣkāra* originated from the *upanayana* rite, which is meant to make one fit for studying the Vedas. The word *samṣkāra* (refining, training, purification), he argues, “came to mean ‘a

According to the *Manusamhitā*, the *pitṛyajña* consists in a *tarpaṇa* (satiating, from *tip*, to satisfy) to the ancestor by making an offering of water. This oblation is made pronouncing the name of the ancestor and the word ‘*svadhā*.’

Shastri also provides a summary of the classification and explanation of the *śrāddhas* as they appear in Maxmüller,⁶⁶ where the theological link of *śrāddha* and *śraddhā* is brought to the attention of the reader. Shastri tries to show how Maxmüller stresses that *śraddhā*⁶⁷ or devotion is part of all the ceremonies of ancestor worship, and it is on that basis that they can be called *Śrāddha*. Shastri himself would go even further, and argue that it is here that one finds the origins of religion.⁶⁸ Quoting from the Nandi Purāṇa, Shastri shows how the three major deities of Hinduism, Viṣṇu, Brahmā, and Maheśvara, can be said to be ‘*Pitṛs*’, They appear, respectively, as the ‘father’ of the universe; the ‘grandfather, and the ‘great grandfather’. As Shastri continues,

According to Nighaṇṭu Koṣa,¹ the word ‘*śrat*’ means truth.² Durgacāryya explains Śraddhā as ‘that which is the receptacle of truth’. That idea which is developed in

merit or improvement originated in one’s own body or in another’s body due to the performance of some duties ordained” (246).

⁶⁶ He says: “Maxmüller, however, classifies the ceremonies of ancestor worship under four heads: – (1) the daily ancestral sacrifices or the *Pitṛyajña* as one of the daily five great sacrifices (*Panca mahāyajña*) (2) the monthly ancestral sacrifice or the *Piṇḍa Pitṛyajña* as a part of the new-moon and full-moon sacrifices (3) the funeral ceremonies on the death of a householder and (4) the *Agapes* or feasts of love and charity commonly called *Śrāddhas* at which food and other charitable gifts are bestowed on deserving persons in memory of the deceased ancestors. The name of *Śrāddha*, remarks the renowned scholar, belongs, properly, to this last class only; but it has been transferred to the second and third classes of sacrifices also, because *śraddhā*, or devotion forms an important part of them” (132). For a detailed account of a later classification of the *śrāddhas*, see also the *Bhaviṣyapurāṇa*, in the *Nirṇaya Sindhu*, Chapter III, *Śrāddha prakaraṇa*.

⁶⁷ Notice that the use of the Christian Greek term *agape* (charity; Latin *caritas*, from *carus*, of value) suggests here the idea of the universality of *śraddhā*. Furthermore, it also suggests its understanding as ‘the soul-force that puts love in motion’, for *agape* has also been translated as ‘love’.

⁶⁸ I quote his words: “Some scholars maintain that (1) ancestor-worship is the root of every religion and that (2) the cult of ancestors owes its origins to the sense of awe among aborigines. . . And again, regarding the second point, there are grounds for believing that ‘awe’ is not the only or even primary reason for the deification of the hero. The cult of the distinguished dead was often founded not so much upon ‘awe’ as upon the desire of the survivors to maintain friendly relations with the spirits of the departed” (287).

mind in favour of and not in opposition to virtue, wealth, pleasure and liberation is Śraddhā. Śraddhā is the essence of Dharma. Where there is no Śraddhā there is no Dharma.³ Vyāsa in his Pātañjalabhāṣya explains Śraddhā as composure of mind.⁴ Śāṅkara in his commentary of Gītā explains Śraddhā as belief in divine revelation.⁵ (369)

¹ III. 10. 2

² Śraditi satya nāmasu paṭhitam.

³ Śrat asyāṃdhīyate iti śraddhā. Pradhānamidamangaṃ dharmasya yā śraddhā; tadabhāve dharmā bhāvāt.

⁴ Cetasah prasādah.

⁵ Āstikya buddhih.

Śraddhā, then, is the essential component which is present, not only in *śrāddha* rites, but in all and any good action.

Before closing this discussion I would like to refer to the first Western publication on the *śrāddha* rites, by D. Urquhart, which I mentioned earlier. My reasons for rescuing this early text is to bring my readers' attention to the author's romantic reaction to what he discovered. The opening statement of this work is worth mentioning in full:

This ceremony [*śrāddha*] belongs to no one race or creed, for it is the link between the races, and the common matrix of their creeds; it transcends all other branches in importance, and exceeds them in difficulty. It cannot be dealt with as history, or as metaphysics, for both are born from it: in the mysteries of life and love its spring is hidden, and is not to be found unless sought for there. As on entering a sacred grove, here also we must deposit the profane vestment of opinion, nor would this (if practicable) be all; we must surrender for a time our judgement as well and give up our wisdom as our folly; for a clear eye will not give you to know man as if he were a crystal or a plant: the eye to see him by is the soul (1).

Urquhart's romantic statement shows how he struggles to find the attitude and method that are needed when faced with an alien subject, one which presents the possibility of completely transforming one's *Weltanschauung*, or world view. As Urquhart shows, he is overwhelmed to find that what he considers a 'primitive' child has a duty toward his or

her parents and the extended line of ancestors. This primitive person must maintain a relationship that does not cease with life: “it is the part of the son to ‘serve his parents dead as he had served them living’” (2).

The link he sees is expressed as follows: “In Sanscrit it [*śraddhā*] is rendered ‘faith.’ Had it originally had this meaning, it could never have been given to any ceremony in particular” (14). The rites of *śrāddha*, he seems to suggest, being concrete, operate in relation with their equivalent universal, or abstract, idea of *śraddhā*. For, he continues, *śraddhā* “is the evidence of the primitive and universal simplicity of faith” (33). The reverence for the beings of the ancestors turns out to be a reverence for the universal being itself. And so, Urquhart concludes, “from a tribe whom we have been accustomed to consider, if warlike, savage – and if conquering, stupid – has proceeded the whole mass of the metaphysical ideas and religious sentiment, no less than the arts of the ancient world” (42).

Lighting this fire on the sacred funeral pyre rites is what we know as the ritual of *śrāddha*. The worship of deceased ancestors extends this, ‘the line of life’, and is what we come to know as *pitriya* (relating to ancestral). Among the offerings of the ceremony, the very first are in the form of grains; for, they come from earth, and thus represent this ‘line of life’. Next come other things, especially, the well-known balls of rice. Then it follows the song of the *Pitṛs* (ancestors), which, in Urquhart’s analysis, shows: “Those of our descendents shall follow a righteous path, and shall reverently present us with cakes of Gaya. May he born in our race give us” (7).

Of importance here is the subtle emotional stimuli to reflect upon a righteous path. Here the universal concept of a ‘righteous path’ is being thought by encouraging this very concrete ritual duty. It is as if the care that the parents taught during life reflect the control in which all life organizes itself. As Urquhart understands it, *śrāddha* provides the foundations of religion. He explains that there are twelve distinct kinds of *śrāddha* (9). The tenth is “Sraddha, in honour of deities,” and the ninth is the solemn rites to the ancestors. Others included the daily sacraments, oblations to the gods, to the spirits, and so on. So, the line between the duties to the ancestors and to the gods is obscured. Slowly a kind of incorporeal trust in the transcendent emerges, first in the form of care for the ancestors and then reverence for deities themselves.⁶⁹

Pandey also understands that, although covered in mystery, the origin of the funeral ceremonies is perhaps linked to the necessity to explain that death only represents the separation of the soul from the physical body (1969, 234-5). Another factor would be the sentiment of affection together with the concern towards the future welfare of the deceased (235-6). And a third important factor could be said to be the necessity of a proper disposal of the corpse (236). From the time of the *Vedas* up to the present, the burning of the dead body has become the most recognized mode of disposal (241). Regarded as the mediator between the human and the divine realms, Agni (fire) would

⁶⁹ In this interpretation, the symbolism of fire is connected with ritual sacrifice; it is connected with paying homage to the ancestors (*pitrs*), and it is connected with ‘religious experience of death. It is then from myth that we first get our imagery for understanding what life is, what soul is, or with placing one in relation to the social and cosmic order (*Brahman*). It is, therefore, this care with the memory of the past that gives the finite individual a sense of the infinite. Following this logic the individual first relates to mythology through the experience of death.

carry, then, the oblations from this world to the beyond, and allow the dead to receive a new body and join the ancestors in Yama's world (242).

In conclusion, life, regarded as a cycle, starts where it also ends, and this was spontaneously represented, without any kind of dogmatic attitude, through the *saṃskāras*, whose origin is lost in antiquity. With the course of time, the symbols and taboos present in the *saṃskāras*, clothed them with the religious garb of the *karmamārga*, fulfilling their aim of creating the conditions for the development of the individual in a world full of natural and supernatural forces (275-6).

With the decline of *Vedic* culture, the advent of Islam, and the development of *Purāṇic* dogmatism, however, “devotion diverted the attention of the people,” “emphasis was laid on idol-worship,” and “life shifted from home – the venue of the *Saṃskāras* – to places of pilgrimage and the temples” (277-9). Yet, while some schools of thought would attack the *saṃskāras* as vain, others would acknowledge that humans could not live without them (277). These rites represent, then, a mastering process, a purifying sacrament, a “religious act regarded as an outward and visible sign of inward and spiritual grace;” a “confirmation of some promise or oath: things of mysterious significance, sacred influence and symbol” (15-6). In these rites, Agni (Fire) is the most important and holy constituent (36), being represented also in the family hearth as the *Gṛhapati*, or the lord of the house and the mediator priest (36-7).

II.4. A Scholarly Dispute on Continuity

The general question about the possible continuity or discontinuity of meaning from one period to the other is one that has troubled scholars since the beginning of Western studies of Indian civilization.⁷⁰ This section discusses to what extent the early traditions' usage of the term *śraddhā* continued in the language of the *Gṛ̥ā* through two connected issues of decisive importance. The first issue is related to the problems involved in distinguishing the term *śraddhā* from *bhakti*, and the second is related to the theological consequences involved in accepting the continuity of meaning of the term *śraddhā* from the *Veda* to the *Gṛ̥ā*.

As we have seen, the term *śraddhā* is central both to the ritual understanding and to the hymnody and myth of the early Indian Tradition. As the Tradition evolved the term remained central, but new terms were introduced as well, and sometimes these new terms fit into the areas once covered by the term *śraddhā*. Scholarship on this matter has not been decisive. The investigations of a number of scholars (Friedrich Otto Schrader,⁷¹

⁷⁰ Paul Younger presents a summary of these issues on continuity in his review of *The Destiny of the Veda in India*, by Louis Renou, *Change and Continuity in Indian Religion*, by J. Gonda, and “Man in the Universe: some Cultural Continuities in India,” by W. Norman Brown (*Journal of The American Academy of Religion* XXXVI, 1 (March 1968): 75-79). Showing how the problem of “change” and “continuity” becomes a “quest for continuity,” Younger reminds us that none of these three scholars convincingly resolves the problem. Professor Renou, he says, “nowhere offers any historical analysis of how or why” “the reverence accorded to the Veda did not prevent its becoming a ‘distant object . . . stripped of its textual substance’”(76). Professor Gonda, he continues, notes the work of Renou, but centers “his discussion on the ritual element in the religious tradition,” and manages to link up ritual patterns of later Hinduism that go back to the Ṛg Veda (76). That is to say, if Renou simply mocks the Indian idea of continuity, Gonda manages to present evidence of continuity limited to the underlying ritual structures (79).

⁷¹ F. O. Schrader, “The Sacrificial Wheel taught in the Bhavavadgītā” (*Indian Historical Quarterly*, Vol. 5, No. 2, 1929), 173-181.

Mrinal Das Gupta, Hans-Werbin Köhler,⁷² G. Dumézil,⁷³ Paul Hacker, Minoru Hara, K. L. Seshagiri Rao, and Gouriswar Bhattacharya,⁷⁴ among others) have dealt precisely with this question: To what extent has the *Vedic* concept of *śraddhā* been superseded by other terms designating the same reality?⁷⁵

⁷² See Köhler (1948/1973). Köhler undertook the task of determining how the meaning of the term *śraddhā* had evolved, and how this development might be understood in the History of religion. From the total of around 550 works (approximately 300 of *Vedic* nature, 150 from ancient Buddhism, and the remaining being of post-*Vedic* nature) he evaluated 301 separate texts (2/3 of *Vedic* nature and 1/3 from the Pali literature). He starts with the occurrences of the verbal cognates, which appear in the form *śrad-dhā*, and are mainly translated as ‘to trust’ (*vertrauen*). Second, he proceeds investigating the occurrences of *śraddhā* as a noun, identifying the following main meanings: a) trust or confidence (*Vertrauen*) – in the sense of loyalty (*Treue*) and/or devotion, dedication (*Hingabe*) – and b) enthusiastic donation or engagement (*Spendefreudigkeit*). Third, he discusses the Hymn to *Śraddhā*. Before moving to the philological details of his study on *śraddhā*, he also provides some examples of *Vedic śraddhā* as ‘belief’ (*Glauben*) (6-7). They are: 1. Aitareya Brāhmaṇa II, 40, 6 (which is similar to the following: Aitareya Brāhmaṇa I, 6, 11; Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa I, 3, 1, 27; Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad V, 14, 4, and Gopatha Brāhmaṇa II, 2, 23): *yataro vivadamānāyor āhām anuṣṭhyā cakṣuṣādarśam iti, tasya śraddadhāti* – when two people are arguing and one of them states “I saw it with my own eyes,” the other one, then, believes (glaubt) it. 2. Jaiminīya Brāhmaṇa I, 151 (ed. Caland): *śraddhāya devarṣī mā mantrakṛtāv avocatām iti* – trusting (Glauben, with the belief) that those who were telling that are two divine seers, two followers of Mantra. 3. Vājasaneyi Saṃhitā VIII, 5b: *śrād asmai naro vācase dadhāna* – You people, believe (glaubt) in these words! 4. Ṛg Veda X, 125,4 (and similarly in the Atharva Veda Saṃhitā IV, 30, 4): *śraddhivam te vadami* – I am telling you something believable. I can see how from the *Vedic śraddhā* taken to mean ‘belief’ one can be led to an understanding of the term in the *Gṛ̥ā* as ‘faith’. For if one can argue that in the *Ṛg Veda* the concept of *śraddhā* is established mostly in the hymns to Indra, with the meaning of ‘belief’, ‘to believe’ (theological Credo), than one is right to translate *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā* as ‘faith’ – at least as the belief in the existence of God. The problem is that as such, ‘faith’ does not explain Arjuna’s final decision to fight, for he had faith before. When it comes to show *śraddhā* as ‘belief’ there are many passages to choose from, as for instance, the *Vājasaneyi-saṃhitā* 19.77, where Prajāpati represents *Śraddhā* as truth and *aśraddhā* as falsehood, or that in *Vājasaneyi-saṃhitā* 19.30, which also says that truth is obtained by *śraddhā*. However, in any case, one who has no *śraddhā* has no motive for engaging in religious activity.

⁷³ G. Dumézil, “Quaestiunculae Indo-Italicae, 4-6” (Hommages `a Léon Herrmann, Collection Latomus 44 1960), 315-329).

⁷⁴ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, “Studies in the concept of *Śraddhā* in post-Vedic Hinduism” (Berlin: Dissertationsdruckstelle, 1971).

⁷⁵ This crucial argument would probably weaken my hypothesis about the importance of *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā*, were it not the very reason of its strength. For it is precisely because by the time of the commentaries on the *Gṛ̥ā* which have survived *śraddhā* had already faded in importance, that the term does not come out of the analysis the *Gṛ̥ā* as it should – the first responsible for such a mistake being Śāṅkara himself.

On the one side, Hara, Gonda, Hacker, Bolle, Das Gupta, Biardeau, Hildebeitel, Krishna Sharma, and even A. Sharma, all⁷⁶ state their belief that continuity is strong and that ritual never dropped its framing role. In the long run there is a common element in concepts such as *śraddhā* throughout the changing literary forms of the Tradition, and it is one of the concepts that defines that continuity. On the other side, Rao, Bhattacharya, van Buitenen, and Renou,⁷⁷ in different ways, argue for a discontinuity in religious terminology.

Before Minoru Hara started the contemporary controversy around the concept of *śraddhā* in 1963-4, when he published the innocently titled article “Note on Two Sanskrit Terms – *bhakti* and *śraddhā*,” Mrnal Das Gupta had already identified the problem involved in distinguishing the terms *bhakti* and *śraddhā*. Both scholars recognized the importance of making this distinction clear because it affects how one understands the development of the *Vedic* ritualistic tendencies, and the theology of the later period. Their articles, therefore, frame the controversy that starts here in the early traditions and continues in the context of understanding the theology of the *Gṛ̥ā*.

⁷⁶ See J. Gonda in his many works and more specifically in *Change and Continuity in Indian Religion* (The Hague: Mouton & Company, 1965), where he shows how ritual continuity holds the tradition together. He criticises the modern scholars who contend that the Vedic *yajña* (sacrifice) loses its importance and is completely overshadowed by the *pūjā* (mostly, the worship of an iconic god) of the Hindu period. Most important, Gonda also denounces their understanding that Hindu concerns with *mokṣa*, *yoga*, were completely foreign to the *Veda*, and due mostly to the influence of heterodox religions and indigenous non-*Vedic* culture (1965,12-6). ‘Discontinuity’, Gonda argues, is the result of scholars being too concerned with the change of outward forms (17). That is to say, Gonda presents evidence for what one may call structural continuity. See also Kees W. Bolle, in *The Persistence of Religion: An Essay on Tantrism and Sri Aurobindo’s Philosophy* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1965), where Bolle also argues for the continuity of religious forms in Indian Tradition.

⁷⁷ See Louis Renou, *Religions of Ancient India* (University of London, Athlone Press, 1953). He argues that “Religious terminology is almost completely transformed between the Veda and the Epic or the Purāṇas . . . Even in those cases where continuity has been suggested, as for Rudra-Śiva, the differences are really far more striking than the similarities” (47).

Das Gupta opens her analysis stating that the term *bhakti*, as a religious term, requires a personal deity for its object (1930, 315). That is to say, for her, *bhakti* means what Krishna Sharma will later call *saguṇa bhakti*. According to Das Gupta, then, *bhakti* is not compatible with the *Vedic* and *Upaniṣadic* tradition of worship. For, if *śraddhā*, evolving from *Vedic* ritual, is intellectually related to the impersonal and abstract idea of *Brahman* of the *Upaniṣads*, *bhakti*, is not.

As Das Gupta argues, the term *bhakti* is not employed with its later religious sense in the *Vedic Saṃhitās* (322). It is true that the root *bhaj*, from which *bhakti* is derived, is used in the *Vedas*.⁷⁸ According to Das Gupta even where the root *bhaj* occurs, it is never used with the sense of ‘to love’ or ‘to adore [a deity]’ in the *Vedic* passages (323). Nevertheless, she admits, by the time of Pāṇini the term *bhakti* had begun to mean ‘worshipped’ ‘loved’, but even then only in the passive sense, and not as a religious act of to ‘love’ or ‘worship’ (324). She argues that *Vedic* poets did not know the later concept of ‘faith’, although some feeling of devotion was never missing (324-5). For her the religious tone in the *Vedic* Hymns was one of fervent thanksgiving, and included an ethical frame of mind and an affectionate manner close to emotional love (326).

Using this analysis, one could argue that something like the later concept of *bhakti* or loving devotion was present in *Ṛgvedic* religion, although Das Gupta is hesitant to acknowledge any sense of the ‘erotic’, or even “a feeling of intimate and loving

⁷⁸ For instance in *Ṛg Veda* 1.127.5, which is a ‘late-*Vedic*’ hymn, even the terms *bhakta* and *abhakta* are distinguished, but according to the medieval commentator Sāyaṇa, these terms distinguish among the *Yajamānas* (the patrons of the sacrifices), between the terms *seva-mānas* (those who go to Agni for protection) and the *aseva-mānas* (those who do not go to Agni for protection) (322).

devotion” (326). The gods were anthropomorphic, and were invoked by name and form, and inspired, especially in the case of Varuṇa, the god associated with *ṛta* (the moral order), a sense of intimacy, which one might associate with personal devotion (327). It is in this context that Varuṇa’s ‘forgiveness’ may appear to some as an act of grace. For, “it is the grace of the god, obtained through his slave-like devotion that make him [the hymn-writer] the beloved of this deity, guiltless and happy-hearted” (329-30).

Das Gupta argues that this language only makes sense in relative and contextualized terms, for she considers it at least partially incompatible with the theologically much more central theory of *karma*.⁷⁹ Das Gupta concludes that “there is nothing un-Indian or extra-Indian” in the frame of mind which the term *bhakti* indicates, and even the *Gītā* (BhG 4.11 and 7.21-3) includes it, and becomes “the earliest authoritative work on monotheistic *bhakti*” (331-2). As Das Gupta summarized the matter both the merit and the weakness of the “plebeian” *bhakti* religion “consists in just this that it needs no metaphysical preparation in its devotees” (332-3).

When it comes to the term *śraddhā* Das Gupta refers to the earlier work of Schrader. According to her reference he had “very pertinently pointed out long ago” that the “Latin *credo* is certainly identical with the Sanskrit *śraddhā* (= “trust, confidence, belief, uprightness”),” but she considers it “wholly arbitrary to assume that the word was an expression of *religio*” (316). Even when the term does possess religious significance,

⁷⁹ As she argues, although it is natural that “the ethical and mystic frame of mind in which an attitude of *bhakti* is possible should find expression in these fervent longings of the human heart for direct communion with divine life and for forgiveness and mercy,” “its philosophical background” was in her opinion not central in Indian Tradition (330).

she holds that it does not possess it in the sense intended for translations such as ‘faith’ or ‘devotion’ to a personal god (316). She states:

Schrader is undoubtedly right in rendering the word in English as ‘trust, confidence, belief, truth, uprightness’, without any implication of a sense of loving devotion, although authorities like Max Muller,² Macdonell,³ Whitney and Lanman⁴ would translate it, rather misleading, by the word ‘faith’. (316)

² *The Upaniṣads* (SBE), Oxford, 1900, *Kaṭha-Upaniṣad*, i, 2.

³ *Vedic Mythology*, p.119; also in Art. ‘Vedic hymn’ in ERE.

⁴ *Atharva-veda, Trans. and Notes* (HOS), pp. 209 (iv, 35, 7), 233 (v, 7, 5 but explained in the notes as ‘confidence’), 372 (vi, 122, 3), 536 (ix, 5, 21), 589 (x, 7, 1), 591 (x, 7, 11), etc.

She quotes from several *Ṛgveda* passages⁸⁰ and makes use of Sāyaṇa’s famous medieval commentary on them to show that *śrat+dhā* means ‘high regard’ (*ādara-atiśaya*; supreme care), ‘esteem’ (*bahumāna*; great respect) or ‘belief in truth’ (*viśvāsa*; trust, confidence) (316-8).⁸¹ She also quotes from the *Vājasaneyi Saṃhitā* of the *Yajurveda* (VS 8.5; 19.30, and 19.77) to show “*śraddhā* as ‘trust’, *viśvāsa*, or ‘belief in the existence and generosity of the gods’, *āstikya-buddhi*,” and also *para-loka-viśvāsa*, or ‘belief in the next world’ – which is *satya*, or ‘truth’, as opposed to *aśraddhā*, which stand for ‘falsehood’ (318-9). She goes on to show that these meanings are in agreement with similar passages of the *Atharvaveda*, where *śraddhā* appears in the interpretation of Sāyaṇa to mean *ādara* (regard), *viśvāsa* (trust), *abhilāsa-viśeṣa* (superior wish), and

⁸⁰ RV 1.55.5; 1.103.3; 1.103.5; 1.104.7; 2.12.5; 2.75.2; 10.39.5; 10.147.1; 1.104.6; 2.26.3; 10.113.9; 8.1.31; 9.113.2; 7.32.14; 1.108.6; 9.113.4, and 1.102.2.

⁸¹ Indian commentators seem to be hesitant to address *śraddhā* as a religious concept. Köhler reminds us that Sāyaṇa prefers to understand *śraddhā* as *viśvāsa* (trust, confidence), but sometimes also as *bhakti* (loving dedication), *āstikyabuddhi* (faithful attitude), *ādara* (regard, respect, care), *bahumāna* (great respect), *abhilāṣaviśeṣa* (a distinct desire), and (*abhi-*) *ruci* (being pleased with) (Köhler, 1973, 10).

āstikya-buddhi, now in the sense of a ‘belief in the efficacy of ritualistic worship’ (319-20).⁸²

Das Gupta then takes up Oldenberg’s interest in *śraddhā*, mostly in later ritualistic *Brāhmaṇa* literature, as gift, or *dakṣiṇā*. In this sense Oldenberg renders the meaning that “he who is liberal in offering *dakṣiṇā* to the priest at the sacrifice is supposed to have *śraddhā*” (320-1). While she recognizes this use, she also points out that *śraddhā* is not usually an external ritual term and also appears in passages such as Nirukta of Yāska 9.30, *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* 12.7.3.11, and *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* 2.3.10.1 with the meaning of an attitude of the mind based on truth. In these contexts the “intuitive attitude of belief,” is rooted in a mythic being or goddess called *Śraddhā*. She is said in these texts to be a manifestation of Agni, the daughter of the Sun, or of Prajāpati (322). Das Gupta’s conclusion, then, is that the meaning of *śraddhā*, at least in the *Vedic Saṃhitās*, cannot be said to be very close to that of *bhakti*.

In the younger *Vedas* and *Brāhmaṇas*, Das Gupta acknowledges that there is a change in the spirit of worship. The older hymnal worship of nature-gods is replaced by a more ritualistic worship in which the priest exerts great control over the the patron (487). The ritual is now mechanically administered as a cure to universal sin and evil, and the belief had grown that, once perfectly performed, ritual would give results

⁸² AV 11.2.28; 11.10.28; 6.122.3, and 11.9.9. Das Gupta makes it clear that even in the passages where there is no commentary by Sāyaṇa (i.e., AV 5.7.5; 9.5.21; 10.7.1; 13.6.2; 15.2.5; 15.7.2-5, and 15.16.4.) the meanings are similar. Smith states that Das Gupta, “as a modern skeptic about ritualism,” takes *āstikya buddhi* as ‘belief in the efficacy of the ritualistic worship’, “whereas the same Sanskrit words [from Sāyaṇa: *tad-anuṣṭhāna-viṣayā āstikya buddhi*] could equally well be rendered as an awareness, or recognition, of its propriety, or obligatoriness.” He then supplies a literal translation: “that positive awareness that manifests itself in the performance of” those ritual actions” (Smith 1979, n.84, 246).

independent of the gods' will. The proper performance of the ritual would give “mastery over the universe and the gods”– a system which critics argued would leave no place for either morality or religion (488).

Das Gupta argues that in fact, both, religion and morality, would remain fully alive in the *Āraṇyakas* and *Upaniṣads* (488). The *Āraṇyakas* and the *Upaniṣads* give continuity to the tradition, and “have the appearance of constituting one whole text with the *Brāhmaṇas*” (490). The *Brāhmaṇas* attach importance to *kriyā* (religious action) or *anuṣṭhāna* (undertaking religious practice) as external sacrifice, as much as the *Upaniṣads* value inner sacrifice (491). She sees a natural transition from the “god-lore of the *Ṛg Veda* and the sacrificial lore of the *Brāhmaṇas*,” to the theories of the *Upaniṣads* (492). In her view “it would not be absolutely correct to suppose that the *Upaniṣads* are concerned only with Knowledge and not with Being, that they are content only with the explanation of Reality and not give intimations of its mystical attainment” (494).

Das Gupta argues that the *Upaniṣadic saḡuṇa* descriptions of *Brahman*, as exemplified in the doctrine of Śāṇḍilya (*Chāṇḍogya Upaniṣad*, III.4), which many see as the origin of the *bhakti-vāda*, are best understood as a poetical personification of *Brahman*. In other words, she argues in the spirit of the *Vedānta* that *saḡuṇa Brahman* only occupies a lower position in relation to the impersonal Absolute. The fuller understanding is represented by Yajñavalkya's *nirguṇa* theory, described in the third and the fourth chapters of the *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad*.

Minoru Hara generally agrees with Das Gupta's line of argument. He is, for instance, of the opinion that in the *Gñā bhakti* is generally seen as related to dependence on a theistic god, and that is not the case with *śraddhā*, which preserves a more traditional concept of religion, independent of theism. As we have mentioned earlier, it was his article in 1963 on the terms *bhakti* and *śraddhā* that really started the contemporary controversy around the concept of *śraddhā*. He does not acknowledge the earlier study of Das Gupta, perhaps thinking that her arguments are arranged in terms of a more Indian style of scholarship.

Hara's study of the terms *śraddhā* and *bhakti* was in the form of a classic philological study, a style of scholarship he learned in Germany. He did not consider the thesis of Dr. Hans Werbin Köhler, *Śraddhā in der vedischen und alt-buddhistischen Literatur* (Göttingen, 1948), which would only be published in 1973, and may or may not have known about it. Hara's own investigation is very thorough. In the case of the term *bhakti*, besides considering the sentences in which the term occurs by itself, he also analyzed the many instances in which the term occurs either as first or as last member of a compound. In these compounds different connotations were often revealed (Hara 1963, 124-5). For the term *śraddhā*, his arrangement was somewhat different, because *śraddhā* seldom occurs in compounds. So, he discussed both the nominal and verbal occurrences of the term, also taking notice of its use in the commentary literature (132).

Studying examples from the classical period of Sanskrit; *Meghadūta* I. 55ab, *Kathāsaritsāgara* 24.105, *Kumārasaṃbhava* 6.73cd, *Kūrmapurāṇa* I.16.219, and *Saudarananda* 5.1cd, he shows that *bhakti* often appears as the first word in a compound

with words derived from the verbal root *nam* (to bow). Hara concludes that this attitude of ‘bowing’ to somebody is evidence that the term *bhakti* commonly refers to interaction between persons, and in religious contexts to personal devotion (125). Studying the passages *Kathāsaritsāgara* 13.53; 13.196; 16.9; 17.48; 22.246, *Veṅṣaṃhāra* 2.24 3-4; 6.12 17-18; 6.46.b, *Raghuvamśa* 8.26 ab, *Mallinātha ad Raghuvamśa* 12.9, *Kumārasaṃbhava* 8.77 e *Ratnāvalī* 4.20 1-2, where *bhakti* appears as the last member in a compound, he again observes the personal link implied in the term, with the reference often to someone emotionally related to the speaker, such as father, wife, and so on (126-7). Considering the passages *Kaivalya Upaniṣad* 5b, *Cārudatta* 1.21.12 TSS. p.27 line 3, *Nāgānanda* I.16 11-13; 1.6cd; 5.13; 5.38 1-3, *Veṅṣaṃhāra* 6.17 ab, *Kathāsaritsāgara* 13.107; 14.65; 20.56; 24.156; 26.154; 81.56, *Saudarananda* 4.29; 6.17ab; 14.46ab; 14.47; 16.86, *Śukasaptati* 7 p. 23 lines 22-23; 19, *Śvestāsvatara Upaniṣad* 6.23, *Mattavilāsa* 21ab, *Raghuvamśa* 5.14; 12.34, *Pañcarātra* 2.5ab; 2.60ab, *Uttararāmacarita* 4.11, *Abhiṣekanāṭaka* 2.14ab, *Mālatīmādhava* 5.25, *Bālacarita* 1.5ab, where the term *bhakti* appears as simplex, he observes that there too the context has a personal and emotional nuance (127-30). Considering the passages *Kathāsaritsāgara* 15.10; 20.56; 21.48-49, *Saudarananda* 4.29ab; 14.18-19; 18.4, *Raghuvamśa* 5.20cd, *Īśvaragītā* 11.73, *Uttararāmacarita* 6.10, and *Kāvyaḍarśa* 2.276-277, in which the word *bhakti* appears in an enumeration, he again finds the emotional and reverential aspect of *bhakti* (130-1). A brief glance in the Commentaries of *Mallinātha* on *Meghadūta* 1.36, 55, *Raghuvamśa* 2.22; 5.14; 8.26; 10.58; 13.67, and *Kumārasaṃbhava* 8.77, confirms his results (131).

In the case of the term *śraddhā*, Hara discusses both secular and religious contexts such as: *Uttararāmacarita* 2.6 15-16; 7.6ab, *Saudarananda* 12.30; 12.33-35; 12.43, *Kathāsaritsāgara* 21.47; 24.119; 29.48, 34.214, *Kāvyaḍarśa* 3.65ab, *Pratijñānāyugaḍharāyaṇa* 2.9ab, *Chāḍdogya Upaniṣad* 1.1.10; 6.12.3; 7.19-20, *Raghuvamśa* 2.16; 11.42; 15.72, *Priyadarśikā* I, p. 8, line 6, *Cārudatta* 3.15, *Pañcarātra* 2.34cd; 3.191.1, *Śakuntalā* 5.26.4; 7.29, *Pañcatantra* I, p. 27 lines 11-12, *Veṇiśaṃhāra* 5.34.1, *Pratimānātaka* 4.27ab, *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* 1.5.3; 3.9.21; 5.14.4; 6.2.15, *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* 1.2.11; 2.1.7; 3.2.10, *Bhavavadgṇā* 3.31; 4.39; 17.1;17.13; 18.71, *Manusmṛti* 3.2593.275, *Taittirīya Upaniṣad* 2.4.1, as well as a couple of verses from commentators such as Śaṅkara, who discuss *śraddhā* when commenting on the *Gṇā* and the *Upaniṣads* (132-141).

Noting that ritual terms such as *ṛta* (settled order) and *mahas* (greatness, power) usually appear in juxtaposition with *śraddhā* (138), Hara suggests that in the *Vedic* period, the ritual (*karma*) is said to be more effective when performed with *śraddhā*. In this sense, *śraddhā* is set in a totally different context than the inter-personal *bhakti*. *Śraddhā* is usually associated with words such as *tattva*, *śreyas*, *agni*, and *pauruṣa*, which are either objective and impersonal in character (132), or refer to substances and abstractions (134). Even when in some passages *śraddhā* is construed with words for human beings, as is common in the case of *bhakti*, it is still possible to distinguish what aspect of the relationships is referred to (135). When referring to a person, *śraddhā* does

not refer to the kind of relation that person is in, but rather to an essential quality of that person (135).

Hara goes on: “the object of *śrad-dhā* is not precisely persons but the trustworthiness of persons” (135-6). The best example for understanding what Hara means by this ‘objective’ evidence of trust associated with *śraddhā* comes from passages that refer to *Brahmanic* ritual arrangements, even though there are also passages of the *Upaniṣads* and chapter 17 of the *Gṛ̥ā*. As Hara puts it:

The foundation of the sacrifice (*yajñā*) is the sacrificial fee (*dakṣiṇā*), which is again founded upon *śraddhā*. Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad 3.2.10, while prescribing how the knowledge of *brahma* (*brahma-vidyā*) should be transmitted, mentions *śraddhayantaḥ* together with other qualifications such as observance of vedic ritual (*kriyā*) and the offering of sacrifice (*hu-*) to the sacrificial fire (*eka-rṣi*). Two passages from *Bhavavadgṛ̥ā* 17 put *śraddhā* in juxtaposition with ritual terms such as sacrifice (*yaj-*, *yajñā*), ritual prescription (*vidhi*), sacrificial formula (*mantra*) and sacrificial fee (*dakṣiṇā*). The correlation of *śraddhā* with *vidhi* is so strong that Raghuvamśa 2.16 uses it as simile of accompaniment. (137)

In other words, the correlation of *śraddhā* with *vidhi* confirms the ritual atmosphere of *śraddhā*. Hara concludes, then, that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* present a fundamental difference, which he summarizes as follows:

In the first place, *bhakti* has a personal connotation and implies a human relation. . . . Secondly, *bhakti* has an emotional connotation. A third shade of connotation, . . . , is one of a reverential character. . . . As opposed to the personal object toward which the force of *bhakti* is exerted, we find in this *Vedic* cycle an impersonal and neutral principle as the object of *śraddhā*. . . . Furthermore, from an Indological point of view, the one [*śraddhā*] is particularly a vedic and brahmanical concept, whereas the other [*bhakti*] is rather Hinduistic. (132-139)

His conclusion, then, is that *śraddhā* expresses a kind of *Vedic* state of mind resultant of a ritual context, trust directed toward impersonal objects, and ritual arrangements. He sees

this state of mind in contrast to the Hinduistic context of *bhakti*, which is personal and theistic. Stating in another way this opposition, he says; “We have thus seen the ritual atmosphere of *śraddhā* in striking contrast to the theistic aspect of *bhakti*” (140). In trying to underline the contrast between *Vedic* and ritual based meaning of *śraddhā* and the newer concept of *bhakti*, Hara even suggests that the personal and theistic connotation of *bhakti* could have a Dravidian, or Non-Aryan, origin (n. 45, 142).⁸³

Hara uses Śaṅkara’s discussion of the *Gītā* and *Upaniṣads*⁸⁴ to support his conclusion that the central conception of *śraddhā* as *āstikya-buddhi* or trusting judgement is a *Vedic* concept. In that *Brāhmaṇical* circle *śraddhā* refers to a ritual state of mind rather than to a theistic concept in which one postulates a personified God, as in the case of Christianity and *Bhakti* Hinduism (141-42). The later forms of ‘*Bhakti*’ religion do not take the different aspects of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* entirely into consideration,⁸⁵ and ignore the fact that the *Gītā* is not as much a sectarian work as it is a source of philosophic and theological inquiry.⁸⁶

I have already mentioned how *śraddhā* is connected with Arjuna’s immediate experience of the transcendent in chapter 11. My argument in the following chapters,

⁸³ Das Gupta (1930, 315-333 and 487-513) suggests the same. Hara does not mention her article, although he was probably aware of its content.

⁸⁴ Hara discusses some passages of Mallinātha, Vyāsa, Gaṇapatiśāstri, Sāyana, Vīrarāghava, Kullukācārya, Patañjali, and, from Śaṅkara, he discusses his commentaries on BhG 6.37, BhG 9.23, BhG 17.1, BhG 17.71, *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* 7.19.1, *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* 3.9.21, *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* 2.1.7.

⁸⁵ These aspects of *śraddhā* help the re-evaluation of the “*Bhakti*” religion. It is in accordance to a theistic reading that one is able to state, “The individual soul aspires to reach the goal not by virtue of its ‘works’ like sacrifice, penance, etc., but by *śraddhā*; his confidence is not in his ‘works’ but in His love and mercy (Rao, 1971, 174). This portrayal of God’s grace, however, although clearly expressing the view of the *bhaktas*, cannot easily be defended as representing the core teaching of the *Gītā*.”

⁸⁶ Arjuna’s *śraddhā* results from his philosophical inquiry, which already is a form of fervent action.

then, will partially build⁸⁷ on considerations of Hara’s conclusion that *śraddhā* appears as *āstikya-buddhi*. Hara makes his suggestion after analysing BhG 3.31 and BhG 4.39 and the commentary of Śaṅkara. In the context of the *Gītā* he observes that, in contrast to *bhakti*, BhG 3.31 and BhG 4.39 give what he calls ‘an intellectual’ connotation to *śraddhā*, similar to the use of the term in the older texts such as *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* 1.1.10 and 7.19-20 and *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* 1.5.3 (140). Hara’s linkup of the thought of the *Upaniṣads* and *Gītā* is central to what we are arguing in this thesis.

In the *Gītā*, *sattvic śraddhā* is said to increase when the egocentric actor, *ahaṃkāra*, decreases its influence. Essentially, *sattvic śraddhā* implies that whatever the *śraddhāka* does, he does it as an offering for the benefit of the whole world (including oneself), and most important, he or she does it with his or her whole being. *Śraddhā*, then, is *āstikyabuddhi*, the positive knowledge, will, and performance that is proper of those striving for entering the sphere of influence of *ātman*. For, Arjuna is invited to move his original *guṇa* oriented functioning based in *ahaṃkāric* filial attachment to the *ātman*-oriented non-personal functioning. This gradual acquiring of soul force, or *sattvic śraddhā*, allows one to overcome, or discipline, the influence of the other *guṇas*.

⁸⁷ I insist in saying partial agreement due to the fact that Hara’s final conclusion, pointing to “a connecting link between the two concepts, *śraddhā* and *bhakti*, the former being a fundamental principle, and the latter being a developed mode of it, although the connotations of the two are in sharp contrast,” (145) is one I intend to challenge in the end after seeing all the evidence of the *Gītā*. While Hara was adamant that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* were terms with very different connotations, generally, his conclusion that BhG 6.47, BhG 12.2, and BhG 12.20 link them by suggesting that persons already possessed of *śraddhā* can become *bhaktas* seems to place *bhakti* in the climax position in the context of the plot of the *Gītā*. His conclusion that *śraddhā* is a ‘more fundamental principle’, if understood in the sense of a ‘more general principle’, as his analysis of the above verses suggests, leads one to see *bhakti* as a special sub-set of *śraddhā*. This interpretation, however, does not answer the central question, which is what leads Arjuna from non-action to action. What Hara’s conclusion leaves one with is the general question as to how much continuity and discontinuity there was in the early Indian tradition.

Though respectfully, Arjuna questions Kṛṣṇa all the time. When he finally agrees with Kṛṣṇa, he does it not because of any imposition of a ‘belief,’⁸⁸ not because he accepts ‘conversion,’ but only and exclusively because he concludes and feels through his renewed *śraddhā* that which seems to him to be the right thing to do. We will have to wait until the verses of the *Gītā* are analyzed to see why I take this state of mind to be a kind of intellectual mysticism, which I describe as the fervour of the *śraddhāvānt* (one who is possessed of *śraddhā*) who is transformed by the self-transcending experience of chapter 11.⁸⁹

Another important paper on the subject of the continuity of the meaning of *śraddhā* is that of Paul Hacker from around the same time as Hara’s essay. Although they both approach the issue from the viewpoint of the continuity argument, their theological perspectives are slightly different. Hacker, like Bhattacharya, Rao and others,

⁸⁸ It is worthwhile to notice here the Roman Catholic definition of faith as *fides quaerens intellectum*. The Latin term ‘*fides*’ (faith) implies this urge to accept some ‘truths’ prior to understanding them, which has generated strong debates among philosophers. Krishna Sharma, for instance, denounces the “theological exercise undertaken by the Christian thinkers from 17th to the 19th century to safeguard the Christian concept of a personal God” (1987, 8). For, “the growing trend towards the impersonalization of God in modern European philosophy had posed a serious threat to Christianity which could be counteracted only through a reiteration of faith in the Biblical God, who was personal in nature, and was different from the God of the philosophers” (9). The consequence, she argues, was the radical separation of religion and philosophy in the Western world. Such a separation was followed by the Christian explanations that religion was “a matter of faith and emotion, and not of knowledge and reason” (9). That is to say, the differentiation between religion and philosophy was an outcome of the Christian understanding of religion as a dogma of faith in *one personal god*. The more sophisticated “philosophical explanations of the oneness of God in impersonal terms” were, then, labelled “as either pantheism or monism” (9).

⁸⁹ The outward appearance of this ideal form of austerity (*tapas*), which is expressed as *sattvic śraddhā* in BhG 17.17, is described, then, as engagement in worldly affairs, though it consists essentially in the complete inner withdrawal from the world of perceptions. This inward withdrawal means study, detached sovereignty over earthly things, and the performance of all actions as if in the state of unity (*dhyāna*), where the senses and mind operate under the inner guidance of *ātman*. This seems to be in accordance with the Vedic understanding, which regards *tapas* (heat) to be the first cause of all things, producing in due order law and truth, etc. There, Prajāpati (Lord of creatures), regarding *tapas* as the principle of change, is said to derive the whole world from it.

comes to the subject with a very specific idea of what the term ‘faith’ means, which has strong consequences for how they choose which Sanskrit words can most closely convey the meanings he sees in the term ‘faith’. The issue of continuity, however, is never overruled.

Hacker explains the continuity of meaning of *śraddhā* through the postulation of a twofold definition: *śraddhā* would have developed an intellectual constituent, which nowadays may be understood as ‘faith’, but it would also have kept its foundational ritual constituent. Hacker believes (as all Catholics do in consequence of their definition of faith as *fides quaerens intellectum*) that faith must precede understanding, and this is the theological view he assumes when discussing the nature of *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā*. When defining ‘intellectual *śraddhā*’ in the *Gṛ̥ā*, he states that *śraddhā* must precede the knowledge that leads to salvation (1963, 153). *Śraddhā* is to him, so to speak, the preparatory step leading first to knowledge and then to salvation. Yet, although arguing that *śraddhā* is mainly the acceptance of a doctrine (intellectual *śraddhā*), he is also constrained to acknowledge, when discussing BhG 18.71, that redemption comes primarily from action, with *śraddhā* constituting its driving force (154).

In order to build his argument on ‘intellectual *śraddhā*’, Hacker opens his essay arguing that the Sanskrit term that best designates belief (*Glauben*) is *śraddhā*, which the Indian Theologians describe as *āstikyabuddhi* (a positive disposition of mind of a believing nature).⁹⁰ He argues that the practice of *bhakti* demands a prior faith (*śraddhā*)

⁹⁰ Hacker first addresses *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā* as ‘*Glaube*’, the pre-requirement for knowledge, stressing its characteristic component of free will. In this first group, he includes the occurrences of the term in the

in the mythological tradition (151). That is to say, *śraddhā* has its place in all paths – the *jñānamārga* and the devotional *bhakti* included. He acknowledges that *śraddhā* comes close to *bhakti* in some passages, and that the commentator Madhusūdana, in his discussion of BG 7.21, equates *śraddhā* to *bhakti*. Hacker reminds us, however, that in Śāṅḍilya Bhaktisūtras 22-4 such equivalence is expressly denied.

These Śāṅḍilya *sūtras* demonstrate the difference between *śraddhā* and *bhakti* with a logical argument: *sūtra* 22 states that *śraddhā* is the common element of all paths; *sūtra* 23 states that the identity of *śraddhā* and *bhakti*, therefore, would lead to infinite regression, and *Sūtra* 24, then, states that it is impossible to equate both terms.⁹¹ Hacker’s conclusion, then, is that *śraddhā* is a pre-requirement of the paths of knowledge, action, *yoga*, and devotion, and that there seems to exist two kinds of *śraddhā*: one intellectual, belonging to the *jñānamārga*, and another ritualistic, belonging to the *karmamārga*.

verses BhG 3.31; BhG 4.39-40; BhG 9.3, and BhG 18.71 (152-4). He observes the link between *śraddhā* and *anasūyā* (freedom from spite; absence of ill-will) in BhG 3.31 and BhG 18.71, and quoting Venkaṭanātha, explains the absence of *asūyā* (indignation, envy, jealousy) in the attitude of *śraddhā* (faith) towards Kṛṣṇa’s doctrine. Hacker, then, argues that *śraddhā* could also mean ‘teaching body’ (Dozilität) and, therefore, ‘respect’ (Respekt). The different possibilities and nuances of meaning, according to Hacker, is made clear in BhG 4.39-40, where he sees the essence of what he calls Hindu “intellectual *śraddhā*.” Secondly, Hacker considers the verses of the *Gītā* where he sees *śraddhā* as a pre-requirement to *bhakti*. They are: BhG 6.47; BhG 7.21-2, and BhG 12.20. Here he acknowledges the ‘intellectual *śraddhā*’ as well as the ‘ritual *śraddhā*’, as components of *śraddhā*. For, he says, *bhajana* (worship) may be either purely intellectual or ritualistic. According to him, in BhG 7.21-2 this ‘ritual *śraddhā*’ can be said to be linked to *bhakti śraddhā* (155). Thirdly, Hacker deals with BhG 6.47, which relates *śraddhā* to *Yoga*. Here, he says, *śraddhā* is a force that leads to *Yoga*, but it is not that *śraddhā* referred to in the *Yoga* system. Finally, in the fourth group of verses, he discusses ‘ritual *śraddhā*’. The verses taken into consideration are: BhG 9.23; BhG 17.1-3; BhG 17.13; BhG 17.17, and BhG 17.28. He argues, then that *śraddhā* remains as a ritual constituent. Without *śraddhā*, the *yajña* represents nothing but ontological darkness (157).

⁹¹ When they are identical, the result is infinite regression – *tasyāṃ tattve cānavasthānāt*. *Śraddhā* is an instrument (*aṅga*), or a presupposition, of *bhakti* (as well as of the other paths). If then they were identical, the *bhakti mārga* would not make sense as an independent path. The identity would require another *śraddhā* as an instrument (*aṅga*), which, again, would also be identical to *bhakti*, to the infinite (151-2).

According to him, this is best seen in the *Gṝā*, where the terms *śraddhā*, *śraddhāvāt*, *śraddadhāna*, *aśraddhā*, and *śraddhārahita* can be linked with these four paths (152).⁹²

Another important scholar on the subject of continuity is Krishna Sharma. Her concept of *nirguṇa bhakti*, which we have already discussed, represents a struggle to disprove what she calls the Christianizing of *bhakti*. According to her, the idea of *bhakti* as being exclusively theistic was put forth by biased Christian scholars interested in keeping the Western division between religion and philosophy.⁹³ As she argues, “the

⁹² These findings of Hacker have not impressed Smith. Smith criticizes those ‘students’ who argue that *śraddhā* presents many different meanings, “speaking of ritual *śraddhā*, intellectual *śraddhā*, moral *śraddhā*, and so on,” in a way that betrays the understanding of its inherent simplicity, as well as of its objects (1979, 61-2). For, *śraddhā* “does not designate a relationship to anything,” but “indicates rather the attitude or initial act whereby they enter into one or another relation” (62). And further, “It has to do with man’s capacity to become involved: the tendency or quality inherent within each person to move outside him- or herself and to become engaged” (62). Clearly, one of the ‘students’ Smith is referring is P. Hacker, who also “has made the most thoroughgoing studies of the concept to date,” and who indicates by ‘faith’ (*der Glaube*) both *āstikya buddhi* and *śraddhā* (n. 28, 222). Smith argues that Hacker has complicated the matter by “including the object of *śraddhā* in the consideration of the various usages and then exploring the resultant modalities of faith in their intricate variety, in such a way as to obscure what is common to all and is relatively simple.” That is to say, because of “the Western tendency to define faith in terms of its objects,” Hacker “has clearly been influenced by his prior mental association of faith with intellectual content (an association from his modern Christian heritage),” and the consequence is that he produces a complicated “typology of ritual *śraddhā*, intellectual *śraddhā*, etc. (n.40, 227). Smith remarks, then, that *śraddhā* is not a primarily intellectualistic concept, and therefore, if we manage to “understand *śraddhā* at all we can understand it in all its Hindu forms” (n. 40, 228). When it comes to Hindu writers, he says, he prefers Rao, who, more cautiously than others, has generally taken *śraddhā* to mean ‘faith’, but has also stressed that it is “misleading to translate the word uniformly and without qualification” (n. 28, 222).

⁹³ Rao, for instance, goes as far as to argue that in the *Gṝā* there can be no liberation without ‘grace’ – a term he chooses to translate the Sanskrit ‘*prasāda*’ (clarity, purity). He argues:

God and soul are stated to be companions living on the same tree (body), but always distinguished from each other. The one is said to enjoy happiness and misery while the other is untouched by them.²⁸ The individual soul, however, is freed from sorrow when united with God. But the knowledge of and the union with God is not obtained by intelligence or learning, etc., but He is to be obtained when God *chooses* [stress is mine] to reveal Himself to the Seeker.²⁹ In other words, knowledge of truth about God and the self is not a sufficient condition of salvation. There can be no liberation without the grace of God. (Rao, 1971, 102)

29 [28]. Ibid [*Muṇḍaka*], III.1.1.2.

29. Ibid, III.23

Rao’s reading of the later *Upaniṣads* and the *Gṝā* as texts imposing a personal relationship with a personal god as pre-requirement for salvation, explains his failure to distinguish *bhakti* and *śraddhā* in the *Gṝā*.

parameters under question relate to the acceptance of a clear division between religion and philosophy, between personal and impersonal concepts of God, and between monism and monotheism” (1987, x). These parameters, “that the true religious spirit is not possible without the belief in a personal God; and that the philosophical explanations of God in impersonal terms must be treated as philosophy,” bear no relevance in the context of Hinduism (53). In her view Hindu explanations of *bhakti* covered the whole range from Caitanya’s view of a very emotional devotion to a personal deity, to Śaṅkara’s definition of *bhakti* as *jñāna niṣṭhā*, or the discipline of knowledge. *Bhakti*, then, is not synonymous with monotheism. As Krishna Sharma points out, “whenever monotheism and monism are used as distinctive categories in the study of Hinduism, the fact is overlooked that the Hindu thinkers had evolved the concept of *Brahman/Ātman* within the realm of religion itself” (53). Furthermore, she argues,

Contrary to modern opinions (rooted in Western theorizations), the philosophy of the *Gṝā* was never placed at variance with that of the *Upaniṣads* by the Hindu theologians. . . . The fact that the *Gṝā* conveyed the knowledge of *Brahman* was always accepted by the Hindus and no new concept of a personal God, as separated and opposed to the idea of *Brahman*, was ever attributed to it. (110-1)

It was only towards the end of the nineteenth century that the *Gṝā*, once accepted as “the scientific and allegorical ‘systematization of the scattered tenets’ of Hinduism,” became a Vaishṇava text, understood as dealing with *bhakti* (82-3). Thus, in the words of Sharma, “bhakti, which was identified with Kṛṣṇa-worship by Wilson, and described as a religion of grace by Weber, was finally associated with the *Bhavavad Gṝā*” (82).

Krishna Sharma shows how the *Gṝā* has been differently acknowledged by the scholars as authoritative in ‘philosophical’ Brahmanism, ‘sectarian’ Hinduism, and as a

Vaiṣṇava exposition of the *Bhakti* doctrine. Sharma is of the opinion, though, that “the religious fervour inspired by the medieval bhaktas had resulted in the galvanization of people into groups with a common ideology and a common code of conduct” (1987, 3). As she explains, the term *bhakti* denotes loving devotion or attachment in general. Yet, its meaning can get particularized when it indicates a particular theology and religious mode: “For example, Viṣṇu-bhakti (as well as its variations, i.e., Kṛṣṇa-bhakti, Rāma-bhakti) and Śiva-bhakti can legitimately be explained in terms of Vaiṣṇava and Śaiva theologies” (5-6). Still, “By itself, it does not suggest any doctrinaire or ideational position, nor any particularized concept of God, personal or impersonal” (6). For, as she also acknowledges, “Bhakti was never treated as a dharma in the Hindu religious texts; nor it was ever discussed as a siddhānta [doctrine] or a mata [doctrine]” (42).

The last scholar I want to consider, who also looks for continuity of meaning from the *Vedic* period up to the *Gṝ̥ā*, is A. Sharma. He reminds us that the *Gṝ̥ā* does not necessarily need to be identified with the Vedānta, for “The *Gṝ̥ā* starts with Arjuna having certain doubts about pursuing a particular course of action – that of engaging in battle. It ends as soon as Arjuna indicates his willingness to pursue that course of action, namely, to engage in battle” (1990/1, 46-7). In such a context, he points out that an expression such as “the ritual of battle”⁹⁴ suggests “that the application of a “ritualistic” approach to the *Gṝ̥ā* may not be entirely out of place” (48). If a *Mīmāṃsīc* approach to the *Gṝ̥ā* is adopted, then even some apparent contradictions of the text can be accounted

⁹⁴ Alf Hiltebeitel, *The Ritual of Battle: Krishna in the Mahābhārata* (Ithaca, New York: Cornell University Press, 1976).

for more easily and logically (50). “One needs only to remind oneself here that according to *Mīmāṃsā* the real purport of the *Vedas* is contained in those sections of the *Vedas* which deal with injunctions. If such an approach is extended to the *Gṛ̥ā* it would imply that the real purport of the *Gṛ̥ā* is represented by statements like: “Therefore, Arjuna, fight” (2.18); “Arise determined to fight (2.37); etc.” All other discussion, then, is to be considered secondary, “secondary to the primary purpose of rousing Arjuna to fight” (48-9) for the sake of *lokasaṅgraha* (world’s welfare), as stated in BhG 3.20 and BhG 3.25.

Despite all evidence on continuity, however, many have followed Renou’s striking thesis, influential for a time, that *Vedic* religion was essentially different from later Hinduism. Rao’s and Bhattacharya’s theses on *śraddhā* were written at that time, and accepted that theory of discontinuity almost without question.

When Rao discusses over 32 occurrences of the term *śraddhā* or its cognate forms in the *R̥gveda*, 21 in the *Atharvaveda*, 26 in the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*, 9 in the *Aitareya Brāhmaṇa*, 46 in the *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa*, 19 in the *Jaiminīya Brāhmaṇa* (Rao 1971, 12, and 190-3), he only explores these instances according to his own theological adherence to the discontinuity argument, according to which, the content of *śraddhā* changes drastically from the *Brāhmaṇas* in general and the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*⁹⁵ in particular,

⁹⁵ For a more detailed account of the occurrences of *śraddhā*, see Maurice Bloomfield, *A Vedic Concordance*, Harvard Oriental Series Vol. 10 (Cambridge: Harvard University, 1906), 937. See also Vishva Bandhu Shastri, ed., *A Grammatical Word-Index to the Four Vedas*, VVRI S.V. Series Vol. 19 (Hoshiarpur: Vishveshvaranand Vedic Research Institute Publication, 1963), 966, and the KEWA, or the concise etymological Sanskrit dictionary of M. Mayrhofer, *Kurzgefaßtes etymologisches Wörterbuch Das Altindischen* Band III (Heidelberg 1956-76), 386-7.

the major *Upaniṣads*⁹⁶, and some classical commentaries⁹⁷ to the *Gṛ̥ā*. Rao’s underlying assumptions are never spelled out, but he seems to espouse the classification of Indian thought in terms of a Western evolutionary perspective, which is quick to judge the impersonal dimension of the Vedic rituals as evidence of childish blind faith. His effort, then, is to prove that this impersonal dimension is overcome by the theism of the *Gṛ̥ā*. Once those two leaps in logic are accepted he can argue that in the *Gṛ̥ā śraddhā* is a synonym for *bhakti*, even though the two terms are crucial in very different contexts. Yet, Rao also agrees that “there is a principle of unity in all forms of worship and that principle is *śraddhā* itself” (1971, 140).⁹⁸ What Rao did not do is explain how this ‘particularly religious element’ brought the teachings of the *Gṛ̥ā* together.

⁹⁶ They are: *Isā*, *Kena*, *Kaṭha*, *Muṇḍaka*, *Māṇḍūkya*, *Aitereya*, *Taittirīya*, *Chāndogya*, *Bṛhadāraṇyaka*, *Śvetāśvatara*, and *Maitrāyaṇīya*. The relevant passages related to *śraddhā* in the major *Upaniṣads* can be found also in G. A. Jacob’s *A Concordance to the Principal Upanishads and the Bhavavadgṛ̥ā* (Bombay: Bombay Sanskrit Series No. XXXIX, 1891; reprint Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1963), 931-2. See also Vishva Bandhu Shastri, ed., *A Grammatical Word-Index to the Principal Upaniṣads*, VVRI S.V. Series Vol. 21 (Hoshiarpur: Vishveshvaranand Vedic Research Institute Publication, 1966), 472-3, and M. Mayrhofer’s KEWA, 386-7.

⁹⁷ They are: Sāyaṇa’s commentary on *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*, and the commentaries of Śaṅkara, Rāmānuja, and Madhva on the important *Upaniṣads* and the *Gṛ̥ā*.

⁹⁸ This fact of plurality is not always acknowledged as a virtue by those siding with the discontinuity argument. Louis Renou (1953, 89), for instance, says, “Sects arise more readily in religions which have no clearly defined dogma; for there is then no risk of heresy”. However, as we have already mentioned, the whole life work of W. C. Smith represented a search for an universal element under the different faiths. In his many books he has sought to do comparative theology in a new way, more open to certain subtle conceptual distinctions, and without falling into the risk of heresy. Even though Smith has succeeded in showing how shallow the Enlightenment approach to religion is, being a devout Christian, he also failed, when looking for a more authentic religion, perhaps because he also remained stuck with the theistic understanding of ‘faith’.

As shown below, he clearly builds on the arguments of those scholars who have assumed that in the *Gītā* being possessed of *śraddhā* only means that one is devoted to Kṛṣṇa:⁹⁹

It is important, in this connection, to note that the ‘knowledge’ referred to here is not the knowledge of an impersonal reality or Brahman. On the contrary, the divine and saving knowledge referred to here is the knowledge and work of the divine Incarnation. The Lord is the fountain-head of knowledge, He is the mainspring of action, Nothing is equal to this divine knowledge.¹⁸ A *śraddhāvān* acquires it by doing honour (*praṇipāta*), by enquiry (*paripraśna*) and service (*sevā*)¹⁹ (131-2)

¹⁸ *na hi jñānena sadṛṣam*. IV.38 [in the *Gītā*].

¹⁹ IV.34.

And further, he adds,

Aśraddhā springs from ignorance and confusion, and results in the failure to recognize the Incarnation. An *aśraddadhāna* fails to ‘see’ the *saving* action of the Incarnation. He fails to understand that his own ultimate salvation is bound up with the merciful and loving descent of God on earth. (133)

No one would deny that *śraddhā* does present some elements that are similar to those involved in the theist concept of faith. Furthermore, in a theological sense, even Rao recognizes that what Arjuna had lost was his *śraddhā*, and, after Kṛṣṇa’s counsel, what he recovered was his *śraddhā* (167). He does not explain, however, the theological

⁹⁹ None of the recent scholarly comment on Arjuna’s transformation, however, has made any specific mention of the role of *śraddhā* in this process. See, for instance, Alf Hiltebeitel, “India’s Epics: Writing, Orality, and Divinity” (*THE STUDY OF HINDUISM*, ed. Arvind Sharma, 114-138. South Carolina: University of South Carolina Press, 2003); Arvind Sharma “The *Bhagavadgītā*: a Mīmāṃsīc Approach” (*The Journal of Studies in the Bhagavadgītā* vol. X-XI (1990-91): 46-56), and Madeleine Biardeau “Etudes de mythologie hindoue” (*Bulletin de l’Ecole Française d’Extrême-Orient*, LVIII (1971): 17-89). In the case of Alf Hiltebeitel, he brings this issue up when he discusses Katz’s *Arjuna in the Mahabharata*. According to Katz, Arjuna’s heroism and humanity are brought together by *bhakti* (devotion). Hiltebeitel, then, limits himself to point out that she is not convincing (121).

implications of this recovery and does not allow that fact to influence his primary conclusion that *śraddhā* is the same as *bhakti*.

In another thesis on *śraddhā* which may be said to be built around the ‘discontinuity hypothesis’, Bhattacharya starts by agreeing with Köhler’s conclusions on the *Vedic* meanings of the verb *śrad-dhā* and the noun *śraddhā*. He argues that in the *Samhitās* *śraddhā* designates ‘trust’ first in the *devas*, and later in the efficacy of the sacrifice and ‘willingness to offer’ (1971, 11). However, he then wants to find discontinuity and argue that in post-*Vedic* literature *śraddhā* means ‘faith’, as in *śraddhā dharme* – ‘faith in the religious Law,’ so he questions Köhler’s refusal to argue that *śrad-dhā* could also mean ‘to believe’ (in the existence of a god) (11).¹⁰⁰

Bhattacharya argues that while the *Vedic* concept *śrad-dhā*, ‘willingness to give’ remains unchanged in the post-*Vedic* period, a drastic shift as to the objects of *śraddhā* takes place when the direct object of both *śraddhā* and *śraddadhāna* shifts from a god to the abstract idea of *dharma* (16). For instance, he observes, *dharma* is used in the genitive case as an object of the participle of *śrad-dhā* in BhG 9.3, which he translates, ‘the persons who do not believe in this religious law, return, O tormentor of foes, on the path of the world of death without attaining me’ (17-8).

¹⁰⁰ In summary, Köhler’s examples help us to understand how the etymology of *śrad-dhā* suggest the general meaning of ‘to place one’s heart in’. As a consequence, expressions such as *yathāśraddham* are better translated as ‘in accordance to desire’ than ‘in accordance with the faith’, as we have already seen when discussing the adverbial compound *yathāśraddham* in the passages *Taittirīyabrahmaṇam* III, 12, 5, 11 (where the reference is to the *dakṣiṇā*, meaning the will to donate) (5), and the passage MBh. III.2160, where Damayantī asks Nala to manifest the desires that please the heart (6).

Yet, he also observes, that in the commentary on the still later *Yoga Sūtras* 3, 1, 5, *śraddhā* is called ‘the particular form of trust based upon the ability for success’ (21). “It is not faith,” he says, “but the positive attitude in fulfilling the various duties of *dharmā* [. . .], based on the confidence in the efficacy of these rites” (21- 2). This zeal in every action, according to him, is nowhere better expressed than in BhG 17.28, which states the worthlessness of acting without *śraddhā* (22-3) – which is in accordance with the *Gītā*’s central belief, stated in BhG 17.3, that one’s existence is determined by one’s *śraddhā*, or soul force. The idea is that this inner strength, or fervent disposition (*śraddhā*), varies according to the three *guṇas*, and this, according to Bhattacharya, is implied in BhG 7.30 and BhG 8.3. In BhG 7.30, *śraddhā*, as that disposition at the time of death, is related with the root ‘*vid*’ (‘and even at the time of death, they know me to be with disciplined mind’); in BhG 8.3, *śraddhā* is related with the root ‘*smṛ*’ (‘and at the time of death, he who, while leaving his body, meditates only on me’) (24). This is in accordance with BhG 17.4, which states that pure men (those endowed with *sattvic śraddhā*) worship gods; the passionate (those with *rajasic śraddhā*), demons, and others (those with *tamasic śraddhā*), ghosts. This flexible understanding of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* helps one to see how problematic is the translation as ‘faith’ – a term which designates a much more inflexible concept. As discussed in BhG 17.17, growing out of the right and austere intention to sacrifice, *śraddhā* reveals one’s character, rather than one’s faith.

Bhattacharya, however, who practically postulates that “śraddhā is a grace accorded by God,” and synonymous with bhakti (32-3), argues that *śraddhā* means faith,

based mostly on evidence from the *Purāṇas*. He says that the *Purāṇic* ‘*niścālā bhaktiḥ*’, ‘unshaken devotion’ is the same as the ‘*acalā śraddhā*’, ‘unshaken faith’ of BhG 7.21, inferring, therefore, that “*śraddhā* or *bhakti* refer to the grace of God, and that individual good-will alone is not enough to obtain it” (33). He strengthens his argument showing the equivalence in Buddhism first of the pair *pasāda* (*prasāda*) and *saddhā* (*śraddhā*), and second of *prasāda* and *bhakti*. His conclusion, then, is that for Buddhism, *prasāda*, *bhakti*, and *śraddhā* are all synonyms (37).¹⁰¹

Outside Buddhism, nevertheless, his arguments are not totally convincing. For, if the terms *śraddhā* and *bhakti* were synonymous they would produce similar sentence syntax. This, however, is never the case outside Buddhism. Bhattacharya recognizes that *śraddhā* is never presented “with a word in the locative case which designates a faithfully worshipped person” (29). *Bhakti*, however, is found “construed with the locative case of the person,” as in “*bhaktir* īśvare, ‘devotion towards the Lord’” (29). That is to say, Bhattacharya acknowledges that where “Viṣṇu and Śiva are concerned,” they are “rather

¹⁰¹ Bhattacharya offers some illustrations presented by Köhler, which he thinks show that in Buddhism *śraddhā* means ‘desire’ in the *secular* sense corresponding to its ‘religious sense of willingness’ (25). However, one might but wonder if his ‘Western’ distinction between ‘secular’ and ‘religious’ was ever made clear in either the *Vedic* and in the *Post-Vedic* periods. He also provides the following passage from *Mahābhārata* 12, 199, 25 as a case where *śraddhā* appears with the *secular* meaning of desire: “*na me śraddhā svargaṃ gantuṃ vinā ‘tmanā*, I have no desire to go to heaven without myself, i.e. without my body” (25). The passages he chose, however, also accept ‘enthusiasm’ – a term that is both ‘secular’ and ‘religious’ – as a fair translation for *śraddhā*. Bhattacharya’s statement, however, ignores that the sense in which the term ‘faith’ is used by Western tradition is not the same as used by Buddhism to translate the terms *saddhā* and *pasāda*. I will come back to this point later on. Yet, when comparing Vyāsa’s commentary on *Yoga Sūtras* I, 20 (where *śraddhā* is said to precede *samādhi*), *śraddhā cetasaḥ samprasādaḥ* – ‘*śraddhā* is serenity of mind’, with BhG 2.64-5, where *prasāda* also occurs, he admits that *bhakti* and *prasāda* are different, with *bhakti* corresponding to the devotion that the Lord demands, *prasāda* corresponding to the grace that the devotee expects – with *prasāda* not being, therefore, a synonym for faith, at least in the case of the *Gṛh* (38-9).

an object of *bhakti*” (16), while “in the Post-Vedic period the direct object of *śraddhā* or *śraddadhāna* is not a god but the abstract idea dharma” (19).

The conclusion, then, is that Bhattacharya and those arguing for discontinuity are wrong. For, even when the exhaustive investigation of the continuity argument would require the work of a lifetime, I think that scholars such as Hacker, Hara, Köhler, and others have succeeded at least in establishing the continuity of meaning between the *Vedic* term *śraddhā* and the *Gṛ̥ā* term *śraddhā*.

This seems to be also the understanding of W. C. Smith, the last scholar we will study in regard to the continuity argument. In his monumental study called *Faith and Belief* (1979),¹⁰² he comments on this scholarly discussion of the term *śraddhā*. He starts his analysis noting that the major *Vedic* commentator Sāyaṇa, and the major commentator on the *Gṛ̥ā*, Śaṅkara, take *śraddhā* to mean *āstikya buddhi* – a kind of orientation of yes-ness (59). He uses both Hara and Hacker to support his understanding that Śaṅkara exegetes the term as *śraddhayā āstikyabuddhayā* (n. 22, 217), which he translates as ‘awakeness to transcendence’ (59). Noting that the term is linked with ‘*buddhi*’ rather than ‘*manas*’ or the ‘mind’ he concludes that it means more than ‘believing’ or giving mental assent to something.

¹⁰² Smith, who had mentored both, Rao’s thesis on *śraddhā*, published in 1971, and MacQueen’s 1972 unpublished study on *saddhā* and *pasāda*, acknowledges Bhattacharya’s 1973 thesis *en passant* in a note in his *Faith and Belief*, stating that “the author at a few points argues for linking the Sanskrit concept more closely than would I with “belief” and “doubt”, though without inquiring closely into the significance of these English terms” (1979, n. 3, 209).

The visionary or spiritual dimension of the psyche associated with ‘*buddhi*’ is where the experience of *śraddhā* takes place¹⁰³ (n. 23, 218). The problem is that this subtle distinction between *manas* and *buddhi* is hard to express in the Western theological vocabulary. And that perhaps is the reason why many have fallen back on to the awkward term ‘faith’ to translate *śraddhā*. Smith, then, is at pains to redefine ‘faith’ in a way that includes the higher category of *buddhi* and truly encompasses ‘*śraddhā*’. In attempting to look for a proper term to describe this range of experience Smith is inclined to allow ‘*śraddhā*’ to maintain its essential meaning through the different periods of Indian thought.¹⁰⁴

Smith acknowledges that the concept of *bhakti* is also closely related to the meaning of the English term ‘faith’, especially when ‘faith’ is taken not as simply belief, but as an account of the relation between humans and God (n. 25, 218-9). The similarities between ‘*bhakti*’ and Western Christian, especially Protestant, interpretations of ‘faith’, according to him, are well established in Rudolf Otto’s *Christianity and the Indian Religion of Grace* (Madras: Christian Literature Society for India, 1929) and John

¹⁰³ Furthermore, Smith explains in another note, “*śraddhā . . . āstikyabuddhir bhakti sahitā*. This formula occurs in his [Śāṅkara] exegesis of *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad*, in the section (3:9:20-25) where it is being set forth that the visible forms, life-generative matter, the truth (*satyam*), and also faith (3:9:21) are dependent upon, are firmly supported by, dwell steadfast in (*pratiṣṭhītāni bhavanti*) the heart – and indeed, the heart alone (*hṛdaye hy eva*). Ed. cit. (above, our ref. 52), p. 484. (It may be noted that “heart” here is explicitly interpreted by Śāṅkara as what Westerners would call the mind: namely, the two discriminated organs *buddhi* and *manas* together – *ibid.*, p.483, commentary on 3:9:20” (Smith 1979, n. 66, 239).

¹⁰⁴ When exegeting the occurrence of the term *śraddhā* in BhG 4.39, for instance, Smith points out that Sāyaṇa gets a similar meaning for the term in the *Atharva-Vedic* passage 6:122:3, and concludes “that the man of faith [*śraddhā*] is he for whom the performance of ceremonial works is of primary importance and concern” (1979, n. 51, 233).

B. Carman, “Is Christian Faith a Form of *Bhakti*?” (*Visva-Bharati Journal of Philosophy*, 1968, pp. 24-37 [2-15].) (n. 25, 219).

Besides the difficulties involved in distinguishing between *manas* and *buddhi* with the Western theological vocabulary, a second problem Smith sees is that only by the nineteenth century did the term ‘faith’ begin to also denote non-Christian forms of religiosity (n. 25, 220). Furthermore, the Western view is “that faith is nothing if not faith in some x,” which is external and strange.¹⁰⁵ The term ‘faith’ as used by the Buddhists, then, to translate the terms ‘*saddhā*’ and ‘*pasāda*’, would hardly be called ‘faith’ in the Western sense.¹⁰⁶

¹⁰⁵ Smith suggests here another way to distinguish both terms *śraddhā* and *bhakti*, for the various connotations of *bhakti* always involve subject-object relationships, whereas this is not always the case with *śraddhā*.

¹⁰⁶ I have with me Graeme MacQueen’s interesting but unpublished “The Concept of Faith in Early Buddhism” (1972), written for W. C. Smith, in a seminar at Harvard University. The paper addresses the *Dīgha* and *Majjhima Nikāyas* of the Buddhist Pāli Canon, deals with the terms *saddhā* (Skt. *śraddhā*) and *pasāda* (Skt. *prasāda*), and throws new light over the meaning of ‘faith’, in terms of trust, confidence, and so on. MacQueen observes that the term *bhakti* (Skt. *bhakti*), which occurs in other parts of the Canon, “is either absent or at any rate of very minor significance in these two texts” (1972, n.1, 1). He also stresses the theological grounds in which the term ‘faith’ is to be understood in the Buddhist scheme of salvation (2). That is to say, “faith (*saddhā*), in Buddhism, is not merely a matter of assenting to certain statements” (8). For, “*saddhā* involves ‘believing that certain things are the case’ and that the things which are thus assented to or affirmed are neither obvious nor trivial nor can they be called “presuppositions”, either of the particular persons concerned or their culture” (9). In other words, “insofar as a ‘creed’ may be said to be that through which one affirms that he believes in a certain object, the early Buddhists may be seen at times as having a creed” (9). Yet, “it is only after these claims have been verified that the person reposes faith or trust in Gotama” (10). For, as Walpola Rahula says, “Almost all religions are built on faith – rather ‘blind’ faith it would seem. But in Buddhism emphasis is laid on ‘seeing’, knowing, understanding, and not on faith, or belief” (21). MacQueen explains the Rahula passage with the following words: “The Buddhists are forced to show that their own faith is properly grounded and acceptable. This is done in two ways: (i) it is said that before ‘putting one’s heart on’ the Buddhist path, one should examine the evidence available to him, (ii) it is claimed that the Doctrine (Dhamma) given by the Buddha is *ehi-passika* (‘come-and-see-able’)” (24). Faith, however, is not cancelled by this knowledge, but rather is “fulfilled by knowledge” (28). MacQueen’s conclusion, then, tends to be that faith, or what Buddhists understand by *saddhā* and *pasāda*, is both necessary and sufficient for the winning of Nibbāna (Skt. *nirvāṇa*). For, the Buddhist ‘faith’ actually involves what Westerners usually understand by ‘faith’ plus knowledge: “faith and knowledge are seen as mutually supporting: that knowledge grounds faith and faith prepares the way for new knowledge” (29-32). Yet, he closes his paper by carefully remarking that, “faith in itself is neither sufficient nor

Even though Smith has not fully investigated the relation between *śraddhā* and *bhakti*, he is able to state his impression that “although one may say that *bhakti* is a form of faith, one may *not* quite say that *bhakti* is a form of *śraddhā*” (n. 25, 220).

Furthermore, he adds,

This demonstrates, if proof were needed, that *śraddhā* is a component of generic faith (as it is of specific *bhakti*), but is not that generic faith itself. Agreed. Ours is not a study of Hindu faith, nor of its self-understanding; except partially (cf. at our ref. 31 below). As indicated in the opening sentence of this note, our avowal that *śraddhā* is faith was not meant to equate the two so that the converse could also have been said, that faith is *śraddhā*. (n. 25, 220)

That is to say, Smith agrees with my general thesis that *sattvic śraddhā* is part of *bhakti* (if you have *sattvic śraddhā*, then you have *bhakti*), but *bhakti* is not part of *śraddhā* (being a *bhakta* does not necessarily entail that one is possessed with *sattvic śraddhā*).¹⁰⁷

Moreover, he also agrees that ‘faith’ is not *śraddhā*. What he does not say, however, is that *śraddhā* “being a component of generic faith” should, perhaps be translated as “enthusiasm, fervour, or soul force.” For, any good translation should also guarantee the converse, which in this case implies the affirmation that enthusiasm, fervour, and soul force *are śraddhā*.

Smith prefers to follow those who translate *śraddhā* as ‘faith’. However, implicit in his attempt to formulate an Indian concept of faith is his belief that the term *śraddhā* would convey the necessary continuity of meaning through the different periods. For,

insufficient for the attainment of the Goal, the essential nature of faith (both *saddhā* and *pasāda*) being that *it is not* [the stress is mine] ‘in itself’ (36). Over and above, MacQueen stresses the importance of *saddhā* in Buddhism.

¹⁰⁷ That is to say, if you are Brazilian, then you are a human being. But being a human being does not necessarily mean you are Brazilian.

what he truly believes is that “in the future its [*śraddhā*] meaning will be tributary to what the term “faith” is now going to mean as, globally, we broaden and deepen (and sharpen) our corporate understanding in this realm” (60).

As a matter of fact, one could argue that, if Smith’s good intentions in postulating ‘faith’ as this general human quality hinders the theological view of *śraddhā* as we have it in the *Gṛā*, the understanding of *śraddhā* as soul force and religious enthusiasm frees even the modern understanding of ‘faith’ from its dogmatic and exclusive past. For, *sattvic śraddhā* represents that which is common to all honest and true attempts to achieve salvation. Moreover, as we have seen, it is a category foundational of the idea of religion itself, being present in the earliest times in the death rites as well as in other rituals in general.

As Smith admits, *śraddhā* “almost constitutes the differentiating characteristic that qualifies any human activity as religious,” for it means ‘to set one’s heart on’ since the times of the *Ṛg Veda*, where the two parts usually occur separately (61). Further on he adds,

That on which one puts or might put one’s heart, in the gamut of India’s complex religious life, has been varied. Yet the religious man has been characterized (might we not say, “of course”?) by the fact that he has put his heart on *something* within it. The term *śraddhā* is open, in the sense that it does not itself specify or even suggest what it is on which one puts one’s heart. The concept as a concept has no particular object, or type of object. (61)

Smith touches here on the issue of the universality of *śraddhā*, which is not completely dependent on one’s faith, for it represents that inter-faith that allows everyone to see

things under the viewpoint of the heart,¹⁰⁸ perhaps in the *ātmic* sense presented by Kṛṣṇa to Arjuna, as we have been arguing.

In relation to this attitude designated by *śraddhā*, as dealt with above, it is interesting also to consider how Smith addresses the work of Köhler. He says that Köhler sees “the enthusiasm that is *śraddhā* as perceived by the priests in quite non-transcendentalist terms (enthusiasm for the ritual, expressing itself in a crass generosity towards its functionaries” (n. 36, 226). Smith acknowledges, then, that *śraddhā* has sometimes been perceived as this religious zeal that makes the patron of a sacrifice become more generous at heart, even if at the moment of the sacrifice it appears to be only towards the priests.

That is to say, *śraddhā* implies engagement, or as Smith puts it, “involvement” with our own reality as well as with its metaphors for the transcendent (62). For, as it says in the *Gṛ̥ā*, whatever is done without *śraddhā* is worthless. Salvation, then, is not to be achieved mechanically, or by those who are stonehearted and perform deeds like automatons. Merit depends on one’s real motive behind the actions; it depends on how one cares; it depends on one’s *śraddhā*, as it requires that one’s mind do not be elsewhere. For, as Smith puts it, *śraddhā* “contrasts with a mind that is wandering” (63). It “denotes a way of doing things in the religious life: the way a ritualist performs a rite, the way a moralist carries out an obligation or a set of injunctions, the way one listens to

¹⁰⁸ As Smith points out, the regular classical Sanskrit word for ‘heart’ is *hṛdaya*. The term *śrad* has been motive of some dispute by the linguists. However, “the question is only as to whether *śrad*/**kred* is ‘heart’, the visceral organ, and has nothing to do with the figurative sense in which it is being used here. Smith reminds us that relatively few languages have four distinct terms – mind, brain, organ of feeling, organ of pumping blood – for the potentially thinkables (n. 35, 223-4).

the *Gñā*, the way an intellectualist relates his mind and himself to the truth, the way a *bhakti*-devotee worships, and so on” (64). For, the “placing of the heart that is *śraddhā* is closely linked with that devotional adoration that is *bhakti*” (64).

In conclusion, Smith makes it clear that *śraddhā* is not identical to *bhakti*.¹⁰⁹ He also gives enough evidence that there is no instance of *śraddhā* where the notion of “putting the heart” “is not relevant and appropriate” (n. 44, 229). For, if one’s heart is not in the performance of the righteous deed, to use the *Gñā* term, the result is *asat* (n. 45, 230). That is to say, “once it has been affirmed that *śraddhā* means ‘placing one’s heart on’, there is in a sense nothing more to be said” (62). The religious life, whatever its form, presupposes *śraddhā*, and *śraddhā* lights the path, developing itself within that life, where someone gives one’s heart. As a consequence, this truth transcends what is ‘religious’ and transforms all human affairs in a sacred experience, as we will see next.

¹⁰⁹ Let me quote him in full: “This [the identity of *śraddhā* and *bhakti*] is a common view, against which careful scholars feel impelled to write. Hacker speaks of ‘Die hin und wieder begegnende Behauptung, die *śraddhā* stehe besonders der *Bhakti* nahe’ (1963, p. 151), and Das Gupta is at pains to write that ‘even [sic] in later [sc. post-Vedic] literature *śraddhā* is not always used synonymously with *bhakti*’ (p. 322). This latter writer had dismissed Sāyaṇa’s equating of the two (our previous ref., just above) as “obviously inadmissible (Das Gupta, p. 319, fn.1). Hara, similarly: ‘The two terms are often treated as synonymous, but a careful philological study will show their fundamental difference’ (“Note, p. [124]. For Hacker, Das Gupta and Hara here, see our ref. 3 above.)” (Smith 1979, n. 64, 238). Furthermore, he adds: “An identifying of *bhakti* with *śraddhā* is expressly denied in, for example, Śāṅḍilya, Bhaktisūtra 24, on the grounds that *śraddhā* is common (*naiva śraddhā tu sādharāṇyā*) – to *jñānins*, *karmins*, *yogins*, as well as *bhaktas*, whose way is superior to these (verse 22). All religious persons have *śraddhā*, only the best have *bhakti*, is the argument here. Besides this, it is further contended, to identify *śraddhā* and *bhakti* would lead to an infinite regression (*tasyām tattve cānavasthānāt* – verse 25): as the commentators (e.g., Svapneśvara) explain this, the point is that *śraddhā* is a subordinate or ancillary part (*aṅga*) of *bhakti*. Similarly to this last, the late-mediaeval *bhakta* Rūpa Gosvāmī makes *śraddhā* an *aṅga* of *viśvāsa* (cf. our ref. 57 above) on the way towards *bhakti*. The Śāṅkara characterization cited in our ref. 67 just below might be seen as implying that, contrariwise, *bhakti* is subordinate to (is *aṅga* of) *śraddhā*” (n.65, 238-9).

III. THE TERM ŚRADDHĀ IN THE GĪTĀ

We have seen how *śraddhā* in the *Vedic* period serves as an essential inner companion of external rituals. In the *Rgvedic* passage X.151.1-5, for instance, personified as a goddess, *śraddhā* is praised as that which kindles Agni and grants the desire of the patron of the *yajña*. In passages such as *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* XII.7.3.1, *Vājasaneyi Saṃhitā* IX.77, and *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* II.3.10.1, *śraddhā* expresses a truthful attitude of enthusiasm, linked to ritual duties as the human desire for a higher mode of existence. In other words, the practical *Vedic* sense of *śraddhā* implies ‘a desire to perform holy work’, ‘the willingness to sacrifice’, or ‘a cordial desire to sacrifice and to give’.

We have also seen how the *Upaniṣads*, through their search for the inner reality behind the phenomenal world, reflects on the *Vedic* use of the term *śraddhā*, and internalizes the ritual without changing the essential meaning of the pair *śraddhā* and ritual. Ritual remains important in the whole plot of the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad*, for instance, where the sentiment of ancestor worship is given a central place, and the term *śrāddha* or funerary rites is included in a theological discussion. That is to say, *Vedic* fire becomes in the *Upaniṣads* a ‘symbolic fire’ where the longings of the person are merged into the flame as they are in a funeral pyre. The sense of fundamental courage and inner strength

present in the *Upaniṣadic* quest represent, then, a reworking of that *Vedic śraddhā*, which resides in the heart of every living being as an innate quality.¹¹⁰

Next, we will see how *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* is related to its *Vedic* roots and *Upaniṣadic* developments. This chapter will focus on how *śraddhā*, understood as soul force or enthusiasm, carries both the *Vedic* ideal of *pravṛtti* and the *Upaniṣadic* ideal of *nivṛtti*¹¹¹ into the new religious questions raised in the *Gītā*. Stated differently, the *Gītā* makes use of the concept of *śraddhā* to synthesize the *Vedic karma-mārga* thesis and the *Upaniṣadic jñāna-mārga* antitheses. The newness of the argument of the *Gītā* lies precisely in this synthesis called *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*, which allows Arjuna to learn different views on the science of being, and to gradually shift from the state of *aśraddadhāna* to that of a *śraddhāvānt* (one possessed of *śraddhā*). Arjuna's particular experience with *ātmavidyā*, that is triggered by his dialogue with Kṛṣṇa and brought forth

¹¹⁰ In the *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad*, for instance, *śraddhā* means the search for the truth (BU VI, 2, 15) through working on oneself and understanding that the ritual payment or *dakṣiṇā* is now placed in *śraddhā* and *śraddhā* in turn is placed in the heart. In the *Chāndogya Upaniṣad*, arising out of knowledge, *śraddhā* is a pre-condition for salvation. In passages such as *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* V, 4, for instance, *śraddhā* ascends conducted by Agni; in V, 9, 1, it is identified with *Soma*, and in V, 10, 1, *śraddhā* becomes *tapas* (asceticism). In *Praśna Upaniṣad* I.10 *śraddhā*, *tapas* and *brahmacarya* are pre-conditions to the knowledge of *Brahman*. And in the *Taittirīya Upaniṣad* II.4.1 *Brahman* is to be attained through *śraddhā*. That is to say, although losing some of its magical connotation, the concept of *śraddhā* keeps its essential nature in the *Upaniṣads* and represents that *Vedic* virtue rooted in the heart, which is the deepest religious dimension of the human.

¹¹¹ The tendency one shows to express oneself through external action is known as *pravṛtti*, and the tendency one shows to refrain from external activity is known as *nivṛtti*. In other words, *pravṛtti* denotes active functioning in the processes of *saṃsāra*, whereas *nivṛtti* denotes a kind of inactivity, which is usually said to represent the ascent from *saṃsāra* toward *nirvāṇa*. Yet, in the *Gītā*, both processes are made one through the discipline of *niṣkāmakarma*. That is to say, once the attitude of *niṣkāmakarma* is what defines how both of them are to be performed, no one can be exclusively attached to either of them. For selfishness (*svārtha*) is what enslaves one's actions, either in the form of *pravṛtti*, or *nivṛtti*. Therefore, non-personal *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti* together, as defined in the *Gītā*, is what constitutes *karma-yoga*, as we will have the opportunity to see.

from *ātman*, or the ‘selfless’ self, represents what is new in the ancient¹¹² corpus of sacred knowledge.

III.1. The Exegetical Plan

Before undertaking the exegesis of the twenty-one occurrences of the term *śraddhā* as they occur in the text, I need to point out some of the differences in the commentarial styles used in India and in the West. The Indian style, sometimes pejoratively called ‘allegorical’, attempts to deal with issues such as metaphysics and intuition in the course of a commentary. This tradition derives from the commentaries of Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja¹¹³ who distinguished their method from that of the Mīmāṃsā.

¹¹² As for this connection and continuity of meaning of what is ancient and yet new, one might refer to Kṛṣṇa’s saying in the *Gṛā* that among the Rudras he was Śiva (BhG 10.23), the deity in charge of the destruction of the old perverted structures and of the renewal of its essence. Being connected to Indra and Agni and having sprung as half male and half female from *Brahman*’s forehead, Rudra – the *Ṛgvedic* god of death who drives away sorrows and evil, and is an early form of Śiva –, is also the bestower of *śraddhā*. Once Arjuna beheld this truth (BhG 11.22), he becomes progressively amazed, and was filled with the purest *śraddhā*. It is as if he becomes able to see things in proper perspective, learning that there are two classes of beings in this world: (1) those who persevere with an *ātmic* disposition in the *praxis* (*yoga*) of righteousness (*ārvavam*), without displaying any kind of fear, with self-control (*tapas*) and a disposition to give oneself (*dāna*) in self-sacrifice (*yajña*) (BhG 16.1); and (2) those who stick to their *ahaṅkāric* selfish interests (BhG 16.6). The first class of beings reveals the divine (*dāva*) nature of the human beings, whereas the second class only displays the humans’ demoniac side. To the first class belong those who understand *ahiṃsā* (non-violence) in terms of their action being compassionate (*dayā*) and truly (*satyam*) expressing *tyāga* (self-surrender) and *śānti* (inner peace), without any display of anger (*akrodha*) (BhG 16.2-3). That is to say, into this class would fall all those who understand *ahiṃsā* from the *ātmic* perspective, as exemplified in the famous claim of Gandhi that we should “hate the sin, not the sinner.” Into the other class, then, would fall all those whose understanding of *ahiṃsā* is reduced to the material realm, where violence is defined as anything that can ‘hurt’ *ahaṅkāra*’s demands. This later group is full of pride, arrogance, hypocrisy, and express their anger through their actions (BhG 16.4-5).

¹¹³ They both have argued against the exegetical Mīmāṃsā tradition. See, for instance, Śaṅkara’s *Sūtra-Bhāṣya* (trans. V. M. Apte. Bombay: Popular Book, 1960), where his ‘extended’ interpretation of the term ‘*dharma*’ differs from, and exceeds the notion of *dharma* as ‘ritual injunction’ of the Pūrva Mīmāṃsā. See also Rāmānuja’s *Śrī-bhāṣya*, specifically in I.IV.6, where the definition of *dharma* is also ‘extended’ as a means of realization in ways very similar to that of Gandhi and Aurobindo when dealing with the *Gṛā*.

Many readers regard the *Gṛ̥ā* as a sacred and divine treatise, and a source for religious fervour. The text clearly unfolds ethical and philosophical issues, and places the human experience and activity beyond the boundaries of ordinary experience. Gandhi’s admitted use of the ‘allegorical’ method has made him the interpreter Western scholars have chosen to critique, but his ‘spiritual’ interpretation of Arjuna’s learning process probably represents a fairly typical case of how Indians interpret the exegetical conditions prescribed in the text itself, in BhG 18.71.¹¹⁴ Gandhi’s personal *śraddhā* or confidence (*viśvāsa*) and his obsession with truth¹¹⁵ (*satyam*) are in accordance with a long tradition of interpretation. While scholars can legitimately accuse the followers of the allegorical method of finding in the text what they thought the content *should* be, they, themselves, are really in no better position with a text of this kind. What the ‘historical’ school of scholars would like to assume is that they can access and work with what they call the *actual* content of the *Gṛ̥ā*, without any concern about the traditions of truth underlying Kṛ̥ṣṇa’s arguments. On the other hand millions thought Gandhi grasped the heart of the teaching brilliantly, even though they were not sure how he got there.

In our exegesis we will follow the Indian style of interpretation, at least in the first steps, in that we will accept the full text as it has been handed down in the tradition. In

¹¹⁴ Indian teachers who see the *Gṛ̥ā* as a consistent and coherent scriptural treatise have generally used this approach. Rāmānuja, for instance, argues that the first methodological criteria for a successful undertaking of a study on the *Gṛ̥ā* is to take it to the heart, as advised on BhG 18.71. Through his reading of the *Gṛ̥ā*, full of *śraddhā*, Rāmānuja came to understand that the mysterious message Kṛ̥ṣṇa was teaching was about the proper method to perform any deed (such as studying the *Gṛ̥ā* itself) with *śraddhā*. Tilak, Aurobindo and Gandhi are modern examples of successful use of this same methodological posture. Modern Western scholarship on the *Gṛ̥ā*, on the contrary, often underlines its lack of *śraddhā* in its approach to the *Gṛ̥ā*.

¹¹⁵ Gandhi’s approach to the truth is to be regarded as “experiments with truth”; it is not a matter of theological dogma. The same, I have insisted, is the approach taken in the *Gṛ̥ā*.

addition we will examine the uses of the term *śraddhā* in the sequence in which they appear in the text. And, finally, we will look for a theological meaning in the argument as it develops in the text. In order to emphasize our respect for the unity of the text we will begin by presenting a fairly literal translation of all 21 uses before examining each one separately.¹¹⁶

(1) *ye me matam idaṃ nityam anuśiṣṭhanti mānavāḥ śraddhāvanto' nasūyanto mucyante te'pi karmabhiḥ* (BhG 3.31).

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 3.3, says:] Those who ever carry out this teaching of Mine [of the real 'I', *ātman*], full of *śraddhā*, and without ill will, are also freed through actions.

(2) *śraddhāvāṃl labhate jñānam tatparaḥ saṃyatendriyaḥ jñānaṃ labdhvā parāṃ śāntim acireṇādhiḡacchati.* (BhG 4.39).

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 4.5, says:] One who is possessed of *śraddhā* gets knowledge; being devoted to that (knowledge), restraining one's senses; having attained knowledge, one soon attains supreme peace.

(3) *ajñāś cāśraddadhānaś ca saṃśayātmā vinaśyati nāyaṃ loko' sti na paro na sukhaṃ saṃśayātmānaḥ* (BhG 4.40).

[Kṛṣṇa says:] However, the ignorant, whose *ātman* is sleeping (*saṃśayātmā*) or dispossessed of *śraddhā*, is destroyed. There is not happiness, neither in this world nor that beyond, for the one whose *ātman* is not awake.

¹¹⁶ The total of twenty-one occurrences are as follows: BhG 3.31, 4.39, 4.40, 6.37, 6.47, 7.21 (2 occurrences), 7.22, 9.3, 9.23, 12.2, 12.20, 17.1, 17.2, 17.3 (3 occurrences), 17.13, 17.17, 17.28, and 18.71. When used as a noun the term *śraddhā* occurs mostly in the instrumental case (BhG 6.37, 7.21-2, 9.23, 12.2, 17.1, 17.17, and 17.28). It also occurs three times in the nominative case (BhG 17.2 and 17.3 – the first occurrence in the verse), and one time in the accusative (BhG 7.21 – the second occurrence in the verse). The term *śraddhā* also appears in the adjectival form in compounds such as *aśraddadhāna* and *śraddhāvānt* (BhG 3.31, 4.39-40, 6.47, 9.3, 12.20, 17.3 – the second and third occurrences of the term in the verse –, 17.13, and 18.71. The first occurrence of *śraddhā* appears before the first occurrence of *bhakti*, and its last occurrence happens after that of *bhakti*. Moreover, while the preliminary chapter 12 is dedicated to *bhakti*, to *śraddhā* is reserved the climactic chapter 17, right before Arjuna's last question to Kṛṣṇa in BhG 18.1, concerning the nature of the renunciation (*saṃnyāsa*) and self-surrender (*tyāga*) he is about to embrace due to his renewed mental disposition. The term '*bhakti*' and its cognate '*bhakta*' appear in the text of the *Gītā* 30 times: BhG 4.3, 7.17, 7.21, 7.23, 8.10, 8.22, 9.14, 9.23, 9.26 (2 occurrences), 9.29, 9.31, 9.33, 9.34, 11.54, 11.55, 12.1, 12.14, 12.16, 12.17, 12.19, 12.20, 13.10, 13.18, 14.26, 18.54, 18.55, 18.65, and 18.68 (2 occurrences). It is also worth noticing the occurrence of the verbal form *bhaj* (to honour, to worship) in at least 12 other times: BhG 4.11, 6.31, 6.47, 7.16, 7.28, 9.13, 9.29, 9.30, 10.8, 10.10, 15.19, and 18.67.

(4) *ayatiḥ śraddhayopeto yogāc calitamānasa aprāpya
yogasiddhiṃ kām gatiṃ kṛṣṇa gacchati* (BhG 6.37).

[Arjuna asks:] One who is possessed of *śraddhā*, but has not yet controlled one's dispositions (*ayati*), whose mind deviates from *yoga*, who fails to obtain perfection – what path, O Kṛṣṇa, does he tread?

(5) *yoginām api sarveṣaṃ madgatenāntarātmanā
śraddhāvān bhajate yo mām sa me yuktatamo mataḥ* (BhG 6.47).

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 6.40, says:] Among all yogins, the one who has gone to me through one's inner *ātman*; who honours me full of *śraddhā*, he is considered the best *yogi* (devotee) by me.

(6-7) *yo yo yām yām tanuṃ bhaktaḥ śraddhayārcitum icchati
tasya-tasyācalām śraddhām tām eva vidadhāmy aham.* (BhG 7.21)

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 7.1, says:] In whatever way a devotee wishes to worship with *śraddhā*, in that way I make that very *śraddhā* unshakable.

(8) *sa tayā śraddhayā yuktas tasyārādhanamīhate labhate
ca tataḥ kāmān mayaiva vihitān hi tān.* (BhG 7.22)

[Kṛṣṇa says:] Hence, I fulfil the desires of the one, who is endowed with this *śraddhā*. That one obtains those desires as they are brought about by me.

(9) *aśraddadhānāḥ puruṣā dharmasyā'sya paraṃtapa
aprāpya mām nivartante mṛtyusaṃsāravartmani* (BhG 9.3)

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 9.1, says:] O scorcher of the foe, humans who do not possess *śraddhā* in regards to this *dharma*, do not reach me, but are reborn in the path of mortal *saṃsāra*.

(10) *ye'pyanyadevatābhaktā yajante śraddhayānvitāḥ
te'pi mām eva kaunteya yajanty avidhipūrvakam.* (BhG 9.23)

[Kṛṣṇa continues:] Even those who are devoted to other deities, when they worship them full of *śraddhā*, they are also worshipping me, O Son of Kunti, though not in the best manner [in accordance to the rules].

(11) *mayy āveśya mano ye mām nityayuktā upāsate
śraddhayā parayopetās te me yuktatamā matāḥ* (BhG 12.2).

[Kṛṣṇa speaks:] Those who placing their minds on me [*ātman*], revere me ever disciplined, and endowed with the highest *śraddhā*, they are deemed by me the best in *yoga*.

(12) *ye tu dharmayāmṛtam idaṃ yathoktaṃ paryupāsate
śraddadhāna mataparamā bhaktās te'tīva me priyāḥ* (BhG 12.20).

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 12.2, speaks:] Those who honour this immortal *dharma* thus taught possessed with *śraddhā*, honouring me [*ātman*] as the Supreme; such devotees are extremely dear to me.

(13) *ye śāstravidhim utsṛjya yajante śraddhayānvitāḥ
te śāṁ nīṣṭhā tu kā kṛṣṇa sattvam āho rajas tamaḥ* (BhG 17.1).

[Arjuna says:] Those who, neglecting the injunctions of scriptures, perform acts of worship filled with *śraddhā* – what is their standing, O Kṛṣṇa, as regards *sattva* (goodness), *rajas* (passion) or *tamas* (darkness)?

(14) *trividhā bhavati śraddhā dehināṁ sā svabhāvajā
sāttvikī rājasī caiva tāmasī ceti tām śṛṇu* (BhG 17.2).

[Kṛṣṇa says:] Of three kinds is the *śraddhā* of embodied beings. Hear that their innate nature, is *sattvic*, *rajasic*, and *tamasic*.

(15-7) *sattvānurūpā sarvasya śraddhā bhavati bhārata
śraddhāmāyo' yaṁ puruṣo yo yac chraddhaḥ sa eva saḥ* (BhG 17.3).

[Kṛṣṇa continues:] *Śraddhā* is in accordance with the essential nature of every one, O Bhārata. A man consists of his *śraddhā*. He verily is what his *śraddhā* is.

(18) *vidhihīnam asṛṣṭānnaṁ mantrahīnam adakṣiṇam
śraddhāvīrahitaṁ yajñam tāmasaṁ paricakṣate* (BhG 17.13).

[Kṛṣṇa continues:] The sacrifice in which no scriptural injunction is observed, no food is distributed, in which there is no recitation of *mantras*, no *dakṣiṇā* fee to the priests, and which is devoid of *śraddhā*, is regarded to be *tamasic*.

(19) *śraddhayā parayā taptaṁ tapas tat trividhaṁ naraiḥ
aphalākāṅkṣibhir yuktaḥ sāttvikam paricakṣate.* (BhG 17.17).

[Kṛṣṇa continues:] When the three-fold austerity [of body, speech, and mind] is practised with the highest *śraddhā* by people of self-control [those who bring forward '*oṁ tat sat*' through *dāna*, *yajña*, and *tapas*], without longing for the fruit, it is called *sattvic*.

(20) *aśraddhayā hutam dattam tapas taptam kṛtam ca yat
asad ity ucyate pārtha na ca tat pretya no iha* (BhG 17.28).

[Kṛṣṇa continues:] O Son of Pṛthā, whatever oblation is offered [into the symbolic fire], or austerity [*tapas*, heat] is practised – all that is called *asad* (non-existent) if it is done without *śraddhā*, and it is of no account to us here or here after.

(21) *śraddhāvān anasūyaś ca śṛṇuyād api yo naraḥ so'pi
muktaḥ śubhān lokān prāpnuyāt puṇyakarmaṇām* (BhG 18.71).

[Kṛṣṇa, who has been speaking since BhG 18.2, says:] And whatever person listens to it [this dialogue, the *Gītā*] with *śraddhā* and without ill will, this person too shall be released and attain the fair worlds of those whose actions are virtuous.

The theological ascending order in which the occurrences are arranged in the text is somehow implied in the first and last occurrences. For, whereas in the first occurrence Kṛṣṇa already advances the idea that whoever practices the teaching he is about to unfold to Arjuna will become free from *saṃsāra*, in the last occurrence he promises that who ever even listens to that dialogue with *śraddhā* will be released. One recognizes the sequence of issues raised by Kṛṣṇa to help Arjuna find his deepest self. In each case it is the person with *śraddhā* who stays on the path. Finally in chapter 17 it becomes clear that it is a truly *sattvic śraddhā* that is the goal of the teaching.

Before embarking on the exegetical work of the next section, I want to bring up two keys to our interpretation. The first has to do with whether the *Gītā* fits into the *Mahābhārata*. We will deal with this question in detail in chapter V, but I want to point out before we begin how the verses BhG 4.39-40, 6.37, 6.47, 7.21-2, 9.3 and 9.23 work as keystones to address the central question of the *Mahābhārata*, which is fundamentally concerned with the meaning of *dharma*.¹¹⁷ Second, I want to point out how the verses

¹¹⁷ The central sections *Bhīṣmaparvan*, *Aṅgīrśāsanaparvan*, and *Āśvamedhikaparvan* deal with limiting circumstance of death, and *dharma* always appears in relation to the pair *śraddhā* and *śrāddha*. After all peace attempts of the *Udyogaparvan* had failed, *dharma* is thought of in these *parvans* in the limited context of *dharma-yuddha*. As I will argue, *śraddhā* links the different *parvans* together as a number of different reflections on *dharma*. After the *śrāddha* rites of Pāṇḍu in the *Ādīparvan*, for instance, Duryodhana decides he may as well perform the *śrāddha* rites of the remaining *Pāṇḍavas* as well. He realizes he needs to finish the *Pāṇḍavas* in order to protect what he believed to be his own royal right: to become the new crown prince. That is why he plots, for instance, the burning of the house of wax (MBh 1.132.1). Advised by Vidura, however, the *Pāṇḍavas* escape the fire. Bhīma and Arjuna wanted to confront the *Kauravas*, but Yudhiṣṭira, because of his *śraddhā* in *dharma*, convinced them to follow the *niṣkāmakarma* path, and hide themselves in the forest to avoid unnecessary family confrontation (MBh

BhG 12.2, 12.20, 17.1-3, 17.13, 17.17, and 17.28 synthesize the *Vedic* teaching on *varṇāśrama dharma* and the *Upaniṣadic* teaching on *mokṣa-dharma* under the new category of *ātma-dharma*.¹¹⁸

As I intend to show through the exegesis of the term *śraddhā* in the next section, the *Gītā* provides a satisfactory synthesis of the *Vedic* teaching on action and the *Upaniṣadic* teaching on salvation. In the system of ethics it portrays the moral order or *dharma* rooted in the transcending experience of the *ātman*, and at the same time enjoins a very ordinary individual into action.

III.2. Exegesis of the Twenty-one Occurrences

The first occurrence of the term *śraddhā* appears in BhG 3.31 in relation to the *karma yoga*. Prior to discussing its sentence syntax and the controversies regarding its interpretation I will say a few words about the context in which the verse occurs.

The first chapter of the *Gītā* already starts the discussion around the meaning of action through the opening question of the king Dhṛtarāṣṭra, who is ‘blind’, as he stands

1.134-6). The problem with Duryodhana is his attachment to the letter of the *Vedas* and aim at the goal of enjoyment (*bhoga*). Whereas Kṛṣṇa teaches *yoga* to Arjuna, Dhṛtarāṣṭra transmits to his son the desire to enjoy (power). There is a point, however, where *bhoga* can be *yoga* and *yoga bhoga*, and that is one of the reasons why the concept of *dharma* is so hard to define. Both *bhoga* and *yoga* can be part of a religious posture, with the first bringing a joyous focus to natural desires, whereas the other brings the need of self-discipline and a willful determination to achieve a particular goal. For more details on the relation of *bhoga* and *yoga*, see Paul Younger, *Playing Host to Deity* (Oxford: Oxford Press, 222), 61-66.

¹¹⁸ The *Mahābhārata* showcases in different episodes how one is endowed with the capacity to recognize the different truths. This too is the core teaching of the *Gītā* as Kṛṣṇa shows both how *śraddhā* is both the experience of universal truth, as well as one’s partial capacity to gradually recognize that truth. Whereas BhG 12.2 and 12.20 may be said to describe those like Arjuna who have just come out of a self-revealing experience with Kṛṣṇa, the *Mahābhārata* episode of Draupadī’s bridegroom choice shows how Kṛṣṇa is the only one with the capacity to identify Arjuna in the disguise of a *brāhmin* (MBh 1.180.10-20).

in the field of ethical action (*dharmakṣetra*). He asks: “what did they do?” (BhG 1.1). Saṁjaya’s reply, which constitutes the narrative of the *Gītā*, starts, then, by describing Duryodhana’s attitude as one based on egoistic self-interest and the desire to enjoy (*bhoga*) more power. Next, Saṁjaya describes how the *Kuru* prince, Arjuna, unable to act out of this same egoistic self-interest, cannot decide about the best course of action he should take.

Chapter 2 presents Arjuna’s main reason for not fighting: he does not know how to decide what is the best (*śreyas*) thing to do. He looks for the help of Kṛṣṇa, and asks: “what is the best thing to do?” (BhG 2.7) His partially unselfish and honest question leads to Kṛṣṇa’s initial response that his focus should not be even partially in that which can be slain (the body which has *ahaṁkāra* as its constituent), but exclusively on that which is social in nature, and represents the universal interest – the *ātman*, or the real, and eternal Being. Kṛṣṇa reminds Arjuna that only the ignorant [like Duryodhana] can be attached to the letter of the *Vedas* and aim at the goal of enjoyment (*bhoga*) and power (BhG 2.42-4). Stating that “*Yoga* is skill in action” (BhG 2.50), he teaches Arjuna not to be attached to the fruits of actions, or to the *Vedas* (BhG 2.53), but to leave behind all personal desires (*kāma*), withdrawing from the senses [controlled by *ahaṁkāra*] as a tortoise withdraws its limbs into its shell (BhG 2.58). For, with this discipline, even though engaged with the objects of the senses, one will be under the guidance of *ātman* (BhG 2.64). However, if the mind is guided by the senses [which are in the jurisdiction of *ahaṁkāra*], then, the senses will blind one’s judgement (BhG 2.67). For, “the man of restraint is wakeful in that which is the night of all beings, and the time in which all

beings are wakeful is the night of the sage who sees [or perceives the light of *ātman*] (BhG 2.69). Then, to reach the *brahmanirvāṇā*, one is to act always free from lust and desires, or free from the influence of *ahaṅkāra* (BhG 2.71-2).

In conclusion, once in the world, which constitutes itself as a *kurukṣetra* (a field – *kṣetra* – in which it is imperative to act – *kuru*), the main question becomes one about the course of actions. Kṛṣṇa’s explanation in chapter 3 will make it clear that it is naïve to believe that one has non-action as an option. This *Sāṃkhya* reasoning plus the *ātmic* perspective constitutes the *Sāṃkhya-Yoga* of the *Gītā*, and represents the guide to help one to decide about any course of action. It provides the context in which the term *śraddhā* appears in the *Gītā* for the first time in BhG 3.31. As shown below, the term appears in an adjectival compound, *śraddhāvanta* (people possessed of *śraddhā*), in the nominative plural:

(1) *ye me matam idaṃ nityam anuṣṭhanti mānavāḥ
śraddhāvanto’nasūyanto mucyante te’pi karmabhiḥ* (BhG 3.31).

Those who ever carry out this teaching of Mine [of the real ‘I’, *ātman*], full of *śraddhā*, and without ill will, are also freed through actions.

This verse uses the unusual expression *me matam*¹¹⁹ to refer to Kṛṣṇa’s teaching. I take this ‘*me matam*’ (my thinking) to refer to the previous verse where Kṛṣṇa cheers up Arjuna by suggesting that he should reflect on the Supreme Self (*adhyātman*) in order to act properly. The emphasis is on action and on the adjectival sense that there are persons full of something (*śraddhāvanta* – people possessed of *śraddhā*), which liberates them.

¹¹⁹ On this matter, see R. Minor, *Bhagavad-Gītā – An Exegetical Commentary* (New Delhi: Heritage Publishers, 1982). He states that, following Kṛṣṇa’s doctrine, *me matam*, with a firm faith, one is free by their very actions (134). Minor does not consider that the teaching referred to is the *ātmic* discipline.

Thus, in BhG 3.30-1 taken together, Kṛṣṇa points out that *śraddhā* comes from the trust and confidence in the universal¹²⁰ *ātman*. As a consequence, those who trust and have confidence in this teaching and example of Kṛṣṇa are said to be endowed with *śraddhā*.

The novelty of the teaching of the *ātmic* discipline introduced in BhG 3.30 is that it works as the foundation of this brand new theory of action, discussed for the first time in the third chapter of the *Gītā*, entitled *Karma-Yoga* (The Mode of Action). The concept of non-personal action,¹²¹ or the action performed without any egocentric and selfish interest – *niṣkāmakarma* is built upon an understanding of the idea of *ātman*. For, if an action is motivated by the impure *ahaṅkāra* (the selfish conception of the individual), through its relation with the *triguṇas*, it cannot be said to be *ātman*-oriented, or rooted in, or motivated by, *ātman*, which is the real Self. This is explained initially in BhG 3.27, where Kṛṣṇa introduces the concept of *ahaṅkāravimūḍhātmā*, or he whose self (*ātman*) is confused by the influence of egotism (*ahaṅkāra*). This distinction is not easy to grasp in English, as the expression ‘self-interest’ denotes also those who are motivated by selfish and egotistic purposes of individual profit. The ‘Self’ referred to here is the *ātman* or divine essence not the individual ego, and it is therefore only altruistic actions, performed without selfish interest (*niṣkāmakarma*), that represent the interest of the real and universal Being or Self (*ātman*).

In chapter 3, Arjuna’s opening question proves that he was unable to fully apprehend the core teaching of Kṛṣṇa, who had just declared in closing chapter 2 that he

¹²⁰ The *ātman* is present in every alive being, as opposed to the person of Kṛṣṇa, who is not.

¹²¹ Later on we will see that, ‘non-personal action’ means ‘non [-personal] action’, and expresses a renewed sense of ‘non-action’.

outlined the discipline necessary to reach *Brahmanirvāṇa*, (1) act free from the influence of *ahaṃkāra* (egotism), which means to act free from lust, desires, and attachment to possessions (BhG 2.57, 2.61, 2.71), and (2) cultivate the *ātman* (the light of the soul), which means withdrawing one's senses from objects and calming down the mind (BhG 2.55-6, 2.58-9, 2.64, and 2.68-9). His prescription even included a summary of his previous diagnosis: (1) the tormenting senses seize the mind of the one dwelling in the objects of the senses, which means that one gets confused because of the arising of desire, anger, delusion, loss of memory, and destruction of intelligence (BhG 2.60, 2.62-3), and (2) without peace of mind one cannot think properly, nor concentrate, which means that one's understanding is carried away as does the wind to a ship (BhG 2.66-7).

In other words, after chapter 1 focused Arjuna's state of confusion, and chapter 2 focused Kṛṣṇa's presentation of his diagnosis (BhG 2.2-3 and BhG 2.11), chapter 3 starts to unfold the suggested prescription from BhG 2.55 to BhG 2.72. There Arjuna had been told what he should do to reach the goal established in BhG 2.54, namely the state beyond all mental distress and confusion, known as *samādhi*, which would make possible the action Arjuna was refusing to perform (BhG 2.4-9). Kṛṣṇa starts the chapter 3 to reinterpret the *Vedic* notion of obligatory work (*niyatam karma*), expanding its ritualistic meaning and making it the foundation of all human endeavour. This teaching on *karma* reaches its climax with the definition of *niṣkāmakarma* in terms of *saṃnyāsa* in BhG 3.30. There it is said that one should perform all deeds with one's mind focused in the Supreme *ātman* – a deeper understanding of the truth already implied in a preliminary way in the statement of Arjuna's diagnosis (BhG 2.12-30).

It is striking that in the *Gītā*, the philosophical speculations of the two *kṣatriyas*, Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna, around the real-life issue of *dharma-yuddha* or the ethics of war provide an opportunity to discuss *karma* in terms of *niṣkāmakarma*, or *karmayoga*. In this sense BhG 3.31 is the opening of an Appendix on the war discussion which argues that ‘people of *śraddhā*’ and ‘people without ill will’ should be able to follow this teaching on how to act guided by *ātman* until they later on achieve a final release in *ātman*. Because ‘people of *śraddhā*’ is used to refer to a kind of traditional spirituality in BhG 3.31 and is contrasted to ‘people of ill will’, it allows the reader to link this whole discussion to *Vedic* and *Upaniṣadic* forms of spirituality. In this sense the verse says that this ‘new’ teaching about action-without-attachment is available to those rooted in traditional spirituality. For, once one seeks convergence toward *ātman* while acting (BhG 2.41 and BhG 2.47-8), one will be able to go beyond the legalisms of the *Vedas*, which still belong to the realm of the three *guṇas* (BhG 2.42-6). Beyond *Vedic* injunctions (BhG 2.52-3), which are directly linked to their fruits, one can now seek *yogic* injunctions, which arise through an understanding of the way action is rooted in *ātman*.

Some scholars have not seen Kṛṣṇa’s teaching of BhG 3.30-1 in this light, and have wanted to see the ‘*me matam*’ reference as a first introduction of the idea of faith in a personal deity. Paul Hacker’s effort to make *śraddhā* more in accord to Catholic teaching, for instance, seems strained. He argues, for instance, that in BhG 3.31 *śraddhā* appears as that attitude of doctrinal acceptance, without criticism, which precedes

knowledge (1963, 151-2).¹²² Implied in this view, of course, is the understanding of Kṛṣṇa as something higher than *ātman* itself. Thus, although the idea of the ‘*me matam*’ of BhG 3.31 refers to the teaching on the importance of *ātmic* works¹²³ that is being set out, we need to look to other verses for more on the theological content of the *Gītā*’s spirituality.

The next two occurrences of the term happen in chapter 4, entitled Jñāna-Yoga (The Mode of Knowledge).

(2) *śraddhāvāṃl labhate jñānam tatparaḥ saṃyatendriyaḥ jñānaṃ labdhvā parāṃ śāntim acireṇādhiḡacchati.* (BhG 4.39).

One who is possessed of *śraddhā* gets knowledge; being devoted to that (knowledge), restraining ones senses; having attained knowledge, one soon attains supreme peace.

(3) *ajñāś cāśraddadhānaś ca saṃśayātmā vinaśyati nāyaṃ loko’ sti na paro na sukhaṃ saṃśayātmanaḥ* (BhG 4.40).

However, the ignorant, whose *ātman* is sleeping (*saṃśayātmā*) or dispossessed of *śraddhā*, is destroyed. There is not happiness, neither in this world nor that beyond, for the one whose *ātman* is not awake.

In BhG 4.39 *tatparaḥ* literally means ‘having that as ultimate’, and the idea is that one is concerned only with that. *Saṃyatendriyaḥ* literally means ‘with the sense-organs drawn in tight, held under close control’. The foremost purpose of Kṛṣṇa here is to get Arjuna

¹²² Such acceptance represents in itself a religious and voluntary act, which Hacker understands in relation to *anasūya* (absence of ill-will) – a relation that also appears in BhG 18.71. Hacker understands *anasūya* as absence of negative criticism to what is considered true doctrine, to begin with. According to him, being a requirement of the four paths toward salvation dealt with in the *Gītā* (*jñāna*, *karma*, *bhakti*, and *yoga*), *śraddhā* is a component of *bhakti*, or the positive, sincere, and compassionate belief in the myths. For, according to him, in Sanskrit, *śraddhā*, defined as *āstikyabuddhi*, is what best designates ‘belief’. A slightly different position is seen in Archie J. Bahm. In his translation, *The Bhagavad Gita or the Wisdom of Krishna* (Bombay: Somaya, 1970) he provides the reason for translating *śraddhā* as ‘confidence’ in this verse: “the attitude is one of commitment and of full willingness to accept whatever risks may be involved.” That is to say, differently from what Hacker states, “Shraddha is not concern about doctrinal consistency but is a *feeling* [the stress is mine] of trust” (1970, n. 52, 39).

¹²³ Minor correctly criticizes Zaehner, who does not think that the *Gītā* is teaching a path based on activity. Zaehner, when discussing this verse, avoids the instrumental ‘by works’ and uses ‘from works’, arguing that ‘by works’ is not consistent with the doctrine of the *Gītā* (Minor, 1982, 134).

to act according to the old *ātmic* practice he has just revealed: one should always react to external stimuli guided solely by the light of *ātman*. Thus, with *śraddhā*, suppressing interest in non-*ātman*, one reaches the Supreme. But, hesitation (BhG 4.40) leads to destruction. Some scholars translate *saṁśaya* here by terms such as ‘full of doubt’ (Edgerton,¹²⁴ 1964, 27), ‘of doubting self’ (Zaehner, 1969, 198), etc., but as Smith wisely points out, “the root *sam-śi* means to be in doubt not in the sense of doubting as distinct from believing, but rather to hesitate, to be irresolute, to be confused” (1979, n. 54, 234). S. Radhakrishnan,¹²⁵ when discussing the term *śraddhā* as faith in BhG 4.39, says: “Faith is not blind belief. It is the aspiration of the soul to gain wisdom” (1971, 171).¹²⁶

Underlying this teaching is the idea that the world is consistent. This means that what validates one’s activity is the principle of *lokasaṁgraha* or world order (BhG 3.20 and BhG 3.25), as the context given in BhG 4.1-9 suggests. Being ritually established by *ātman*, the world represents a theatre where it is possible to give full manifestation to *ātman* as the primary protagonist. Kṛṣṇa is such a protagonist, and his role is to help others to develop the ability to play this same role.

The refusal to take advantage of one’s role in life to develop such an *ātmic* capacity is due to *ahaṁkāra*, which by definition, expresses the placing of *lokasaṁgraha* second to one’s selfish goals. The capacity to show restraint, or one’s acquiring of self-

¹²⁴ Franklin Edgerton, *The Bhagavad Gītā – Translated and Interpreted* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1944; reprint, New York: Harper & Row, 1964).

¹²⁵ S. Radhakrishnan (trans.) *The Bhavavadgītā – With an Introductory Essay, Sanskrit Text, English Translation and Notes* 2 ed., 10th impression (London: George Allen & Unwin, 1971).

¹²⁶ Yet, as we have seen in chapter 2, these two verses provide the occasion for Hacker to define his ‘intellectual *śraddhā*’, as the pre-requirement for salvation.

control, therefore, is what leads one to decide properly which deed is to be performed. In BhG 4.1-3 Kṛṣṇa states that he was proclaiming the *ātmic* knowledge (*Yoga*), which was already known by the royal seers (*rājaraṣayas*), to Vivasvat,¹²⁷ who communicated it to Manu, and so on. In BhG 4.4, Arjuna reveals that he cannot understand who was the source of such knowledge, since the birth of Visvarat was earlier than that of his friend Kṛṣṇa. In BhG 4.5-6 Kṛṣṇa explains that persons like Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna, have had many births, but the *ātman* (real self) in them is birthless and imperishable.¹²⁸ Then, in BhG 4.9 Kṛṣṇa explains that those who understand this process of the divine *ātmic* awakening in the person [which means to place *ahaṁkāra* under the guidance of *ātman*] also manage to achieve *ātman* and free themselves from rebirth.

Some scholars translating verses BhG 4.39-40 follow a tradition that presents Kṛṣṇa as the Saviour.¹²⁹ Therefore, instead of stressing the ancient science of the *ātman*

¹²⁷ This name, meaning “the one who spreads the light,” is also applied to Agni.

¹²⁸ Some have troubles understanding these two verses, pointing to what seems to be a contradictory statement of Kṛṣṇa, as no one can be birthless and have many births at the same time. Theologically speaking, though, this apparent contradiction disappears, once we understand that, although as persons we die, once we reach *ātman*, we realize that our real self is birthless. That is to say, Kṛṣṇa is not referring to himself from the viewpoint of a concrete person anymore, but from the viewpoint of his real nature, which is *ātman*. Therefore, every time he uses the personal pronoun, he is referring to the real self, or *ātman*. For, as he has revealed, he can say he is *ātman*. One sees that the germs of the doctrine of the *Avatāra* is here stated, with Kṛṣṇa being seen as someone who got enlightened long ago, and now has come back in a mission of restoring the truth. In BhG 4.7 Kṛṣṇa seems to be suggesting precisely this, as he affirms that whenever the understanding of *dharma* is exhausted, *ātman* manifests itself in the form of a person.

¹²⁹ Rao translates BhG 4.39-40 as follows: “The man of *śraddhā* gets knowledge intent upon it and restraining his senses; having attained knowledge, he soon attains supreme peace. But the man without knowledge, wanting in *śraddhā* and of confused nature perishes; for the confused man there is neither this nor the other world nor happiness.” Commenting on these verses, he says: “He [Kṛṣṇa] offers Himself to be a channel of grace. He invites souls to trust and love Him and promises to lead them to salvation” (1971, 131). In Zaehner’s translation, we have: “A man of faith, intent on wisdom, his senses [all] restrained, wins wisdom; and, wisdom won, he will come right soon to perfect peace. The man, unwise, devoid of faith, of doubting self, must perish: this world is not for the man of doubting self, nor the next [world] nor yet happiness.” Zaehner, then, asks: “*śraddhāvāṁṣi*, ‘a man of faith’: faith in what? This adjective is elsewhere applied to faith in Kṛṣṇa (3.31: 6.47: 18.71)” (1969, 197-8).

that Kṛṣṇa is attempting to transmit to Arjuna,¹³⁰ they prefer to focus on Kṛṣṇa as one who is capable of granting grace and destroying doubts. These scholars choose to disregard the fact that Kṛṣṇa is teaching the ancient discipline about the immortal *ātman*, and introduce the notion of worshipping Kṛṣṇa. They ignore the opening of the chapter in which Kṛṣṇa made clear to Arjuna that he was going to teach him the ancient science of the *ātman*, a science known by the ancient *Ṛṣis*.

Kṛṣṇa says he is not teaching anything new. Therefore, he cannot be said to be teaching the worship of the person of Kṛṣṇa, as the person of Kṛṣṇa has never been worshipped before. The person of Kṛṣṇa does, indeed, express the universal and impersonal *ātman*. In other words, in the person of Kṛṣṇa, *ahaṅkāra* is under the command of *ātman*. This line of thought is not strange to the Indian Tradition. There are many *Upaniṣadic* passages where the impersonal *Brahman* is expressed through personal figures of speech, forms of devotion that at first might suggest theism.¹³¹

¹³⁰ As a protagonist, Kṛṣṇa advises Arjuna to be purified through knowledge (*jñāna*) and austere practices (*tapas*) to attain his state of being (which is *ātmic* rather than *ahaṅkāric*) (BhG 4.10). His path (*vartman*) leads beyond the success (*siddhi*) born of Vedic rituals, for *ātman* is the eternal non-doer (*akartṛ*, non-active), who has no desire for the fruit of action (BhG 4.11-4). Therefore, every action is to be performed with disciplined manner and awareness of the nature of the action, so that one can perceive non-action in action and action in non-action (BhG 4.15-8). For, if one acts as if he were not acting, that is to say, without egotism, without attachment to the fruits of actions (*karmaphalāsaṅga*), one does not incur evil – and this is what is to be understood as the path of the non-action (BhG 4.19-21).

¹³¹ Das Gupta, for instance, mentions the ecstatic emotion of the experiences with the divine in a way that reminds us of the attitude of Arjuna when he finally recovers his *śraddhā*. This being so, Kṛṣṇa represents a living proof that the shifting from *ahaṅkāra*'s domain to *ātman*'s domain is possible for everyone. If we accept that Kṛṣṇa is a concrete example of the theory of the *ātman* he is teaching, we will also have to accept that his teaching should be called science, rather than 'doctrine'. For, where doctrines present dogmas, he is presenting himself as factual evidence. Das Gupta states:

The well known description of the Indwelling Lord or Antaryāmin in *Bṛhad-Āraṇyaka Upaniṣad*, iii, 7, or of the Akṣara or the Immutable Lord as Lawgiver to the universe in the same text iii, 8, may be cited as illustrations to the point [of the figurative personal connotation]. Like Kṛṣṇa in the *Bhavavadgāṇā*, again, *Indra* proclaims himself a true object of knowledge and worship in

In conclusion, according to BhG 4.39-40, *śraddhā* comes from placing *ahaṅkāra* under the jurisdiction of *ātman*; it means the awakening of *ātman*. For, the ignorant is he whose *ātman* is sleeping¹³² – a fact that manifests itself as one being dispossessed of *śraddhā*. *Śraddhā*, therefore, is what expresses the sovereignty of *ātman*. And perhaps that is why Kṛṣṇa uses as his strategy to remind Arjuna that it is the *kṣatriya* duty to protect the sovereignty of *dharma* in the kingdom. What could possibly be worse to Arjuna, then, than losing his *śraddhā* – a fact that would lead to the destruction (of himself and) of the state of *dharma* in the kingdom?

The next two occurrences happen in chapter 6, entitled *Ātma-Saṃyama-Yoga* (The Way of Self-control, or the Way of Meditation):

(4) *ayatiḥ śraddhayopeto yogāc calitamānasa aprāpya
yogasṃsiddhiṃ kām gatiṃ kṛṣṇa gacchati* (BhG 6.37).

Kauṣṭhiki Brāhmaṇa Upaniṣad, iii, 9 (cf. also *Bṛ-Ār. Up.*, ii, i) as well as in *Bāṣkala-Mantropaniṣad* where Medhātithi appears in the role of a loving devotee to *Indra*, who describes himself as the Brahman. Although the original idealism reveals itself, a similar attitude of adoration underlies the conception of *Ātman-Vaiśvānara* as the *Virāt- Puruṣa* or world-soul in a famous passage in the *Chāndogya Up.* (v, 11-18 = *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*, x, 6, 1), which finds its analogue in the conception which is involved in the *Yajñavalkya-Maitreyī* dialogue in *Bṛhad-Araṇyaka Upaniṣad*, ii, 4 and iv, 5. In all these passages, no doubt, the impersonal Brahman¹ is spoken of. (Das Gupta 1930, 496-7)

- ¹ Whether the term *brahman* originally meant prayer, hymn or spell need not be discussed here. Hillebrandt (art. “Brahman” in *ERE*) who gives *Sāyaṇa* seven different and in most cases justifiable interpretations of the word, is of the opinion that the original sense was ‘magic’; but the view cannot be taken as widely accepted. It is interesting, however, to note that if the term meant prayer, then Gedden (*Studies in the Religions of the East*, London 1913, pp. 235-36), following Deussen, is probably right in stating that the prayer in this case is to be conceived not as a petition but as the mystical exaltation of feeling and thought in communion with the Divine. This seems also to be the view of Geldner in his *Der Rg-Veda in Auswahl*, pt. 1, p. 122f. If this view is correct, then we can understand the ecstatic emotion or exaltation of feeling which is described as accompanying *Brahma*-realization in the *Upaniṣads*, which employ the term to signify their loftiest conception of absolute reality.

¹³² Kṛṣṇa is using in Bh 4.40 the same metaphor he had used in BhG 2.69: the sage is awake to *ātman*, which is the night of the other beings.

[Arjuna asks:] One who is possessed of *śraddhā*, but has not yet controlled one's inferior dispositions (*ayati*), whose mind deviates from *yoga*, who fails to obtain perfection – what path, O Kṛṣṇa, does he tread?

(5) *yoginām api sarveṣaṃ madgatenāntarātmanā
śraddhāvān bhajate yo mām sa me yuktatamo mataḥ* (BhG 6.47).

[The Blessed Lord replies:] Among all yogins, the one who has gone to me through one's inner *ātman*; who honours me full of *śraddhā*, he is considered the best *yogi* (devotee) by me.

The context of these two occurrences above is related to the idea that *yoga* implies mastery over all actions. In chapter 5, entitled Karma-Samnyāsa-Yoga (The Way of Renunciation in Action), Kṛṣṇa explains to Arjuna the meaning of this mastery, stating right away that only the fool¹³³ declares *sāṃkhya* (reasoning) and *yoga* (practice) to be dissociated from each other (BhG 5.4). Mentally renouncing all actions, the *yogin* is the one who enthrones the embodied one (*ātman*), who, as the ruler of the body, never acts nor causes action (BhG 5.13). Once this *yogic* knowledge about *ātman* arises, one reaches the end of rebirth and approaches *Brahman* (BhG 5.16-9).¹³⁴ Being able to endure in the body the agitation that arises from *ahaṅkāra* in the form of desire and anger, manifesting *ātman*, the inner nature of pure radiance, one becomes a knower of the *ātman*, and ascends to *Brahmanirvāṇa* (BhG 5.23-6).

¹³³ As we will see in more details in the next chapter, Śāṅkara, who hardly discusses the verses where the term *śraddhā* occurs, is a later representative of this class of *Vedānta* criticized by Kṛṣṇa. Śāṅkara insists in an absolute dissociation of what belongs to the path of knowledge (*Sāṃkhya*) and what belongs to the path of action (*Yoga*). Rāmānuja, as we will also see, discusses some of the mistakes of the *kevala jñāna* view of Śāṅkara, and recovers the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* view here discussed by Kṛṣṇa.

¹³⁴ *Brahman* is conceived as being the ground of reality of the universe and its cause, combining within itself both the efficient and the material cause of the world (*jagat*). *Brahman* is the material cause of the world because its lower nature, the non-sentient *prakṛti* or *pradhāna*, evolved itself through *Brahman*, and not by itself as maintained by the atheistic *Sāṃkhya* thinkers. The *Gīā* agrees with the *Upaniṣads*, according to which *Brahman* alone was there in the beginning to will 'May I be many.' This justifies Arjuna's description of *Brahman* as the cosmic vital principle and light, which, though infinite and all pervading, also resides as *ātman* within the lotus of the heart (Samjaya summarizes Arjuna's epiphany in BhG 11.12-3, and Arjuna gives its full account in BhG 11.15-51).

Chapter 6 starts with Kṛṣṇa stating that the real *saṁnyāsin* is the yogin who ritually performs all his actions, without attachment to their fruits. The simple avoidance of *Vedic* rites of fire does not make anyone a *saṁnyāsin*. For, *saṁnyāsa* is nothing but *yoga*, whose prerequisite is the performance of actions without personal interest (BhG 6.1-2). One should raise oneself by operating focused in the *ātman*, without allowing oneself to be dejected. For, this *paramātman* in oneself alone is the friend for the seekers and the enemy for the non-seekers (BhG 6.5-7). When the *yogin* is absorbed in the *ātman*, he cannot deviate from the truth, even when in profound pain (*duḥkha*). This capacity to disassociate oneself from *duḥkha* is called *Yoga*. Therefore, the *ātman* in him who is a *yogin* sees equally *ātman* as present in all beings, everywhere (BhG 6.18-29).

Having explained all that, Kṛṣṇa, then, equates himself with *ātman*, states *ātman*'s oneness, and says how the *yogin* is to act dwelling in Him [*ātman*] (BhG 6.30-1). Arjuna replies to Kṛṣṇa saying that he cannot perceive the foundation of this *yoga* based on the evenness of the mind, because his own mind is instable and difficult to control (BhG 6.31-4). Kṛṣṇa admits that this conception is difficult to grasp by those who have not cultivated the *ātman*. However, he argues, those who cultivate the *ātman* can overcome the difficulties Arjuna points out through practice (*abhyāsa*) and the discipline of detachment from worldly desires (*vairāgya*) (BhG 6.35-6). One should not avoid acting even when one is incapable of completely controlling oneself through *yoga*.

This is the context that triggers Arjuna's question in BhG 6.37. Arjuna is indeed willing to know about his own fate (he also can be said to be acquiring some *śraddhā*,

although his mind is still uncontrolled), when he asks about the fate of those who have acquired some *śraddhā*, but whose mind remains uncontrolled. Kṛṣṇa's reply immediately associates the presence of *śraddhā* with the generic performance of good deeds: “no doer of good actions treads the road of woe” (BhG 6.40). For, one reaches the radiant and pure state (*śuci*), which leads to a rebirth as a *yogin* (BhG 6.41-3), by making room for the attainment of the meritorious action (*puṇyākṛta*). Then, inheriting the lessons of the previous life, the new *yogin* becomes able to strive toward perfection (*saṃsiddhi*) once more.

This new opportunity happens, not because of an act of grace, but because of one's previous practice (*abhyāsa*). The controlling of the mind comes from one's continual persevering effort. Then, being free from any fault (*kilbiṣa*) and having perfected oneself through manifold births, the *yogin* reaches the path that leads to the Supreme. That is why Kṛṣṇa asks Arjuna to become this *yogin* full of *śraddhā*, who is established in the inner *āman*, and whose mind enjoys the Spirit of God (BhG 6.44-7).

The text does not endorse the opinion that man's effort comes second to Kṛṣṇa's grace in the process of obtaining *śraddhā*. Even Zaehner¹³⁵ acknowledges that it “seems to mean faith in the possibility of ultimate liberation” (1969, 198). Clearly, then, *śraddhā* is not directed towards Kṛṣṇa in BhG 6.37. Yet viewed within the theistic context these

¹³⁵ Kṛṣṇa may be said to be the source of all grace only in the sense that he is an embodiment of *āman* and, as such, he also can be said to be an expression of the *Īśvarāman*, representing the descending (*avatara*) of *āman* into the realm of *prakṛti*. This is the sense in which even Zaehner understands BhG 6.47:

Here we are told with the utmost clarity that no integration of the personality around its admittedly eternal and divine centre can be complete until it is combined with the adoration of God transcendent. In Christian terminology, we whose bodies are the temples of the Holy Spirit are not thereby exempted from adoration of the Father. (242)

two verses have led some¹³⁶ to see in *śraddhā* a component of *bhakti* as theistic adoration toward Kṛṣṇa. Hacker, for instance, argues that in BhG 6.47 *śraddhā* seems to appear as a pre-requirement of *bhakti*, as indicated by the use of the verbal root *bhaj* to express the idea of worship. He uses his Catholic classification here and sees *śraddhā* representing both ‘intellectual-*śraddhā*’ and ‘ritual-*śraddhā*’, and sees them as preparation for the worship (*bhajana*). A more natural reading would be that being full of *śraddhā* is the way a true *yogin* reaches *ātman*.

Rao, on the other side, restricts the meaning of *śraddhā* in BhG 6.37, and relates it to those who, aspiring “for the right goal,” have “trust in the Lord,” and employ “the right means.” In other words, “right aspiration should ripen into right practice and finally into realization of communion with the Lord”(134). The conclusion, then, is that it is okay to flounder in practice, as long as “a man has right aspiration and the knowledge of the right means” (135). This, however, is not convincing, for it contradicts precisely what Kṛṣṇa is trying to show to Arjuna, who, because of his unwillingness to act, was floundering in practice. Even if the passage might be taken as extolling “loving devotion of God” where “the word *śraddhāvān* is almost synonym with the word *bhakta*” (Rao, 1971, 136-7), we would have to be uneasy about the assumption implicit here that *bhakti* is always theistic – a view that infuriates Krishna Sharma.

In conclusion, as Angelika Malinar has noticed when discussing *śraddhā* in chapter 6, *Yoga* is primarily a *karman*, or activity (1996, 225). Merit (*puṇya*) works as a

¹³⁶ See Rao (1971, 174); Hacker (1963, 154-155), and also Minor, who stresses that “the total fixation upon Kṛṣṇa” is what is accomplished by *śraddhā*, and that, therefore, *bhakti* becomes “the key element,” taking “the form of worship, *pūjā*, and surrender, *prapatti* to the deity (1982, 235-6).

means to make one advance in the path toward the final goal, and trust or *śraddhā* is the experience of the *yogic* actor. For, disciplined (with *śraddhā*) activity is, by definition, *yoga*, and the perfect *yukta* (disciplined in the *ātman*), or *yuktātmān*¹³⁷ of BhG 6.47 is he who shows, as a consequence, devotion too. And that is why this ending verse of chapter 6 portrays the perfect *yogin* as he who acts full of *śraddhā* and with great devotion.

The next three occurrences of the term happen in two verses of chapter 7, a chapter entitled Jñāna-Vijñāna-Yoga (The Way of Theoretical and Experiential Wisdom). It is no wonder that the realism of the *Gñā* would come condensed in a full chapter, dedicated to those practices that lead to the discrimination of the higher and lower natures of the Supreme. There were those at that time who were asserting that *prakṛti* has no real existence, and all that appears to exist is illusion. Chapter 7 achieves two goals: it preserves the realistic spirit of the *Vedas*, and curbs any possibility of understanding *māyā* (material power, *prakṛti*) as illusion. The three occurrences of *śraddhā* are:

¹³⁷ This point is extensively discussed by Edgerton (1964, 164-171). Edgerton acknowledges that the knowledge spoken of in the *Gñā* is the knowledge of God, with its higher and lower natures (soul and body are two distinct substances named respectively *ātman* and *prakṛti*). True knowledge, or *jñāna yoga*, appears redefined to imply, then, the knowledge of a practical method, *karma-yoga*, together with an intellectual method, *sāṃkhya*. The word *yoga* becomes in the *Gñā* associated with “energetic performance, exertion.” That is to say, Edgerton hints that *yoga* in the *Gñā* is almost synonymous with *śraddhā*. The word *sāṃkhya*, on the other side, is redefined to signify a speculative method for diagnosing reality, where *saṃnyāsa* becomes *karma yoga*. At the bottom, Edgerton states, *sāṃkhya* and *yoga* are really one. His conclusion, however, that exclusive devotion to any of these methods as understood by tradition will lead to the fruit of both, does not seem to hold (167-8). For, in this case there would be no reason for Kṛṣṇa asking Arjuna to act. Furthermore, as we have seen when discussing the *Gñā*’s critique of the *Śruti*, the idea is that both, *kevala jñāna* and ritual activity, when considered in isolation, represent nothing more than preliminary steps in the path that leads to *Brahmanirvāṇa*. The final step implies the harmonious synthesis expressed in the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* view. Edgerton hints at this understanding when he admits, “I wish to reaffirm the fact that, in spite of occasional disparagements of the “way of knowledge,” the *Gñā*’s doctrine of disciplined activity really has an intellectual basis” (170). The reason he provides, however, does not seem to be accurate: “The reason for acting with indifference is that actions cannot really affect the soul for good or ill; they concern matter exclusively” (170). If such were the case, the whole *Gñā* would be pointless, for it would not be possible to consider it a Scripture concerned with *lokasaṃgraha*.

(6-7) *yo yo yāṃ yāṃ tanuṃ bhaktaḥ śraddhayārcitum icchati
tasya-tasyācalāṃ śraddhāṃ tām eva vidadhāmy aham.* (BhG 7.21)

In whatever way a devotee wishes to worship with *śraddhā*, in that way I make that very *śraddhā* unshakable.

(8) *sa tayā śraddhayā yuktas tasyārādhanamihate labhate
ca tataḥ kāmān mayaiva vihitān hi tān.* (BhG 7.22)

Hence, I fulfil the desires of the one, who is endowed with this *śraddhā*. That one obtains those desires as they are brought about by me.

In BhG 7.21-2 the three terms *bhaktaḥ*, *śraddhayā*, and *arcitum icchati*, appear in one sentence. ‘*Bhaktaḥ*’ is nominative singular and refers in a matter-of-fact way to a person who is a ‘devotee’. ‘*Arcitum icchati*’ is the verbal compound meaning ‘wishes to worship’. ‘*Śraddhayā*’ describes the state of mind of the worshipper which makes his or her desire a truly spiritual quest.¹³⁸ There is uncertainty about their object of worship – ‘yo yo’ (whatever); ‘yāṃ yāṃ’ (that indeed) –, but whatever it is becomes a legitimate spiritual quest when approached ‘with faith’ (*śraddhayā*). *Śraddhā* here is not theistic devotion to a particular deity, but a state of mind that transcends in worship.

Some scholars see this verse in which the terms ‘*bhakti*’ and ‘*śraddhā*’ are both used as evidence that they are identical.¹³⁹ I see it in the opposite way. A person designated ‘devotee’ has an experience of ‘ecstatic trust’ which needs to be stabilized.

What Kṛṣṇa explains in BhG 7.21-2 is the way in which the universal soul (*ātman*) lays

¹³⁸ Smith observed that the term *śraddhā* is often associated with the verb *iṣ* (seek, desire) (Smith, 1979, n. 56, 235), and in chapter 2 we already noted relation of desire to *śraddhā* in several *Rg Vedic* passages.

¹³⁹ Smith observes that Madhusūdana’s commentary on BhG 7.21 is cited for an equating of *śraddhā* and *bhakti*, and that Sāyaṇa does the same on *Atharva-Veda* 4:30:4 “*śraddhā* is *bhakti*” (*śraddhā bhaktiḥ*) (Smith, 1979, n. 63, 238). One of the consequences of such equating is the understanding of these two verses as a proof of *Gṛ̥ā*’s monotheism. See, for instance, Winthrop Sargeant (trans.), *The Bhavavad Gṛ̥ā* (Garden City: Doubleday & Company, 1979). Glossing BhG 7.22, he says, “All religions are subsumed here, and the speaking God explains that all worship, of whatever kind, goes to Him, and that all boons, begged from whatever gods, are granted by Him alone. The stanza is an instance of the strong monotheistic element in the *Gṛ̥ā*, also of its religious tolerance” (n.*, 352).

out (*vi + dhā*), or stimulates through the *prakṛti*, the gradual (*triguṇic*) development of *śraddhā*, or ecstatic trust. The persons' theistic naivety may confuse them into equating their own particular faith (*bhakti*) with the universal attitude of *śraddhā*. The two terms refer to very different parts of the religious experience.

The general issue of this chapter is to explain the importance of understanding the higher and the lower nature of the divine. The lower nature (BhG 7.4-5) hinders the perfect knowledge, but is part of everyday religions. *Śraddhā* is what links these lower forms with the final goal (BhG 7.20), and this is the reason why other forms of worship are acknowledged by Kṛṣṇa if in accordance to one's own nature. In Kṛṣṇa's scheme every religious desire possesses a relative value. For, all deities, in all forms – allegorical, mythological, and so on, are part of the cosmic reality and are useful to a certain extent in the different stages of spiritual development.

In BhG 7.21-2 Kṛṣṇa is subsuming all different faiths, for, any worship, of any kind, ultimately is rooted in the Supreme. What these two verses state is that *śraddhā* transforms and elevates, for it works from 'within', from the heart, from where one is always impelled towards *ātman*. These verses show that, from the *ātmic* perspective, there can be nothing but tolerance towards any kind of religious belief. This impersonal *ātmic* aspect, however, has been strangely taken by some to be the introduction of an exclusive theistic religion into the *Gṛhā*. Western scholars are particularly inclined to see here the germs of an Indian monotheism.¹⁴⁰

¹⁴⁰ Rao says, "Worship in the highest sense is, according to the *Gṛhā*, the worship of the incarnate Lord, Kṛṣṇa, who is behind and beyond all His manifestations" (1971, 138). And Minor also says, "This verse

The context of BhG 7.21-2 allows us to ascribe a different, and perhaps deeper, kind of meaning to his argument. Chapter 7 starts with Kṛṣṇa anticipating that he is going to transmit to Arjuna the knowledge about the nature of the Supreme. He observes that scarcely anyone strives for perfection, and that of those who do, scarcely anyone has the knowledge of the two natures of the Supreme. The material and inferior nature is *prakṛti* (where *ahaṁkāra* serves as the sense of personal identity), but it is the superior and spiritual nature that generates life (*jīva-bhūta*) and provides support to the moving universe (*jagat*) (BhG 7.1-5).

All creation (*bhūta*), the entire universe, originates from the two natures of the Supreme, who remains both present as life in all beings, and transcendent, as the Highest Being (BhG 7.6-9). Yet, due to the influence of the three *guṇas* of *prakṛti*, beings are not aware of the immanence of the Supreme in them (BhG 7.12-3).¹⁴¹ The divine *guṇa*-made *pra-kṛti* guarantees that only those who are not evildoers (*duṣ-kṛti*) have access to this

[BhG 7.22] seems to function to explain why people who worship the other deities which Kṛṣṇa has rejected, actually receive answers to their desires. It is Kṛṣṇa who gives them, not the deities they worship (cf. 9.23-24). The implication is, why worship these other deities when it is Kṛṣṇa who is true Lord” (1982, 253). It is also worthwhile to notice that ‘Hindu monotheism’, even in its later forms, does not include the Western idea of the negation of the deities of the different faiths in favour of ‘the’ one personal god. On the contrary, it is an outcome of the identification of all beings with the idea of *Brahman* and *ātman*. As Krishna Sharma reminds us, it is the Christian bias that leads one to relegate *Brahman* or *ātman* “to the realm of philosophy with the argument that it lacks the true spirit of religion” (1987, 53).

¹⁴¹ Malinar presents a different reading of this passage. She is of the opinion that in BhG 7.13 what is at stake is the qualification of Kṛṣṇa’s divinity in relation to the other gods (1996, 231) *Prakṛti* is presented, then, as what deludes and is the reason for the confusion in relation to the ‘states of being’ (*bhāva*), which stops everyman from recognizing the real nature of Kṛṣṇa. According to Malinar, in BhG 7.14, *māyā* is said to be Kṛṣṇa’s *prakṛti*. She follows Johnston and Frauwallner, and understands ‘higher nature’, not as ‘*ātmic* nature’, but just as ‘higher *prakṛti*’ (1996, 228). In other words, Malinar prefers to ignore the fact that Kṛṣṇa uses the terms ‘higher nature’ and ‘lower nature’ to distinguish between the categories of *ātman* and *prakṛti*. This distinction becomes impossible when one refers to *ātman*, as ‘Kṛṣṇa’s higher *prakṛti*’. Furthermore, as shown by Van Buitenen, it is clear in the *Gītā* that ‘*prakṛti*’ denotes ‘nature’, and ‘higher nature’ denotes the *ātmic* or spiritual reality (Van Buitenen, 1981, n. 29.2, 165).

immanence of the Supreme in them (BhG 7.14-5). All the good-doers (*su-kṛti*) are noble (*udāra*), but only the ones with the knowledge of *ātman*, who learn to abide in the *ātman*, can reach the Supreme Vāsudeva. However, such a Mahātmā (great manifestation of *ātman*) is hard to find.

In other words, the kinds of deity (*deva*), which originate from popular religious disciplines (*niyama*), are a function of people’s material constitution (in conformity with their *guṇa* composition). This fact makes it necessary that all kinds of devotees (*bhakta*) be rewarded in accordance with their *śraddhā* (BhG 7.16-21).¹⁴² Consequently, as their *śraddhā* improves (BhG 7.22), it helps them to liberate themselves from the misunderstanding (*moha*) about the nature of the Supreme Self (*Adhyātman*), which comes with birth (*sarga*) (BhG 7.27-9).

These two verses on *śraddhā*, however, have troubled many scholars. Hacker sees in these verses evidence of how ‘devotional-*śraddhā*’ is close to ‘ritual-*śraddhā*’. According to him, the term *tanu* (manifestation, form) in BhG 7.21 suggests the *Avatāra* theory, where a god may assume different forms, perhaps according to the idea that all gods are manifestations of Viṣṇu-Kṛṣṇa (1963, 155). For, those who worship ‘whatever form’ (*yāṃ yāṃ*), do so with their hearts, which represent Viṣṇu, Kṛṣṇa, and so on, despite how ordinary their cults are. Minor also, when trying to understand the reasons why some would worship “deities that are not supreme as is Kṛṣṇa” (1982, 251), says:

¹⁴² According to Malinar, however, BhG 7.21-4 only proves that *śraddhā* is the pre-requirement of *bhakti*, as shown in the findings of Hacker (1963) and Hara (1963-64). She stresses that the term *tanu* points to an *Avatāra* proto-doctrine, where all ‘forms’ come from Viṣṇu-Kṛṣṇa. As such, *śraddhā* represents the trust in ritual worship. Yet, it also represents a theistic movement against the realm of *devas*, through the *bhāva* of Kṛṣṇa. For, *tanu* represents the manifestations of Kṛṣṇa and also the lower manifestations (1996, 232-4).

Their *obstinate refusal* [*sic*] to worship Kṛṣṇa indicates they are *programmed* [*sic*] to do so by the *prakṛti* of [the person of] Kṛṣṇa. . . . Kṛṣṇa, as *Lord* [*sic*] of *prakṛti*, is responsible for ordaining the fact of the worship of other gods. . . . Does this mean that the devotees of other gods may seek these gods but not necessarily attain them? This is the sense of 7.22-23 and 9.23-24. When prayers are answered it is none but Kṛṣṇa who answers them. They may get answers (from Kṛṣṇa), but they will not attain liberation. The attitude toward other deities, then, is not as positive as it has been interpreted. (251-2)

In the view of Minor, it is not an attitude of tolerance and understanding of one’s spiritual maturity that is being considered in these two verses. Instead, the verses are a disguise for a subliminal postulating of Kṛṣṇa as the only one who truly interferes, and “answers requests to other gods if asked with non-attachment” (252).¹⁴³

The two occurrences from chapter 9, entitled Rājavidyā-Rājaguhya-Yoga (The Discipline of Royal Science and Royal Mystery) seem to prove that considerations of sectarian rights are quite alien to the argumentation of the *Gītā*. They are:

(9) *aśraddadhānāḥ puruṣā dharmasyā’sya paraṃtapa
aprāpya mān nivantante mṛtyusaṃsāravartmani* (BhG 9.3)

O scorcher of the foe, humans who do not possess *śraddhā* in regards to this *dharma*, do not reach me, but are reborn in the path of mortal *saṃsāra*.

(10) *ye’pyanyadevatābhaktā yajante śraddhayānvitāḥ
te’pi mān eva kaunteya yajanty avidhipūrvakam.* (BhG 9.23)

Even those who are devoted to other deities, when they worship them full of *śraddhā*, they are also worshipping me, O Son of Kunti, though not in the best manner [in accordance to the rules].

¹⁴³ According to Malinar, Minor is following Hacker in his analysis. She points out that BhG 7.20-4 are many times evaluated as representing the proof of the universality and tolerance of the *Gītā*. Hacker had coined the concept of ‘inclusiveness’ to mean the idea that alien religious groups would present similar central ideas (Malinar, 1996, 234). According to this view, the author of the *Gītā* would have attempted to subsume other cults in relation to Kṛṣṇa, even when they would not fit. For, in those cases, Kṛṣṇa himself would guarantee their results. That is to say, Hacker’s inclusiveness concept tries to denounce the fact that Kṛṣṇa’s cult is not inclusive at all (234-5). Following Hacker, Minor also rejects the idea of these verses having a positive tone.

Faith, trust, confidence, religious fervour, soul force, and enthusiasm in regards to *dharma* are what constitute *śraddhā* in BhG 9.3. It is not ‘faith’ in the person of Kṛṣṇa that is asked here, but zeal, regard, or *śraddhā* for the *Ātma-dharma* teaching he is offering to set forth in the following verses. It is this regard in *śraddhā* that begins the process that defines the basic divide between those who will eventually move toward what Kṛṣṇa represents or will return to the hopeless state of *saṁsāra*.

After laying out in the intervening verses the ‘secret knowledge’ promised about how the Highest Being is related to the world of creation, Kṛṣṇa returns to the question of multiple forms of religious life in BhG 9.23. Here he says more simply than in chapter 7 that the devotee who worships other deities with *śraddhā* or true trust and zeal is worshipping the Highest Being – even though without full understanding.

Radhakrishnan observes that these other gods are lower forms of the ‘One Supreme’, and so “the gods in whom people have faith are tolerated” (1971, 64).¹⁴⁴ In other words, because “the direct contemplation of the Absolute is more difficult” (238), knowledge is usually triggered by one’s initial identification with different deities,¹⁴⁵ as it happens with Arjuna in relation to Kṛṣṇa. Minor, however, disagrees with

¹⁴⁴ He says, “The faith demanded is the faith in the reality of saving wisdom and man’s capacity to attain it. The first step to grow into the freedom of the Divine is faith in the Godhead in us, which supports our being and action. When we surrender ourselves to that inner Divine, the practice of *yoga* becomes easy” (238).

¹⁴⁵ Edgerton hinted at this point in 1944, when he wrote: “Any religion is better than none. . . . The ‘materialistic’ school here referred to is accused by its opponents of having taught that all religion and philosophy were nonsense; that there was no guiding principle in the world; that all was chance; that the alleged moral law of the effect of deeds on the doer was baseless; that there was no soul, and no life after death; and that consequently the wise man was he who devoted himself to getting as much worldly enjoyment out of life as he could. . . . On the other hand, those who genuinely tho erroneously worship other gods are really worshipping the true God, tho they do not know it; and God accepts their worship, imperfect tho it be. . . . So each religion brings its suitable reward” (Edgerton, 1964, 182).

Radhakrishnan, and argues that Radhakrishnan goes a step further than the text, “for the *Gṛā* it does matter whether one worships Kṛṣṇa or not” (1982, 298). He asserts that the *Gṛā* does not approve such worship as on an equal level with worship of Kṛṣṇa.¹⁴⁶

The context of these verses comes from the preceding chapter, entitled Akṣara-Parabrahma-Yoga (The Way Toward the Imperishable Brahman). There Arjuna places before Kṛṣṇa seven questions; about the meaning of *Brahman* (Supreme Imperishable), *Adhyātma* (the inherent nature which originates the state of being), *karma* (action, sending forth), *Adhibhūta* (perishable existence), *Adhidaiva* (Supreme *Puruṣa*), *Adhiyajña* (The Basis of Sacrifice, which is the Self), and *prayāṅakāla* (the moment of death) (BhG 8.1-2). In explaining these categories, Kṛṣṇa is able to clarify that by *abhyāsa* (practice of *Yoga*) beings manage to focus on the Supreme *Puruṣa*, ultimately reaching It, who is the Ruler, the Imperishable (BhG 8.8-11). This practice, which ends rebirth, Kṛṣṇa explains, means learning to make the mind abide in the heart (*ātman*), constantly in *yoga* (BhG 8.12-6). This practice, once perfectly performed, brings *Brahmavidyā*, which leads to *Brahman* (The Northern Path). If practiced less perfectly, it still leads to auspicious rebirth (which means to approach the end of rebirth) as a *yogin* (The Southern Path).

In chapter 9 Kṛṣṇa explains that those without *śraddhā* cannot understand this secret *Rājavidyā*. Their fate (of the *aśraddadhānas* who show ill will towards this secret

¹⁴⁶ Minor is following Zaehner, who had stated: “Kṛṣṇa says that He strengthens the faith of people who worship other gods. The reason is, as He here reveals, that they are really worshipping Him” (Zaehner, 1969, 282). I prefer to think that what Kṛṣṇa is suggesting in the verse is how each religion brings some sort of reward, in Edgerton’s sense that “any religion is better than none.”

of the *Gñā*) is to be reborn in the path of death and *saṃsāra* (BhG 9.1-3). Kṛṣṇa explains that, among the *Mahātmās*, there are devotees (*bhakti*) and sacrifice-performers (BhG 9.13-15). Those who perform *Vedic* sacrifice, having interest in the fruits of the sacrifice, attain the world of Indra, and achieve meritorious rebirth. And as BhG 9.23 says, even those who do not sacrifice according to the rule are rewarded, if they perform with *śraddhā* (BhG 9.20-3). Finally he concludes, those who are devoted to the gods (*devavrata*s),¹⁴⁷ go to the gods; those devoted to the ancestors (*pitṛvata*), go to the ancestors, but those who sacrifice to me (*mad-yājīnas*), reach me as the same self (*samo'ham*), or *ātman*, in all beings (BhG 9.25-9).

We are halfway through the *Gñā*, and so far *śraddhā* is consistently used as both, a pre-requirement, and a consequence, of a true willpower and understanding. If the term shows any link to *bhakti*, it is only as an experiential dimension of a worshipper which makes their action effective. *Śraddhā* appears so far fitting with *Vedic* usage (a) in that it is the inner part of a desire or a ritual initiative, and (b) it opens the person to trans-personal contact with otherness.

So far, *śraddhā* has appeared as the zealous soul-force which is the vehicle for all meaningful activity. It cannot, therefore, be equated to *bhakti*, which is usually associated with non-Vedism and a devotional attitude. If in the *Vedic* period *śraddhā* appeared associated with the fruits of ritual activities, here it is not. This fact, however,

¹⁴⁷ I do not think that it is by mere coincidence that Kṛṣṇa chooses here the word '*devavrata*', as *Devavrata* is also the birth name of the chief of the Kauravas, Bhīṣma. If Kṛṣṇa is helping Arjuna to recover his *śraddhā* in the *Gñā*, later in the *Mahābhārata*, Arjuna, full of *śraddhā*, will start in a practical and symbolic sense, *Devavrata*'s *śraddha* rites. First Arjuna shoots Bhīṣma, and second, he provides Bhīṣma's lethal and yet comfortable bed of arrows, from where Bhīṣma would witness the whole development of the war.

should not be the cause of confusion, for it is precisely this dissassociation from the fruits that explains the core essence of *śraddhā*, when it appears associated to *ātman* in the *Gītā*. In other words, the *Vedic śraddhā* keeps in the *Gītā* its essential nature in the form of the mind's serene asceticism toward *ātman*. It expresses the confidence that the world of *saṃsāra* makes sense, as it functions under the subtle supervision of a higher *dharma*,¹⁴⁸ where actions present logical consequences in accordance to the nature of the actions.

In conclusion, up to this point, *śraddhā* is nothing but a kind of magnetic needle pointing towards how much one is deviating from *ātman*. It represents the mariner's only help during his journey over the seas of life.¹⁴⁹ It represents both a knowledge and a feeling that together trigger those intuitive jumpings into the unknown that one needs to face and tame. And perhaps that is why its outward look is the energetic and enthusiastic attitude of 'trust and confidence' in the inner *yogic* goal to be achieved. To be sure that *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* is not a matter of accomplishing selfish personal purposes, and that it is rather a matter of renouncing all these purposes, we will have to look to the remaining occurrences of the term in the text.

¹⁴⁸ The very first question, before any other epistemological enquiry should be about the subject. Only after assuming some metaphysical position concerning the subject, one can define to whom this subject will be relating. Broadly speaking, there are two main positions that we may assume: the subject is to be thought of as interconnected with the objects, like in the relation of the parts and whole. The other view is that the subject is not connected. Western tradition has chosen to assume that there is no such a connection, while Eastern tradition has assumed this holistic connection of life, whose name is none other than *dharma*.

¹⁴⁹ Kṛṣṇa uses the verb *nam* (to bow, to greet) just one time in the *Gītā*. This happens in BG 9.14, when Kṛṣṇa is explaining to Arjuna how one is supposed to pay homage. Arjuna, then, after his delusion (*moha*) is destroyed (BhG 11.1), pays reverence to Kṛṣṇa as Agni, the god of fire, and as Yama, the god of death in *Triṣṭubh* metre (a metre of 4 per 11 syllables applied to chanted interjections in order to praise, celebrate, and greet (*namas*) the other (*te*)), repeating the greeting *Namaste!* And *namaste!* (BhG 11.30-9). Kṛṣṇa replies that the Universal Form was made manifest to Arjuna through *ātmayoga* (the power and the practice derived from *ātman* cultivation) (BG 11.47-8). For, no Vedic rite was powerful enough to produce that which was due to Arjuna's perfect devotion alone (BhG 11.54).

The next two occurrences of *śraddhā* happen in chapter 12, which is entitled Bhakti-Yoga (The *Yoga* of Devotion). This chapter comes just after the great revelation of the Universal Form, and some scholars have wondered if the *Gītā* did not at one time end with the climactic chapter 11.¹⁵⁰ The following two verses where the term *śraddhā* occurs, however, show that chapter 12 takes up a new dimension of the dialogue where Arjuna finally becomes attuned to Kṛṣṇa's *ātmic* manifestation, discussed originally in BhG 6.31-2.¹⁵¹ Once again Kṛṣṇa brings *śraddhā* into the opening and closing verses of his reply:

(11) *mayy āveśya mano ye mām nityayuktā upāsate
śraddhayā parayopetās te me yuktatamā matāḥ* (BhG 12.2).

Those who placing their minds on me [*ātman*], revere me ever disciplined, and endowed with the highest *śraddhā*, they are deemed by me the best in *yoga*.

(12) *ye tu dharmayāmṛtam idaṃ yathoktaṃ paryupāsate
śraddadhāna mataparamā bhaktās te 'tīva me priyāḥ* (BhG 12.20).

Those who honour this immortal *dharma* thus taught possessed with *śraddhā*, honouring me [*ātman*] as the Supreme; such devotees are extremely dear to me.

¹⁵⁰ According to Malinar, W. v. Humboldt (1826, 46) was certainly the first to consider chapters 12-18 as later additions, and to suggest that the *Gītā* (with the necessary additions of a couple of verses from the last chapter) could have ended there (1996, 318). Zaehner, when discussing chapter 12 says, “the opening of this chapter must be one of the biggest anti-climaxes in literature” (Zaehner, 1969, 321). Minor also points to the fact that perhaps the *Gītā* should end with chapter 11, when he is commenting on Zaehner's note about Arjuna's dispassionate reaction to the vision of the last chapter.

¹⁵¹ This passage has troubled many scholars. Malinar, for instance, sees the tension between BhG 6.32 and BhG 12.2 as puzzling (1996, 320), for BhG 6.31-2 clearly establishes *ātman* as the object of worship, whereas in BhG 12.2 this meaning is only implied. The problem is that scholars coming out of the theistic tradition cannot accept the possibility that BhG 12.2 refers to *ātman* through the person of Kṛṣṇa as his representative. As a consequence, they denounce the ‘tension’, or contradiction of the verses, one referring to *ātman* and the other to Kṛṣṇa. Minor, for instance, even suggests that although the *Gītā* conceives devotion to the Unmanifest [BhG 6.31-2], what it really means is that the goal is to be attained in fact only through Kṛṣṇa [BhG 12.2] (1982, 367). However, what Kṛṣṇa's acceptance of diversity in the *Gītā* suggests is that all humankind has been religious for a very long time. Since the time of the great *Rṣis* the remarkable fact is that a number of great thinkers arose and they were scattered among people of different values and views. In common they shared an inner sense of religiosity, but none felt the need to subscribe to any formal institution. In this same spirit we cannot say, for instance, that Jesus was part of a ‘Christian’ institution, or that the Buddha was in the same sense a Buddhist. On the contrary, they both critically questioned tradition, pretty much in the style of modern free thinkers, or indeed, the ancient *Rṣis*.

The *Gñā* could never end with chapter 11, for it is only after the experience of chapter 11 that Arjuna starts to be in tune with Kṛṣṇa, to understand the extension taking place in his own experience. The summit of such understanding, of course, will only come in the last chapter when Arjuna decides to engage in righteous action. Such a decision is not even mentioned until after chapter 11. How could the *Gñā* end before the problem with which it started is resolved? Only after the theoretical discussion of the types of *śraddhā* in chapter 17 will come Arjuna's decision to fight, which is what really defines the end of the *Gñā*.

After chapter 11 *śraddhā* starts to take on a new focus. It makes devotion one pointed, and represents the psychology coming out from the experience in chapter 11 of the togetherness of the universe, as explained by Kṛṣṇa in chapter 10. In chapter 10, entitled Vibhūti-Yoga (The Discipline of Sovereign Power), Kṛṣṇa reviews all his earlier teaching. He describes the manifold conditions of beings, the beings arising from him, and how those who have knowledge of him, who dwell in the state of *ātman*, can cause that which is ignorance-born (*ajñānaja*) to be destroyed (BhG 10.4-9). Arjuna, then, in a mood different from that of the opening chapter, acknowledges that he recognizes as truth all that Kṛṣṇa has spoken to him. He is now aware that he is endowed with some sort of *śraddhā*. Moreover, having accepted this teaching as theoretical knowledge, he is now willing to experience it. It is then that he asks Kṛṣṇa about the means to get the divine and transcendent revelation (BhG 10.12-18). Kṛṣṇa explains it as the process, which triggers the manifestation of the excellences of *ātman* (*ātmavibhūti*). To exemplify his

point, he reveals that he is speaking from this very center (*aham ātmā*), and describes the excellences of one who is abiding in *ātman* experiences. He can see himself as Viṣṇu among the Ādityas, the mind among the senses, consciousness¹⁵² in the beings, and the Supreme science of *ātman*, among the different kinds of knowledge (*vidyas*), and so on (BhG 10.19-42).

Then, chapter 11, entitled Viśvarūpa-Darśana-Yoga (The Mystical Revelation of the Universal Form of God), opens with Arjuna stating that his delusion (*moha*) is all gone. Now he is desirous and ready to see the form (*rūpa*) of the Supreme Being (Puruṣottama) (BhG 11.1-4). Kṛṣṇa provides Arjuna divine eyes (BhG 11.5-8), and Arjuna, trembling, experiences the Puruṣottama in his own inner self (*antarātman*) (BhG 11.24).¹⁵³ Next, full of *śraddhā* he pays homage to the representative of the Lord of Creatures, in the person of Kṛṣṇa, saying, “reverence (*namas*); reverence to you (*namaste*)!” and in fear, tells Kṛṣṇa that he desires to see him in his human appearance

¹⁵² By consciousness, *cetanā*, it is meant the summation and unity of the three characteristics of human beings, namely, *jñāna* or understanding, *icchā* or will, and *kriyā* or activity. The theology of the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* theory seems to be borne upon these three aspects of consciousness.

¹⁵³ It is precisely impersonal knowledge that Arjuna seeks when he asks to see Kṛṣṇa’s true form – which is certainly not asking to see Kṛṣṇa, who is already standing there in front of him. Kṛṣṇa grants Arjuna divine vision so that he can have a personal experience with something that is non-personal – a cosmic divine form, which is not normally accessible even to the mystics. Arjuna even sees the allegorical death of the *Kauravas*, who appear being chewed up into the Supreme *Puruṣa*’s mouth (BhG 11.26-7). Kṛṣṇa, speaking on behalf of Kāla, explains to Arjuna that he is the slayer, and Arjuna only the occasion, which means that such a required killing was nothing but an expression of *dharma-yuddha* (BhG 11.32-4). That is to say, as a way to practice *yogic* self-control, Arjuna should act, or fight, without attachments and further considerations as to concerns with victory and defeat in that outer war. Those enemies, having already been killed by Kṛṣṇa, would die by other hands than those of Arjuna, if he had refused to fight in that war. Later on, in the course of the *Mahābhārata*, Arjuna will communicate to Yudhiṣṭira, who was terribly concerned with how to break through the formations arranged by the invincible Bhīṣma, that Nārada had confirmed to him that victory was a certainty. For, according to Nārada, “where there is Kṛṣṇa, there goes the victory” (MBh 6.21.11-7).

(BhG 11.39-46). With Arjuna’s mind restored (*sacetas*) to its natural state, Kṛṣṇa tells him that by undisrupted devotion alone he could be known (BhG 11.51-54).

This one pointed devotion, which is not that inactive devotion Arjuna had shown before, is characterized by *śraddhā*, or the willingness to do the works that are inspired by the Highest (BhG 11.55). It represents a divine alchemy where all previous theological hearsay, now tested and verified, becomes *Brahmavidyā*, or that synthetic (*yogic*) knowledge from which action can only arise as a consequence of one’s true loving devotion.¹⁵⁴

This is the context of BhG 12.2, where Kṛṣṇa says that he holds to be perfect in *yoga* those endowed with the highest *śraddhā*.¹⁵⁵ In the ending verse BhG 12.20, Kṛṣṇa reaffirms that those endowed with *śraddhā* are dear to him. A. J. Bahm (1970, 100 and 103) translates *śraddhā* in these verses as ‘confidence’. They have less to do with Arjuna’s theological ‘faith’ than with his self-recovery, through a process involving dialectical knowledge, good will, and mystical experience. This is stated in a more

¹⁵⁴ Radhakrishnan says: “When we see the One Self in all things, equal-mindedness, freedom from selfish desires, surrender of our whole nature to the Indwelling Spirit and love for all arise. When these qualities are manifested, our devotion is perfect and we are God’s own men (1971, 299).

¹⁵⁵ See Anilbaran Roy (ed.), *The Gita – With Text, Translation and Notes Compiled From Sri Aurobindo’s Essays on the Gita* (Pondicherry: Sri Aurobindo Ashram, 1946). This Supreme *śraddhā*, according to Aurobindo “is that which sees God in all and to its eye the manifestation and the non-manifestation are one Godhead. He is Purushottama, Parameshvara and Paramatman” (199). Rao, on the other hand argues that BhG 12.2 spells that the ‘highest *śraddhā*’ means personal worship of Kṛṣṇa. He stresses the phrases, “worship of ‘Me’ and thoughts directed to ‘Me’” (Rao, 1971, 147). That is to say, “*parā śraddhā* has the same significance as *bhakti*; it has reference to the personal God” (147-8). The conclusion, then, is that “chapter XII goes to prove that *bhaktiyoga*, the devotion to the Lord, is preferable to *jñānamārga*, the contemplation of the impersonal *brahman*” (148). This theistic interpretation leads to the view that in BhG 12.20 “the word *śraddadhāna* is almost synonymous with *bhakta*,” for “*śraddadhāna* is the one who takes the path of devotion to reach the Lord”(150).

Vedāntic way by N. C. Yati,¹⁵⁶ who renders *upetāḥ śraddhayā parayā* in BhG 12.2: ‘with a *fervour* pertaining to the Supreme’ (Yati, 1981, 276). According to him, “what is prized most highly in the *Gītā* is an unfailing attention to the Absolute, which runs through every moment of life like a golden thread, giving unity to life and order to the world. This is called *śraddhā*” (Yati, 1981, 342).

In conclusion, as a result of Arjuna’s increasing soul force or *śraddhā*, which leads him to the experience of chapter 11, his devotion moves from the sphere of religious ‘faith’, passing on to represent a verified theological knowledge. This means that his *bhakti* represents now that kind of devotion that results from the real experience he had with God. And that is why this chapter is entitled Bhakti-Yoga – it does not represent the discipline of the soft-minded sentimentalist as many have taken it to be.

The next occurrences of the term *śraddhā* happen in chapter 17, entitled *Śraddhātraya-Vibhāga-Yoga* (The Mystical Recognition of the Threefold Religious Fervour), where the term is used a total of eight times in the context of a careful discussion of how a mature sense of *śraddhā* relates to the *guṇa* theory of the person. It is the philosophical and theological explanation of the ancient theory of the three *guṇas* (strands, qualities) of the material reality (*prakṛti*) first introduced in chapter 14. In this context there is a theological rephrasing of the original question on the importance of *śraddhā*, posed by Arjuna in chapter 6, and partially answered by Kṛṣṇa in chapter 9.

¹⁵⁶ N. C. Yati and Nataraja Guru (trans.), *The Bhagavad Gita – A sublime Hymn of Yoga Composed by the Ancient Seer Vyāsa* (Sahibabad: Vikas Publishing, 1981).

In BhG 17.1 Arjuna reframes his original question of BhG 6.37. In the meantime the *triguṇic* understanding of the world was introduced in chapter 14, and now it is possible for Kṛṣṇa to account for all shades of gray between the plain black and white.¹⁵⁷ The earlier treatment of this issue in chapter 9 (and even in chapter 16) was based in the more traditional logic, which sees things simplistically, in absolute terms, as either true or false,¹⁵⁸ right or wrong, *daivic* (good) or *āsuric* (bad), *sukha* (pleasure) or *duḥkha* (pain), and so on.

The whole of chapter 17 is dedicated to the discussion of *śraddhā*, and the term occurs eight times. Yati sees here an exercise that is “diagnostic in character”, where *śraddhā* literally means ‘deep interest’ (1981, 8). According to him, this chapter provides “a symptomatic diagnosis of one’s basic character” (8). This chapter, he adds, shows how one becomes enthusiastically engaged, or fully committed, with such a commitment representing *śraddhā* (361). Furthermore, even when *śraddhā* is translated as ‘faith’ he argues that one should keep in mind that

Faith is not an appropriate word to bring out the entire connotation of the term *śraddhā*. *Śraddhā* means one-pointed attention, perfect bipolarity, total acceptance, pure devotion, ardent faith, full sympathy, unconditional appreciation and an attitude of loving regard which is continuous and consistent, like the unbroken flow of oil. (373)

¹⁵⁷ Malinar also makes reference to this transposition from the dual to the three folded realm (1996, 362).

¹⁵⁸ Edgerton seems overwhelmed by the dialectic and ‘post-modern-like’ approach of the *Gñā* as a whole. He says: “The *Gñā* deliberately brackets two opposing views and asserts the validity of both. It is only in the realm of logic that we must choose between yes and no, or else confess ignorance. The *Gñā* finds no difficulty in saying both yes and no, at the same time. For its point of view is simply unrelated to logic. Even what it calls ‘knowledge’ is really intuitional perception; it is not, and is not intended to be, based on rational analysis” (Edgerton, 1964, 193). Edgerton’s view of logic here is an old fashioned Aristotelian view. One might argue that the dialectic logic being introduced is quite sophisticated.

In Sri Aurobindo’s notes on the *Gñā* compiled by Roy, a foundational meaning of *śraddhā* is brought out as the individual and the community at large evolve, and leave behind some long-established rules. To do so they find in *śraddhā* the necessary support. In this context *śraddhā* represents one’s will to live what one sees to be the truth of oneself and of existence (Roy, 1963, 255-6). This sense is very close to that conveyed by ‘enthusiasm’, ‘soul force’, and ‘religious fervour’, and we will try to bring out that meaning in the passages where the term *śraddhā* occurs in chapter 17.

(13) *ye śāstravidhim utsṛjya yajante śraddhayānvitāḥ
teṣāṃ nīṣṭhā tu kāmā kṛṣṇa sattvam āho rajas tamaḥ* (BhG 17.1).

[Arjuna said:] Those who, neglecting the injunctions of scriptures, perform acts of worship filled with *śraddhā* – what is their standing, O Kṛṣṇa, as regards *sattva* (goodness), *rajas* (passion) or *tamas* (darkness)?

How can worshipping with ‘faith’ coexist with neglecting the Scriptures? This apparent contradiction is easily solved once we turn to the other meanings of the term *śraddhā*. Bahm takes *śraddhā* in this chapter as confidence (1970, 123). Minor, when glossing this verse points to the definitions of *śraddhā* according to Śāṅkara and Rāmānuja: Śāṅkara sees *śraddhā* as “belief in a supreme being,” and Rāmānuja as “eagerness to put into practice what one already has confidence in” (1982, 449). These two definitions work together to demonstrate Aurobindo’s argument that *śraddhā* also represents one’s will to live what one sees to be the truth – a statement which corroborates the view of *śraddhā* as ‘zeal’, ‘soul force’, ‘enthusiasm’, and ‘religious fervour’. For, acting out of *śraddhā* is not so much *following* dogma as it is seeking *ātmic* goals. In other words, BhG 17.1, touches the core issue of one’s relation to

‘*śāstravidhim utsrjya*’ (neglecting the ordinance of Scripture),¹⁵⁹ and provides Kṛṣṇa the opportunity to restate in this new light his teaching on *ātma-dharma*.

The following verses present Kṛṣṇa showing that possessing *śraddhā* is compatible with the neglect of Scripture – a truth he had already stated in BhG 2.42-6.

(14) *trividhā bhavati śraddhā dehinām sā svabhāvajā
sāttvikī rājasī caiva tāmasī ceti tām śṛṇu* (BhG 17.2).

[Kṛṣṇa said:] Of three kinds is the *śraddhā* of embodied beings. Hear that their innate nature, is *sattvic*, *rajasic*, and *tamasic*.

Here we have the paradigmatic case where one can prove that *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* does not have Kṛṣṇa as its object. The passage makes it very clear that *śraddhā* cannot be taken to mean ‘faith’ in this verse, let alone be faith in a theistic being or ‘faith in Kṛṣṇa’. Moreover, if Kṛṣṇa were the object of *śraddhā*, one should expect that chapter 17 would at least mention this fact somewhere. However, in the whole chapter Kṛṣṇa’s divinity is neither directly nor indirectly discussed. What is discussed is the strong connection between *śraddhā* and ritual action – a fact that links the term back to its *Vedic* origins and presents a discussion of spirituality which does not center on theism and devotion to Kṛṣṇa in the form of *bhakti*.

Smith uses Rāmānuja’s commentary on the *Gītā* to provide some evidence in favour of the argument that *śraddhā* cannot be taken as faith:

¹⁵⁹ This point is so devastating for the dogmatic *Vedānta* that it has led Śāṅkara, for instance, to explain the phrase ‘*śāstra-vidhim utsrjya*’ as a matter of ‘ignorance of the ordinance of the Scripture’, rather than its conscious neglecting. Implied in his analysis is the idea that those who deliberately sin against Scriptural knowledge cannot be endowed with *śraddhā*, if *śraddhā* is taken to be simply ‘faith’. Yet, whereas ‘faith’ is not compatible with the neglect of Scripture, Aurobindo’s ‘will to live what one sees to be the truth’, and my definition are compatible.

yatra rucis tatra śraddhā jāyate śraddhā hi “svābhimatam sādhayaty etad” iti viśvāsapūrvikā sādhanē tvarā. “Where there is something attractive, there *śraddhā* is generated. Given the confidence that a particular religious path does indeed lead to one’s goal, *śraddhā* is then one’s eager setting out upon that path”. More literally: “*śraddhā* is the eager pursuit of a (religious) system, a prior element in which [eagerness] is the confidence that this [system] will effectively lead to one’s goal”.

On the first five words, compare the Gospel: “Where your treasure is, there will your heart [sic] be also” (Mathew 6:21 = Luke 12:34) (Smith 1979, n. 82, 245).

As BhG 17.2 stresses, one’s *svabhāva* (innate state of being) shapes one’s *śraddhā*. This means that one’s *śraddhā* includes the full spiritual self including one’s former lives.

Aurobindo, for instance, says:

A man is what he is today by some past will of his nature sustained and continued by a present will to know, to believe, and to be in his intelligence and vital force, and whatever new turn is taken by this will and faith active in his very substance, that he will tend to become in the future. We create our own truth of existence in our own action of mind and life, which is another way of saying that we create our own selves, are our own makers. (Roy, 1963, 257)

Many scholars translate *svabhāva* by ‘character’, ‘nature’, and so on. In any case, *śraddhā* must, at least, be defined as something related to our inner state, as denoted by the term ‘confidence’. It is not comparable to Western notions of a conscious acceptance of doctrine, as denoted by the term ‘faith’. Terms such as ‘confidence’, ‘enthusiasm’, ‘soul force’, and even ‘religious fervour’ are efforts to uncover the *triguṇic* analysis of chapter 17, and seem to get closer to that analysis of experience than does a term such as ‘faith’. That is to say, ‘*śraddhā*’ gives a measure of what one is, while ‘faith’ does not.

The next verse helps to make this point:

(15-7) *sattvānurūpā sarvasya śraddhā bhavati bhārata śraddhāmāyo’ yaṁ puruṣo yo yac chraddhaḥ sa eva saḥ* (BhG 17.3).

Śraddhā is in accordance with the essential nature of every one, O Bhārata. A man consists of his *śraddhā*. He verily is what his *śraddhā* is.

D. Prithipaul's¹⁶⁰ analysis of BhG 17.3 is worth quoting:

Boileau, the famous French critic and writer, is known for this particular celebration of aesthetic refinement: “Style, that is what a man is” (“Le style, c’est l’homme”). The epistle of James says: “Even so faith, if it hath not works, is dead, being alone” (2.17). Again, “Ye see then how that by works a man is justified, and not by faith only (2.24). And again, “For as the body without the spirit is dead, so faith without works is dead also” (2.26). Lenin advises that in a politician one must not look at his mouth, but at his hands. (Prithipaul, 1993, 857)

Śraddhā in this context is a privileged mode of self-expression (1993, 858), it is that which governs participation and active engagement in life – the *Īśvara* inside oneself. For, the true ascetic is the one who renounces, not actions, but selfish interest in actions, according to BhG 18.2. Radhakrishnan also says *śraddhā* “is not acceptance of a belief;” “it is striving after self-realization.” For, “the incontrovertible evidence of any religious faith is the evidence of the believer’s heart” (1971, 343).

Finally, in BhG 17.13 Kṛṣṇa starts to answer the question of BhG 17.1:

(18) *vidhihīnam asṛṣṭānnaṃ mantrahīnam adakṣiṇam
śraddhāviraḥitaṃ yajñam tāmasaṃ paricakṣate* (BhG 17.13).

The sacrifice in which no scriptural injunction is observed, no food is distributed, in which there is no recitation of *mantras*, no *dakṣiṇā* fee to the priests, and which is devoid of *śraddhā*, is regarded to be *tamasic*.

(19) *śraddhayā parayā taptaṃ tapas tat trividhaṃ naraiḥ
aphalākāṅkṣibhir yuktaiḥ sāttvikam paricakṣate.* (BhG 17.17).

When the three-fold austerity [of body, speech, and mind] is practised with the highest *śraddhā* by people of self-control [those who bring forward ‘*oṃ tat sat*’ through *dāna*, *yajña*, and *tapas*], without longing for the fruit, it is called *sattvic*.

¹⁶⁰ D. Prithipaul, *The Bhagavad Gītā -- With Sanskrit text, Translation and A Comparative Commentary*, 2 vol. (New Delhi: Cosmo Publications, 1993).

If one is careless, and one’s heart is not in the action one is performing, the action itself is pointless. On the contrary, when one acts full of *śraddhā*, one’s action is *sattvic* (pure and good).¹⁶¹ As was the case for BhG 17.2, BhG 17.17 also constitutes a real problem for scholars who have argued on the basis of other passages that *śraddhā* should be translated as ‘faith’ and that the object of this ‘faith’ is no other than the person of Kṛṣṇa. For, while one senses a spiritual longing perhaps for the impersonal *ātman*, there is nothing else here to indicate a personal source or object of *śraddhā*. Smith also notices this highest realization:

This passage [BhG 17.17] is crucial in illustrating that *śraddhā* -- and indeed *śraddhā* of the most excellent type (*parayā* here) – characterizes, at least on occasion, men unattached to the fruits of their actions, men seeking no reward. This, therefore (and the spirit of the passage is hardly exceptional), dissuades me from accepting without more ado the view (e.g., as advanced by Seshagiri Rao in our ref. 58 above, and others) that *śraddhā* inherently involves a conviction that a given means will lead to a given end that is desired. (Contrast, however, our citation at ref. 82 below of Rāmānuja, where the instrumentalist word *sādhana*, “means”, is indeed used.) Some might hold it theoretically possible, perhaps, to construe *aphalākāṅkṣin* in the *Gītā* verse above as *aphala* / *ākāṅkṣin*, “desiring fruitlessness”, as well as *a* / *phalākāṅkṣin*, “not desirous-of-fruit”; but I find this quite unlikely. There would seem to me a tension between the view that *śraddhā* is the confidence or trust or even the belief that the ritual act or whatever will “work”, and the often-observed position that precisely this attachment (non-detachment) vitiates it. Faith is the capacity to recognize and to live sincerely in terms of cosmic purposes rather than one’s own. (Smith 1979, n. 60, 237)

The next passage shows that *śraddhā* does represent the capacity to recognize and to live sincerely in terms of cosmic purposes – a capacity which can only be realized on *one’s own* soul force, through *ātman*.

¹⁶¹ Aurobindo says, “Here comes in all that quiets or disciplines the *rajasic* and egoistic nature and all that replaces it by the happy and tranquil principle of good and virtue. . . . And what will remain then will be the spirit’s immaculate *Tapas* [austerity], a highest will and luminous force in all the members, acting in a wide and solid calm and a deep and pure spiritual delight, *ānanda*” (Roy, 1963, 263).

(20) *aśraddhayā hutam dattam tapas taptam kṛtam ca yat
asad ity ucyate pārtha na ca tat pretya no iha* (BhG 17.28).

O Son of Pṛthā, whatever oblation is offered [into the symbolic fire], or austerity [*tapas*, heat] is practised – all that is called *asad* (non-existent) if it is done without *śraddhā*, and it is of no account to us here or hereafter.

Here the centrality of *śraddhā* is established, not only in the text of the *Gītā*, but as the principle ruling existence itself. In Aurobindo's words,

The soul's faith, not a mere intellectual belief, but its concordant will to know, to see, to believe and to do and be according to its vision and knowledge, is that which determines by its power the measure of our possibilities of becoming, and it is this faith and will turned in all our inner and outer self, nature and action towards all that is highest, most divine, most real and eternal that will enable us to reach the supreme perfection. (Roy, 1963, 267)

The centrality of *śraddhā* as pointed out by Aurobindo was, in fact, evident right in the opening question of Arjuna in BhG 17.1. Arjuna asks about the position (*niṣṭhā*) of those who follow religious rites and ceremonies casting aside the *śāstra vidhi*. Kṛṣṇa's reply constitutes the entire chapter 17. He, points out that *sattvic śraddhā* is in harmony with *śāstric* injunctions (BhG 17.17, BhG 17.20, and BhG 17.23-24), and that any ritual action without *śraddhā* is useless (BhG 17.28).

Kṛṣṇa starts his reply in BhG 17.2-3, where he says that, being never imposed from outside, *śraddhā* is in accordance with the essential nature of everyone, being *sattvic*, *rajasic*, or *tamasic*. Not only is the quality of *śraddhā* dependent on one's nature, but also one really is what one's *śraddhā* is. In BhG 17.13, it is said that, without *śraddhā*, one cannot be said to have one's heart in the *yajña*. For without *śraddhā*, the *yajña* is *tamasic*, and should be considered as devoid of scriptural sanction (*vidhihīna*). In BhG 17.17 Kṛṣṇa describes *sattvic śraddhā* as an expression of the threefold *sattvic*

tapas— austerity in the body, in words, and in thoughts. In BhG 17.28, the criteria for any ritual performance present someone with *sattvic śraddhā* as one’s connection with the true being, or the goodness, *sat*.

In the passage BhG 17.28 *śraddhā* is directly related to *sat*, and whatever is done in life without *śraddhā* is *asat* (non-existent), pointless and of no account here or here after.¹⁶² As in the *Upaniṣads*, where *tapas* is frequently associated with *śraddhā*, also in the *Gītā*, through *tapas*, *śraddhā* appears in relation to the formula *Om tat sat*, which Kṛṣṇa introduces in BhG 17.23. According to Aurobindo’s analysis, which we will see in detail in the following chapter, *Om* is associated to *Brahman* and the *Veda*, and represents the orthodox actions performed in accordance with scriptural injunctions. By *sat* one is to understand the essence of reality itself, whereas by *tat* one should understand all actions to be perfect, and should be performed without desire for fruit and dedicated to God.

The implication of this argument is that salvation depends essentially on *śraddhā*. The last occurrence of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*, in chapter 18, Mokṣa-Samnyāsa-Yoga (The Mystical Liberation by Renunciation), demonstrates this point:¹⁶³

¹⁶² In his “Sri Aurobindo on the Types of Sraddha (Faith) in the Gita,” (*Journal of Asian Literature*, Vol. 24, No. 1, East Lansing, 1989), Rao discusses this point. He seems in this context to agree that it is the spirit of *śraddhā* that really matters. “Actions issue forth from individuals in accordance with the type of their *śraddhā*,” “the quality of faith depends on the thoughts a person thinks, the desires one entertains, and the work one does,” and also one “should not abandon *sāttvic* activities such as altruistic service.” For, “the spirit of *sāttvikī śraddhā* is indicated by the formula *Omtatsat*” (1989, 173-5). That is to say, works are to be commenced with the utterance of *Om*, as a way of setting one’s mind in the proper sacred mood. *Tat* indicates the Lord, to whom we should dedicate any consequent fruit. *Sat* means that *sattvic śraddhā* represents altruistic activities, which are good and true.

¹⁶³ To what extension was the emotion side of *śraddhā* the reason for Kṛṣṇa’s devotees to transform the concept of *śraddhā* into *bhakti*, with the two words becoming synonymous, is something that is far beyond

(21) *śraddhāvān anasūyaś ca śṛṇuyād api yo naraḥ so'pi muktaḥ śubhānī lokān prāpnuyāt puṇyakarmaṇām* (BhG 18.71).

And whatever person listens to it with *śraddhā* and without ill will, this person too shall be released and attain the fair worlds of those whose actions are virtuous.

There are two points of interest in relation to this verse. The first point is that in BhG 18.71 *śraddhā* as taught in the *Gītā* is taken to be a sufficient condition to enter the path that leads to *mokṣa*.¹⁶⁴ The second point is related to the role played by two special listeners to Kṛṣṇa's message. Dhṛtarāṣṭra, a man of ill will, plays in the *Gītā* one single role: he is who, for the very first time, listens to the dialogue between Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna, narrated by Saṁjaya. And he does so without any *śraddhā*. His passive listening was not conducive to the generation of *śraddhā*, which would represent a means to salvation. Arjuna's listening to Kṛṣṇa's words, on the other hand, was in accordance to his active engagement in seeking the righteous deed. These two points may be summarized, indeed, as raising a question about the role of *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti* in the approach toward *mokṣa* in the *Gītā*. Kṛṣṇa's explanation seems to lead to a different understanding of *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti* than that understood by tradition. This discussion starts in chapter 4

the scope of this thesis. That is to say, how the medieval *bhakti* movement has succeeded in imposing such a theistic reading over the text is not the point here, for the *Gītā* itself does not affirm the identity of these two terms. Even when many scholars see in BhG 18.71 the result of an emotional side in the concept of *śraddhā*, one should not forget that since the *śrāddha* rites, *śraddhā* was already seen in the sense of an emotional connection with the metaphysical realm of gods and ancestors. Furthermore, it is only after the imposition of a theistic reading over the text that some scholars would state when considering BhG 18.71 that the individual soul reaches the goal through God's grace. Rao, for instance, says, "The individual soul aspires to reach the goal not by virtue of its 'works' like sacrifice, penance, etc., but by *śraddhā*, his confidence is not in his 'works' but in His love and mercy" (Rao, 1971, 174).

¹⁶⁴ Rāmānuja makes a similar point in explaining the concept of *Prapatti*, when he argues that even those without a deeper understanding of metaphysics or of the *Vedic* Scriptures can attain salvation. This point will become clear after we discuss Rāmānuja's *Gītā Bhāṣya*.

(BhG 4.16 and BhG 4.18) and only ends in chapter 18 with Arjuna’s 87th and final statement (BhG 18.17 and BhG 18.73).

In the next chapter we will have the opportunity to see how the classical commentaries of Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja understand the *Gītā*’s view of the process which leads to *mokṣa*. Here it is enough to point out that when one considers how Śaṅkara sees *pravṛtti*, *nivṛtti*, and its relation toward *mokṣa*, one is led to consider to whom the words of Kṛṣṇa are really addressed. According to Śaṅkara, they appear not to be meant for Arjuna.¹⁶⁵ Śaṅkara’s strategy in his long discussion of the *Gītā*’s chapter 18 is to build an argument to prove that, although Kṛṣṇa seems to be addressing Arjuna, he does not mean his words for him, as Arjuna was previously described by him as unwise and not fit for *Sāṃkhya*. Śaṅkara’s evaluation is, of course, determined by the *kevala jñāna* framework he insists the *Gītā* is within.

One cannot accept Śaṅkara’s views, however, because BhG 18.71 is more than sufficient to justify the appropriatedness of *niṣkāmakarmayoga*, as defined in the context of *śraddhā*.¹⁶⁶ For, BhG 18.71 speaks of *śraddhā* as that which ‘wakes up’ *ātman*, or the eternal inner *Avatāra* in us. As words coming from *ātman*, the *Gītā*’s words, once made

¹⁶⁵ See *Sri Śaṅkara’s Bhagavadgita Bhasya*, translation by C. V. Ramachandra Aiyar (Bombay: Bharatiya Vidya. Bhavan, 1988). When glossing BhG 18.17, for instance, Śaṅkara says, “*He*, the person whose understanding has been refined by the (study of the) *śāstra*, the teaching of the Preceptor, and reasoning, and *who is free from egotistic notion*, to whom the conception, of the form “I am the doer”, does not occur, who perceives that, “these five alone, the seat, etc., which are ascribed to the Self through *avidyā*, are the performers of all actions; and not I. (. . .) A man of the foregoing description is the wise man; he sees rightly; *though he kills these worlds*, all living creatures, *he kills not*, he does not perform the act of killing, *nor is he bound* either, by the fruit of *adharmā*, which is the (normal) consequence of that act” (562).

¹⁶⁶ Minor, however, perhaps following Śaṅkara, says: “Such an unexpected statement, which promises a reward by a means which appears to be incongruous with the teaching of the *Gītā*, is not unusual at the end of Indian texts” (1982, 496). I have no idea why he calls the verse ‘incongruous with the teaching of the *Gītā*’.

our own, help us to free ourselves from the *triguṇic* bonds. They renew one’s own *śraddhā* and help one to focus on the salvation path made of *saṅgyāsa* and *tyāga*, as defined in BhG 18.2.¹⁶⁷

Although *saṅgyāsa* and *tyāga* are both constituents of the final path, *saṅgyāsa* represents more of the path itself, while *tyāga* represents that state where path and goal are already becoming one and the same. For, reaching *tyāga* means becoming and acting like Kṛṣṇa himself. This process, which starts with *saṅgyāsa*, is really like a poison in the beginning, but as soon as one reaches *ātmabuddhiprasāda*, or ‘that which is born from the clear insight into *ātman*’ (BhG 18.37), it becomes as sweet as nectar.¹⁶⁸

In conclusion, *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* helps us to realize how the terms of the earlier tradition work to convey an explanation of the process by which an individual consciousness is linked to a social process and to history. Arjuna’s eventual renouncing of his individual *preyas* or longing for the sake of the social *śreyas* or good, allows him to show his *śraddhā* or engagement, established a complex new interrelation of the *Vedic* rituals and *Upaniṣadic* wisdom. Arjuna does recover his *śraddhā* through his personal and warm dialogue with Kṛṣṇa, but this fact does not contradict the fact that *śraddhā* is non-personal, as it has always been, since the *Vedas* and *Upaniṣads*. In other words,

¹⁶⁷ When glossing BhG 18.2, van Buitenen, for instance, says: “*saṅgyāsa*, “giving up entirely” (lit, “throwing it all down), and *tyāga*, “giving up with generosity what one could properly have kept.” He explains that even when Arjuna decides to fight, there is no doubt that he does not take pleasure in that. He does not take pleasure in the killing of Bhīṣma, for instance. He does it as an act of *saṅgyāsa*. Kṛṣṇa, however, remaining beyond good and evil, makes all of his life an act of *tyāga* – he takes neither pleasure nor pain in the events of the war, for he represents pure joy and generosity.

¹⁶⁸ Tilak, also, when glossing the first verses of *Gītā*’s chapter 18 on his *Śrīmad Bhavavadgītā Rahasya*, states that *saṅgyāsa* refers to the renunciation of *kāmya* (desire-prompted) action, and *tyāga* to the abandonment of hope for the fruit of the required *niṣkāma* (desireless) action. Aurobindo, on his *Essays on the Gītā* sees *saṅgyāsa* as outer renunciation, and *tyāga* as inner renunciation (1970, 468).

whereas the previous chapter has shown that *śraddhā* is not identical to *bhakti*, and that there is no instance of *śraddhā* where the notion of ‘putting the heart’ is not relevant, the present chapter has shown that in the *Gṛ̥ā* a righteous life presupposes *śraddhā*. This means that *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā* transcends the merely ‘religious’ sense of *bhakti*, for it transforms all human affairs in sacred experience.

In the next section we will explore how *śraddhā*, understood as ‘soul force or religious enthusiasm’, works as a strong candidate to the vacant seat of that fundamental religious category, which accounts for religious diversity and tolerance, as advanced by the *Gṛ̥ā*.

III.3. *Śraddhā* as ‘zealous soul force’ or ‘religious enthusiasm’

My translation¹⁶⁹ of the term *śraddhā* (from *śrat*, heart; and *dhā*, to place) as ‘enthusiasm’ is not intended to convey the usual sense of ‘enthusiasm’ as ‘fancied inspiration and vain confidence’. What I want to capture is the joy, which is triggered by the awareness of the divine in the heart, ‘*en-theos*’. I want to point to an experience of ‘being inhabited by God’, as the original meaning of the Greek root of ‘enthusiasm’

¹⁶⁹ This translation is closely related to the majority of translations listed by Hara for the *Vedic śraddhā*: S. Schayer (*das rituelle Vertrauen*, the ritual trust), H. Oldenberg (*die zum Geben treibende Seelendisposition*: the soul-disposition driving the performer, *das Vertrauen des Opfers zu den Brahmanen*: the trust of the sacrificer toward the *Brahmin*, *das Vertrauen des Laien, des Opferversanalters zu den Priestern*: the trust of the layman, the sacrifice-organizer, toward the priests), H. Köhler – as referred by L. Alsdorf (*Spendefreudigkeit*, enthusiastic engagement or contribution), A-M. Esnoul (*croyance en l'efficacité du sacrifice*, belief in the effectiveness of the sacrifice), and A. Walde & J. Pokorny (*die Zauberkraft worauf setzen, glauben*, to believe, or that which sets the spell-force). What is to be stressed, according to Hara, is that “*śraddhā* is rather a secular trust in the efficacy of the sacrifice” (Hara, 1963-4, 139).

suggests.¹⁷⁰ The understanding of *śraddhā* as ‘zeal, soul force, and religious enthusiasm’ instead of ‘faith’ also makes better sense of the continuity of meaning from the *Vedic* to the Epic period. In the *Vedas* ‘*śraddhā*’ is that internal fire or urge which gives conviction and courage in action, keeping one moving in spite of the difficulties. The fact that in the *Vedas* whatever is well done is necessarily done with *śraddhā* shows even more the importance of this concept, and links other important *Vedic* concepts, such as, *ṛta* (cosmic law), *vrata* (solemn vow) *yajñā* (act of worship or sacrifice) and *tapas* (the heat of religious austerity) in the role of dependent on it. Moreover, as we have seen, it is possible to infer that even the funeral rites were later named *śrāddha* (with the first ‘a’ a long vowel) because *śraddhā* appears as an essential component in the the funeral ceremony.

Furthermore, *śraddhā* presents the dimension of subjectivity in human experience. As that relates to the *guṇas* of the person involved, it does not refer to a class of action in itself. In the *Gītā*, worship, sacrifice, or warfare, are not good or bad in themselves, but only as they reflect the attitude of the performer. Kṛṣṇa’s message is not concerned with the type of action Arjuna should consider as much as with the motives and the quality of his understanding of that performance.

¹⁷⁰ This interpretation is also meant to remind us that the Latin term ‘*credere*’, which is usually rendered by the English term ‘*creed*’, can be etymologically traced back to the same Sanskrit root as the term ‘*śraddhā*’. The metaphorical sense of ‘putting one’s heart on’ is also present here, pointing to the common origin of these terms, both rooted in the primitive Indo-European term *kred-dhe*. W.C. Smith exemplifies this matter in a note with the help of the Christian saying, “Where your treasure is, there will your heart be also” (Mathew 6:21 and Luke 12:34). See W.C. Smith’s *Faith and Belief* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1979, n.35, 223).

Being the element that is common to people of different *mārgas*, *śraddhā* represents a universal measure of an action defined as evil (*duṣkṛti*), or good (*sukṛti*). For, whatever is done with *śraddhā* is acknowledged as being valuable in a religious sense. This plurality in the forms of worship (even when they might be *tamasic* and/or *rajasic*) allows for cultural diversity and ecumenical humility. On the other hand it shines a light on the subjective element of religious fervour and enthusiasm, which, once transformed into *sattvic śraddhā*, leads one towards the final goal.

The usage of the term *śraddhā* involves elements of religious, personal, non-personal, intellectual, and emotional, nature. The understanding of *śraddhā* as that zealous soul force responsible for putting true love in action explains the *Gṛ̥ā* as a manual on *ātma-dharma*. This reinterpretation of the *Gṛ̥ā* in the light of *śraddhā* satisfies the views presented by many different scholars in relation to the occurrences of the term in texts as old as the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*, where *śraddhā* is conceived of in relation to the fights the *devas* undertake against the *asuras*. In the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇas* the term *śraddhā* is said to mean ‘a desire to perform holy works’. It is also said to be related to the correct repetition of *mantras* in the oblations to Agni (*agnihotra*), where *śraddhā* appears in the formula as the strong will to perform the necessary action, without any second thought. *Śraddhā* is both a requirement and an outcome of the ritualitic endeavour. Ritual action feeds *śraddhā* inasmuch as it is fed by it – which means that even the essence of *Agnihotra*¹⁷¹ itself is nothing but an expression of *śraddhā*.

¹⁷¹ Since the *Ṛg Veda*, the term ‘*Agni*’ denotes many related things: a deity, the fire, the sun and the light coming from the sun, the heat that rises from the sacrificial fire, the light of the *mantric* knowledge which

The mere theoretical knowledge is tested and transformed into practical wisdom precisely during the *praxis* of the ritual activity. For, in all ritual activities the main emphasis is on the capacity to endure its performance. The idea is that a wise king becomes wise through his wise decisions, and never otherwise. The emphasis on the desire to perform the action, then, is what defines the attitude of *śraddhā*. For *śraddhā* is not a matter of mere awareness of the pertinence of the action, but an inclination and an aspiration to perform the righteous deed.

Furthermore, in the *Gṛ̥ā* also there is a kind of initiatory ceremony (*dīkṣā*) fashioned out of *śraddhā*, similar, for instance, to that of the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*

the *Rṣi* experiences, and so on. Agni, ‘the son of waters’, ‘the first-born’, ‘the first manifestation of Godhead’s one Spirit’, the *Hiraṇyagarbha* or the Golden Foetus from which all the gods and the mysterious creation emerges, is the upholder, through the gods and by means of *mantra*, of the world. For Agni pervades the whole creation, being re-born at each human sacrificial kindling, and moving in accordance to *dharma* in the cosmic task of upholding creation and bringing, through his brother *Indra*, the daily emergence of the sun and of the many forms of light, such as *mantra*. It is by Agni’s virtue that *Indra* protects (*kṣatra*) the cosmos. *Indra*’s vital power (*ojas*) expresses Agni’s ‘life-germ’ or *garbha*, which unfolds, supports, and nourishes all forms of life. It is through sacrificial action (*yajña*), then, that any member of the community can help in the task of supporting the cosmos. What precisely can this possible mean is the subject of the *Gṛ̥ā*’s dialogue. In the case of the *Gṛ̥ā*, Kṛṣṇa uses the metaphor of *yoga* being an igneous practice, which links the inward and the outward realities, to explain to Arjuna that it is by one’s deeds that one becomes able to know the eternal form of *ātman*. That is how Agni, together with the symbolism of casting sacrificial materials into the fire, as we have already mentioned, is present in the *Mahābhārata* and in the *Gṛ̥ā*. In chapter 4 of the *Gṛ̥ā*, for instance, Kṛṣṇa says he had earlier exposed this *yogic* symbolism of the fire to Vivasvat, the primal ancestor, who is known to be the father of Manu Vaisravata, the seventh of the fourteen Manus. He defines as a *paṇḍit* the one who has consumed his *karma* (deeds) in the fire of wisdom (BhG 4.19), and associates the entire rite of fire with the eternal *Brahman* (BhG 4.24-7). The worship is *Brahman*; the fire in which the action is performed is *Brahman*, and so, the worshipper himself expresses or becomes *Brahman*. Finally, Kṛṣṇa states, “As burning fire reduces firewood to ashes, O Arjuna!, so does the fire of wisdom reduce all *karma* (deeds) to ashes” (BhG 4.37). This statement, then, is related to what is discussed in chapter 8 of the *Gṛ̥ā*, where Kṛṣṇa starts to update some technical terms of the *yoga* system, and also mentions to Arjuna the importance of one’s last thoughts at death as well as what is the destiny of the deceased. Kṛṣṇa uses the fire metaphor (BhG 8.24) to explain the fate of those who are endowed with *Brahmavidyā* (theological knowledge). Furthermore, Kṛṣṇa stresses he is Viṣṇu among the *Ādityas* (the group of powers associated with the light of Agni known as the sons of *Āditi*) of the *R̥g Veda* (BhG 10.21), and as such he reveals himself to Arjuna (BhG 11.6 and 11.22), as that brilliance which resides in the sun (BhG 15.12). Through the practice of his igneous *Yoga* as a *yajña* is such a brilliance revealed (BhG 5.16 and 8.9).

XIII.1.2.1. For, in BhG 11.8, Kṛṣṇa gives Arjuna a divine eye, so that he can establish the connection with the supernatural world and set a solid basis for achieving the goals of his further self-sacrifice. In both texts, then, *śraddhā* represents this desire for the ultimate goal which leads one into the sacrificial performance. The difference, one could argue, is that in the *Gītā* it is made clear that there is no aspiration for the fruits of the sacrifice, whereas in the *Brāhmaṇas* there is this sense of an aspiration for *svarga* in the form of a longing of the heart, and a kind of confidence that the desired goals will be achieved.

Arjuna's fighting is to be done not because he is confident he can count on a helping god in order to win, but because he has become confident that he will be engaging in *dharmayuddha* as a holy sacrifice for the sake of *dharma*. Arjuna's final determination to fight results from his *śraddhā*. He decides to fight, not because he wants to win the favour of Kṛṣṇa, but because he had become confident that fighting was the right thing to do. After Arjuna decides to engage in that war, offering himself in self-sacrifice out of his own *śraddhā*, the *Gītā* is over.

This interpretation of the *Gītā* in the light of *śraddhā* helps to clarify the centrality of *śraddhā* in some of the *Upaniṣads*, where the mysteries of death and dying appear in relation to *agni* (fire), which represents the essence of beings. For *śraddhā* represents the essence that ascends when the body is cremated. This means that the way of the Fathers (*pitṛyāna*) and the way of gods (*devayāna*), as we have seen previously, are defined in relation to *śraddhā*. For *śraddhā* represents “the recognition that the Self (*ātman*) is the

basis and support of all gods and all things; and that the Self (*ātman*) is the ultimate subject” (Rao, 1971, 60). For the sake of eradicating any signs of uncertainty over this point, let us readdress the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad*, where *śraddhā* occurs only twice, but in a decisive fashion. The following passage appears in *Kaṭha Upaniṣad* I, 1, 1f. (and *Taittirīya Brāhmaṇa* III, 11, 8):

usan ha vai vājaśravasaḥ sarvavedasaṃ dadau. tasya ha naciketā nāma purtra āsa. taṃ ha kumaraṃ santaṃ dakṣiṇāsu nīyamānāsu śraddhāviveśa.

Indeed Vājaśravasa, with a heart-urge, gave up his whole belongings. He had a son by the name of Naciketas. *Śraddhā* (*Spendefreudigkeit*) was transmitted to him, still a boy, while the cows, the sacrifice-prize, were brought over.

If *śraddhā* in the *Brāhmaṇas* is a value related to a customary attitude of devotion or dedication, here it becomes well established as an ethical virtue, religiously rooted in the heart. Considering the *dakṣiṇā* in a deeper sense, Naciketas proposes to his father his own offering in self-sacrifice. So, Naciketas’ *śraddhā* is not to be understood as ‘faith’, as suggested by Röer, or ‘belief in salvation’, as suggested by Deussen, but as ‘*Spendefreudigkeit*’ – enthusiastic engagement (Kohler 1973, 43).

Naciketas describes himself as a *śrad-dadhāna* who offers himself as *dakṣiṇā*. His religious attitude, no doubt is completely ritualistic in nature – when *śraddhā* is manifested in his heart, the reference is to a system of rites. When one compares the experience of Naciketas with that of Arjuna, the parallelism is evident. First of all, what else is Kṛṣṇa asking from Arjuna, if not that he overcome his attachment to *preyas* through *śreyas*, a request that expresses precisely the core teaching of the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad*? When Kṛṣṇa, in BG 12.12, tells Arjuna that *karmaphalatyāga* (renouncing the

fruit of action)¹⁷² is superior even to *dhyāna*, he is teaching the very example of Naciketas, who also rejects the highest fruit of sacrifice.

Furthermore, considering the third of Naciketas's questions, where he expresses his curiosity about the phenomenon of death, one cannot but remember a passage in Das Gupta's study on the terms *bhakti* and *śraddhā* that helps us to reinterpret the *Gṛh̄ā* in the light of the continuity of meaning. The passage reads,

The *Kaṭha* is one of the major *Upaniṣads*, which is interesting from our point of view as being one of the sources which supply many images and ideas of the *Bhavavadgṛh̄ā*. Apart from the poetical form, the narrative prelude and dialogue, the well known image of the *Aśvattha* tree, the parable of the chariot, the description of the *Ātman* as neither the killer nor the killed, which are common to the two works, it has been even suggested that the famous figure of the *Ātman* as the chariot-driver in the parable referred to, is responsible for the *Gṛh̄ā*-episode itself of the *Mahābhārata*. It is not necessary for us to consider here the sources of the *Gṛh̄ā* in detail; but it may be noted that the *Kaṭha* inspired or supplied the metaphysical rather than devotional passages of the later theistic work. (1930, 503)

The crucial *Upaniṣadic* matter by the time of the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad* is the discussion over the issue of the proper performance of sacrifice, where the metaphor of death is discussed in relation to *śraddhā* as a complex notion rooted in *Brahmanic* ritual, but with *ātmic* elements together with its multiple secondary theistic variations. This consideration of things from the viewpoint of the heart, which implies the theory of the superiority of *śreyas* (good) over *preyas* (pleasant), is also decisive in Kṛṣṇa's arguments. For one may argue that the *Gṛh̄ā*'s definition of *saṃnyāsa* stresses the priority of *śreyas* (good) over

¹⁷² See also the BhG verses: 2.47; 4.14; 4.20; 5.12; 5.14; 6.1; 18.11; 18.27

preyas (pleasant). In BhG 6.1-2,¹⁷³ Kṛṣṇa stresses that the true relinquishing of the performance of any act is compatible solely with its perfect realization. Unless and until a person, having undertaken to do a given act, performs it in its entirety, he or she is bound, as it were, to the doing of that act; and freedom from this bondage is what in fact constitutes the real *saṁnyāsa*. The attitude of placing *śreyas* (good) over *preyas* (pleasant) is, then, what Kṛṣṇa prescribes to Arjuna, for he should act, not for his own *ahaṅkāric* benefit, but for the sake of the *ātmic* world at large.

As people do not always agree upon absolute roles of conduct, nor follow uniform disciplines; as there are distinct systems of faith and distinct modes of worship characterizing the different groups; as at one time what were the ordinances and beliefs of a people are utterly discarded by them at another time,¹⁷⁴ *Upaniṣadic* thinkers and *Ṛṣis*, they all seem to agree that one should prefer the *ātmic śreyas* over the *ahaṅkāric preyas*. In this sense, the meaning in which *śraddhā* is applied to the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad* is not significantly different from the meaning the term gets in the context of the *Gītā*. In both texts the term plays a crucial and central role in relation to the doctrine of *ātman*, without, however, disregarding the *Vedic* learning as a valuable preparatory stage in the path towards *Brahman*. In other words, the dialogue of Naciketas and Yama on the question

¹⁷³ BhG 6.1-2: He who does the work which he ought to do without seeking its fruit is the *saṁnyāsīn*, he is the *yogin*, not he who does not light the sacred fire, and performs no rites. What they call renunciation, that know to be disciplined activity, O *Pāṇḍava*, for no one becomes a *yogin* who has not renounced his selfish purpose.

¹⁷⁴ That is why *śraddhā* is not acceptance of a belief. It is, as Smith puts it “striving after self-realization by concentrating the powers of the mind on a given ideal” (1979, n. 70, 240). For, *śraddhā*’s indeterminateness “goes along with a position that what one should strive for is the marriage of faith and truth” (1979, 64). This link between *śraddhā* and *satyam* is thoroughly discussed in chapter 17 of the *Gītā*. Smith shows that “such a link is apparent already in the *Ṛg-Veda*: cf. 1:108:6 and 9:113:2, where the two terms are found in juxtaposition” (1979, n.73, 241).

of the immortality of the self; where the body is seen as the chariot of the self, is a reminder of the view that *ātman* cannot be known by the senses and reason, but only by direct realization – a thesis similar to that of Plato’s Allegory of the Cave. For, in the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad śraddhā* represents something subjective whose basis is the *puruṣa*– a view which agrees with Kṛṣṇa’s definition of *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā*.¹⁷⁵

When it comes specifically to the understanding of the connection between the concepts *ātman* / *śraddhā*, the *Atharvavedic Upaniṣads* can provide us with some help.¹⁷⁶ For, the *Muṇḍaka* (shaven) *Upaniṣad*,¹⁷⁷ the *Praśna Upaniṣad*, and the *Māṇḍūkya Upaniṣad* are all supposedly leading to ‘transgressions’ of the *Vedic* ritual prescriptions, but only in terms which are very similar to those pointed out by Aurobindo in his writings on the *Gṛ̥ā*. Then, if in the *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* the *saṃnyāsin* is shaved of ignorance, it

¹⁷⁵ The *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* also presents a teaching of this process of the gradual apprehension of the more abstract nature of the divine through representations of the *Vedic* lore. In *Muṇḍaka* 3.1.1-3, we find the *Ṛgvedic* imagery of the two birds – one enjoying the fruits of the actions and the other merely gazing on the scene – which in the realism of the *Gṛ̥ā* can be said to correspond to *ahaṃkāra* and *ātman*. Even when this passage has troubled Śaṅkara due to its dualistic nature, which is more akin to the *bhakti* schools, there is no doubt that the passage can be read in accordance to the theology of the *Gṛ̥ā*, where the Supreme is said to possess a higher and a lower nature, with one being subsumed in the other.

¹⁷⁶ This view on *śraddhā* is also present in other *Upaniṣads*. For instance, the *Taittirīya Upaniṣad* II.4.1 shows *śraddhā* as the head of *Brahman*, indicating that *Brahman* is to be attained through *śraddhā* – a conclusion that reminds us of that of the *Gṛ̥ā*. For knowledge alone means nothing. It must be put into practice (*yoga*) to become wisdom – this is the leading idea behind the concept of *śraddhā* and of the concept of *yoga* in this *Upaniṣad*. Similarly, as we have seen, *śraddhā* appears in the *Gṛ̥ā* as an outcome of the *yoga* (practice) based on the knowledge of the *ātman*. Furthermore, the *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* (through its saying ‘*tat tvam asi*,’ — You are That), and the *Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad*, (through its saying ‘*neti, neti*’ — not this, not this) already point toward the *ātmic* discipline as discussed by Kṛṣṇa. The name “*chandoga*,” means the priest specializing in the *Sāmaveda* (*Sāmam*=chant), while the term *bṛhadāraṇyaka* means ‘great forest-book’.

¹⁷⁷ There are over 200 *Upaniṣads*, although the traditional number is 108. Of these, the principal are said to be ten, perhaps because Śaṅkara wrote a commentary on them. They are *Iśa*, *Kena*, *Kaṭha*, *Praśna*, *Muṇḍaka*, *Māṇḍūkya*, *Taittirīya*, *Aitareya*, *Chāndogya*, and *Bṛhadāraṇyaka*. The most ancient, supposedly pre-Buddhistic, belonging to the eighth and seventh centuries B.C., are: *Iśa*, *Kena*, *Kaṭha*, *Taittirīya*, *Aitareya*, *Chāndogya*, *Bṛhadāraṇyaka*, and *Kauṣṭhiki*. According to Olivelle, it was only by the first half of the second millennium CE that the *Upaniṣads* were detached from the *Brāhmaṇas*, and gathered into collections; being 52 in number in the north and 108 in the south (Olivelle 1992, xxxiii).

is because he understands that, of the two kinds of knowledge, the lower (*aparā*) is represented by the *Vedas*, and the higher (*parā*) is the one achieved through direct *ātmic* experience. Already inquiring into the nature of *ātman*, the *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* I.1.3, for instance, asks, “What is that which, being known, everything else becomes known?” It is *nirguṇa* (qualityless, formless, but immanent in everything) *Brahman*, who also is envisaged as *saguṇa* (possessed of forms) *Brahman*, or *iśvara*, a personal god. The *Muṇḍaka* and *Praśna Upaniṣads*¹⁷⁸ corroborate my arguments about the concept of *śraddhā* by explaining¹⁷⁹ that rituals and *śraddhā* are two steps of the path of the *devayāna*. That is to say, the goal of *śraddhā* as conceived by *Muṇḍaka* is to link *yajñakarma* (sacrificial action) with *parāvidyā* (the highest knowledge). *Aparāvidyā* (lower knowledge), then, consists in helping us direct our attention to the eternal.

The *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* does not seem to condemn the ritualistic knowledge of the *Vedas*, but only to consider it, when compared to the knowledge of what is immortal (*akṣara*), which is *parāvidyā* (higher knowledge), to be *aparāvidyā* (lower knowledge). The same happens in the *Gītā*, where Kṛṣṇa also makes this same statement,¹⁸⁰ without actually condemning rituals. Moreover, in *Muṇḍaka* I.2.11, where *śraddhā* occurs, *Brahman-ātman* is considered a *puruṣa* in the same sense that the *puruṣasūkta* hymn in the *Ṛgveda* X.90 addresses the Supreme Being of the Universe as *puruṣa*. This somehow

¹⁷⁸ There are three occurrences of the term in the *Muṇḍaka* and five in the *Praśna*.

¹⁷⁹ Also, the realistic (*satyam*) account of the world described in the second chapter of this *Upaniṣad*, contains a cosmogony that portrays the *Vedas* as being born from the primeval *puruṣa* (being,).

¹⁸⁰ For instance, in BhG 2.45-6, Kṛṣṇa confines the reach of the *Vedas* to the scope of the three *guṇas* and asks Arjuna to free himself from the *guṇas*, adding that for the one who knows *Brahman*, the *Vedas* have so much value as a well when water is flooding on every side.

impersonal superior reading of the text does not imply that in an inferior level a relationship with a personal representative is not possible.¹⁸¹ In conclusion, the three passages of the *Muṇḍaka*¹⁸² considers *śraddhā* mostly in relation to a life dedicated to *tapas*, *dāna*, and *yajña*, where the concrete instance of Vedic sacrifice is closer to the essential notion of self-sacrifice than the notion of grace is. That is why even those performing self-sacrifice are said to be knowers of the *Vedas*.

The *Praśna Upaniṣad* discusses the path of those possessed of *śraddhā* and of those who, failing to acknowledge that *prāṇa* is *ātman*, are *aśraddadhānas*.¹⁸³ The context of the *Praśna Upaniṣad* is similar to that of the *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad*. In *Praśna* I.2, for instance, the teacher tests his disciples on *śraddhā*, in a way very similar to that in which the master (Yama) tests the disciple (Naciketas), before imparting the discipline of *ātman* to him in the *Kaṭha Upaniṣad*. In both texts, no doubt, as it happens also in the

¹⁸¹ It is this ‘impersonal’ person that is the object of Arjuna’s *viśvarūpa* (many forms) description, starting in BhG 11.15, and not the person of Kṛṣṇa, as theistic scholars defend. This impersonal ‘person’, which is the object of experience of Arjuna, like the one described in the *Muṇḍaka*, is considered to be higher than everything, with the *prakṛti* itself resting in It.

¹⁸² For instance, *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣad* I, 2, 11: *tapahśraddhe ye hy upavasanty arāṇye* – which, in the forest, turn to the discipline of the Self (the real asceticism is that of the mind) and faithful dedication. See also *Muṇḍaka* II.1.7, and III.2.10.

¹⁸³ The bearer of life is *prāṇa*. Humans live so long as they breathe. The term ‘*jīva*’ (from *jīv*, ‘to breathe’) refers to this biological nature, which breathes. Sometimes the *jīva* is called *puruṣa* in the sense of *puriśaya*, or a reminder that at the core of *jīva*’s structure is *ātman* ‘that which dwells in the citadel of the heart’. Other times the term ‘*puruṣa*’ is used for the *ātman*, which is higher than everything that belongs to the objective hierarchy of being. In BhG 11.3, BhG 11.18, and BhG 11.38, for instance, *puruṣa* represents the subjective light of consciousness that is described by Arjuna. Even the term ‘*ātman*’ itself also shows connection with *prāṇa*, as ‘*ātman*’ is derived from the verbal root *an* ‘to breathe’. In this sense, as the breath of life, *ātman* is what remains when everything that is not the self is eliminated. It is the unborn and immortal element, which is not to be confused with body in any of its external expressions, such as life, mind, or intellect. This is exemplified in a story that appear in the *Chāndogya* and *Bṛhadāraṇyakopaniṣad*, where different life forces dispute which one is of superior rank. Accordingly, speech, eyes, ears, thought and semen leave the *jīva*. When, however, the breath began to pull itself out, the life forces requested it to stay, as they cannot live without its presence. The *R̥gveda* speaks of this ‘unborn part’ as ‘*ajo bhāgaḥ*.’ (X.16.4). So, in a sense, this highest and unborn being is *ātman* in one’s self.

Gñā, śraddhā appears as a voluntary act, it does not result from an imposition or restraining of one's freedom. The conclusion is that the one who places anything above *ātman* can be said to be, in a relative sense, an *aśraddadhāna*.

In *Praśna Upaniṣad* I.10 those who practice *tapas, brahmacarya, śraddhā,* and *vidyātmān*¹⁸⁴ are said to gain the sun by the northern path. Prajāpati, the Lord of creatures, is represented by the sun, the life giver; creatures themselves are represented by the moon – the matter, which is enlightened by the sun. Those in the *pitṛyāna* (way of the Fathers), or southern path, evolve in the world of the moon (*saṃsāra*), or the material path, until they are ready to take the northern path, which is also called *devayāna*. Then, in *Praśna* II.3, *Prāṇa*, as a deity, presents the reasons for someone to become an *aśraddadhāna*. It is *prāṇa* that as agni, burns, as sun, shines, and as Indra, reigns. And that is why it may be said that behind the Indriyas (sensory functions) and the vital functions is where lays the underlying reality that supports all forms of life. Reality is *prāṇa*. And *prāṇa* is *ātman* – without *ātman* none can live, and the one who recognizes this is said to possess *śraddhā*.

Lastly, the *Māṇḍūkya Upaniṣad* deals with the sacred syllable OM (AUM). Its historical importance is said to be dependent on the famous gloss (*kārikā*) *Māṇḍūkya Kārikā* by Gauḍapāda (about 780 A.D.), traditionally identified as the teacher of Govinda, who was Śaṅkara's teacher. In our case, it is also of interest that, before Śaṅkara, the Vedānta view was indeed *jñānakarmasamuccaya*— the theory which affirms that one

¹⁸⁴ *Praśna Upaniṣad* I, 10: *tapasā brahmacaryeṇa śraddhayā vidyayātmānam anvīṣya* – which has sought the knowledge of *ātman* through the discipline of the Self, *brahmacarya*, and *śraddhā*.

cannot rely either on *jñāna* or *karma* alone for the attainment of *mokṣa*. Although the *Māṇḍūkya Upaniṣad* does not refer to the term *śraddhā*, it is worthwhile noticing that it refers to the Supreme Self as *Brahman*, representing, in the words of Radhakrishnan,¹⁸⁵ the first time in the history of thought that the relation between *Brahman*, the Absolute, and *Īśvara*, its personal representative, is clearly elaborated (Radhakrishnan 1953, 697). *Brahman*, which is beyond all word and thought, becomes accessible in the form of *Īśvara*, who ultimately also rests in *Brahman*. OM (*AUM*) thus represents both *Brahman* as well as its aspect as *Īśvara*, which, as Kṛṣṇa explains, dwells in everyone as *ātman*. For, as he has also said, among all the Vedas he is the syllable *Aum*.

Therefore, once we understand that our metaphorical heart is the *ātman*, is the syllable *Aum*, is Kṛṣṇa, and is also all that we consider sacred and that pushes us towards what is better, we will also have understood and answered Smith's puzzle about the object of *śraddhā*, or 'on what' to put our heart. For, as it says in BhG 17.3, 'as a man's *śraddhā* is, so is he'. And *sattvic śraddhā* is *sat*, that which is real, good, and true, and that leads one toward the transcendent. Placing one's mind at the heart is, then at the same time, the process and the definition of that which leads toward salvation – *sattvic śraddhā*.

It is by placing one's mind at the heart that one develops that soul-force, as opposed to physical force, that Gandhi named *satyāgraha*, and which represents nothing but an expression of *śraddhā* itself. For it is through this soul-force that one can truly

¹⁸⁵ S. Radhakrishnan, *The Principal Upaniṣads* (George Allen & Unwin, 1953; Atlantic Highlands. Reprint, 2nd ed., Humanities Press International, 1993).

see, as did Arjuna in the *Gītā*,¹⁸⁶ how one should engage in what is worthwhile pursuing. Whenever one knows what is worth doing and has developed the necessary strength to make the decision of doing, *śraddhā* will already be there. *Śraddhā* starts with simply intellectual understanding of the role played by the pair *ātman* / *ahaṅkāra* (as shown in Kṛṣṇa’s exposition), but next it requires commitment, courage and will to make the decision to reverse this role: the mind should leave the realm of *ahaṅkāra* and inhabit the heart, which is *ātman*’s realm. It is when one has one’s mind at the heart that the necessary action can be naturally performed in the spirit of *niṣkāmakarmayoga*, in a spirit full of *śraddhā*.

For, ultimately *śraddhā* is a “material” phenomenon manifested as energy¹⁸⁷ in our body through the modulations (*guṇas*) of *prakṛti*. It shapes our activity and presents the *Gītā* as a treatise on an ethics of motives. An act involves: (1) the desire to know the best course of action to take at every single moment, (2) the will to take this path one sees as right, (3) and the vigilant performance, where there is no possibility for the mind to leave its focus from the *ātman*, or to allow it to go astray under the influence of

¹⁸⁶ Arjuna’s *śraddhā*, then, represents that which is expressed by the Greek terms *agape*, in the sense used by Maxmüller in his classification of the ceremonies of ancestor worship, as we have seen when studying the work of Shastri. That is to say, *śraddhā* as *agape* represents the unconditional and volitional self-sacrificing and thoughtful love of that which is below oneself. It also represents *philia*, or the love between equals, and *eros*, or the love of the divine, which is above oneself. Thus it expresses something similar to the new Commandment Jesus gives at the Last Supper, when he asks that all relations should be based on love (which can only happens when ‘one places one’s heart on’). This trans-cultural identity is well represented by Gandhi through his coining of, and living by, what the term *satyāgraha* meant.

¹⁸⁷ Commenting on the *Yogasūtra* of Patañjali (trans. by M. N. Dvivedi. Delhi: Sri Satguru Publications. Revised Ed., 1980), I.20, where the term *śraddhā* occurs, Vyāsa says (15), “*Samādhi* is preceded by *śraddhā*.” Further, he adds, “*Śraddhā* is the firm and agreeable conviction of the mind regarding the efficacy of *yoga*.” Then, he concludes, “Energy (*vīrya*, power, valour, strength, dignity, heroic deed; from *vī*= to overpower, to be valiant) is born in him who pursues knowledge with *śraddhā*.”

ahaṅkāra. Those are the inherent characteristics an action in the form of *śraddhā* takes in the *Gītā* and *Upaniṣads* as well.

The ‘particularly religious element’ named *śraddhā* is, at least, what brings Kṛṣṇa’s teachings on *ātma-dharma* together. An example of how *śraddhā* is related to *ātman* in the *Gītā* can be taken even from the Laws of Manu. In its section II.12, it is said that there are four ways of determining right and wrong: *Veda* (*Śruti* (that which has been heard), or The Orally Communicated Revelation (from *vid*= to experience, to feel, to know)), *Smṛiti* (memory, remembrance, tradition; from *smṛ*= to remember or think of; to recite), *ācāra* (custom, good conduct; from *ā-car* = to approach, to undertake, to apply: *ā* = prefix near, towards; *car* = verb to move to behave), and the cultivation of our inner conscience (*ātmanaḥ priyam*). While the first three (which express *abhyāsa* yoga, or practice of *karma* yoga) make for social order, social development is achieved by the last (which expresses *saṁnyā* yoga, or that mastering of *karma* yoga that leads to *brahmasānīpya*).

The meaning of this fourth way (*ātmanaḥ priyam*) is precisely what Kṛṣṇa explains to Arjuna in the *Gītā*. Depending on the circumstances, any action, any ritual, can be *sattvic*, even the killing of brothers and grandfathers. That is to say, the *Gītā* does not condemn all performers of *Brahmanic* ritual as being *tamasic* in nature, nor does it declare them to be the most elevated. The *Gītā* is only revealing how all actions are ritual actions, which, when properly grounded in *ātman*, transcend the *triguṇas*.¹⁸⁸ Arjuna’s

¹⁸⁸ Evidently, this is not the view of those who see the *Gītā* as a theistic text. Rao, for instance, states in the concluding part of his chapter on the types of *śraddhā*: “To sum up, the *Gītā*’s conception of *parā śraddhā*

dejection in the *Gītā* is not because of his concern with killing, which he had done before, as much as it is because of his passionate, *rajasic*, filial love, which is interfering with his duties as a prince. It is because of this nepotistic attitude of protecting those of his own clan, even when occupying an official position in the government, that makes Arjuna decide he cannot kill his relatives. This same mistake had already happened in his family, in the person of Bhīṣma, who had renounced his duties to please his indulgent father and descendents. The whole *Mahābhārata*, as we will see in chapter 5, can be seen as the consequence of Bhīṣma's decision, based on his misunderstanding that filial love represented *dharma*.

In the *Gītā*, then, the opportunity is presented for Arjuna to reverse this process of misinterpreting *dharma*, started by accident and unintentionally by the great Bhīṣma. As happened with Bhīṣma, the established *śāstras* cannot help Arjuna decide about the best course of action. Arjuna's mission seems to be in contradiction with the prescriptions of the *śāstra*. Once he notices the contradiction, he loses his *śraddhā*. Kṛṣṇa, then, teaches him about the science of *ātman*, which leads one to overcome *ahaṅkāric* attachment, and Arjuna experiences a little of what *ātman* really is. Without *ātman* none can live, and once one understands this, one becomes endowed with the highest and universal *śraddhā*.¹⁸⁹ Therefore, when it comes to the significance of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*, there is

is orthodox; it does not break away from established *śāstras*. It only professes to discover and to present hidden dimensions of the age-old *śāstras*. It advocates adherence to the *śāstra* not mechanically and formally, but in spirit and truth, that is, with a sense of duty, without attachment to the fruit of action and with a dedication to the service of Kṛṣṇa, the supreme Lord" (166).

¹⁸⁹ We have already illustrated how the *Praśna Upaniṣad*, for instance, discusses the path of those who cultivate *śraddhā*, and of those who are *aśraddadhānas*. The awareness that *prāṇa* is *ātman* is what expresses the amount of one's *śraddhā*.

no embodying of a strong protest against, or support to, *Vedic* ritualism. The *Gṝā* only remind us that when the Vedas, or any dogmatic text bewilders our judgement (BhG 2.53), we should stand firm in *ātman*. This means that the way to the Supreme is through the ritualistic performance of one’s duties as self-surrender.¹⁹⁰ *Śraddhā* in the *Gṝā* is to be understood in the context of social activism, where one renounces selfish-interest (*ahaṃkāra*-based) for the sake of social-interest (*ātman*-based), which represents the real ‘Self-interest’ of the righteous ones (*jīvātmas*). As suggested in the Laws of Manu II.12, and restated by Kṛṣṇa, our heart (*ātman*) should decide which duties are obligatory, and we should act according to them.

At the core of the *Gṝā*’s dialogue is Kṛṣṇa’s framing of *śraddhā* as a natural constituent of what one freely thinks, or of what one truly is. It is the *triguṇic* layers of *śraddhā*, differently distributed in everyone, that allows for the establishment of different minor and provisory truths: in a lower sense, yes, even the knowledge imparted to Arjuna can be seen as being related to an act of grace. And, yes, at this elementary theological level, one may even argue that it is not completely out of place to understand *śraddhā* as faith, and that Kṛṣṇa brings about Arjuna’s salvation.

Rao, as we have seen, does it. He says: “The loving devotion (*bhakti*) of Kṛṣṇa is the easiest (*susukham*) and best form (*uttamam*) of worship.” Furthermore, Rao is right to point out that chapter 2 of the *Gṝā* truly brings “a note of protest against the *Vedic* view of *śraddhā*” (Rao, 1971, 145). For, chapter 2 does not endorse ritual activity aimed at personal gain, as the *Vedas* do. Moreover, chapter 3 clearly presents a theory on action

¹⁹⁰ That is to say, *śraddhā* cannot be separated from any path to salvation. Thus its centrality in the *Gṝā*.

that at first sight seems to represent, in Rao’s words, “an aversion to severe austerities, renunciation of the world and the intellectualism of the *Upaniṣads*.”

Rao¹⁹¹ is right when he points out that the important thing in the *Gītā* is “the attitude of the devotee – *śraddhā*.” Yet, as we have also seen, the *Gītā* allows for the higher and *sattvic* understanding that, beyond the “emotional attitude of love and trust to the incarnate Lord” (146) – which has been interpreted as *bhakti* –, one’s attitude of *śraddhā* comes straight from *ātman*. For, according to Kṛṣṇa, the main focus of the one who has *sattvic śraddhā* is the impersonal reality – *ātman*. This means that the core message of the *Gītā*, which is implied in the initial admonition of Kṛṣṇa to Arjuna, is that by loving devotion alone, without *śraddhā*, or confidence to act according to what is the best, Arjuna would not go anywhere – not even with the help of Kṛṣṇa’s ‘grace’.

As I have tried to demonstrate, when it comes to understanding the role of *śraddhā* in Arjuna’s final decision to fight, there is no need to search outside the context

¹⁹¹ At a very basic and preliminary understanding of the message of the *Gītā*, perhaps one could say that *śraddhā* does not depend “on man’s efforts alone; for the knowledge and the practice of *yoga* might themselves be due to the grace of God” (Rao, 1971, n. 29, 136). The *Gītā*’s deepest secrets, however, are only open to those who understand that in the *Gītā* the *Īśvaraprasāda* (grace of God) is defined in BhG 18.61-2, where Kṛṣṇa states that the *Īśvara* abides in the heart of all beings, and that from *Īśvara*’s grace (*prasāda*), one attains supreme peace and eternity. Kṛṣṇa’s detailed explanation of how *Īśvaraprasāda* leads to the supreme is attained, is given, as we have seen, in the final verses of chapter 2. In BhG 2.64, for instance, Kṛṣṇa says *prasāda* is attained by the one who, succeeding in eliminating desire (*rāga*, passion) and hatred (*dveṣa*), even when operating through the senses (*indriyas*), is governed by *ātman* alone. The remainder of the *Gītā*, up to BhG 18.58, unfolds and discusses this *ātma-dharma*. In BhG 18.56-8, Kṛṣṇa summarizes his teaching saying that what leads to *Īśvaraprasāda* is the performance of all kinds of works or duties (*sarvakarman*) with an *ātmic* disposition, impeding *ahaṅkāra* (egotism) to be in control. Therefore, grace, as understood in a higher sense in the *Gītā*, is *Īśvaraprasāda*, and constitutes the *Īśvara*’s revealing of itself as *ātman*. Furthermore, because in the *Gītā* *Īśvara*’s will is to be accomplished through our human actions, *Īśvaraprasāda* cannot be fully taken in the Christian sense of grace. For, when it comes to the *Gītā*, only at the lower level of understanding one would expect the *Īśvarātman* to be performing miracles in the form of ‘non-deserved or non-earned’ grace. According to the *Gītā* we all already are the repositories of the Supreme Grace. We all have already been granted salvation, and achieving it is just a matter of time. There is no eternal damnation for the soul in the *Gītā*.

of the *Mahābhārata* itself. There is no need to bring to the fore the medieval discussion of the theological status of Kṛṣṇa, for instance. For, it is not a matter of his arguments being authoritative that really counts here. It is a matter of how they make sense in the theological context of the *Gītā* and also of the *Mahābhārata*.

As Köhler, Hacker, and Hara have also stressed, *śraddhā* presents an intellectual attitude of trust, and contains certain elements of *bhakti*, without, however, being mixed up with it. This point is further discussed by Krishna Sharma, who helps us to see the importance of the sacrificial context – a fact that was ignored by those who belong to the theistic trend of interpretation of the *Gītā*. According to her, “the religious fervour inspired by the medieval bhaktas had resulted in the galvanisation of people into groups with a common ideology and a common code of conduct” (1987, 3). As she explains, the term *bhakti* denotes loving devotion or attachment in general. However, its meaning can get particularized when it indicates a particular theology and religious mode: “For example, Viṣṇu-bhakti (as well as its variations, i.e., Kṛṣṇa-bhakti, Rāma-bhakti) and Śiva-bhakti can legitimately be explained in terms of Vaishṇava and Śaiva theologies” (5-6). However, “By itself, it does not suggest any doctrinaire or ideational position, nor any particularised concept of God, personal or impersonal” (6). For, as she also acknowledges, “Bhakti was never treated as a dharma in the Hindu religious texts; nor was it ever discussed as a siddhānta [doctrine] or a mata [doctrine]” (42). Her findings, therefore, helps us to see that in BhG 7.16-21 Kṛṣṇa states that only in a provisory sense is it okay for ordinary men to worship any kind of personal representation of the divine that they believe constitute this divine itself. In other words, Kṛṣṇa seems to authorize

his own worship (as he does with any other kind of worship) also in a preliminary and preparatory way. For, the form of worship a man adopts depends on his heart. As Kṛṣṇa also states in the remaining verses of this chapter, and elsewhere, it is *ātman*, the Inner Ruler in every person, which constitutes the highest object of worship, and not any particular deity (not even the person of Kṛṣṇa).

The context of the *Mahābhārata*, as we will have the opportunity to see in more detail in chapter 5, helps us to see that *ātman*, or the real *Īśvara*, is non-personal and present in everyone, though personally expressed in the person of Kṛṣṇa. For, Arjuna's dilemma in the *Gītā* represents an expansion of the dilemma Bhīṣma had faced in the beginning of the *Mahābhārata*. As a prince, Arjuna is not supposed to base his decisions upon nepotistic notions of filial love, as Bhīṣma had done in the beginning of the *Mahābhārata*, with catastrophic consequences. So the real question is what comes first: family or social duty? By giving up the throne in favour of his father and his descendents, Bhīṣma chooses family. His mistake was that he ignored the fact that all moral and social actions must result from a love of God, and must be done for the sake of general welfare, not only of one's own family welfare.

Arjuna was ready to follow the same path as Bhīṣma, believing that to give up worldly affairs for the sake of benefiting his cousins would constitute the right thing to do. His honest doubt and will to know what would constitute the best thing to do, however, triggers Kṛṣṇa's teachings on how to develop *sattvic śraddhā* to march toward *ātmic* duty and *ātman*. Kṛṣṇa's teaching on *śraddhā* diverges from that of Bhīṣma, based

on notions of altruism as devotion and filial love. During the dialogue of the *Gītā*, then, Arjuna’s true disposition to renounce even filial love is thoroughly put to a test. Arjuna’s victory over Bhīṣma represents his capacity to renounce even filial love, and places him at the level of those operating with the non-personal *sattvic śraddhā*.¹⁹²

As such, the lack of *śraddhā* is what desecrates religious life and life in general. The opposite of *śraddhā*, then, is not disbelief, but the shunning, for the sake of *ahaṅkāra* (one’s sense of self-interest), of what tries to arise from *ātman* (one’s metaphorical heart). Thus *śraddhā* is contrasted with complaining and despondency when in the line of performing the ritual deeds. *Śraddhā* arises from understanding one’s mission and putting one’s heart in the practice of disinterestedness and detachment from the fruits of such a mission. It arises from *niṣkāmakarmayoga*. For, *śraddhā*, as opposed to faith, is not a product that you receive from the outside world; it is rather an innate capacity that is nurtured by the way in which we follow our mission in this world. *Śraddhā*, therefore, does not express the ‘faith of Hindus’, so much as it expresses the way in which every ‘faith’ of the world is to be practiced – wholeheartedly, with religious fervour and enthusiasm, no matter if through theistic expressions of devotion or not.

In conclusion, a definition of *śraddhā* that matches Arjuna’s experience in the *Gītā* would be something like ‘awakeness to transcendence’, as pointed by Smith (1979, n. 79, 244-5). Furthermore, Smith’s unanswered question ‘place your heart on what?’ can be considered answered, as soon as one understands that *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* means

¹⁹² This does not imply, however, that *śraddhā* does not mean what Rao has pointed out in his definition, which involves “(i) a longing of the heart of yearning for some end, and (ii) confidence or trust in some ‘means’ which can lead to the desired end” (176).

soul force, enthusiasm, or ‘the placing of the heart on . . . *the heart*’!¹⁹³ For, as we have already seen, the *Gñā* explains how any given act should be properly performed, which can be summarized as follows. First it is essential to have the knowledge (*jñāna*) as to the ways and means of what is to be done. But knowledge alone (*kevala jñāna*) is not enough. One must present the inclination, or soul force (*śraddhā*), to perform any given righteous deed. Finally, comes the actual doing of what is to be done. In the case of Arjuna, he first solves his doubts and acquires new knowledge, then he develops his will-power, and finally decides to act – in this order. Then, once engaged in the righteous deed, what Kṛṣṇa guarantees is that, such an *ātmic* discipline will update his soul force and lead him to learn even more about the divine, in a convergent process leading to *Brahmanirvāṇa*.

In other words, *ātma-dharma* may be said to trigger *karma-yoga*, and vice-versa, through a process leading to final salvation. But in case one of the steps discussed above is not properly performed, one cannot expect to succeed. For, if one knows how to perform a given deed, but is not well motivated, the work may end up being poorly performed. On the other hand, one may intensely desire to perform his work, but if he or she does not develop the proper knowledge, the final result will also be inadequate. The conclusion is that for the mastery over action, which the *Gñā* defines as *yoga*, one must synchronize (*yoga*) *buddhi* (which represents the realm of *jñāna*), *manas* (which

¹⁹³ This is also in accordance with the *Upaniṣadic* tradition, of which the *Gñā* may be said to be a representative. Although ‘to put the heart on *the heart*’ may sound tautological, it helps to understand the essential meaning of *śraddhā*. For, when one wholeheartedly searches for what is on one’s heart, one is but giving precedence to the *ātmic* claim, which is represented by the heart itself.

represents the realm of *śraddhā*, and *indriyas* (which is the realm of the physical senses). *Karma yoga*, therefore implies the understanding that every single act involves co-ordination of knowledge and will, into activity.

When a given act is thus completed in its entirety, one may be said to have approached the final relinquishment of the bonds of *karma*. Such a relinquishment, therefore, implies the complete performance of any duty – and this corresponds to what the *Gṛh̄* defines as *saṃnyāsa*. That is to say, *saṃnyāsa* expresses *karma yoga* or the perfect and altruistic fulfillment of any necessary activity. For, *karma yoga*, which is the performance of any *karma* without desire for its fruits, is what liberates one from the bonds of *karma*. The attitude of service and self-sacrifice for the sake of the world at large, therefore, is what is determinant in *saṃnyāsa*. Such a desireless state, which results from *saṃnyāsa*, is also called *tyāga*. It signifies the understanding that nothing is worth doing which is not for the world. For, when in *tyāga*, one is already experiencing the divinity of *ātman* in one's own heart and in the heart of all.

In order to prepare the basis in which chapter 5 will propose a new understanding of the *Gṛh̄* under the light of *śraddhā*, the next chapter will discuss the view of several classical commentators, and offer a brief summary of the history of interpretation on the *Gṛh̄*.

IV. A BRIEF HISTORY OF INTERPRETATION ON THE GĪTĀ

IV.1. Śaṅkara's *kevalajñāna* and Rāmānuja's *bhaktikarmasamuccaya*

There have been many commentaries (*bhāṣyas*) and notes (*tīkas*) written on the *Gṝā*. It is a well-established fact that the two main commentaries, that of Śaṅkara (A. D. 788-820), which is the earliest that has survived, and that of Rāmānuja (A. D. 1056 – 1137), have limited the importance of one's deeds in the *Gṝā* as a means to *mokṣa*. They both have been accused of imposing their pre-conceived *Vedāntic* notions on the text of the *Gṝā*. They both approach the text as a *Smṛiti* treatise that expounds the *Śruti* (The *Upaniṣads*), without any further improvement. According to them the *Gṝā* corresponds to something that could be logically deduced, or inferred, from the *Śruti*, representing, therefore, a kind of sub-set of those same truths. While Śaṅkara has tried to subsume the path (*mārga*) of *karma* into that of *jñāna*, Rāmānuja has tried to understand *karma-mārga* as a means to *bhakti-mārga*. Furthermore, Rāmānuja denies the absolute identification of the creator with the creatures, suggesting that the different 'selves' exist in God, as the drops of water in the ocean. For him, the *Gṝā* teaches the path of devotion.¹⁹⁴ His qualified non-dualism (*viśiṣṭādvaita*) system challenges Śaṅkara's view, and argues for the reality of the world, with a personal God ruling it, as an aspect of the Impersonal and Transcendent *Brahman*.

¹⁹⁴ Other commentators, in general, tend to agree that devotion is what is mainly emphasized in the *Gṝā*. This is the position that the commentary of Madhva (1238 – 1317 CE), based on his dualistic (*dvaita*) philosophy, where God and the souls are seen as eternally different, will try to demonstrate. The commentaries of Nimbārka (13th century) and Vallabha (1486 – 1533 CE) also center in the importance of devotion in the *Gṝā*.

In one way or another, Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja are reacting to the ancient *jñānakarmasamuccaya* (knowledge and action together) view,¹⁹⁵ which stresses the importance of both action and knowledge in the path towards liberation. Śaṅkara needs a reading of the *Gṛ̥ā* that can fit his non-dualist (*advaita*) understanding of reality, and as such, he defends his *kevalādvaita* (non-dualism alone) position against the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* view, which was supposedly held by a former commentator. Śaṅkara's position can be understood as a result of his theological understanding of reality, where the world, and the work done in it, is ultimately unreal, or *māyā*.¹⁹⁶ According to him, the only reality is *Brahman*, which means that the reality of this world is illusory (*māyā*), with ignorance (*avidyā*) being the cause of such an illusion. The *Gṛ̥ā*,

¹⁹⁵ Bhāskara (c. 1000 CE), who has written a commentary on the first chapters of the *Gṛ̥ā*, also accepts the *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*, and criticises the *māyā vāda* as a kind of Buddhism in disguise. He is of the opinion that both *bheda* and *abheda* (difference and non-difference) are real. For, it is a fact that difference and non-difference coexist, as in set theory: objects of the same set share general properties (say it, be a number) whereas objects of different sub-sets share specific properties (say it, be a rational number or be a transcendent number). In other words there is no contradiction in accepting a certain kind of difference and non-difference at the same time, as we do with the terms 'unity' and 'multiplicity', as both describe what is real and can be shown to coexist. A completely different matter would be to state, for instance, 'avidyā is both existent and non-existent'. Here the logical contradiction is clear, once 'existence' cannot be said to coexist with 'non-existence'. Bhāskara also accepts the view presented in the *Gṛ̥ā* that *Brahman* has two forms and that both of them are real: the *kāraṇa-rūpa* (the cause, i.e., gold) and the *kārya-rūpa* (the effect, i.e., the golden objects), which represents more than simple illusory modifications (*vikāra*).

¹⁹⁶ The concept of *Māyā*, which is very vital in Śaṅkara, is only used in the *Brahmasūtras* of Bādarāyaṇa in III.2.3, where it merely represents the creation of the dream-state. It is not used there in the sense of the empirical world being illusory. Even there, the world is not an apparent modification (*vivarta*), but an actual transformation (*pariṇāma*) of *Brahman*. Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja accept these *Sūtras*, but in different ways. Śaṅkara understands them as expressing the idea that *Brahman* alone is real and the world is an appearance (*Māyā*) of *Brahman*. The world is not an actual transformation (*pariṇāma*) of *Brahman*. The world is an apparent transformation (*vivarta*) of *Brahman*. It is an illusion similar to the one by which a rope is taken to be a snake. Śaṅkara even commences his *Bhāṣya* with a praise of that which he sees as beyond the Unmanifest – the *Aṅḍam* (the Cosmic-Egg, *Brahmāṅḍam*), which he calls Nārāyaṇa, and which represents his *Iṣṭa-Devatā* (one's chosen Deity). Rāmānuja, on the other side, refutes the doctrine of the unreality of the world. According to Rāmānuja, the world and *Brahman* are one as the body and the *jīva* are one. The individual being and *Brahman* are related, but are not identical. Rāmānuja's monism, then, is said to be qualified, *Viśiṣṭādvaita*. If the world is real, then, it does not make any sense to give up the deeds as a way to *mokṣa*.

then, must be seen as setting forth the achievement of knowledge as the necessary condition for salvation. For, as he argues when discussing BhG 18.48, ignorance (*avidyā*) is to be held responsible for the illusion of the manifest world together with activity.

Śaṅkara's *Bhāṣya* does not pay much attention to the verses where the term *bhakti* and its cognates occur, nor to the *Gītā*'s chapters which are involved with ritual action and Arjuna's transformation. I refer specifically to chapters one, ten, eleven, and seventeen. In the first chapter Arjuna is seen to be *aśraddadhāna*; in the tenth, as someone who has acquired *brahmavidyā*; in the eleventh, as someone who is able to prove his acquired knowledge, and finally in the seventeenth, as someone who is endowed with *śraddhā* and understands that, without ritual action in the form of good will, not even knowledge would lead him to the ultimate salvation. Śaṅkara barely comments on these passages. For, as one can infer from Śaṅkara's statements in his introductory gloss, prior to the first verse he exegetes (BhG 2.11), he wants Self-Knowledge preceded by the complete renunciation of all work.

Śaṅkara thinks that it is the duty of every *kṣatriya* to engage in *dharma yuddha*, as established in passages such as BhG 2.33, 2.47, 4.15, and so on. And as for statements such as, 'through action alone have Janaka and others aimed at perfection' (BhG 3.20), 'perform action' (BhG 4.15), Śaṅkara would understand that after going through the stage of renunciation of works these persons had reached the stage where they had the right to engage in activity for the guidance of the world.

Śaṅkara¹⁹⁷ wants the *Gṝā* teaching to state that salvation is attained by knowledge of truth alone, and not in conjunction with works. When glossing BhG 4.39-42, for instance, Śaṅkara limits himself to the word “*ātmanah,*” meaning that the Self is the subject-matter of doubt. And for this reason one should cut the doubt about the Self with the sword of knowledge (1988, 179). It will be only when glossing BhG 17.3 that Śaṅkara will explain that the *śraddhā* of each living being is in accordance with his *antaḥkaraṇa* (inner-organ) with its specific tendencies (*saṃskāra*) (1988, 527). Then, in a short comment upon BhG 17.17, he adds that *śraddhā* is *āstikyabuddhi*.

Śaṅkara’s silence becomes significant if we remember the importance he assigns to the doctrine of knowledge as the sole means to salvation. His silence is clearly intentional, and is meant to facilitate his refutation of *karma niṣṭhā*, and his later attempt to identify *bhakti* with *jñāna niṣṭhā*. Verses that propound *bhakti* as a means to salvation Śaṅkara deals with by simply equating the meaning of *bhakti* and *jñāna*. On the other hand, those verses that argue that *karma* not be abandoned, he argues that the reference there is not to a *saṃnyāsin*, but to ignorant persons (*avidvas*) like Arjuna.

For his own rhetorical need, Śaṅkara can go as far as to understand *Brahman* as *saṃnyāsa*, as he does when discussing BhG 5.6. He clearly wants a *Gṝā* that merely explains some truths of the *Veda*, without any new revelation or further clarification. Consequently, he starts his *Bhāṣya* after BhG 2.10, where the teaching of Kṛṣṇa also starts. In order to preserve his view Śaṅkara is forced to introduce at least two

¹⁹⁷ I am following mostly P. V. Panoli’s translation, *Gṝā in Sankara’s Own Words*, 3 vols. (Calicut: S. Paramasivan, 1975), but I also make some use of C. V. Ramachandra Aiyar’s translation, *Śri Śaṅkara’s Gṝā Bhāṣya* (Bombay: Bharatiya Vidya. Bhavan, 1988).

misconceptions. His first misconception is his *Vedāntic* understanding of the meaning of *saṁnyāsa*, as giving up all action. This is in clear contradiction with BhG 6.1, where *saṁnyāsa* means giving up the fruits of actions (*karmaphala*), but not actions themselves. The second misinterpretation is his belief in the superiority of (the *Vedāntic* notion of) *saṁnyāsa* over *karma yoga*, a belief that contradicts BhG 5.2,¹⁹⁸ where the superiority of *karma yoga* over the *Vedāntic* notion of *saṁnyāsa* is clearly stated.

Śaṅkara maintains that the *Vedic* ritualistic path and the *Upaniṣadic* path of knowledge are mutually exclusive.¹⁹⁹ For, while the first, known as *pravṛtilakṣaṇadharmā*, is a path characterized by action, and includes observances of class duties and rites such as *nitya* (daily and necessary rite), *naimittika* (occasional rite), and *kāmya* (optional observance, performed with desire for some personal advantage), the second, known as *nivṛtilakṣaṇadharmā*, is the path characterized by ceasing from acting. As scriptural evidence, he mentions the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* (*Bṛhadāraṇyaka Upaniṣad* 4.4.22) which says, “Desiring this world (the Self) alone, the *Brāhmaṇas* having non-

¹⁹⁸ It is Śaṅkara’s contention that this verse is meant only for those who have not attained *jñāna*.

¹⁹⁹ According to Śaṅkara, this two-fold Religion enjoined by the Veda characterized by *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti*, is verily the cause of the sustenance of the universe. For, the first to be created were Marīci and other Prajāpatis (they are ten in number in Manu *Smṛiti* I.34). They hold on to the Religious Path characterised by *pravṛtti* (literally, ‘tendency to go outward’ i.e., activity, action). However, later on others such as Sanaka and Sanandana were also created and made to adopt the Religious Path of *nivṛtti* (literally, ‘tendency to come back’, i.e., abstain from activity, renunciation), characterized by knowledge and non-attachment. That is to say, the object of the *Gṛh̄yā śāstra* (Scripture of *Gṛh̄yā*), described in BhG 18.66, is final beatitude, which is characterised by the complete cessation of *saṁsāra*, and it is attained through fixity in self-knowledge, preceded by *saṁnyāsa*, understood as complete renunciation of all *karmas* (action). S. Radhakrishnan, in his *The Bhavavadgṛh̄yā – With and Introductory Essay, Sanskrit Text, English Translation and Notes* (1948), 2nd ed., 10th impression (London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd., 1971), says, “He [Śaṅkara] believes that *Vedic* rites are meant for those who are lost in ignorance and desire” (17). And further, “Śaṅkara’s views are developed by Ānandagiri, who is probably as late as the thirteenth century, Śrīdhara (A.D. 1400) and Madhusūdana (sixteenth century), among others” (17).

attachment to the worldly life become recluses.” And further, “What shall we achieve through children, we who have attained this world, this Self?” (1988, 37)

Śaṅkara reminds us, “all the rites such as the *śrauta karma* etc. are intended only for the ignorant having desires” (Panoli, 1975, v.1, 40). For, “liberation is meant only for him who yearns for the real of Self and is free from desire” (1975, 40). That is to say, *Vedic* rites and *jñāna* cannot go together (i.e., they cannot be followed simultaneously by the same person), otherwise their “categoric definition would not be logical,” nor would Arjuna’s third chapter opening question become proper (1975, 40-1). That is to say, “the combination of the knowledge of the Self with any sort of *karma* enjoined either in the *Śruti* or *Smṛti* can never be observed by anybody in the *Gītā śāstra*” (1975, 43).

It is Śaṅkara’s contention that the teaching of the *Gītā* is *ātmajñānaniṣṭhā* (the discipline of the knowledge of *ātman*), but only in the *Vedāntic* sense which is clarified in his discussion of BhG 18.54-5, where *jñānaniṣṭhā* (devotion to knowledge) means *parābhakti* and implies renunciation of all works. According to Śaṅkara, BhG 2.21 teaches that ‘enlightened’ people should reject the path of action.²⁰⁰ When criticizing the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* theory in the opening of the third chapter of his *Bhāṣya* (ŚBh),²⁰¹ Śaṅkara considers that even when *karmayoga* produces purity of mind and reduces the binding *karma*, it does not lead to *mokṣa*, since *mokṣa* is not a consequence of action.

²⁰⁰ He says in his commentary of BhG 2.21: *hetvarthasya avikriyatvasya tulyatvād viduṣaḥ sarvakarmapratiṣedha eva prkaraṇārthaḥ ābhīpreto bhagavataḥ* – the immutability (*avikriyatva*) of the Self should hold good equally in denying all manner of *karma*. Thus the teaching of the Lord here appears to be that all actions (*karma*) are denied to the knower of the Self (Panoli, 1975, vol. 1, 74).

²⁰¹ Śaṅkara’s *Bhāṣya* states: *mokṣasya ca akāryatvād mumukṣoḥ karmānarthakyam* – Deliverance, not being an effect of any *karma*, it (*karma*) is of no avail to the desiring for deliverance (Panoli, 1975, vol. 1, 149).

For, even when *karma* – alone or in conjunction with *jñāna* – can lead to the path of *jñāna*, it still belongs to the realm of *avidyā*. Therefore, a *saṁnyāsīn* is he who abandons *adharma* as well as *varṇāśrama dharma*, since both hinder the path to *mokṣa*.²⁰² That is to say, it is only through *ātmadharma*, understood as Self-knowledge alone (*kevala*), that the binding effects of *karma* will be destroyed.

Śaṅkara reads *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti* as *karma mārga* and *saṁnyāsa mārga*, respectively. He does not consider the meaning intended by Kṛṣṇa, where ‘*pravṛtti*’ might express actions worth pursuing, and ‘*nivṛtti*’ the actions to be avoided. Yet, these meanings are implied in the context of the whole text, and more specifically in the discussion starting in BhG 18.40, where Kṛṣṇa prepares the argument on the relationship between the *guṇas* and *svadharmā*. For, according to his previous arguments, one can infer that *saṁsāra* (the existence, manifested in the form of movement and actions) presents some sort of reality²⁰³ and cannot be completely fashioned by *avidyā*.

Contradicting BhG 18.40, where it is said that there is no entity on earth, or in heaven, that is completely devoid of these three *guṇas*, born of *prakṛti*, Śaṅkara argues, “Even of *sāttvic* action, the doer is only the un-enlightened man who has got egotism (idea of being the agent); much more is this the case of *rājasic* and *tāmasic*” action (Ramachandra Aiyar, 1988, 570). According to Śaṅkara (BhG 18.10-66²⁰⁴) the *Gītā* distinguishes *kāmya karma*, or the action that is not good and represents the cause of

²⁰² See ŚBh 4.21: *dharmāḥ api mumukṣoḥ kilbiṣam eva bandhāpādakatvāt* – To the one desirous of deliverance even *dharmā* (virtuous deeds) is a sin, for it is productive of bondage (Panoli, 1975. vol. 2, 53).

²⁰³ The concept of *māyā* of the *Gītā* seems to be akin to the *Sāṅkhya* concept of *prakṛti*. The *Gītā* is nearer to the *Upaniṣads* and never speaks of a doctrine of illusion or the unreality of the world.

²⁰⁴ See Ramachandra Aiyar (1988), 554-637.

transmigratory existence, from *nitya karma* (obligatory action), or the good and agreeable action.

Śaṅkara imposes on the text of the *Gītā* the idea that ‘disagreeable work’ (*akuśalam karma*) *is* ‘*kāmya karma*’ and ‘agreeable work’ (*kuśala karma*) *is* *nitya karma*. He prefers to ignore the fact that the *Gītā* has in Arjuna an example of someone who, at first, does not want to perform his duty (*nitya karma* = obligatory rites), precisely because it is extremely unpleasant, or *akuśalam*. The consequence is that Śaṅkara fails to see in Arjuna someone who is seeking *mokṣa*. For, according to Śaṅkara, Arjuna belongs to that class of unenlightened people for whom “*it is not possible to relinquish actions entirely*”. For, “the unenlightened man, whose duty is in the performance of action, and *who*, while performing the obligatory works, *relinquishes* just the thought of *the fruits of action, is verily called a relinquisher*,” only as a way of courtesy (1988, 556).

According to Śaṅkara, then, calling Arjuna a *saṁnyāsin* is only a special deference meant to praise his action (BhG 18.17), considering that he was not fit for the higher *Sāṁkhya* (562). Śaṅkara disregards the fact that BhG 18.30²⁰⁵ reintroduces the question about the meaning of the terms *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti* precisely in order to redefine what a real *saṁnyāsin* is. Śaṅkara simply reads BhG 18.30 as if ‘*pravṛtti*’ meant ‘bondage’ and ‘*nivṛtti*’, liberation. He says, “*That which knows action, “pravṛtti”, which leads to bondage, the path of Works, and inaction, “nivṛtti”, which leads to mokṣa (Liberation), the path of samnyāsa*” (573).

²⁰⁵ BhG 18.30: The intellect which knows what is *pravṛtti* and what is *nivṛtti*, what ought and what ought not to be done, fear and fearlessness, bondage and liberation, is said to be of *sattva*, O Pārtha!

Śāṅkara does believe that the *Gītā* preaches that it is possible to renounce action entirely, since it is only through *avidyā* that the *guṇas* can be ascribed to the Self (592). His understanding of BhG 18.49, then, is that freedom from action (*naiṣkarmya siddhi*) represents the sole *jñāna niṣṭhā*, which leads to the state of immediate liberation (*sadyo mukti*) (594). In other words, Kṛṣṇa's teaching of renunciation of actions by the mind only (BhG 18.57-9) were meant to show Arjuna how he could overcome the difficulties he was facing as a simple *kṣatriya*, destined to fight, due to the constraints of his own *prakṛti* (609).

The sense Śāṅkara gives for the text does not seem quite right. If, BhG 18.59 is understood in the context of BhG 18.63, where one's free will is presented as the way to determine one's course of action at every single moment, Arjuna could have avoided fighting. In that understanding the whole point of the *Gītā* is to convince him of the inappropriateness of such a decision. Śāṅkara, however, for the sake of his own arguments, prefers to disregard that interpretation of BhG 18.59. Had Arjuna decided not fight, *prakṛti* would constrain him to react in one way or another, and he would remain bound by that line of action. Such an alternative would not solve his problem nor lead him to liberation, since it is due to one's own *karma* that the unpleasant situation one wants to avoid recurs again and again until one is able to face and overcome it (BhG 18.60).

Śāṅkara's long discussion of BhG 18.66 (1988, 613-632) shows how uncomfortable he was with these verses that lead Arjuna into his final action of fighting

as if he were not fighting,²⁰⁶ without any attachment to the fruits of his actions. In BhG 18.66, considering the context of the imminent battle, *ekam śaraṇam vraja* (take refuge in me alone) is to be understood in the sense of one’s posture of devotion, which should permeate the actual *praxis*. Kṛṣṇa clearly wants to lead Arjuna into such a righteous mode, where self-surrender is what determines everything else. Yet, when discussing this passage, Śāṅkara once again emphasizes abandonment of one’s duty,²⁰⁷ which is precisely the opposite of what Kṛṣṇa is suggesting to Arjuna. For, according to BhG 12.12,²⁰⁸ devotion in/with performance of duty, without any desire for the fruits, is indeed

²⁰⁶ The meaning is that activity (*kriyā*), which is characteristic of *prakṛti* and, therefore, dependent on one’s material frame, rooted in *ahaṅkāra*, is now fully regulated by *ātman*, as clearly stated in BhG 3.27-8. Under such a special circumstance, *ahaṅkāra* (the individuation sense that allows for multiplicity) cannot be said to hinder the full expression in *buddhi* (the faculty that allows for the oneness of reality) of *ātman* (or the universal conscious principle) anymore. The result is that one acts as if one were not acting. For, the one whose *ātman* is shining in *buddhi* sees beyond one’s self-identification with the material body, and understands how the *guṇas* of *prakṛti* frame the doing of all activity, leading one to identify oneself with *ahaṅkāra*. The later *Maha-Nārāyaṇa Upaniṣad* addresses this issue on agency, as represented by statements such as, “I do not do anything, and nothing is left undone by me (when the ‘I’ becomes a channel for God’s will and deeds).” It is the man’s sense of individuality that is responsible for the feeling of separateness and one’s false identification with *ahaṅkāra*, which only expresses one’s aggregate of body and organs. The *Maha-Nārāyaṇa Upaniṣad* brings a kind of ritual for one’s *ahaṅkāra*’s purification. There is a part which is known as *saṅkalpa*, and following it, as part of a *nitya-karma* a *mantra*, one reads: “I am not the one who acts (nāham kartā). . . I am not the doer (nāham kārayitā),” etc. This is in accordance to the idea expressed in the *Gītā* that the Puruṣottama subsumes agency through its lower *prakṛti*. For, basically *ātman* is without activity and substratum. That is to say, the ‘*aham*’ seems to refer to *ātman* in that *mantra*. According to Śāṅkara’s non-realist interpretation of *tat tvam asi*, however, *ātman* is identical with *Brahman*. Scholars disagree as to whether according to the *Gītā*’s theology one is made of *Sat*, the conscious (*ātman*) and material (*prakṛti*) principle known as *Brahman*, the universal Self, from which the whole universe has originated. Anyway, even when scholars may differ in their opinions of the meaning of *Sat* and in their interpretations of it, there is no vagueness about *Sat* or *ātman* being the very subtle essence of beings. Furthermore, Arjuna’s questions were targeted to understanding whether *ātman* could be experienced, and if so what was the path toward such a realization.

²⁰⁷ When Kṛṣṇa says in BhG 18.66 ‘abandoning every duty come to me alone for refuge’, he is clearly stressing the importance of self-surrender – a fact that Śāṅkara disregards, preferring to see in Kṛṣṇa words the necessity to give up the performance of all duties.

²⁰⁸ I will not discuss here the convenient view of those scholars fond of Śāṅkara, but not as much of the *Gītā* itself, who prefer to consider this verse as ‘spurious’. For, once we reject Śāṅkara’s *kevala jñāna* doctrine as being representative of the core teaching of the *Gītā*, we will also reject both, Śāṅkara’s saying that this verse represents a mere praise of *karmaphalatyaṅga* (meant only for unenlightened people such as

better than knowledge alone. As such, what BhG 18.73 finally brings about is Arjuna’s statement that, as a consequence of the destruction of his delusion, he will engage in action.

Śaṅkara, in conclusion, asks, “What is it that has been settled in this *Gītā śāstra* as the means to final beatitude (*niḥsreyas* – Highest Good, Highest Bliss)? Is it Knowledge, or Action, or both together?” (614) He concludes, “the delusion of *saṃsāra* is simply the effect of a false conception that is not absolutely real; and, consequently its total extinction is brought about only by Right Knowledge” (631). Yet, when addressing BhG 18.73, he adds, “*I will do thy word*: – by this Arjuna means to say: “Through Thy Grace, I have attained the supreme End of life; there is nothing for myself to do”. The teaching of the *Gītā śāstra* is over” (637). This statement, acknowledging Arjuna as a kind of *saṃnyāsin* who is free from acting is confusing. He either contradicts his earlier statement that Kṛṣṇa’s teaching of *Sāṃkhya* was not meant for Arjuna, as Arjuna was only fit for *karma yoga* (556), or totally ignores Arjuna’s final decision to fight.

It is my contention that if we understand Śaṅkara’s contradictory statements in the context of *śraddhā* as dealt with in this thesis, Śaṅkara’s argument can be restated to make more sense. For, *karmayoga*, as mastery over action, means also the ultimate overcoming of action. There is a point where action and actionlessness cannot be distinguished from each other anymore, due to the fact that in *karma yoga* action represents a pure and selfless expression of one’s own *ātman* (BhG 18.61). It is in this

Arjuna), and the scholars’ saying that there is something ‘paradoxical’ or ‘clumsy’ about it. Rāmānuja, when commenting upon this verse, presents a convincing defence of this verse being a legitimate praise of *karma yoga*.

sense, then, that in BhG 18.63 Kṛṣṇa reminds Arjuna of his freedom to choose and do as he thinks best. Kṛṣṇa invites Arjuna to act, not out of some sort of blind faith, but as a result of his own *śraddhā* or spiritual longing to reach *mokṣa*. Arjuna could, however, have chosen to remain enslaved to his selfish (*ahaṅkāric*) desire to give up the performance of what he had considered unpleasant.

In conclusion, Śāṅkara's contention that the word 'fight' in BhG 2.18, for instance, is a mere reference to what is already known ("*anuvāda*") and is no (new) commandment ("*vidhi*") (1988, 50), is not completely true in the light of the new *niṣkāmakarma* theory that Kṛṣṇa is introducing, and which is based on the notion of one acquiring *sattvic śraddhā*. The *Gītā śāstra* is for prompting (one) to such an action, which is said to lead to the overcoming of *saṃsāra*, or that which is the cause of grief and delusion. As Bhīṣma and others will be killed in one way or another out of the need of *dharma* working itself out, the sole object which Kṛṣṇa desires to convey to Arjuna is how humans can become instruments of the divine. Furthermore, when God operates through someone, one finally understands that *ahaṅkāra* is not in control, and in these terms, one reevaluates the understanding of expressions such as 'I am the agent', 'this act has to be performed by me' (BhG 3.27), 'without at all acting, or causing to act' (BhG 5.13), and so on. For, the *Gītā* affirms that *śraddhā* represents this capacity to reconnect the individual to the universal, so that action is performed as if one were not acting. This is what I define as the *Gītā's ātma-yoga*, as we will see in the next chapter. It represents the discipline Kṛṣṇa is teaching Arjuna so that he can reach final emancipation. As a bird

cannot fly on one wing, *ātma-yoga* is beyond the reach of those who remain ignoring either the *jñāna* or the *karma* wing. Kṛṣṇa, therefore, is teaching Arjuna how to use both wings.

Rāmānuja, who sees a systematic unity between *Karma Mīmāṃsā* and *Brahma Mīmāṃsā*, rejects the *kevala jñāna* view of Śaṅkara, and also defends the idea that one needs both wings working properly, if one is considering to fly to the final goal. A comparison of Rāmānuja’s commentary on the BhG 4.11 with that of Śaṅkara provides a hint that Rāmānuja is supportive of the reasons implied in my arguments in favour of *śraddhā*. In his commentary on BhG 4.11 Rāmānuja furnishes a paraphrase where the devotees who ‘take refuge in’ (*prapadyante*) God are said to experience God’s entire nature (*svabhāva*). Rāmānuja captures here the idea that this *Gītā* verse does not speak of this or that form of worship, but of a universal and active initiative, which can take many different forms. His sense of ‘take refuge in’ (*pra-pad*), therefore, captures Kṛṣṇa’s non-sectarian or dogmatic colouring, and works as the foundation for the conception of *Prapatti* – a concept that presents some resemblance with the concept of *śraddhā* and with how it was originated from the verbal root *śrad-dhā*. Rāmānuja’s commentary on BhG 4.11 allows one to infer, therefore, that *prapatti* is part of *mokṣa* itself as much as *śraddhā* is. For, in a sense, Rāmānuja’s gloss of ‘*prapadyante*’ suggests that the goal and the means are not totally distinct from each other. As for Śaṅkara, he does not even bother to consider if the word ‘*prapadyante*’ may or may not be theologically relevant in the context of Kṛṣṇa’s discussion. Śaṅkara sees this verse in relation to the previous one,

where he reaffirms his understanding that the path of devotion to knowledge (*jñāna tapas*), being itself the salvation path, requires nothing else. Śaṅkara, therefore, does not allow BhG 4.11 to indicate the theological importance of the attitude of ‘taking refuge in’ – which makes one relate to God’s supremacy in terms of how God ‘works’, of how God works through them, and also for how one becomes God’s co-workers in the world.

The question of Rāmānuja’s general refutation of Śaṅkara’s interpretation of the *Gītā* has been exhaustively discussed by many scholars.²⁰⁹ They all agree that Rāmānuja considers that it is the seeker’s dedication of all actions to *Brahman*, together with disinterestedness in the fruit of those actions, which leads one to the recognition that all actions are indeed non-actions. These actions, according to Rāmānuja, once performed with such an attitude, become non-actions (*naiṣkarmya*) for the performer, due to the fact that the performer is now seen as someone who has renounced agency to become an instrument and channel of God’s will. This idea of non-action is not to be understood as a license for the sage to perform misdeeds without being affected by them, as one might

²⁰⁹ See, for instance, the following works: J. A. B. van Buitenen, *Rāmānuja on the Bhavavadgītā* (2nd Ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1968); idem, introduction to his translation and edition of *The Bhavavadgītā in the Mahābhārata* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1981); Shirley Anne McMurty, “Doctrines and Methods Used by Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja to Elucidate the Relation Between Self-Knowledge and Dharma with Special Reference to their Commentaries on the *Bhagavad-Gītā*” (Ph.D. diss., McMaster University, 1977); G. Sundara Ramaiah, *Brahman – A Comparative Study of the Philosophies of Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja* (Waltair: Andhra University, 1974); Daniel Thomas, “The Path to *Mokṣa* in the *Viśiṣṭādvaita* System of Rāmānuja, and T. G. Mainkar, *A Comparative Study of the Commentaries on Bhavavadgītā* (2nd Ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1969).

infer from Śāṅkara’s interpretation, but it is the result of a full surrender to God, who, then, appears as the real doer, not only of one’s action, but also of this whole creation.²¹⁰

This Supreme Being (*puruṣottama*), whose essence is *Īśvara*, Rāmānuja calls either Nārāyaṇa or Vāsudeva, as opposed to the individual being, which he calls *jīva* in his *Gṛā-Bhāṣya*.²¹¹ In the words of van Buitenen, in Rāmānuja, “everything forms a mode of God, a *prakāra*, which is attributable to Him, subservient to Him and effected by Him. And God and his modes are indissolubly connected in a perfect and everlasting unity” (1968, 3). That is to say, what van Buitenen is suggesting is that Rāmānuja’s metaphysics is not much different from that found in Spinoza,²¹² which implies the existence of a single universal principle, but in different modes. For, in Rāmānuja the *jīva* is a mode of the *Īśvara*, it is not identical to It.²¹³

Furthermore, Rāmānuja holds that we do not directly experience pure consciousness for all experiences are of qualified entities. Even freedom from

²¹⁰ The power of creation inherent in *Brahman* expresses this world as a play (*līlā*) that has its own reality – a reality which Bādarāyaṇa has upheld as actual transformation (*pariṇāmanavāda*), or as that in which *Brahman* appears as the real agent.

²¹¹ I am using *Srī Rāmānuja Gṛā Bhāṣya*, transl. by Svāmi Ādidevānanda (Madras: Sri Ramakrishna Math, n. d.), but here and there I will also quote from *The Gṛābhāṣya of Rāmānuja*, transl. by M. R. Sampatkumaran (Madras: Vidya Press, 1969).

²¹² This point is important to consider because of Krishna’s Sharma argument that Western theology is theist, and only values theistic approaches. As what Spinoza does is considered ‘only’ philosophical speculation of minor importance and interest, one may almost advance that this same kind of prejudice is to be shown toward Rāmānuja, when he is considered on these grounds. Furthermore, when Rāmānuja takes into account Śāṅkara’s view, he develops a qualified monism which allows even for a theistic interpretation of the text. Whereas Śāṅkara argues that the individual soul as such cannot claim any reality, Rāmānuja reminds us that knowledge is only of qualified objects. If multiplicity is the consequence of *avidyā*, as Śāṅkara argues, then Scriptures themselves should be included in the group of what is false.

²¹³ The *Upaniṣads* and also Bādarāyaṇa speak of the *jīva*, though it is not easy to ascertain exactly their view on the relation between the *jīva*, the empirical self, and *ātman* and *Brahman*. For, entities that are omnipotent, free from sin, and the source of the whole universe, do not fit in with *jīva*. Bādarāyaṇa, for instance, presents the view of Audulomi, who thinks that the individual being remains tainted on account of its association with the body, but becomes serene (and purified) through the *yogic* process.

qualification still is a quality. This means that the *jīva* keeps its individuality in the same fashion as does the wick-light whose brightness is subsumed by the sunlight. The *jīvas* enter into God, though the relation between the Supreme Being and the particular being is that both substance and the attributes are real, being parts of a whole. For *Brahman* contains within itself matter and soul in a condition of seed (*bījā*). In other words, the highest principle carries within its own nature the element of mystic power (*māyā*) from where the worlds arise. *Prakṛti*, the unconscious matter, functions as the field of change, or *saṃsāra*, where the *jīvas* develop the consciousness of their own nature and their relationship with the Absolute, or *Īśvara*, through the complex *yogic* process of communion²¹⁴ named *prapatti* (surrender). *Mokṣa* is attained when the *jīva*, clothed in *śuddha-sattva*, is released from the dominion of the human ego, or the *ahaṃkāric* ‘I-sense’. If in Śāṅkara *bhakti* becomes an expression of *jñāna*, and *mokṣa* is to be attained through *kevala jñāna*, in Rāmānuja *bhakti* ends in *prapatti*.²¹⁵

²¹⁴ While *prakṛti* is the aspect qualified by insentiency (*acit-viśiṣṭam*), *ātman* is the aspect qualified only by consciousness (*cit-viśiṣṭam*). Although *Brahman* is one, by virtue of its attributes, he is said to have these two modes of being. Especially in Rāmānuja we see *Brahman* in this triune sense, where its two modes, *prakṛti* (material reality) and *ātman* (spiritual reality), define the third, Puruṣottama (Supreme Being), inasmuch as a human being (*puruṣa*, *jīva*) can be defined in terms of body (*prakṛti*) and soul (*ātman*). In the *Gītā* these two modes of the Puruṣottama are spoken of as the higher and the lower nature (*prakṛti*) of *Brahman*. Furthermore, as the whole creation appears in the modes of *prakṛti*, in *Brahman* stays the effect of what is its own creation, which means that the effect is only a modification of its cause.

²¹⁵ Regarded as the leading exponent of the ‘theistic’ *Viśiṣṭādvaita* system, Rāmānuja, though he acknowledges his debt to Yāmunācārya, the author of the *Gītārthasaṃgraha*, is considered the first Indian thinker to relate the Vedānta philosophy with popular religion based on devotional hymns. According to Rāmānuja, one may say that the *Gītā* teaches *prapatti* as synthesized in BhG 18.66. The later history of Rāmānuja’s *Viśiṣṭādvaita* shows that emphasis on *prapatti* (complete reliance on God’s grace and self-surrender to Him) may also be understood as the exclusion not merely of *karma* and *jñāna*, but also of *bhakti*. That is to say, some argue that *prapatti* as a way of salvation relies purely on God’s grace. However, if this were the case, one would be led to enquire for the reasons why Rāmānuja had chosen to teach *bhakti* also. The defenders of the view that *prapatti* alone leads to *mokṣa* points to the scriptural evidence present in the *Kaṭha* and *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣads*, where it is declared that God reveals Himself only

Nancy Nayar shows how the *prapanna* (follower of *Prapatti*) understood his path²¹⁶ to *mokṣa* as “a radical once-for-all altering of the attitude of life, lying the entire burden of liberation on God himself,” in “a life of faith and tranquility with each of his activities consecrated to the service of God,” and with all activities “performed as an expression of his total self-surrender to the Lord, the one eternal end” (112).

Before Rāmānuja could develop the ideas set forth by his predecessors, he had to prove that Śāṅkara’s views were mistaken. For instance, Rāmānuja refutes Śāṅkara’s argument in BhG 13.2-12 that it is due to *avidyā* that one sees *kṣetrajñā*, or *ātman*, as different from *kṣetra*, or *prakṛti*. For what Kṛṣṇa states in BhG 13.1-2 seems to represent a realist view of the world that does not give support to Śāṅkara’s absolute idealism – a point that does not go unnoticed by Rāmānuja, who discusses the passage at length. He finds enough support in the *Śruti* literature and in the *Gṛ̥ā* itself (i.e., BhG 7.4-5; BhG 9.7-10; BhG 13.19, and BhG 14.3) to show that the insentient matter (lower *prakṛti* or nature) and the sentient soul (higher *prakṛti* or nature) are to be properly distinguished in terms of their creation and relationship, as it is stated in BhG 13.2, where Kṛṣṇa states he represents the Field-Knower in all Fields. Rāmānuja says, “both the Field and the Field-

to those whom He chooses. This elaboration in *Purāṇic* grounds, though, ignores the fact that BhG 18.66 is said to refer ultimately to the impersonal *ātman* of whom Kṛṣṇa is only a personal representative.

²¹⁶ Nancy Nayar, “The Concept of *Prapatti* in Rāmānuja’s *Gṛ̥ābhāṣya*” (JSAL 23, 2, 1991), 111-131. She also shows how van Buitenen’s introduction to his translation of the *Gṛ̥ā Bhāṣya* negates the idea that *prapatti* is a means to liberation found in Rāmānuja’s *Gṛ̥ā Bhāṣya* (115). For, noting that *pra-pad* is taken by Rāmānuja to mean “to take refuge in,” and is synonymous with (*sam*) a-*śri* and *śaraṇam* (*upa*) *gam*, van Buitenen says that “to take refuge” may mean to take refuge in God in his human form by following his command, or to take refuge in God by regarding him as the supreme end of all worship, or it may refer to “an activity which leads to *bhakti*” or to the sole means for the *arthin* and *jñānin* attaining their respective goals. According to van Buitenen, therefore, Rāmānuja considers *prapatti* as a preliminary step or even as an equivalent with *bhakti*.

Knower, on account of their being My attributes, cannot exist as entities separate from Me, and hence can be denoted as ‘one with Me’ by way of co-ordinate predication [*samānādhikarīya*]” (Rāmānuja *Gītā Bhāṣya* translated by Ādidevānanda, n. d., 419-20). And further, “both the *Kṣetra* (Field) which is an aggregate of earth etc., and the *Kṣetrajñā* (the *Jñā*) have the Lord for their Self, because of their being of the nature of the body of the Lord” (Ādidevānanda, 420). And finally, “Vāsudeva constitutes the Self of the distinct entities (*Kṣetra* and *Kṣetrajñā*): The senses, *Manas*, *Buddhi*, vigour, splendour, strength, courage, both *Kṣetra* and *Kṣetrajñā* have Vāsudeva for their self (Ma. Bha. Śā., 149.136)” (Ādidevānanda, 431). For, in the three *Vedas* “the distinctive existence of the *Kṣetra* and the *Kṣetrajñā* is affirmed with *Brahman* for their Self” (432). Moreover, *Brahman* is said “to be neither being [*sat*] nor non-being [*asat*]” (439), once “the terms ‘being’ and ‘non-being’ do not signify the nature of the self,” but “are applied to the self only in the state of bondage” (440). *Brahman*, according to Rāmānuja, is existent and non-existent in terms of Its manifestation only.²¹⁷ And that is why he refutes Śāṅkara’s argument that ‘being’ and ‘non-being’ refer to the nature of the self.

In his treatment of the *Gītā* Rāmānuja follows the 32 verse *Gītārtha-saṅgraha* of Yāmuna.²¹⁸ Yāmūnācārya observes that release has no meaning, if the released being

²¹⁷ Sampatkumaran, in his introduction to his translation of The *Gītābhāṣya* of Rāmānuja, brings the verses BhG 4.5, BhG 7.7, BhG 7.14, BhG 9.4, BhG 9.28, BhG 12.8, BhG 18.61, and BhG 18.65, where the term which designates ‘God’ appears in all the eight cases of the Sanskrit grammar as evidence that the *Gītā* portrays God as involved in all kinds of intimate relations with the world (1969, xiii).

²¹⁸ Van Buitenen, for instance, states, “Rāmānuja, carrying on what Yāmuna had only just begun to do, attempted to give the *Bhāgavadgītā* its legitimate place among the authoritative texts of *Vedānta*” (1968, 3-4). And further, “Just as Śāṅkara, after the decline of Buddhism, restored the continuity of Brahmanism by reaching back to the *Upaniṣads*, so Rāmānuja restored the continuity of Hinduism by making room in

does not survive in its distinctive individuality. The individual, therefore, should last for ever and even in release enjoy its individuality.

According to Yāmunācārya the first group of six chapters of the *Gītā* deals with *Jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*; the second group of six chapters explains the next and higher step where *jñāna* and *bhakti* appear as the two sides of the same coin, with higher *jñāna* and higher *bhakti* (as distinguished from *prapatti*) expressing the oneness of *jīva* and *ātman* as a continuous flow of consciousness,²¹⁹ and the last group of six chapters deals with *prapatti* or devotion and self-surrender of the *kṣara* (the changeful *jīva* of BhG 15.16) to the *akṣara* (changeless *ātman*) as the road to salvation expressed in the paradigmatic BhG 18.66. Yāmuna’s *prapatti* is taught in verse 31 of his *Gītārtha-Saṅgraha* in relation to *bhakti*, but there is no agreement as to the quality of such a relation.

Prapatti, then, represents a direct path to God; *bhakti* is generated by the contemplation of the divine, as a source of love and in its pervading mystery and absolute majesty. *Bhakti* means practising love of God; it is built upon *jñāna*. *Prapatti* is not built upon *jñāna*. *Prapatti* means self-surrender to God, who becomes both the means and the

Vedānta for the *Bhavavadgītā*” (8-9). And finally, “We do not exaggerate when we say that practically all the salient features of the GBh. [Rāmānuja’s *Bhāṣya*] are contained in Y’s [Yāmuna’s] scheme” (9).

²¹⁹ In Rāmānuja *Brahman* is *vibhu* (all pervading) and *jīva* is *aṇu* (atomic), and there are both identity and difference between them. This idea is also in Bādarāyaṇa who speaks of soul as a part, *aṇśa*, of *Brahman*. But he also speaks of the *jīva* in *sūtra* 50 as a reflection, or *ābhāsa*, of *Brahman*, which leaves the matter undecided. Whether or not the *jīva* and *Brahman* have identical essence, which is consciousness (with the difference being that *jīva* is an agent and an enjoyer or sufferer of pleasure and pain), it is a matter hard to decide. In Rāmānuja the *jīva* is a composite entity consisting of *ātman* (soul) in association with *prakṛti* (the psycho-physical aggregate). The essence of the *jīva* is expressed in the word *jñā* (consciousness). It is the ego-consciousness, or the subject in expressions like ‘I eat’, ‘I go’, that requires an embodied self, or *jīva*.

end. *Bhakti* would be related to the *Upaniṣadic* way of *Upāsana* and would result from *Jñānakarmasamuccaya*. *Prapatti*, as absolute self-surrender, would perhaps represent a behavior of trust, or *śraddhā*, in relation to the Absolute, as proposed in many passages of the *Gītā*, and in particular in BhG 9.22-32. *Prapatti*, then, understood as complete surrender to God, represents what elevates all irrespective of caste restrictions. This means that the one who engages in *Prapatti* is a universalist who enjoys servitude to God and all creatures, no matter one's caste and beliefs. In other words, as defined by Rāmānuja, *Prapatti* already represents a kind of emancipation while in the world in the same sense that *sattvic śraddhā* does. That is to say, *Prapatti* actually works as a synonym to *śraddhā*. For, while working under the influence of any of them, one does not feel bound by Scriptural duties. In both cases one feels that one is entirely connected with the divine.²²⁰

When considering the first group of six chapters of the *Gītā*, Rāmānuja explains how the text teaches the nature of the self as distinct from the body, and tries to refute the Advaita *Vedānta* belief that this distinction arises from *avidyā*. According to Rāmānuja's discussion of BhG 2.16, the perishableness of the body is the only reason for considering it 'non-existent' (*asattva*). Rāmānuja prepares here the argument that *jñāna* and *karma*,

²²⁰ I will not go into the divergences here between the two groups of Rāmānuja's followers, the Vadagalai (northern school), who held two separate ways to salvation, and the Tēngalai (southern school), who held *prapatti* as the sole path toward salvation. For this divergence becomes irrelevant here, once neither *bhakti* nor *prapatti* can be defined as independent of the attitude of *śraddhā*. This is made clear through the two metaphors that define these schools: the monkey theory and the cat theory. While the Vadagalai school prefers the metaphorical idea conveyed by the statement that the baby monkey must hang on his mother; the Tēngalai school prefers to say that a baby kitten is carried by the mother alone. In both cases, however, the mark of being carried is nothing but the display of *śraddhā*, which puts the problem of the opposition of divine justice and divine mercy as apparent and non-real – a statement that also makes sense of BhG 18.66.

as stated in the *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*, are perfectly compatible and mutually inclusive, once both *jñāna* and *karma* are seen as necessary for the development of *bhakti*. Arjuna's *karmaphalatyāga* (offering of the fruits of action to God) is exemplified, then, in his perfect compliance to his duties.

When commenting on BhG 2.53, Rāmānuja says,

In such a concentrated mind, purified by the performance of duties without attachment, will be generated true *Yoga*, which consists in the vision of the self. What is said is this: *Karma Yoga*, which presupposes the knowledge of the real nature of the self obtained from the scriptures, leads to a firm devotion to knowledge known as the state of firm wisdom [*jñānaśthā*]; and the state of 'firm wisdom', which is in the form of devotion to knowledge [*sthithaprajñatā*], generates the vision of the self; this vision is here called *Yoga*. Arjuna, thus taught, questions about the nature of 'firm wisdom' which constitutes the means for the attainment of *Yoga* and which itself is attainable through *Karma Yoga* which consists in work with detachment, and also about the mode of behaviour of a man of 'firm wisdom'. (Ādidevānanda, n. d., 101)

The ethical implication here is one which insists on action in all stages of the spiritual journey. For, sense control and mental concentration are outcomes respectively of *niṣkāma-karmayoga* and *saṁnyāsa-jñānayoga*,²²¹ and constitute a preparation for the way of *bhakti yoga*.

In the opening of the second group of six chapters, Rāmānuja reinforces the relevance of *karmayoga* and *jñānayoga*, and shows how activity becomes central even in the *bhakti yoga*. For, it is the active life that, once dedicated to God, will characterize the four types of aspirants described in BhG 7.16 – namely, *arta* (the one who desires to recover from suffering), *jijñāsu* (the one who seeks knowledge), *arthārthi* (the one who

²²¹ In RBh 6.1-2 Rāmānuja works this idea of *saṁnyāsa* (which in Śāṅkara is an element of *jñāna yoga*) being in fact an aspect of *karma yoga*. He says, "such a person is a *saṁnyāsin*, i.e., one devoted to *Jñāna Yoga*, and also a *Karma Yogin*, i.e., one devoted to *Karma Yoga*" (Ādidevānanda, 212).

aspires for the Higher Truth), and *jñāni* (the one who has wisdom). Van Buitenen also implies this point when he says, “[BhG] 6.47 marks the transition from the first to the second *ṣaṭka*” (1968, 22). As we have seen previously, Hacker sees *śraddhā* here as a pre-requirement of *bhakti*. For, the verse describes the *yuktātman*, or the perfect *yukta* (disciplined in the *ātman*), who is disciplined with *śraddhā*, and shows, as a consequence, great devotion.

Then, in his commentary on BhG 9.34, Rāmānuja deals with the question of what *bhakti* really is. He emphasizes that its devotional and emotional aspects play their part in conjunction with acts to make up the *bhakti yoga* capable of leading to God. Trying to reconcile the paths of knowledge and non-attached action as dealt with in the *Gñā*, he points to *ātman* as the central category where knowledge becomes manifest in action, and vice-versa. It is this integration that leads to *bhakti yoga*. For, *bhakti yoga* means a vision of the self as described in the *Gñā*'s eleventh chapter,²²² which already is a result of Arjuna's *jñāna yoga* and *karma yoga* – the two *yogas* which Rāmānuja describes as interdependent and similar in RBh 6.1-2 and in perspective to *bhakti yoga* in RBh 6.46-7.

Then, when discussing the third group of six chapters, the real question behind his analysis seems to be related to the sense in which *prapatti* is also an act or perhaps a mental act, which may, or perhaps may not, include physical activity.²²³ *Prapatti* appears as an activity performed with *bhakti*, where God reveals his grace. *Prapatti*, or the

²²² In RBh 11.54, Rāmānuja stresses that it is “by single-minded devotion” (*ananyā bhaktyā*), which Ādidevānanda glosses as “extreme ardour and intensity,” that the *Īśvara* (*ātman*) can be reached.

²²³ We have already mentioned in a previous note how Sampatkumaran stresses that the later *Viśiṣṭādvaita* emphasises *prapatti* in the sense implied in a passage found in the *Kaṭha* and *Muṇḍaka Upaniṣads* declaring that God reveals Himself only to those whom He chooses. Such a sense is very close to the Christian notion of relying on God's grace (1969, xxiii).

fervent exertion of the devotee, becomes, then, the culmination of what is called in *Vedānta* provisional (*viśama*) *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*.

It is hard to distinguish *bhakti* from *prapatti*, or to determine which one is the supreme way of attaining God. On one side, it is hard to acknowledge the concept of *prapatti* only in a secondary way, because behind the idea of ‘taking refuge in’ (*pra-pad*) is the suggestion that one is, in fact, ‘reaching it’. On the other side, as long as Kṛṣṇa’s discourse can be interpreted as describing the way Arjuna should act as he moves toward *mokṣa*, Kṛṣṇa’s grace is to be seen as dependent on Arjuna to recover from his state as an *aśraddadhāna*. That is to say, Rāmānuja wants *prapatti* to be either a synonym of *bhakti* or its subsidiary (*śaraṇagati*, seeking refuge) in the form of Kṛṣṇa’s grace, as described in BhG 10.10. But in that case even *śraddhā* would become subsidiary to *bhakti*. This issue is hard to tackle and I am not sure if I dare to go any further. For this point is hardly discussed by Rāmānuja.

He advances smoothly from the discussion of *kṣetra* and *kṣetrajñā* in chapter 13 to the discussion of the three *guṇas* in chapter 14, where he comes close to identifying *bhakti yoga* and *prapatti* before concluding that it is through them that one is able to conquer the *guṇas* (RBh 14.26-7). By the last chapter of his *Bhāṣya*, we are left with the impression that what he is trying to say is that the *saṃnyāsa* of the *jñāna yogin* is really the ‘renunciation in action’ of the *karma yogin*, now called the *tyāga* of the *bhakti yogin*. In the end this seems to be a definition of *prapatti* in terms of *śraddhā*: the will to act by

surrendering oneself to the Lord, exemplified by Arjuna in BhG 18.66.²²⁴ In other words, Rāmānuja integrates *jñāna*, *karma*, and *bhakti* within the path toward *mokṣa*. For, *karma yoga* is a necessary condition for awakening *bhakti*; *bhakti* itself is seen as a category of knowledge that fills the heart, and *jñāna* is nothing but the renunciatory dimension of *niṣkāma-karmayoga*. Together they constitute the person full of *śraddhā* that Arjuna is at the end. That is to say, no matter the view adopted by the different commentators in relation to the relative status of the different *yogas* of the *Gītā*, what is important to stress is that *śraddhā* can never be disregarded as irrelevant or nonessential. Its warm and ecstatic nature appears in Rāmānuja’s discussion as much as in Śāṅkara’s.

Next, let us evaluate how Westerners, without fully acknowledging Will as representing a faculty independent from Reason,²²⁵ have addressed the *Gītā*.

²²⁴ In RBh 18.63, Rāmānuja says, “Thus in this manner, has been set forth everything that is to be acquired by those aspirants for release – the mystery of mysteries, concerning *Karma Yoga*, *Jñāna Yoga*, and *Bhakti Yoga*. Reflecting on it fully, do what you wish to do according to your qualification – i.e., follow *Karma Yoga*, or *Jñāna Yoga* or *Bhakti Yoga* according to your liking” (Ādidevānanda, 595). This is so because according to RBh 18.40, *tyāga* “is of the same meaning of the word *saṁnyāsa*. It is rooted in the relinquishment of the sense of agency in actions” (Ādidevānanda, 576). And further, in RBh 18.66, “Relinquishing all Dharmas means the complete relinquishment of the sense of agency, possessiveness, fruits, etc., in the practising of *Karma*, *Jñāna*, and *Bhakti Yogas* in the way instructed,” where *Īśvara* is “the agent, object of worship, the means and the end” (Ādidevānanda, 598). In all these comments, Rāmānuja’s *prapatti* seems to be inferred from its connection to *śraddhā* through BhG 18.71 – the verse that places *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*, as a sufficient condition for salvation, and provides scriptural support for the idea of release without knowledge of *Vedic* Scriptures, as postulated by Rāmānuja, through the concept of *prapatti*, or total self-surrender (*saraṇāgati*) to the Lord. For, placing *śraddhā* in this dialogue of the heart means precisely self-surrender and taking refuge in this heart which constitutes the divine in oneself.

²²⁵ It is unfortunate that the West has not developed such a philosophically sophisticated distinction. It is understandable, therefore, that Westerners have found it difficult to identify the theological relevance for the *Gītā* of a term such as ‘*śraddhā*’, which clearly does not belong to ‘Reason’. As we have seen, *śraddhā* is something that is directly related to one’s own heart. And perhaps that is why, as a whole, the West has failed to understand that which for an Indian mind is quite obvious: that the *Gītā* is presenting *Ātma-Yoga Mārga* as a way (*mārga*) to face critically the being (*ātman*) while emerging into its *praxis* (*yoga*). For, the *Gītā* tries to debate a compromise between the *Vedic karma mārga* and the *Upaniṣadic jñāna mārga*. Whether it succeeds is a matter of debate and opinion. My view, of course, is that it does so in the light of *śraddhā*.

IV.2. The Western Interpretations

All over the world there have been around 3,000 translations of the *Gītā* into around 50 different languages.²²⁶ The first translations seem to have been in Persian, whereas in English the first, among the total of almost 1,000, is the wellknown 1785 Charles Wilkins' translation published in London, which generated a whole movement in Europe.²²⁷ More recent translations have improved our understanding of the text, and some have become classics in the field. We have already mentioned Zaehner's (1969) 'philosophical' translation and commentary, for instance, where he also acknowledges among others Edgerton's (1944), Lamotte's (1929), and Hill's (1928) works on the *Gītā*. There is also van Buitenen's (1981) translation, which considers the *Gītā* inside the context of the *Bhīṣmaparvan*, rather than as an entity of its own. Though I do not follow his translation, I find it very useful to compare his theological approach with mine.

Eric J. Sharpe, who we have already mentioned,²²⁸ gives us a clear account of the different Western theological approaches to the *Gītā*. According to him, the *Gītā* was made by the West to conform to one or more of three broad patterns of interpretation: the transcendental, the technically orientalist, and the socio-political. He suggests that in the socio-political area, the *Gītā* got more attention than it deserves (54). The transcendental pattern, he argues, would be exemplified by those of the Emerson and Thoreau generation and of the Theosophical Society, later connected with the counter-culture of

²²⁶ For an account of these translations see Jagdish Chander Kapoor, *BHAGAVAD-GĪTĀ – An International Bibliography of 1785 – 1979 Imprints* (New York & London: Garland Publishing, 1983).

²²⁷ It was translated to French in 1787, and to German in 1801.

²²⁸ See Eric J. Sharpe, "Western Images of the Bhagavadgita, 1885-1985" (JSAL 23, 2, 1991), 47-57.

the late 1960s. The Orientalists, mostly following Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja, produced new translations, such as those of Hill, Edgerton, Zaehner, and perhaps Radhakrishnan (54). While the transcendentalists have something in common with popular Indian interpreters such as Aurobindo, Tilak, Gandhi, Vinoba Bhave and others, the Orientalists were careful to avoid transcendental lines (47).

On the one extreme, then, Sharpe shows us how the first Orientalists, such as Garbe, and his disciple Rudolf Otto, summarized the *Gṛ̥ā*. They might say: “there was once a *kṣatriya* named Kṛṣṇa; he called his god the *Bhagavad*; his followers called themselves Bhāgavatas; gradually Kṛṣṇa became the Bhagavad, and his “religion” became *bhakti*” (1991, 50). Otto, as is well known would later apply methods of Biblical criticism to the text of the *Gṛ̥ā* in his 1939 *The Original Gṛ̥ā*, and use his own criteria to distinguish an (early) (historical) core from the (later) (theological) parts of the text. His was a missionary approach, but was not much different from that shown in the strongly ethnocentric J. W. Hauer’s *An Indo-Aryan Metaphysic of Battle and Action* (1934).²²⁹ On the other side Sharpe shows us how some western transcendentalists understood the *Gṛ̥ā* as a theologically coherent text and a kind of scripture, much as modern Indians like Aurobindo and Gandhi do.

A. Malinar also presents a clear account of the different schools of western investigation of the *Gṛ̥ā*. She mentions two dominant schools – the historicist (mostly theistic) and the romantic (mostly non-theistic) in which the text is dealt with as

²²⁹ Hauer refers to how Gandhi uses the *Gṛ̥ā* as a tool for his nationalism, and Otto stresses the similarities between the ideology of the *Gṛ̥ā* and that of the Nazi regime.

possessing semantic consistency (1996, 52-64). Malinar reminds us of the goal behind Charles Wilkins' first English translation of the *Gṛ̥ā* by pointing out that it was funded by Governor General Warren Hastings, to whom the *Gṛ̥ā* presented a “perverted morality.” She quotes the words of Hastings to explain that the goal was to lessen “the weight of the chain by which the natives are held in subjection,” for the *Gṛ̥ā* would help to imprint “on the hearts of our own countrymen the sense and obligation of benevolence” (24).

Schlegel's Latin translation (1823) was intended as an eradication of the bias and mistakes in the interpretation of the *Gṛ̥ā* due to Wilkins' translation. For, he was of the opinion that, in accordance with the missionary agenda, the only interest in knowing the *Gṛ̥ā* was to figure out a way to refute it (Schlegel, 1820, 2; quoted in Malinar, 1996, n. 10, 24). Schlegel's romantic approach, however, was much appreciated by W. von Humboldt, who truly admired and respected this new interpretation of the *Gṛ̥ā* portrayed as a non-theistic treatise. It also, however, attracted a profound critique from G. W. F. Hegel²³⁰ and Langlois, among others. That is to say, from the very beginning of western scholarship on the *Gṛ̥ā*, the two main trends of interpretation were clear: the non-theistic romantics,²³¹ who would *feel* the truth of the *Gṛ̥ā*, and the theistic historicists, whose

²³⁰ Herbert Herring in his introduction to *On the Episode of the Mahābhārata known by the name Bhagavad-Gṛ̥ā by Wilhelm von Humboldt – Berlin 1826*, by G. W. F. Hegel, trans. Herbert Herring (New Delhi: Indian Council of Philosophical Research, 1995) points out the prejudice of Hegel, who is unable to apprehend Indian thought as philosophical. Curiously, Hegel teaches against Hinduism since 1805 (Herring, 1995, xv), though he also writes his ‘original’ *Phenomenology of Spirit*, which looks like a treatise on Śāṅkara's monism, in 1807. See also Wilhelm Halbfass, “Hegel on the Philosophy of the Hindus,” in *German Scholars on India*, Embassy of FRG, vol. I, Varanasi, 1973, p. 116, and Hegel's *Lectures on the History of Philosophy*, ed. Lasson/Hoffmeister, vol. XV a, 226.

²³¹ Schelling, for instance, observes that the text of the *Gṛ̥ā* represents one of the deepest realizations of the Indian mind, as it offers a serious reflexion about the unity and multiplicity of the world (Malinar, 1996, 27). Hegel, on the other side, finds in the *Gṛ̥ā* an opportunity and a way to repress what he feared the most – the romantics, together with their religious enthusiasm toward India and increasing influence. Hegel is

critical method would convey a certain *neutrality*, and yet, aimed at the same ideals pursued with the first English translation funded by Warren Hastings.

A running summary of the western scholarship on the *Gītā* is presented by Malinar (27-52). In this discussion she demonstrates how the now hegemonic, or historical and analytical tradition, triumphed. The main names she lists are:

1. A. Holtzmann (1891), who proposed an ‘inversion theory’, according to which the *Pāṇḍavas* are the bad guys;
2. E. W. Hopkins (1895), to whom the *Gītā* was a Kṛṣṇaite version of an older Vaiṣṇava poem, which was perhaps originally a late *Upaniṣad*;
3. Richard Garbe (1905/1921), who believed that the *Gītā* is essentially theistic, with later modifications to express some pantheism;
4. Moriz Winternitz (1907), who translates Deussen and follows Garbe’s interpretation;
5. Paul Deussen (1906/1911), for whom the *Gītā* has no philosophic²³² value, sees it as the way in which the Epic makes a transition from *Sāṃkhya* to *Vedānta*, with the pantheistic doctrine of *ātman* conserving the seeds of theism;
6. H. Jacobi (1918) thought the *Gītā* represented a manual of the Bhāgavatas, which was later inserted into the *Mahābhārata*;

guilty of committing the same sin he had blamed his adversaries for: he admonishes us against the enthusiastic generalizations done by the romantics, and yet has no problem in attributing to himself the capacity to encompass the total knowledge of the Indian *Weltanschauung* (26).

²³² Mervin Sprung brings an interesting quote from Nietzsche about Deussen’s philosophical talents on his “Nietzsche’s Trans-European Eye” in Graham Parkes’ (ed.) *Nietzsche and Asian Thought* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 1991). Nietzsche, who, through the works of Schopenhauer, developed a lifelong interest in Sanskrit philosophy, once said about the eminent Sanskritist and his friend, Paul Deussen: “You are not gifted philosophically” (Sprung, in Parkes, 1991).

7. Hermann Oldenberg (1920), who refutes Garbe’s main thesis, sides with Jacobi, and points out the importance of the ‘visions’ and ‘experiences’ as opposed to the historical development;

8. Franklin Edgerton²³³ (1925) saw the *Gṛ̥ā* as a mystical and devotional poem that “seeks to inspire and exalt, not to instruct or train the intellect” (Edgerton, 1940, 447; quoted in Malinar, 1996, 35). He is the first historicist to postulate that the *Gṛ̥ā* possesses a unity of sense: “We must think of the *Gṛ̥ā* primarily as a unit, complete in itself, without reference to its surroundings” (Edgerton, 1925, 2; quoted in Malinar, 1996, 35);

9. W. D. P. Hill (1928) and Etienne Lamotte (1929) accept Edgerton’s view of the *Gṛ̥ā* as presenting a unity of thought, but they saw it as representing a Bhagavata synthesis of different schools at a time when Kṛ̥ṣṇa was already being identified with Viṣṇu;

10. Jarl Charpentier (1930), still believed that the text is a collage of contradictory statements and failed to advance beyond Garbe’s results;

11. F. Otto Schrader (1930), who believes that the *Gṛ̥ā* has come down in more than one recension, and argues in favour of a Kashmirian recension. As evidence, he points out the reference to a *Gṛ̥ā* with 745 slokas²³⁴ – a number given in some recensions of the

²³³ See Franklin Edgerton’s *The Bhagavad Gṛ̥ā or Song of the Blessed One* (Chicago: Open Court, 1925) and his two reviews of Rudolf Otto – “The Kashmir Recension of the *Bhavavadgṛ̥ā*” (*Journal of the American Oriental Society* 53: 68-75) and “The original *Gṛ̥ā*: The Song of the Supreme Exalted One” (*Review of Religion* 4 (1940): 447-8).

²³⁴ Even when Śaṅkara’s text of the *Gṛ̥ā* still is considered the most authentic and oldest text of the *Gṛ̥ā*, one cannot disregard Dr. Schrader’s thesis of a different recension, such as the one postulated as the Kashmirian Recension. See also his “Neues über die *Bhavavadgṛ̥ā*” (*Aus Indiens Kultur, Festgabe zum 70. Geburtstag von Richard von Garbe* (1927), 171-183). In particular, I am fond of the recension of the *Gṛ̥ā* with 745 verses published in the Suddha Dharma Mandala Series, as well as the introduction of Dr. Sir

Mahābhārata, and which corresponds, for instance, to the number referred to in the commentary of Hamsayogin and to the *Gītā* published by the *Suddha Dharma Mandala Series*, which Schrader acknowledges but with suspicion.

12. Jacob Wilhelm Hauer (1934), whose Nazi political agenda determines his reading of the *Gītā* as representing nothing but the inheritance of the Hindu-German religiosity – a thesis that is also related to that of Rudolf Otto;

13. Rudolf Otto (1939), who sees Arjuna’s despondency as a consequence of his failure to acknowledge himself as an instrument of God’s will. According to him,²³⁵ the original *Gītā* (consisting mostly of a couple of verses from chapters 1, 10, 11 and 18) was meant to express a religious experience rather than to discuss philosophical issues related to *Sāṃkhya*, *Yoga*, and other systems. His ideas, however, being not much different from those of Garbe, have not survived the critique of Belvalkar, Edgerton, and others;²³⁶

Subramania Iyer, which F. Otto Schrader calls ‘non-scientific’ (*unwissenschaftliche*) and ‘unfortunate’ (*leider*) (1927, n.1, 173). I also find Hamsayogin’s *Gītā-Bhāṣya* to this recension a constant source of inspiration. Moreover, as Hamsayogin speaks of an Ur-*Gītā*, this fact proves that in India also there has been this awareness of the existence of a short version of the *Gītā* – a fact that in no way changes the value of the present expanded version (1927, 178). Anyway, in spite of all criticism, I still see this *Gītā* of 745 verses as a great source from where one can extract arguments for the thesis of the centrality of *śraddhā* in the plot of this *Gītā* as we have it now. I got the 1984 Sanskrit-English edition as soon as it was released by the Brazilian section of the *Suddha Dharma Mandalam* Organization. In our days this *Gītā* is hard to find. But one can easily find it in its Spanish and Portuguese editions, also published by the *Suddha Dharma Mandalam* Organization, though they do not bring the Sanskrit text. As the text is arranged in 26 chapters, and with a completely different verse order, it is hard to compare it in a few lines with the *Gītā* of 700 verses. The seven verses which I use to summarize Kṛṣṇa’s diagnosis and prescription to Arjuna (BhG 2.2, 2.3, 2.11, 18.61, 18.62, 18.64, and 18.66) appear there respectively as BhG 2.3, 2.4, 2.2, 25.23, 25.24, 24.1, and 25.25, which means that both texts convey the same core message. Schrader’s *Neues über die Bhavadgītā* provides an initial comparison and discussion of the more relevant similarities and dissimilarities.

²³⁵ Rudolf Otto, *The Original Gita: The song of the Supreme Exalted One* (London 1939).

²³⁶ See S. K. Belvalkar’s “Miscarriage of the attempted stratification of the *Bhagavadgītā*” (*Journal of the University of Bombay* 5 (1937): 66-133). He says, “Such a miracle-mongering mysticism would convert the Poem into an argumentum ad baculum. Arjuna of all persons in the world cannot be expected to meekly submit to such Hitlerism from Olympic Heights” (Belvalkar, 1937, 81; quoted in Malinar, 1996, 41). See

14. S. K. Belvalkar (1937 up to 1962), who is the editor of the critical edition of the *Mahābhārata*. He disagrees with Schrader’s thesis of a different recension, and argues that those additions are mostly insignificant doctrinary repetitions. Moreover, he also stresses the unity and consistency of the text;

15. S. C. Roy (1941), who also defends the unity of the text, and points to the fact that theistic scholars, such as Garbe, due to their bias, are too willing to find contradictions in the text and to present it as a sectarian work;

16. Heinrich Zimmer (1942), who sees the *Gītā* as a great synthesis of *Sāṃkhya* and *Vedānta*, and whose interpretation places him closer to the tradition of transcendentalists, leaving him, therefore, almost alone in the midst of so many skeptical scholars;

17. Surendranath Dasgupta (1952), who also defends the unity of the text, and whose interpretation of the *Gītā* stresses the centrality of the ethical issues related to caste-duties;

18. Miroslav Marcovich (1958), whose Garbe-like bias hinders the possibility of any interpretation that could go beyond the narrow understanding of the text as the gospel of the Bhagavatas;

19. D. D. Kosambi (1962), whose Marxist method, which disregards the religious domain, only leads him to incoherent results, without any theological significance;

also his “The *Bhavavadgītā* “Riddle” unriddled” (Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute 19: 335-348). Edgerton says, “I see no reason whatever for assuming the originality of any the additional parts of K., nor of even a single one of K’s variant readings. I am obliged to conclude that the attempt to prove the superiority of K is a failure” (1932, 75; quoted in Malinar, 1996, n. 41, 42).

20. R. C. Zaehner (1969), whose translation and notes on the *Gītā* we have been discussing;

21. Madeleine Biardeau (1981), who sees the *Gītā* as a ritualistic *bhakti* treatise whose context is given by the *Mahābhārata*²³⁷ – a text that in *Purāṇic* terms presents mystical unity. Arjuna, then, is the “yajamāna who never stops sacrificing and the battle as a sacrifice is his own variety of it, for which he is the sacrificer, the priest and the victim” (Biardeau, 1981, 93; quoted in Malinar, 1996, 48);

22. J. A. B. van Buitenen (1981), who acknowledges that the *Gītā* provides a religious as well as a philosophical context whose tone is suprasectarian, as we have already mentioned, and

23. Robert N. Minor (1982), whose exegetical commentary concentrates on his rejection of the transcendental and synthesizing views on the *Gītā*. He also criticizes elsewhere the lack of citation of secondary literature, which has led to a huge amount of repetition of what had been written before.

Historicists and romantics have investigated the *Gītā* through completely different and exclusive methods. While Holtzmann, Jacobi, Schrader, Oldenberg, Charpentier, Hauer, and others had concluded that the ancient *Gītā* would end around BG 2.38, with the further expansion being the work of the Bhagavatas; romantics, including here also those representing the Indian side, prefer to believe that the remaining verses are essential in the process of Arjuna’s recovering. They see the present version as non-sectarian and

²³⁷ See M. Biardeau, “The salvation of the king in the *Mahābhārata*” (Contribution to Indian Sociology, Paris, New Series 15: 75-97).

non-theist, as opposed to what Garbe and Holtzmann, for instance, believed. Instead of treating the *Gītā* as a later attachment, as for instance in the view of Hegel and Jacobi, the romantics consider the *Mahābhārata* as a whole, with the *Gītā* forming a unity, which is central to the whole Epic.

Biardeau helps us to understand the romantic approach. It is clear from her many different analyses that the structure of the epic is rooted in a cosmogony and theogony of a *Vedic* nature (or perhaps *Purāṇic*, according to her), and that they shape the physical and the cultural universe of the epic, in terms of the different levels of understanding of *dharma*. Symbols or structural elements are the means to interpret the text, and it is in reference to them that one can establish the unity of the text. Even van Buitenen, who criticizes ‘Biardeau’s structuralism’, acknowledges this symbolic or structural unity, when he states:

The *Bhavavadgītā* was conceived and created in the context of the *Mahābhārata*. It was not an independent text that somehow wandered into the epic. On the contrary, it was conceived and developed to bring to a climax and solution the dharmic dilemma of a war which was both just and pernicious. (van Buitenen, 1981, 5; quoted in Malinar, 1996, 57)

That is to say, he also acknowledges that the *Gītā* presents a clear and coherent goal, as opposed to what Hopkins, Jacobi, and others have argued. It is true that some Bhagavata sects have appropriated the work, but this fact does not make it a sectarian work, as believed by Garbe, Lamotte, Charpentier, and others. For, in the *Gītā* a philosophical and universal dimension is also present, as stressed by Belvalkar, Dasgupta,²³⁸ and even

²³⁸ Roy, Belvalkar, Das Gupta, and Kosambi are, of course, Indian. Here we try to fit them into ‘Western’ scholarship.

Deussen. The text brings ethical and metaphysical issues forward without leaving aside the symbols of religiosity and mysticism.

The unity of the *Gītā* lies in its praise of *praxis* and its aim of a true multiculturalism, which goes beyond the irrationality of the different sectarian religious movements. Such is the spirit of the *Gītā* in the view also of scholars such as Roy and Zimmer, for instance, to whom the *Gītā* represents the Indian understanding of what is humane, universal and transcendent. For, the *Gītā* is not a treatise of the dominant class, as postulated by Kosambi,²³⁹ since the *Gītā* is not a treatise on *bhakti* as he thinks. The *Gītā* results from the epic context, where Arjuna is required to perform *niṣkāmakarmayoga*, which in his case represents the doing of what goes precisely against his dominant class and nepotistic family values.

In other words, *bhakti yoga* is not the central idea in the *Gītā*, for it comes second in relation to the practice of *niṣkāmakarmayoga* and the consequent acquiring of *śraddhā*. As pointed out by van Buitenen, Biardeau, and many others, the central issue in the *Gītā* is in regard to *dharma*, whose dominant view is being challenged. The *Gītā* cannot be reduced to a gospel, or a manual, on theism. The *Gītā* really overcomes theism through its higher syntheses.

The tensions and apparent contradictions the text had presented are turned into its own dialectical strength, allowing for the dramatic climax of the whole *Mahābhārata*.

²³⁹ Writers with a Marxist orientation are accustomed to question the social relevance of the *Gītā*, based on their belief that the *Gītā* is a devotional text concerned with the preservation of the social structures that have nothing to do with equality and the ideal of social justice. According to their view, the *Gītā* is a religious tool of the dominant class used to oppress and exploit the other classes.

Arjuna's initial state of *aśraddadhāna* in the *Gītā* is to be understood, not as an occasion for dogmatic propaganda, but as the true dramatic moment of the whole *Mahābhārata* – a point where all questioning necessarily leads to some sort of conclusion and practical engagement. Arjuna conveys a metaphysical, social, and political attempt to reach *orthopraxis*, and the *Gītā* represents that point of the *Mahābhārata* where all questions ask for some sort of resolution.²⁴⁰ For, the struggle between war and peace represents the moment and opportunity to rethink the meaning of law, family ties, rights, righteousness, and above all, the meaning and role of one's own conscience in the larger social process.

IV.3. The Eastern Approach: Tilak, Gandhi, and Aurobindo

The 'Eastern' approach of some modern Indian leaders favours the romantic view as defined by the West. For them Arjuna's dilemma not only ties up the dramatic scenario of the epic and the historical problems of his clan and kingdom, but also suggests the more general humane drama where the individual soul develops its journey. This understanding of the text is best represented in twentieth century works such as Tilak's *Srimad-Bhagavadgītā-Rahasya* which appeared in many languages and editions – in Marathi by 1915, in Hindi by 1917, and in English by 1936; Aurobindo's *Essays on*

²⁴⁰ The ethical and practical question 'what should I do?' is indeed a question that everybody poses to oneself from time to time. Perhaps that is why romantics, among whom I include myself, have looked at the dramatic dialogue of the *Gītā* as having two layers of meaning: In the first layer, which is expressed by the concrete pair Arjuna-Kṛṣṇa, the individual conscience and its process of consciousness are shown in the actual field of experience, in interaction with the outer world. In the second layer, which is represented by the abstract pair Nara-Nārāyaṇa, the individual conscience and its process of consciousness hint, through images and signs, at an inner and religious process by which the non-personal representation of the absolute conscience (*ātman*) could be reconnected inside the individual person (*jīvātman*).

the Gṝā, which came out around 1920, and Gandhi's translation and notes on the *Gṝā*, which were prepared around 1925. The three of them have in common their admiration for the idea of *lokasaṃgraha* as discussed in the *Gṝā*: Tilak focuses more on its socio-political consequences; Aurobindo on its nature as the goal of the divine action, and Gandhi, perhaps representing a middle way between Tilak and Aurobindo, stresses *lokasaṃgraha* as a consequence of the salvation path.

Because the Indian debate on the *Gṝā* before these twentieth century accounts was usually excluded from the Western scholarly debates, one is led to believe that the *Gṝā* was 'rediscovered' by the British and 're-introduced' by them to the Indian audiences. The consequence is that the contemporary Indian interest in the *Gṝā* is seen as nothing but a reaction, first to the British enterprise, and second to the German romantics. The truth is that there is not much in the romantic and transcendentalist interpretation of the *Gṝā* that was not already present in the accounts of Śaṅkara and Rāmānuja, from whom Indian twentieth century Indian scholarship is descended.

There is no need, therefore, to allocate the twentieth century Indian scholars to the role of being a secondary and unimportant appendix of the Western accomplishments. They have a place of their own. Moreover, their results only confirm the thesis of the centrality of *śraddhā* in the *Gṝā*. For, the modern Indian scholarship reinforces the idea that the *Gṝā*'s message provides validation to all different religious expressions. They

acknowledge the *Gītā* as an integrated treatise of both philosophy and religion – a fact that, according to Krishna Sharma,²⁴¹ Westerners have not paid much attention to.

Other than these three – Gandhi, Aurobindo, and Tilak – that we will be studying closer, I should bring to our attention many other figures that can be said to represent the Indian side: D. D. Vadekar, S. K. Belvalkar, C. Rajagopalachari, Vinoba Bhave, Swami Chidbhavananda, K. Kalelkar, V. R. Kalyanasundara Śāstri, K. M. Munshi, Swami Sivananda, G. V. Ketkar, D. S. Sarma, K. M. Panikkar, Mahadev Desai, Jitendriya Bonnerjee, M. Rangacharya, K. Damodaran, G. W. Kaveeshwar, P. N. Srinivasachari, Rohit Mehta, P. Nagaraja Rao, P. M. Modi, S. H. Jhabwala, T. M. P. Mahadevan, R. D. Ranade, Swami Vivekananda, Haridas Chauduri, Paramahansa Yogananda, Bhagavan Das, M. N. Roy, and so on.

For the purposes of this work, it is enough to focus on Gandhi, Aurobindo, and Tilak. They bring validity to my thesis about the centrality of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*, and support the argument for intellectual continuity by stressing how the combination of the *Vedic* moral thesis of social engagement with the *Upaniṣadic* ethical antithesis of individual praxis leads to the *Gītā*'s dialectic synthesis in the form of an integral (social and individual) *orthopraxis*, defined as *niṣkāmakarmayoga*.²⁴²

Although not clearly expressed in Tilak's *Srimad Bhavavadgītā Rahasya*, the idea of the centrality of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* is in accordance with his general interpretation of

²⁴¹ See Krishna Sharma, *Bhakti and the Bhakti Movement – A New Perspective* (New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal, 1987). We have already discussed her critique of the way Westerners have postulated an essential difference between religion and philosophy (109-111).

²⁴² See Tilak's *Srimad-Bhagavadgītā-Rahasya or Karma-yoga-śāstra* Translated by Bhalchandra Sitaram Sukthankar (1935) (2nd Ed. Poona: Tilak Brothers (1971), 2 vols.), where he says that the *Gītā* reconciles "the Activism of *Vedic* doctrine with the Quietism of the *Upaniṣads*" through *niṣkāmakarmayoga* (199).

the concepts of *karma* and *ātman*, from where *śraddhā* derives its meaning. According to Tilak, the major commentaries on the *Gṛh̄ā*, either dealing with release through *jñāna* or through *bhakti*, do not completely address the *Gṛh̄ā*'s main position. As a consequence, Tilak looks into the text of the *Gṛh̄ā*, and tries to arrive at the text's conclusion, independent of the doctrinal bias that motivated many of the commentaries.

His conclusion is that the *Gṛh̄ā* is intended to answer why Arjuna should act, which means that it represents a manual on *karma yoga*. What is expected from Arjuna as well as from all who cultivate a *sattvic* nature is the performance of all actions, not only as materialistic tasks, but as *yajñas* unto the Lord, as offerings to *Paramātmān* (Tilak, 1971, 603). It is in this sense that Tilak sees the message of the *Gṛh̄ā* as expressing the way all *yogas* lead to the path of action, once the "Atman-Element saturates fully and eternally both the Body and the Cosmos (357). That is to say, *mokṣa* is not a matter of *jñāna* alone in the *Gṛh̄ā*, as Śaṅkara believed. For, the knowledge that brings the destruction of doubt, and that represents the know how to achieve the final metaphysical goal, which is the *Paramātmān*, is also *karmayoga* (91-92). In other words, *Brahmavidyā* ought to generate will and skill in the form of *śraddhā* to overcome *kāma* (desire) in its relation to *karma*. And that is why *Brahmavidyā* represents the means as much as the ends, in the process of connecting the individual beings (*jīvas*) to *ātman*.

Tilak's understanding of *karma yoga* as expressing an *ātman*-based philosophy of energism is in accordance with the thesis of the centrality of *śraddhā*, once *śraddhā* itself can be said to represent nothing but this *ātman*-based activism, or energism. That is to

say, the fact that Tilak subscribes to the *Advaita Vedānta* metaphysics of Śāṅkara becomes irrelevant, when compared to the fact that he accepts that all actions are to be seen as ritual actions – a fact that places the science of how to act properly at every single moment as the real issue of the *Gñā* (75-83).

Although Tilak builds on Śāṅkara’s metaphysics, in some sense his work also represents a kind of break with Śāṅkara. For, in Tilak the motives behind the actions are not only determinant (530), but also characterize that attitude of *niṣkāmakarmayoga*, which we have been calling *orthopraxis*. Furthermore, the cultivation of *niṣkāmakarmayoga* in the form of selfishless, righteous, and altruistic action is what constitutes one’s highest *dharma*. One’s good motives and reasons constitute what really leads to both the world welfare and individual release (530).

Karmayoga, then, represents a philosophy of social and political action (*dharmayuddha*) in the battlefield of righteousness (*dharmakṣetra*), according to which “one should enthusiastically perform all duties” (698). As one can easily infer, Tilak’s reference to the attitude of enthusiasm in the line of duty is related to his understanding of political activism as being ritualistic in nature and dependent upon one’s attitude of *śraddhā*. Tilak’s understanding of *yoga* in BhG 2.50 as cleverness in the performance of action connects *jñāna*, or knowledge, with *vijñāna*, or skill in the performance of action. It is such a skill, which is required in *karma yoga*, that defines the *sthitaprajñā*, or the one who is steady in the right or transcendental way. He discusses this topic when addressing

BhG 3.4-5, where *naiṣkarmya siddhi* appears as the capacity to carry out actions through the senses, mind, and reason, without desire (*kāma*), or selfish interest.

Tilak links true action with the awareness of *ātman* as the eternal principle behind the phenomenal universe, and disregards, therefore, the theistic tradition that, supported by the *Manusmṛti*, privileges a dogmatic reading of the role of the ascetic and of one's duty (357). It is because *dharma* and *svadharma* are also related to historical circumstances that one should reinterpret them at every moment and situation in terms of one's relation to *ātman* (697).

Tilak is fully aware that the *Gṛā*'s *saṃnyāsa* means *karma yoga*, as he even names chapter four of his commentary '*Jñānakarmasaṃnyāsa*', stressing that real '*saṃnyāsa*' is of the fruit of action accompanied by its dedication to the Highest. Thus, Tilak's political activism, sense of history, and metaphysical position are in agreement with the attitude of *śraddhā* described in BhG 3.30-1, which represents the central requirement of the *orthopraxis* of *niṣkāmakarmayoga* and its social ideal of *lokasaṃgraha*, as discussed in BhG 3.20-5. For, *karmayoga* is a means to both *ātmic* realization and universal welfare.

Tilak's adversaries, however, have argued that he makes the *Gṛā* nothing but a manual on political activism, meant to legitimate the power of religion in the seeking of popular support. Without going into this matter, what is important to stress here is that, even if one can blame Tilak for reading into the *Gṛā* a concern with political independence that is higher than religion, the truth of what he meant is better understood

by comparing it with Gandhi's different but similar message. For, what Tilak meant to prove was that, in its higher form, politics is only an expression of religiosity – a truth that no modern Indian has lived better than Gandhi. Gandhi was well aware of Tilak's *Gṝh̄ā-Rahasya*.

After the death of Tilak in 1920,²⁴³ Gandhi's religious enthusiasm became the most influential force in the political activism of India. Gandhi's understanding of what religiosity is in the *Gṝh̄ā*²⁴⁴ allows him to use religious terms such as *satyāgraha*, *sarvodaya* (the uplift of all), and *ahiṃsā* in a political and wider sense than Tilak.²⁴⁵ In his *Anāsaktiyoga*, or translation of the *Gṝh̄ā* with his commentary, he aims to present the *Gṝh̄ā* as a spiritual guide based on his personal experience. His free style and symbolic reading allows him to go beyond the historical plot and to bring metaphors and images to the center of the philosophical discussion: the object of the *Gṝh̄ā* becomes to describe a way to salvation through *ahiṃsā* (nonviolence) in the form of righteous actions in which one must surrender and dedicate everything to God, renouncing even interest for the fruits of one's good deeds.

²⁴³ I want to call the readers' attention to the fact that in a sense Gandhi and Tilak are very different. For Tilak, who was considered a radical in favor of violence, was very skeptical of Gandhi's non-violent methods of civil disobedience. Yet, they were also similar to the point that when Tilak died Gandhi called him 'the maker of modern India'.

²⁴⁴ See M. K. Gandhi, *The Gospel of the Selfless Action or Gṝh̄ā according to Gandhi*; transl. by Mahadev Desai (Ahmedabad: Navajivan Publishing House, 1930). See also his *The Message of the Gṝh̄ā* (Ahmedabad: Navajivan Publishing House, 1959), *All Religions are True* (Bombay: Pearl Publications, 1962), and *The Teaching of the Gṝh̄ā* (Bombay: Bharatiya Vidyā Bhavan, 1971).

²⁴⁵ Gandhi says, "the *Gṝh̄ā* teaches that what cannot be followed in day-to-day practice cannot be called religion" (Gandhi, 1930, 132). See also Gandhi's *An Autobiography: The Story of My Experiments with Truth*, Trans. by Mahadev Desai (Boston: Beacon Press, 1957). He says, "those who say that religion has nothing to do with politics do not know what religion means" (504). I understand he is using the term 'religion' here to mean 'spirituality' and 'religiosity', without any sectarian connotation.

Gandhi provides legitimation for his interpretation of the *Gṝā* on the basis of his personal experience over the years with it. This step in the interpretation of the poem of the *Gṝā* is not completely out of place, if we understand that the *Gṝā* is not a dogmatic treatise. According to Gandhi, the poem of the *Gṝā* is meant to touch the heart and to awake intuition. It is in this sense that he acknowledges the text as scripture; for, he sees scripture as that which is “concerned with eternal verities,” which are unknown and difficult to grasp, but which also appeal to “any heart whose eyes of understanding are opened” (Gandhi, 1962, 22). In the *Gṝā*, therefore, “the heart accepts a conclusion for which the intellect subsequently finds the reasoning” (Gandhi, 1971, 11).

That is to say, no matter what possibility there is of a *concrete* ‘history of the *Gṝā*’, what is to be affirmed are the universal issues the *Gṝā* is dealing with. For, behind the concrete idea of *yajñā* as a ritual sacrifice, for instance, the *Gṝā* suggests also the abstract meaning of *yajñā* as ‘service for the sake of the whole world’, which in some sense can be seen as an act of *ahiṃsā*, and legitimizes Gandhi’s assertion that the *Gṝā* teaches *ahiṃsā*. One may say that the *Gṝā* teaches *ahiṃsā* because it is very clear that the *Gṝā* teaches selfless action, and selfless action implies that there is no display of anger, attachment, hatred, coldness, indifference, or of any other quality associated with the notion of causing harm or being violent.

One’s detached, mindful, and necessary actions can never be considered harmful or violent, if renunciation of the fruits of action is what is at the centre of the non-violent action. This was the sense in which Gandhi understood the battlefield setting of the *Gṝā* as a metaphor for the struggle between the forces of good and evil to prevail. For Gandhi

is aware that common people are incapable of an attitude of full detachment, which then, makes the discussion allegorical.

Gandhi's *Anāsaktiyoga*, as the title suggests, makes Kṛṣṇa's definition of selfless action the main teaching of the *Gītā*. As such, it also frames and defines what non-violent action itself is to Kṛṣṇa. Kṛṣṇa deals with the apparent contradiction between non-violence as selfishless action and killing in verses such as BhG 2.30-8. Gandhi, when discussing BhG 2.30, comes close to Tilak's position, and also admits killing can be justifiable. Gandhi's position is also in accordance with that of Rāmānuja, who makes use of a medical metaphor in his comments on BhG 2.31 to show that killing is not always an act of violence. As Rāmānuja puts it there, sacrificial killing for the sake of righteousness can only lead to more auspicious rebirths. For, where the killing is beneficial to both the winning and losing sides, there is neither real injury in thought, word nor deed at all – it is only justice that has been served through war (*dharmayuddha*). In Rāmānuja's analysis Arjuna becomes nothing but a physician that should not avoid the procedures of a healing surgery out of fear that the killing of the malign tumour could be interpreted as an act of violence.

Gandhi's interpretation of the poem is considered valid by him due to two main facts: first, that the full meaning of any artistic adventure always goes beyond the limits established by the author, and second, that Gandhi's own practice of what he got from the *Gītā* could only move him towards what could lead to both, beneficial social changes, and positive empowerment of individuals. It is in this fashion, therefore, that Gandhi

concentrates on the universal ethical theory of selfless action, or that action performed in communion with *ātman* in *oneself*.

That is to say, the validity of the *Gṛā*'s message according to Gandhi lies in its capacity to trigger these important personal experiences of a metaphysical and ethical nature. Gandhi's reasoning on the *Gṛā*'s concept of *yajñā*, for instance, allows him to extrapolate its usage to the national movement he was leading, so as to redefine the Western idea of nationalism. For, according to his reading of the *Gṛā*, in a universal idea of nationalism, there cannot be any place for the predilection for race-hatred, as shown by Westerners.

Gandhi's enthusiastic use of religious methods allows him to deal with modern problems in the light of the inspiration and intuition provided by the text of the *Gṛā*. The *Gṛā* becomes with Gandhi a powerful psychological tool to overcome the crisis of identity promoted by British rule in India. For the whole country feels Gandhi's renewed energy, full of a catching soul force, or *śraddhā*, and becomes capable of evaluating the internalized colonial values and Western norms. The practical consequence of such a movement around Gandhi and his *Gṛā* was, as is wellknown, the revival of India's own identity and 'soul-force', or *satyāgraha*. For Gandhi played the role of Yudhiṣṭhira as much as the British and the missionaries represented the egocentric and evil interests of the wicked *Kauravas*, eager to conquer and impose their values and understanding of religion at any price.

Gandhi's identification with the nation as a motherland helped the Indians to restore their self-esteem and the British to re-evaluate their own aggressive and messianic

agenda. The *Gītā*, stressing the path of synthesis and unity in an environment of cultural diversity, worked as a mirror that revealed the British imageries of patriotism, and deflected their bad religious and socio-political preaching and influence. For, Gandhi had found the highest model for a nation in the *Gītā*, not in the British savagery.

Gandhi's attitude of *satyāgraha* is a faithful expression, though in a different cultural context, of the *śraddhā* Kṛṣṇa wanted Arjuna to recover. One may even argue that Gandhi, when coining the term *Satya-graha* (active engagement to the truth as opposed to the passivity of inaction), already anticipates this theological role of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*. Following Kṛṣṇa in the *Gītā*, Gandhi professes that passive resistance is for the weak and coward, and that even a violent way would be preferable to cowardice (inaction). Moreover, *sattvic śraddhā* itself resembles *satyāgraha*, once it is described in many places and also in the *Gītā* (in chapter 17) as coming out of *sat* (truth), whereas *aśraddhā* is described as *asat* (falsehood).²⁴⁶ In Gandhi as well as in Kṛṣṇa, fighting injustice (*adharmā*) by means of 'soul-force' means non-cooperation with evil regimes. It also means, as explained by Kṛṣṇa, an attitude of non-harm (*ahiṃsā*) to the process of being that leads to the eternal soul,²⁴⁷ even when in our days *ahiṃsā* tends to have a utopian, superficial, and sectarian meaning of 'not inflicting pain to, nor causing death of, any corporeal being'. Soul-force, either in the form of the *Gītā*'s *śraddhā*, or in the form

²⁴⁶ Kane stresses that in a passage of *Vājasaneyā-saṃhitā* 19.30 truth is obtained by *śraddhā*, and that in a passage of *Vājasaneyā-saṃhitā* 19.77 Prajāpati represents *Śraddhā* as truth and *aśraddhā* as falsehood (1973, Vol. IV, 352).

²⁴⁷ How are we to understand the reasons that convinced Arjuna to kill his beloved master Bhīṣma if not the certainty that he would not be causing Bhīṣma's soul any harm? Moreover, if not the friendly attitude of *ahiṃsā* in Arjuna's soul, what other reason would make Bhīṣma bless Arjuna and welcome his lethal arrow?

of Gandhi's *satyāgraha*, requires an attitude of love for that soul which is present even in the wicked enemy's body.

If we consider now the famous simile where the *Upaniṣads* are the cows, Kṛṣṇa is the milker, and the *Gītā* is the milk, then, we may add that in accordance to BhG 18.71 devoted students like Gandhi become the new milkers, and *śraddhā* represents the religious milk, which often comes mixed within the many particular faith-based waters of the different religions.²⁴⁸

A similar position seems to be held by Aurobindo in his *Essays on the Gītā*.²⁴⁹ For, he argues, the *Gītā* “builds another [other than the *Vedāntic*] harmony of the three great means and powers, Love, Knowledge and Works, through which the soul of man can directly approach and cast itself into the Eternal” (Aurobindo, 1970, 7). And further, he says:

This greater rule the individual finds usually outside himself in some more or less fixed outcome of the experience and wisdom of the race, which he accepts, to which his mind and the leading parts of his being give their assent or sanction and which he tries to make his own by living it in his mind, will and action. And this

²⁴⁸ In Vinoba Bhave's *Talks on the Gītā* (Varanasi: Sarva-Sevaa-Sangh Prakashan, 1964), we read: “Lord Krishna has drawn the milk of all the *Upaniṣads* and given it in the form of the *Gītā*” (2). The relation between *Haṃsa* and *śraddhā* is inferred from many different works. The *Kubjikānata* or *Kulālikāmnaya* (*Śākta*, from early medieval period) describes *haṃsa* as “the supreme seminal sound that is present in the heart.” Elsewhere, the *mantra* “*Oṃ-Haṃsaḥ-So-'ham*” is said to express how ritual acts work as purifiers, which empowers and fills one with inner strength. Since the early *Upaniṣads* the idea of the *haṃsa* (the swan who drinks the milk, but not the water with which the milk is mixed) has remained in vogue in the different yogic traditions, being understood in terms of the unity of the individual ‘I’ (*ham*) with the universal ‘He’ (*sa*). In the *Dhyānabindu Upaniṣad*, also, one finds: “By the syllable *ha* he departs, by *sa* he enters again; *haṃsa*, *haṃsa*, this *mantra* the soul recites continually.” In the Tantras of the Sakta system, where the energetic aspect of God (*Śakti*) is dealt with, and in the Naradiya section of the Santi-Parva of the *Mahābhārata*, which represents the earliest source of information about the five processes referred to as Pancaratra, numerous courses of ritualistic purification, are also prescribed. For a detailed study of some *Vedic* images one may want to see Henk W. Bodewitz, *Jaiminīya Brāhmaṇa* I.1-65. Translation and Commentary: With a Study *Agnihotra* and *Prāṇāgnihotra* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1973).

²⁴⁹ I am using the eighth reprint of his work, of 1970, published by Sri Aurobindo Ashram, in Pondicherry.

assent of being, its conscious acceptance and will to believe and realize, may be called by the name which the *Gṛā* gives to it, his faith, *śraddhā*. The religion, the philosophy, the ethical law, the social idea, the cultural idea in which I put my faith, gives me a law for my nature and its works, an idea of relative right or an idea of relative or absolute perfection, and in proportion as I have a sincerity and completeness of faith in it and an intensity of will to live according to that faith, I can become what it proposes to me, . . .

But what then shall be the secure base of an action which departs both from the guidance of desire and from the normal law? [. . .], and what then is the clue to be followed, the guiding light on which it [the movement into the new and unknown] can depend or its strong basis in our being? The answer is that the clue and support is to be found in man's *śraddhā*. (462-4)

Aurobindo sees in *śraddhā* as dealt with in the *Gṛā* this movement that represents “man's appeal to himself or to something potent and compelling in himself or in universal existence” (464). For, “everything depends on the nature of his faith, the thing in himself or in the universal soul – of which he is a portion or manifestation” (464-5).

Aurobindo refers to the personal truth represented by *śraddhā* as the human capacity to create its own destiny in action, through the soul's dynamics (466). In the *Gṛā*, he argues, first, “absolute *Brahman* is also supreme Purusha, and Purusha is always conscious Soul,” and second, “the endeavour to become the Divine itself “depends on *śraddhā*” (467). Moreover, such a becoming “is by an act of our conscious substance and a belief in its truth;” it “proceeds by faith [*śraddhā*], acceptance, will to be in the originating consciousness, Chit-Shakti” (467). That is to say, “because *śraddhā* is the central principle of our existence, any of these things [*yajña*, *dāna*, *tapas*, and so on, as dealt with in chapter 17 of the *Gṛā*] done without *śraddhā* is a falsity” (475). Therefore, *śraddhā* “is that which determines by its power the measure of our possibilities of becoming” (475).

Aurobindo sees the *Gṝā* as addressed to those politically awakened to their duty to protect righteousness and justice (43-61), while in the midst of their seeking after the Divine, through an Integral *Yoga* in the form of works, devotion, and knowledge (308-22). His *yogic* understanding of the entire creation as being holistically interconnected frames his *Essays on the Gṝā* as an attempt to deal with the *Gṝā* and its non-sectarian synthesis of all the *yogas* (7-8). Although he cannot fully abandon Śaṅkara's position, according to which the *Gṝā* is a *Vedāntic* work (62), he does manage to see that the text is not opposed to works. For, he sees the *yogas* of the *Gṝā* as those acts of mastering and harmonizing oneself (and which appear in all paths leading towards the final realization) that form the triune way, composed of *karmayoga*, *bhakti yoga*, and *jñāna yoga* (34-5). That is to say, Aurobindo's understanding of the triune path of the *Gṝā* does not privilege *jñāna* nor *bhakti* in the *Gṝā*, and as a consequence, it works to reinforce the thesis of the centrality of *śraddhā*. For, "what the thought, the inner regard, the faith, *śraddhā*, settles itself upon with a complete and definite insistence, into that our inner being tends to change" (281).

Perhaps it is due to his view on *śraddhā* as representing something that includes knowledge, action and devotion, that Aurobindo, although without mentioning the name of Tilak, criticizes those who dismiss the importance of devotion and advocate plain activism as superior to, and independent of, the other forms of *yoga* (Aurobindo, 1970, 27). Perhaps it is also due to this view on *śraddhā* that Aurobindo's interpretation of the *Gṝā* differs a little from that of Gandhi too. For, according to Aurobindo, *Kurukṣetra* is

not only a symbolic battleground, but also a literal field of human activity in general. That is to say, according to Aurobindo, the *Gṝā* is addressed to the righteous fighters whose motives are pure, non-violent, and meant to protect, even when their actual actions may suggest otherwise (Aurobindo, 1970, 44-5).

Despite some divergences among these three commentators of the *Gṝā*, we have to concede, their general understanding of the text is not so different from each other. They all acknowledge the unique status of the *Gṝā* as a secure provider of a universal and non-sectarian *yogic*²⁵⁰ method to recover *śraddhā*, and to approach the Supreme. Furthermore, inasmuch as Tilak and Gandhi, Aurobindo also agrees that one can read in the *Gṝā* a “gospel of pragmatism” (466).²⁵¹

It has been my contention that the synthesis proposed in the *Gṝā* is better understood through the concept of *śraddhā*, once we understand its continuity of meaning from one period to another, and in the *Gṝā* itself. With Aurobindo we can see in what sense the discourse of Kṝṣṇa was meant to remove the numbness²⁵² of Arjuna’s soul, as well as in what sense Arjuna’s *śraddhā* resulted from his self-surrender. For, besides stressing the importance of ritual actions, of sacrifice and self-surrender, Aurobindo also

²⁵⁰ According to Aurobindo, *karma yoga*, *bhakti yoga*, and *jñāna yoga*, harmonized together, compound an integral (*pūjma*) *yoga* (1970, 34) -- a view that is also in agreement with the *jñānakarmasamuccaya* theory, we have mentioned before.

²⁵¹ Even if he may be here only suggesting a preliminary and provisional understanding of the text as we find in the works of those like Tilak, who privileges works, it is worth mentioning that, in a deeper sense, his suggestion reveals an agreement with our thesis on *śraddhā* and, consequently, with our description of the *Gṝā* as a manual on *orthopraxis*.

²⁵² I am borrowing the phrase ‘numbness of Arjuna’s soul’ from P. M. Thomas’ *Twentieth Century Indian Interpretations of the Bhagavadgītā: Tilak, Gandhi, and Aurobindo* (Delhi: The Christian Institute for the Study of Religion and Society, 1987) – a work which I have read, and which has helped me to frame this whole section. When referring to Aurobindo, Thomas says, “The discourses in the *Gṝā* are given to remove the numbness of Arjuna’s soul” (112).

considers the *Gītā* a metaphysical synthesis of the opposing *Vedic* and *Upaniṣadic* systems.

According to Aurobindo, Arjuna “typifies the human soul of action brought face to face through that action in its highest and most violent crisis with the problem of human life and its apparent incompatibility with the spiritual state or even with a purely ethical ideal of perfection” (18). The understanding of such incompatibility, therefore, reveals that there is no need to consider the *Kurukṣetra* setting exclusively in terms, either of its symbolical, or non-symbolical, layers of meaning.

The text lends itself to a symbolic and universal treatment, as Gandhi has shown; and also allows for a non-symbolic and concrete cultural treatment, as Tilak has shown. These different ‘truths’ are brought together by Aurobindo, as expressed, for instance, in the following passage, where Aurobindo describes the process of Avatarhood:

The Avatar is always a dual phenomenon of divinity and humanity; the Divine takes upon himself the human nature with all its outward limitations and makes them the circumstances, means, instruments of the divine consciousness and the divine power, a vessel of the divine birth and the divine works. (155)

And further,

The Gita lays stress upon the struggle of which the world is the theatre, in its two aspects, the inner struggle and the outer battle. In the inner struggle the enemies are within, in the individual, and the slaying is of desire, ignorance, egoism is the victory. But there is an outer struggle between the powers of the Dharma. (165)

In other words, in the *Gītā* the inner struggle appears in the form of *tyāga*; the outer struggle appears in the form of *saṁnyāsa* understood in terms of *niṣkāmakarma*, and, we can add, what unifies these two apparently opposing attitudes is *śraddhā*, as we have defined it.

V. THE GĪTĀ IN THE MAHĀBHĀRATA

This chapter will focus on the theological implications of Arjuna's temporary obtaining of the necessary *śraddhā* to move on his path towards salvation. It will not repeat the detailed textual discussion of the former chapters, but will assume those results, and show how they relate with the main topic of the *Gītā* and of the *Mahābhārata*²⁵³ – the proper way of conceiving the idea of *dharma*. The appearance of the term *dharma* in the first verse (*śloka*) of the *Gītā* as its very first word already suggests how *dharma* is essential to understand the theology and metaphysics of the whole *Gītā*. Furthermore, as Kane reminds us, in the *Ādiparvan* of the *Mahābhārata*

²⁵³ The *Mahābhārata* is made up of 18 *Parvans* (volumes) (sometimes classified into 100 books). The first book of each series names the whole *parvan*, as exemplified below:

1. (01) <i>Ādiparvan</i> : The Book of the Beginning	(225 chapters)	7984 slokas
2. (20) <i>Sabhāparvan</i> : The Book of the Assembly Hall	(72 chapters)	2511
3. (29) <i>Araṇyaparvan</i> : The Book of the Forest	(298 chapters)	11664
4. (45) <i>Virāṭaparvan</i> : The Book of king Virāṭa	(67 chapters)	2050
5. (49) <i>Udyogaparvan</i> : The Book of the Effort	(197 chapters)	6696
6. (60) <i>Bhīṣmaparvan</i> : The Book of Bhīṣma	(117 chapters)	5884
(61) <i>The Creation of the Continent of Jambū</i>		
(62) <i>The Earth</i> – which describes the expanse of the continents		
(63) <i>The Bhagavadgītā</i>		
(64) <i>The Slaying of Bhīṣma</i>		
7. (65) <i>Droṇaparvan</i> : The Book of Droṇa	(173 chapters)	8909
8. (73) <i>Karṇaparvan</i> : The Book of Karṇa	(69 chapters)	4900
9. (74) <i>Śalyaparvan</i> : The Book of Śalya	(64 chapters)	3220
10. (78) <i>Sauptikaparvan</i> : The Book of the Sleeping Warriors	(18 chapters)	870
11. (81) <i>Strīparvan</i> : The Book of the Women	(27 chapters)	775
12. (86) <i>Śāntiparvan</i> : The Book of the Peace	(353 chapters)	14525
13. (89) <i>Aṇuśāsanaparvan</i> : The Book of the Instructions	(154 chapters)	6700
14. (91) <i>Āśvamedhikaparvan</i> : The Book of the Horse Sacrifice	(96 chapters)	3320
15. (93) <i>Āśramavasikaparvan</i> : The Book of the Hermitage	(47 chapters)	1506
16. (96) <i>Mausalaparvan</i> : The Book of the Clubs	(8 chapters)	300
17. (97) <i>Mahāprasthāṇikaparvan</i> : The Book of the Great Journey	(3 chapters)	120
18. (98) <i>Svargarohanaparvan</i> : The Book of the Ascent to Heaven	(5 chapters)	200
Total		82134 slokas

The total of verses given here is approximated, since the C.E. has censored many passages present in the originals, now known as 'Vulgate'.

(MBh 1.2.83) it is said that Vyāsa composed the *Mahābhārata* as a great *Dharmaśāstra*, *Arthaśāstra* (treatise on Government), *Mokṣaśāstra* and also *Kāmaśāstra* (Kane, 1968, vol. 1, 349-50).

In the *Mahābhārata* as a whole, as well as in the *Gītā*, the meaning of *dharma* is discussed in a context where the word ‘*dharma*’ indicates that the best course of action to take is to fulfil what one understands as one’s own duties (BhG 3.35).²⁵⁴ Among the relatives of the *Pāṇḍavas* and *Kauravas* the deep ethical dilemma is to choose on which side to fight. Bhīṣma and Karṇa choose personal loyalty and consider it the heart of *dharma*, but Arjuna and his brothers see social duty over personal interest as the heart of *dharma*. It is in sorting out these differing views that the theology of the *Gītā* emerges, and the patterns and links that we have suggested in the previous chapters become clear.

The present chapter, therefore, is structured to demonstrate my contention all along that the text of the *Gītā* is to be treated as a whole, and interpreted as a central point in the argument of the *Mahābhārata*.²⁵⁵ The challenge now is to describe how the structures arising from the *Mahābhārata* inform the meaning of the *Gītā* and vice versa. What we need to establish here is what exactly the dilemmas about *dharma* are in the

²⁵⁴ Kane opens his *History of Dharmaśāstra* with a study on the meaning of *dharma*, which he sees in *R̥gvedic* passages with the denotation of ‘upholder or supporter’, ‘religious ordinances or rites’ and also ‘fixed principles or rules of conduct’ (1968, vol.1, 1-6). Kane relates the meaning of *dharma* in BhG 3.35, where it is said, *svadharme nidhanaṃ śreyaḥ*, with an exhortation to the pupil that appears in the passage I.11 of the *Taittirīya Upaniṣad* (1968, 4). He indicates a clear continuity of meaning among the different periods, even when the *Vedas* do not contain positive precepts (*vidhi*), as found in the later *dharmaśāstra* literature (7) He places the *Dharma Sūtras* of Gautama, Baudhāyana, and Āpastamba in the period between 600 and 300 B.C. (13).

²⁵⁵ For a brief and thorough account on the historical development of the scholarship on the *Mahābhārata*, I suggest the interesting thesis of Aditya Adarkar, “Karṇa in the *Mahābhārata*” (Chicago: The University of Chicago, Ph. D. diss., 2001).

Mahābhārata, and then show how the theological message of the *Gītā* provides a way to answer these dilemmas. In our case, we want to see how the new meanings and values introduced by Kṛṣṇa around the concept of *dharma* define the theology of the *Gītā* and open out the meaning of the whole *Mahābhārata*.²⁵⁶

The centrality of *dharma* in the *Gītā* is made evident at the outset when the text introduces its central question by presenting what might be seen as a crossbreeding of the previous *varṇāśrama* and *mokṣa dharmas*. Kṛṣṇa’s argument begins by showing that, beyond Arjuna’s initial state of confusion, where these two previous traditions appear to contradict each other, there is a third path – which Arjuna is about to experience. Such is the context of the dialogue embedded in the womb of the *Mahābhārata*. The *Gītā* describes how Kṛṣṇa works in the role of the midwife of Arjuna, who is pregnant with intellectual integrity and good will. It describes the birth of *ātma-dharma* within Arjuna. It demonstrates how *ātma-dharma* works itself out through Arjuna’s good will so that he can understand and act in accordance with that new view. Furthermore, it is not a mere coincidence that the very first word in the *Gītā* is ‘*dharma*’, the word which in the whole context of the *Mahābhārata* is cause for confusion and debate.²⁵⁷

The *Gītā* is Vyāsa’s teaching, through Saṃjaya’s divine eyes (*divyacakṣus*), to his own blind and selfish son, as well as to all his blind and selfish descendents – in other words, mostly, to all of us. For, what the king’s charioteer relates to the king is supposedly powerful enough to trigger *śraddhā*, and help even those, like the blind king,

²⁵⁶ The *Gītā* is mostly accepted as having been composed by the compiler of the *Mahābhārata*, Vyāsa.

²⁵⁷ In MBh 8.69 Kṛṣṇa explains ‘*dharma*’ as that which works holding the universe together. This is in accordance with etymology of the term ‘*dharma*’, which comes from the root *dhṛ* (to hold or uphold).

stuck in a life oriented by selfish motives. Had the blind king developed willpower²⁵⁸ to truly fulfil his *svadharma*, as Arjuna does, the war would never have happened. For, in the *Gītā svadharma* represents one's awareness of one's true mission and vocation; it means *ātma-dharma* rather than mere caste duty.²⁵⁹

This chapter, therefore, considers the fact that the author Vyāsa seems to be contrasting the pair Saṁjaya/Dhṛtarāṣṭra of the framing tale of the *Mahābhārata* with the pair Kṛṣṇa/Arjuna of the embedded tale of the *Gītā* to clarify how *dharma* is differently reflected upon in accordance with each one's own nature. When Vyāsa visits his blind son, king Dhṛtarāṣṭra, just before the beginning of the battle of *Kurukṣetra*, he gives divine sight to Saṁjaya, the blind king's charioteer, because he wants the king and his descendents to acknowledge the divine dialogue of Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna, so that they can reflect upon the meaning of *dharma*. That is how the blind king, the first ever to have the privilege to listen to the dialogue between Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna, learns about the consequences of his own selfishness.

In the *Mahābhārata* the blind king continues to maintain a disrespectful way of enquiring (*paripraśna*) about his fate, but in the *Gītā* Arjuna represents the proper role model (BhG 4.34), always willing to learn and solve the enigma about the meaning of

²⁵⁸ See BG 18.71. In ritual terms, no activity can be considered properly performed in the absence of good will and *śraddhā*. The need of *śraddhā* when reading Scripture is made clear through the common English saying, "Even the devil can cite scripture!" – a statement of Gerald James Larson's "The Song Celestial: Two Centuries of the *Bhagavad Gīta* in English" (*Philosophy East and West* vol. 31, 513-543). Cited in J. I. Bakker's *Gandhi and the Gita* (Toronto: Canadian Scholars' Press, 1993), n. 43, p. 340. That is to say, if your heart is not in the words you are listening, the listening becomes useless.

²⁵⁹ This is the view of many Indian scholars. See, for instance, Vinobha Bhavé's *Talks on the Gītā* (Varanasi: Sarvasevasangh Prakashan, 1964). He is of the opinion that *svadharma*, as an expression of true vocation, is the natural consequence of one's *svabhāva*.

dharma with reverence (*praṇipāta*), proper enquiry (*paripraśna*), and devoted service (*sevā*). That is to say, the *Gītā* represents a revelation of how one is supposed to uncover the lamp of wisdom (*jñānadīpa*) hidden within oneself (BhG 10.11), through growing discernment and a will to perform deeds in accordance with such discernment. It deals with the laws (*dharma*) of *ātman* as they function in *prakṛti*, as well as with the laws of release (*mokṣa*) from this *saṃsāric* functioning, where one feels oneself subject to the opposite pairs, such as those of *sukha* (pleasure) and *duḥkha* (pain), and so on.²⁶⁰

The first section of this chapter will explore the theological implications of one's obtaining *śraddhā*,²⁶¹ as discussed in the *Gītā*, and explain why the idea of *dharma* is differently apprehended by the different groups, as shown in the *Mahābhārata*.²⁶²

²⁶⁰ Once the cause of all manifestation is *Brahman*, and once *ātman* in everyone is the *kṣetra-jñā*, the discipline to be imparted by Kṛṣṇa to Arjuna could not be other than that which explains the *Īśvara* as the inner ruler everywhere. As his representative, Kṛṣṇa himself is led to explain the circumstances in which he was sent to restore righteousness, teaching how one should do what is necessary for the fulfilment of general welfare. This sacred knowledge (*jñāna*), then, helps one to develop the will (*icchā, bhakti*) for the necessary action (*karma*), which, even when it is about to be performed, already reveals the renewed *śraddhā* of the disciple. So, Arjuna's initial lack of willpower is related to his attachment to the objects of desire, or *kāma*. For, everyone, in accordance to one's own *svarūpa* (material form), is more or less subject to the influence of one's lower nature. That is why Kṛṣṇa explains through the concept of *śraddhā* in chapter 17, on the one side, the connection that exists between the higher nature and the *guṇa sattva*, and on the other side, the connection between the lower nature and the other two *guṇas* – with *śraddhā*, then, being *sattvic*, *rajasic*, or *tamasic*, in accordance with one's habits, customs, desires, and aims.

²⁶¹ Once Arjuna regains his *śraddhā*, he becomes able to master his own emotional nature as well as to act properly in the world of actions. In the *Gītā*, the secret of *dharma* is that spirit and matter, *ātman* and *prakṛti*, are the two aspects of the Godhead. *Saṃnyāsa*, therefore, is to be understood in terms of the perfect fulfilment of every single righteous deed, no matter how difficult or painful one may consider its realization. *Saṃnyāsa* and *śraddhā*, then, in the *Gītā*, are in intimate relation, as Arjuna, having recovered his *śraddhā*, is supposed to act out of an attitude of *saṃnyāsa*. Having overcome his initial *kāṛpanya* (from *kṛpaṇa*, misery) *doṣa* (fault) (BhG 2.7), or the evil egocentrism, Arjuna recovers his trust in the true *dharma*. It was due to this *kāṛpanya doṣa* that Arjuna had lost sight of *dharma* and of what he should do so as to follow in the path towards liberation. As he recovers his *śraddhā*, he understands the necessity of that whole process, which represents that aspect of the nature of *Brahman*, which encompasses all creatures – no matter how good or evil they are.

²⁶² *Dharma* is subtle and sometimes it seems to be even opposed to the *Veda*. This is made clear in the *Ādiparvan*, in the passage MBh 13.195.27-31. There the father of Draupadī defines that polyandrous

Furthermore, the first section will make it clear that if there is a truth which is explained by Kṛṣṇa himself throughout the whole *Anu-Gītā*, it concerns the view of the *Gītā* as an allegory²⁶³ of the human soul, which explores effective concrete valuation of the act-performing consciousness, and offers a reflection on the Vedic and *Upaniṣadic* moral values of the *Mahābhārata*. For, whereas in the *Gītā* Kṛṣṇa praises Arjuna, and shows him that the different *darśanas* of the different faiths (BhG 9.20-6, BhG 11.10) only deal with partial aspects of *samadarśana* (BhG 6.29-30) – or the synthetic science of the *dharmātmā* (BhG 9.31), or of the *Puruṣottama* (BhG 11.52, BhG 13.11, BhG 15.18, and so on) –, in the *Anu-Gītā*, Kṛṣṇa criticizes Arjuna, and shows him that the full meaning of *dharma* fades along with one’s losing one’s *śraddhā* (MBh 14.46-51).²⁶⁴ The passage below from the *Anu-Gītā* helps us to see how the *Mahābhārata* considers it difficult to apprehend the concept of *dharma*, despite Kṛṣṇa’s teachings in the *Gītā*:

marriage as *adharmā*, but Yudhiṣṭhira defends his mother’s commandment to marry Draupadī, arguing that *dharma* is subtle, difficult to grasp.

²⁶³ Such an allegorical approach, though, does not necessarily mean that the characteres are not truly humans, as Biardeau has expressed. See Madeleine Biardeau, “Études de Mythologie Hindoue, II,” *Bulletin de l’Ecole Française de l’Extrême-Orient* 55 (1969), 97-8. For a detailed account of her position, see also J. A. B. van Buitenen, introductory section “On Myth and Epic” in *The Book of Virata and the Book of Effort*, transl. J. A. B. van Buitenen, *The Mahābhārata* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1978), 142-184. When discussing the levels of criticism, van Buitenen denounces some holistic interpretations of the mythological content of the *Mahābhārata*. He refers to Madeleine Biardeau as someone who has forgotten the historical dimension of the text (142). His literate but also demythologized academic approach cannot account for the poetic and imaginative world which also is said to constitute ‘reality’. I hope the reader will appreciate my attempt in this section to make use of Mikhail Bakhtin, instead of van Buitenen, to account for the allegorical characterization of the plot in terms of the interplay of *ahaṅkāra* and *ātman*. For, Bakhtin’s typification, rather than being distracting, helps one to understand better Biardeau’s attempts to address the “domestic side of Bhīṣma,” the “imagery of Arjuna on his philandering or heroic wanderings,” and also “Karna’s emotional love for his foster-parents,” and “Dhṛtarāṣṭra’s indecisions” – all important issues, and which frame the different sections of this chapter.

²⁶⁴ The *Anu-Gītā*, properly speaking, forms the chapters 16 to 51 of the Book of the Horse Sacrifice, or *Aśvamedha-parvan* (Book 14 of the *Mahābhārata*). I am using the CE of the *Mahābhārata*, and the Vulgate English translation of Pratap Chandra Roy, *The Mahābhārata of Krishna-Dwaipayana Vyāsa* (Calcutta: Oriental Publishing, 1883-96), Vol. 12, 25-101. I have also made some use of the *Anu-Gītā*’s first English translation, which appears in Max Müller’s series *The Sacred Books of the East* (1882).

The diverse modes of duty we [the *Rṣis*] see, as contradictory. . . . Some say that everything is doubtful. Others have no doubts. Some say that the eternal (principle) is not eternal. Some say that it exists, and some that it exists not. . . . Some applaud action; others applaud perfect tranquility. . . . Some say that knowledge and renunciation (should be followed). . . . We, therefore, wish, O best of all beings, to know what is good. . . .

“—‘Brahmana said, — Well then, I shall declare to you what you ask. . . . The Nature is manifest; while Purusha is said to be unmanifest. . . . Above egoism is understanding. Above understanding is the soul. Above the soul is the Unmanifest. Above the Unmanifest is Purusha. . . . One who knows which is superior and inferior among existent creatures, who is conversant with the ordinances in respect of all acts, and who constitutes himself the soul of all creatures, attain to the Unfading Soul.’” (Roy, 93-7)

The passage clearly tries to recover the message of the *Gītā* by indirect means.

Furthermore, it exemplifies the presence of a *polyphonic perception*.²⁶⁵

The second section of this chapter will explore the results of the first section to show that, besides the narrative element, metaphysics, understood as a complex of philosophical and mythological elements, together with ritual theory frame the structure of the text of the *Mahābhārata*. For, despite all criticism that the synthetic view suffered from scholars such as van Buitenen,²⁶⁶ one cannot disregard the fact that the

²⁶⁵ I will address the different voices that speak in the *Mahābhārata* having in mind how Bhaktin has addressed the writings of Dostoevsky. In the *Anu-Gītā* Kṛṣṇa cannot speak so directly as in the *Gītā*, because Arjuna is now in a different state of mind. The *Anu-Gītā* represents a measure of how Kṛṣṇa’s teachings on *ātma-dharma* had been only partially assimilated by Arjuna, despite all his initial determination. Such a post-war evaluation of Arjuna’s performance in terms of his *śraddhā* is essential to understand how the first section of this chapter will relate the *Gītā* to the *Mahābhārata*. Because Arjuna, the best disciple, had failed to hold a steady understanding of *ātma-dharma*, memory of it was to be recovered indirectly, through tales about *ātman*, and not directly through *ātmic* insights anymore, as in the *Gītā*. Kṛṣṇa now has to give voice to ancient tales (*purātana itihāsa*) that recast his teachings in accordance to the post-war mood, which also signals his own departure (perhaps also a symbol for Arjuna’s losing a bit of his *ātmic* insights). Kṛṣṇa’s departure, then, which by the moment of the *Anu-Gītā* is about to happen, symbolizes Arjuna’s distancing from his past experience with the transcendent. For, Arjuna’s *śraddhā* fades away, and he acknowledges to Kṛṣṇa that he cannot recollect most of their previous dialogue on the nature of *dharma*.

²⁶⁶ See for instance his “The Mahābhārata Introduction” in *The Mahābhārata – 1. The Book of Beginning*, trans. J. A. B. van Buitenen (Chicago: University of Chicago Press), where he criticises the synthetic view

Mahābhārata is, indeed, more than a simple chaotic mess. It does possess an underlying unity. All the main characters face the same set of ethical dilemmas and act passionately against the background of some metaphysical questions about the understanding of reality. This point also can be hinted at through the text of the *Anu-Gītā*. There Kṛṣṇa displays a partial disappointment with Arjuna’s residual condition as an *aśraddadhāna* – he refers to Arjuna’s state using this key-word, which has been generally translated as ‘devoid of faith’ (MBh 14.16.10).²⁶⁷ Such a translation, obviously, makes it difficult to evaluate properly the ritual issues around death and dying, issues which connect the *Gītā* to the *Anu-Gītā* and to the *Mahābhārata* as whole.

of Joseph Dahlmann (xxxi-xxxiii). Van Buitenen reminds us that the philological investigation into the *Mahābhārata* began with the studies in latin of Franz Bopp (1791-1867), who incidentally introduced the habit of starting Sanskrit studies with the Nala episode. Next, Adolf Holtzmann (around 1846) defends the thesis that the *Mahābhārata* was a reworking of an original in which the sympathy of the authors did not lie with the Pāṇḍavas but with their Kaurava opponents. His ideas were defended by Adolf Holtzmann in his *Das Mahābhārata und seine Theile* (1895). As a reaction to Holtzmann’s ‘erudite’ nonsense, Joseph Dahlmann published *Das Mahābhārata als Epos und Rechtsbuch* (1895). He refutes Holtzmann’s theory of different layers of composition making use of a synthetic view, where the Epic appeared entirely in its unity, forming an organic and moralistic message. Van Buitenen disregards his synthetic view arguing, “It is a bit like arguing that *The Iliad*, the Gospels, and the Church fathers form one contemporaneous text” (xxxiii). And he concludes:

This theory was received with utter disbelief; for indeed a cursory reading cannot help but reveal that certain portions are far older than others, breathe a completely different spirit, have contrasting syntactic and stylistic devices, while countless contradictions can be pointed out that are incompatible with the notion of a unified work. The great Sanskritist Hermann Oldenberg dismisses this whole theory in one sentence: there is no point in reasoning the unreasonable. (xxxiii)

As we have argued throughout this thesis, for the purpose of showing the centrality of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* and in the *Mahābhārata*, van Buitenen’s quarrel becomes irrelevant. For, later accretions, if any, would become a problem only if they jeopardized the use of the term *śraddhā* as we have it in the present understanding of the text.

²⁶⁷ The *Anu-Gītā* reinforces the argument that the *Gītā* is not in particular either *Vedānta*, or *Sāṃkhya*, *Tantra*, and the like. With Kṛṣṇa making use of ancient tales to exemplify the discussions of the *Gītā*, the *Anu-Gītā* leaves no room even for *bhakti* – the term or its cognates are hardly found there. If the *Gītā* represents a *Upaniṣadic* tale, the *Anu-Gītā* is more a *Vedic*, or *Brāhmaṇic-like* tale. Leaving aside the philological question whether the *Anu-Gītā* is ‘a later interpolation’ or not, what is important is that, coming after both the *śrāddha* rites of Bhīṣma and the performance of the *Aśvamedha*, or horse-sacrifice, the *Anu-Gītā* brings back the issue of the *Gītā* as a text that neither disregards *karma-mārga*, nor stresses exclusive preference for any of the different paths.

Furthermore, by blaming Arjuna of being partially an *aśraddadhāna*, Kṛṣṇa is suggesting that Arjuna had failed in part in the discipline of *ātma-dharma*, remaining attached to his previous condition as a mere *kṣatriya*. Kṛṣṇa’s disappointment reveals that Arjuna was not able to digest completely his previous *ātmic* experiences, for he had failed to remain in that *ātmic* condition. Had he remained there he would have known the third way, the synthesis of the *Upaniṣadic* teaching on the inner life, and the *Vedic* teaching on the social and ritual life. That is to say, from a Bhaktinian perspective, the *Mahābhārata* undermines the view that *sanātana dharma* can be fully encompassed or expressed in a single human treatise or a doctrinal text – an idea that is reinforced by the *Gītā*, when it hints on the meaning of *ātma-dharma*, whose practice turns into one’s ability to manifest *śraddhā*, as we will see in the second section of this chapter.

The third section of this chapter will explore some gender and caste issues. Even though these issues are seldom the focus of sustained inquiry in the *Gītā*, they do play an important role in the *Mahābhārata* and indirectly in the *Gītā* as well. Kṛṣṇa does not address them directly in the *Gītā* because in his view they belong to our material nature, and as such they are part of what Kṛṣṇa named ‘*ahaṅkāra*’.²⁶⁸ However, conflicts of ‘interest’ or *ahaṅkāra* are governed by gender and caste bias, and understanding these biases is what the *Mahābhārata* is all about. On the other side, detachment and altruism are made possible through *śraddhā*, and this is what the *Gītā* is all about.

²⁶⁸ See, for instance, BhG 3.27; 7.4; 13.5; 16.18; 17.5; 18.53; 18.58, and 18.59.

In the *Gītā* Arjuna is slowly led to acknowledge Kṛṣṇa's contention that *svadharmā* is nothing but an instance of the eternal and universal *ātma-dharma*. For, Kṛṣṇa shows him that the concept of *dharma* involves these two sides, and one is not completely independent of the other: the first side appears in the form of 'Śruti', or the codified views of a tradition of ancient seers on gender and caste issues and related customs, and the second side appears as an actual experience, or revelation, of *ātman*, which is ethical in nature and related to the inner understanding of what leads to salvation (BhG 2.42-6). Arjuna comes to understand that from a superficial reading of Śruti it is possible to argue that the path of *jñāna* is in opposition to the path of action, but from the viewpoint of *ātman* this is not so. Even the *Vedic varṇa-dharma* becomes in experience interpreted as *svadharmā*. It is initially expressed as the duty of kings (*rājan*), the duty of subjects (*prajā*), the duty pertaining to a family (*kula*), caste (*jāti*), social class (*varṇa*), and so on, and the *Upaniṣadic mokṣa-dharma* can appear as a universal that overrides these duties, but in the perspective of *ātman* they constitute a single path. These two paths become one and the same within the understanding of *ātman*. This understanding is experienced as *śraddhā* (BhG 17.2-3) – which is both an expression of the *Upaniṣadic vairāgya* (BhG 18.52), and an expression of the *Vedic* notion of activity in terms of *niṣkāmakarma* (BhG 18.53).

The closing section of this chapter will explore the fact that at the end of the *Gītā* all *dharmas* are reconciled. That is to say, *śraddhā* becomes the key element for redefining previous concepts and, as a consequence, for solving moral dilemmas. BhG

18.66²⁶⁹ implies that old pairs of concepts such as, *karma mārṅa* and *jñāna mārṅa*, *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti*, *saṁnyāsa* and *tyāga*, and so on, are to be reinterpreted and expressed in terms of the attitude of *niṣkāmakarma* and *vairāgya*.²⁷⁰

We will explore how the *Gītā* treats *orthopraxis* as a matter of an ethical choice, rather than as a matter of a simple moral decision based on fear of becoming a sinner. The main hypotheses can be easily reduced to seven verses where Kṛṣṇa diagnoses Arjuna’s state of depression and distrust (*aśraddadhāna*), and prescribes *orthopraxis* (*niṣkāmakarmayoga*) as a means to salvation. Three verses appear in chapter 2, when Kṛṣṇa denounces Arjuna’s depressing idea of the individual as a completely independent entity, and four verses are in chapter 18 – three in which Kṛṣṇa restates his diagnosis and prescription for Arjuna, praising *ātman* as that category by which the whole universe is said to exist and function,²⁷¹ and a fourth, BhG 18.66, which sums everything up. The diagnosis of Arjuna’s condition is described in BhG 2.2, where Kṛṣṇa describes Arjuna in a state of confusion; in BhG 2.3, where Kṛṣṇa denounces Arjuna’s inability to shake off

²⁶⁹ BG 18.66: Overcoming all *dharmas*, take refuge on Me [*ātman*] alone. I [*ātman*, as *Īśvara*,] can cause you [*jīva*] to be released (*mokṣa*) from all evils; do not grieve.

²⁷⁰ One may say that Kṛṣṇa’s counsel in the *Gītā* is meant to awaken Arjuna’s *śraddhā* through the understanding that all is born of the nature of *Brahman*, with everything being, as such, needful, and that, as a consequence, everything should be seen as part of *Brahman*. The discussion about the *Praṇava* (from *pra-ṇu*, to sound, to reverberate) OM (see BhG 7.8, BhG 7.23-4, BhG 8.13, BhG 9.17, and also chapter 11 as whole, where the *Praṇava* is related to the concept of *praṇamya* (*pra-nam*, to bow) conveys this idea that all the cosmos is evolved out of *Brahman*, through the appearance of the twenty-four evolutes of *prakṛti*.

²⁷¹ One could say that the *Gītā*’s *orthopraxis* somehow resembles the Buddhist *heteropraxis* of the eightfold path, with the differences between the Buddha’s and Kṛṣṇa teachings representing mostly the different audiences they have addressed and their respective ‘*doxas*’ – the first addressing the orthodoxy of the *āstikyas*, and the second, the heterodoxy of the *nāstikyas*. The Buddhist eightfold path is usually classified under three main headings: *panna* or wisdom (1. right view; 2. right understanding), *silā* or moral activity (3. right speech; 4. right action, and 5. right livelihood), and *samādhi* or contemplation (6. right effort; 7. mindfulness, and 8. right concentration). Curiously, these three headings remind us respectively of those under which we classify the paths of the *Gītā*: *jñāna yoga*, *karma yoga*, and *bhakti yoga*.

his weakness of heart, and in BhG 2.11, where Kṛṣṇa describes Arjuna, his devotee (*bhakta*), as someone who, despite his knowledge (*jñāna*), is confused.²⁷² Arjuna has some knowledge (*jñāna*) and some devotion (*bhakti*), but he is confused and impotent. Kṛṣṇa’s diagnosis points to the fact that Arjuna is failing to act (*karma*) because of his lack of *śraddhā*. The prescription is synthesised in BhG 18.61, where Kṛṣṇa says that God abides in the heart of every being; in BhG 18.62, where Kṛṣṇa says that Arjuna should cultivate with his whole being that state of mind where he would never lose sight again of the immanence and transcendence of the Lord (*Īśvara*) who abides in the heart, and BhG 18.64, where Arjuna is told about his close connection to the Lord and His supreme secrets.²⁷³ Summing up, the sole verse BhG 18.66 represents the diagnosis and prescription presented in this group of seven verses, which, in a sense, synthesizes the whole message of the *Gñā*. For, the *jñānadīpa* (lamp of wisdom) called *ātman*, being present in everyone, though differently obfuscated by *ahaṁkāra*’s *triguṇic prakṛti* (nature), necessarily leads to the notion of humans as a brotherhood, where the *triguṇic* notions of gender, caste, and so on, gradually lose their apparent importance – the main

²⁷² BG 2.2: Whence has this dejection befallen you in this dangerous moment? O Arjuna! this is not acceptable in a noble person. It does not lead to heaven; it only causes disgrace. BG 2.3: Do not be weak [coward], O Son of Pritha! This does not suit you. Shake off this paltry faint-heartedness! Stand up! O Scorcher of the Opponent. BG 2.11: You grieve for those that should not be grieved for, yet you speak words of wisdom [words that sound wise but miss the deeper sense of wisdom]. The wise grieve neither for the living nor for the dead.

²⁷³ The three verses synthesizing this argument that the Lord abides in the heart of humans, which also represents Arjuna’s understanding, beyond his comrade Kṛṣṇa, of God’s immanence and transcendence, are: BG 18.61: The *Īśvara* (we could say ‘The Lord,’ as long as we remember that *Īśvara* is beyond gender distinctions: ‘he’ is not a stereotyped old male) abides in the heart of all beings, O Arjuna, causing them to live by Its (his? her?) own power, as if they were material machines. BG 18.62: O Descendent of Bharata, with your whole being, go to It (*Īśvara*, the Inner Ruler) alone for refuge. From that clarity (*Īśvara*’s light, rather than ‘grace’), you shall attain supreme peace, and the eternal realm. BG 18.64: Hear again my Supreme word, most secret of all, which I will disclose for your benefit, once you are surely loved by me.

proof of this being Saṁjaya’s privileged role, itself, when compared to that of the blind king.²⁷⁴ For, Saṁjaya’s broadcast to the blind king of the dialogue between Kṛṣṇa and Arjuna represents the first narration of that teaching – Kṛṣṇa’s *ātma-dharma* – meant for solving moral dilemmas.

As we will see in the next sections, therefore, it is due to passion that one remains like the blind king – impotent to recognize the need for *vairāgya* (or the capacity to withdraw from the influence of the *triguṇas*) and *niṣkāmakarma* (or self-control in the performance of one’s deeds). Arjuna, however, differently from the blind king, realizes that spiritual progress means the nurturing of the unifying light of *jñāna* and *karma*, through working without self (-ish) interest (*svārtha*), and with a universalistic attitude (*sarvārtha*) of whole-hearted devotion to the cause of humanity at large. Through *ātma-dharma* Arjuna became able both to fulfill and overcome *dharma* as *varṇāśrama* (caste and stage of life), because he was able to perform the duties of a *kṣatriya* as if he were not performing them at all. This synthesis between doing and not doing proposed in the

²⁷⁴ The low caste Saṁjaya is portrayed in the *Gṛh̄* and the *Mahābhārata* as a highly skilled authority on matters of *dharma*. He lectures the king on kingly matters; he represents the eyes that show the way for the blind king. He functions as an advisor to the king as much as Kṛṣṇa for Arjuna. The difference is that Arjuna praises and honours his master, whereas the blind king, instead of blessing his charioteer, keeps reminding him of his lower social condition. As for the *Mahābhārata* as a whole, the simple fact that Saṁjaya lectures the king and develops divine vision represents an inversion of values and a critique to the caste system. The *Mahābhārata* and the *Gṛh̄*, therefore, champion and pioneer the extolling of honesty and hard work, investing against sloth, corruption, and caste-based privileges. The only similar Western equivalent of such a critique of one’s own tradition is perhaps Hesiod’s *Work and Days*, a text which, like the *Mahābhārata*, talks about a golden age of justice prior to the time of the Trojan war, an age which is compared to that of the *kali-yuga*. Curiously, as in the case of Saṁjaya, Hesiod also presents himself as a humble person, in his case, a simple peasant farmer from Boeotia. In *Works and Days* Hesiod speaks about justice and righteous work. He complains about his brother’s dishonesty and gives advice for living an honest life. By telling his brother Perses to listen to the deity Justice, and by bringing a version of the Prometheus myth to explain why work is man’s lot, he also ties together work and religion. Central to his thesis is the critique of the bribe-swallowing kings. As there was no Bible at that time to organize worship and educate the young, the Greeks used to use Homer and Hesiod’s texts to do so.

Gītā represented the bringing together of what in the framework of the *Mahābhārata* appears torn apart. This involves Kṛṣṇa’s explanation, first, of that which the *Upaniṣads* refer to as “not this, not this,” or *ātman*, and second, of that which the *Vedas* use to refer to as real, or the manifested world, seen as an evolved form of *prakṛti*.

Being part of the main plot of the *Mahābhārata*, the *Gītā* deals with the philosophical enquiry underlying the epic presentation on ethical *praxis*. It attempts to prevent further tyranny in the political domain, as well as the tyranny of those attached to any of the many different kinds of scriptural orthodoxies and heterodoxies. Karna, for instance, solves his dilemma on how to act by choosing to nurture his ego (*ahaṃkāra*) instead of the natural talents of his soul (*ātman*). Blind to Kṛṣṇa’s admonitions, he allows his actions to work for the interests of the wicked *Kauravas*. Arjuna, on the contrary, accepts Kṛṣṇa’s advice, and gives preference to the cultivation of the *ātmic* discipline, putting his sword at the service of justice. Arjuna displays the highest *śraddhā*; Karna, as we will see, nothing but selfish blind faith and stubbornness.

If the *Mahābhārata* demonstrates Arjuna’s *pravṛtti*, or ability in heroic *Kṣatriya* deeds, the *Gītā* demonstrates his inner process of *nivṛtti*, or the return to *ātman* through the overcoming of *ahaṃkāra*’s demands. As understood in the *Gītā*, then, *nivṛtti* and *pravṛtti* are the two inherent aspects of every single action, with the former understanding of non-action being replaced by the idea of inner action, or the proper attitude of detachment in every single external action. Arjuna’s submission to *ātman* in the *Gītā* frees him to act. Shifting then to the larger story these external actions can now be

performed in the context of the *Mahābhārata* without being stained by selfish motives, rooted in *ahaṅkāra*. By bringing his spiritual inner discipline into line with his external place in society, he develops the necessary *śraddhā* to act relying upon the guidance of the divine in himself. Arjuna, the warrior in the *pravṛtti*, or external process, and Arjuna, the disciple seeking spiritual instruction in the *nivṛtti* path, are made one in the *Gītā* through the *yogic* discipline of the realization of *ātman* taught by Kṛṣṇa.

It is in this sense, as this chapter will show, that the *Gītā* appears inside the traditional discussions of the *Mahābhārata* as a new and original Scripture. For, the *Gītā* represents Kṛṣṇa's attempt to deal with *karma* and *jñāna*, and to resolve the fallacious question 'which one comes first – orthodoxy or orthopraxis?', a problem later posed in Western religious debates.²⁷⁵ In a sense, what the *Gītā* shows is that orthodoxy leads to *orthopraxis*; *orthopraxis* to renewed orthodoxy, and so on, in a chain of events without end or beginning. And that is why the meaning of the term '*śraddhā*' cannot match either 'faith', or 'religion',²⁷⁶ leaving the question about whether *orthopraxis* or orthodoxy is given priority irrelevant and misleading. *Sattvic śraddhā* is what allows one to avoid this regression ad infinitum, and to have a glimpse behind both faith and practice. The *Gītā*

²⁷⁵ Inside Judaism, for instance, *orthopraxis* is perhaps what allows the Jews to retain their cultural identity, as this attitude of altruism gains precedence over belief, allowing even atheists to remain, in a sense, as Jews. The same, of course, was true of India as the West discovered it. The Christian tendency to equate the terms 'faith' with 'religion' represents a different option where dogma and orthodoxy are more central.

²⁷⁶ The unconditional freethinking which is characteristic of the attitude of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* is opposed to the dogmatic 'Book'-conditionality of the *fides*, or faith. Faith is conditioned by belief. St. Anselm's *fides quaerens intellectum*, which defines how 'faith' is conditioned by 'belief', therefore, helps us to see why 'faith' is a bad translation for *śraddhā* in the *Gītā*. For, Wittgensteinian fideism reveals the fallacy involved in hindering freethinking, and ends the quarrel about the phrase *fides quaerens intellectum* (the passive acceptance of the dogmas of 'faith' – which supposedly constitute the final truths of humankind – as a pre-requirement to knowledge and self-understanding), which postulates the priority of orthodoxy over everything else.

demonstrates Arjuna’s capacity to put into practice *ātmic* truth, whatever his former *śāstric* views.

Having explained the structure and purposes of the present chapter, let us move to its first section, where the idea is to make use of Bakhtin’s findings to read the *Gītā* into the *Mahābhārata*.

V.1. A Polyphonic Perception

As we have already mentioned, in the *Anu-Gītā* Kṛṣṇa is unable to help Arjuna recall the full extent of their previous dialogue, and has to evoke Brahmanical tales to recast their dialogue. The *Anu-Gītā* legitimates, therefore, the view that the *Gītā* describes, not a system, but a unique and concrete situation, a never-to-be-repeated reality. This fact alone works as an invitation to evaluate the text in terms of Bakhtin’s²⁷⁷ definition of polyphony and philosophy of action. For, as we have seen, the *Gītā* can be explored in terms of its philosophy of the act, where concepts such as *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti*,²⁷⁸ are re-evaluated and redefined. Furthermore, the evaluation of the characters of the *Mahābhārata* allow us to use the category of polyphony to describe the text in Bakhtian terms.

²⁷⁷ See Mikhail Bakhtin’s *Toward a Philosophy of the Act* (Austin: University of Texas Press, 1993). His ideas, applied to the literary field have led to the development of the concept of polyphony – or that which deals with the effect of two or more concurrent and harmonizing parts, where the different voices appear with the same authority, leaving no space for a central ideology.

²⁷⁸ Kṛṣṇa’s understanding of these two paths of forth-going (*pravṛtti*) and return (*nivṛtti*) is that although they seem to be separate and opposite, representing ‘the paths of action’ and that of ‘non-action’, they constitute in reality the two aspects of that one path based on *ātman* that he is presenting to Arjuna.

The distinguishing feature of the whole text of the *Mahābhārata* is the fact that it gives equal voice to the *Pāṇḍavas* and *Kauravas*, without trying to label one group right or wrong in absolute terms. Its realism allows Bhīṣma to be of as much value as any of the best *Pāṇḍavas*, despite their acute antagonism. That is to say, the *Mahābhārata* represents an active conscience, one which refuses to be reduced to a single viewpoint, or a truly final position. Representating what life is at its most concrete, the epic gives every character the opportunity to reflect on different ideas and perspectives. This means that the text places the characters above the author's treatment of them. For the author does not shape the heroes, rather he describes how they make heroes out of themselves. They live in an eternal present which refuses to be encapsulated or determined by the past of each character. These qualities give the *Mahābhārata* its appeal. For its dialogues seem to be permanently pointing toward the immediate future, with the different heroes, among whom the author himself plays an important role, disputing different views on *dharma*. Those different views on *dharma* come to a climax in the *Gītā*'s evaluation of human activity as a kind of philosophy of action.

The dialogue of the *Gītā* gives rise to a phenomenology of conscience where different modes of thinking are laid out. The text makes use of myths and customary values to reveal the different aspects of the human psyche that play themselves out in the field of moral philosophy. The epic showcases a concrete field called *Kurukṣetra*, where the philosophy of action is given a scenario scene against which to develop itself. The *Gītā*'s abstract discussions take place in the field of values, *Dharmakṣetra*. The polyphony of the *Mahābhārata* gain from the *Gītā* the defining categories for laying out

its philosophy of action. *Śraddhā* emerges as the truly central category that can never be reduced to an abstraction.

Perhaps because language exists on that border-zone between the consciousness of a self which is other than oneself, and because the *Gṇā* is an expression of such a border-zone dialogue, meaning, then, comes out of the text as a living communication within a concrete reality. Though historically and socially determined by a certain kind of spiritual ideology related to *ātman* and the freeing of humans from the hierarchically perceived *saṃsāra*,²⁷⁹ defined by the *Vedic* myth of four castes, the dialogue also describes our self overcoming through *śraddhā*. Bakhtin’s philosophy of the act helps us, then, to explore the *Gṇā* in terms of topics such as ‘self and other’, ‘moral discourse’, and ‘multiple voices’. His distinction between the world as experienced in action, and the world as represented in discourse, raises questions about the nature of the symbolic,²⁸⁰ and invites us to consider the allegories of the *Gṇā* in their relation to *śraddhā*.

²⁷⁹ Bakhtin, of course, does not know this language of the *Gṇā*, which is completely outside the Kantian framework. Yet, he aimed to overcome the common contraposition of eternal truth and our temporality as Arjuna did: through a return into oneself, when seeing comes from inside one’s own essence – even when such a completely pure empathizing is impossible (16). In Bakhtin’s own words, “in self-renunciation” I actualize with utmost activeness and in full the uniqueness of my place in Being.” On Western grounds, then, Arjuna’s *saṃnyāsa* actualizes with utmost activeness his relation to *ātman*, the origin of ‘participative consciousness’ based on a non-alibi in being. For, none would doubt, the *Gṇā* deals with some instances of that principle which in Bakhtin appears as a refined version of the golden rule. The *Gṇā*, representing a concrete situation asking actions and taking decisions, fits nicely in Bakhtin’s system, where there is no place for Kantian abstractions.

²⁸⁰ In my experience with ancient Indian thought, I have noticed the pedagogical importance Indians assign to arranging knowledge geometrically, through the symbolic association of figures and numbers to a plot, to its framing, or even to the main chapters of a piece as a whole. Six pointed stars, for instance, have been found in cosmological diagrams in Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism, proving this symbol possesses deep significance in ritual worship and theology. In the case of the *Mahābhārata* as well as of the *Gṇā*, scholars have been puzzled with their geometric arrangement around the symbolic number eighteen, which represents also the total number of *Purāṇas*. In the *Mahābhārata*, there are eighteen books, eighteen armies (Yudhiṣṭhira is joined by seven, while eleven join Duryodhana), eighteen days of battle, and eighteen also are the number of chapters of the *Bhagavadgṇā*. Many sages explain, then, that the two topics of the

We have already mentioned, for instance, how Arjuna was shown by Kṛṣṇa, among the many forms of the divine, that of the *Vedic* deity Rudra (BhG 11.6), the destroyer (*kṣa*) who raises one’s strength in the performance of the ritual. In Bakhtian terms, myths are carriers of meaning that come into being on that inter-individual

Mahābhārata, as well as of the *Gītā*, are *Brahman* (the transcendent) and *adhikārin* (the aspirant), geometrically symbolized by the ancient Indian hexagram— where one of two interwoven equilateral triangles represents Nara; the other, Nārāyaṇa, and their union, release from *saṃsāra*. From the intersection of both triangles, arises, then, six small triangles, with each of the total of 18 sides representing a specific topic, perhaps arranged somehow according to the following logic: The means for the *adhikāri*’s processes of *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti* is through the *saṃsāra*, according to the three *guṇas*, summing up, then, six possibilities – three in each process. The *adhikāri*’s goal is also achieved through six modes of functioning, according to these two modes in which the three faculties of activity, will, and understanding work. With respect to the relation to Brahman, there are also the three primary elements of *sattva*, *rajas*, and *tamas* in both processes, summing up, then, the last six possibilities.

Symbols and allegories, then, constitute an essential part of the religious pedagogy of India, and it is hard to understand Western scholars’ fear of acknowledging them as representing in a nutshell a whole philosophy. For, when a Western scholar acknowledges them, it is to dismiss their author, as it happened, for instance, with Bishop Leadbeater, while he was publishing in the 1920s in *The Theosophist*. His critique of Western scholars’ incompetence in dealing with symbolism, as used in oriental religions in the form of allegories with many layers of meaning, is not completely out of place. The problem with Westerners is that they fear allegory in the interpretation of Scripture, arguing that it represents a bad hermeneutical method. This is exemplified first in the writings of Emanuel Swedenborg, especially in *The True Christian Religion* (1771). So, when it comes to the Theosophists, we have to remember also how much missionaries feared and disliked them, disapproving whatever they proposed. It was only in the end of the period from 1879 to 1883, in which Madame Blavatsky and Colonel Olcott were left with no alternative but to leave an unfriendly New York for Bombay, and then to Adyar (Madras), that they finally announced in “The Theosophist” (August, 1883), 265, that they were about to expound the esoteric meaning behind the text of the *Bhagavad Gītā*. The method of allegorical interpretation developed by Blavatsky and Subba Rao was taken first by W. Q. Judge, who, even after Blavatsky death (1891), continued publishing a series of articles on the *Gītā* (1887-1895). According to him the *Gītā* brings a poetical allegory of the inner struggle going on in human nature, with the *dramatis personae* of the *Gītā* representing human characteristics. I have already brought up this point when discussing Sharpe’s “Western Images of the Bhagavadgita, 1885-1985” (JSAL 23, 2 (1991): 47-57). Dhṛtarāṣṭra is *ahaṅkāra*; Arjuna is the *jīva* fighting a battle inside the body, and Kṛṣṇa is the charioteer of the body – *ātman*, the higher and real self. As we all are constituted with these three categories (*ahaṅkāra*, *jīva*, and *ātman*), the reading of the *Gītā* is supposed to expose us, face to face, with ourselves. For, while the *Mahābhārata* describes the phenomenological (*saṃsāric*) field (*kṣetra*), the *Gītā* presents the ontological (*ātmic*) knower of the field (*kṣetrajñā*). Then in every *jīva* rages this threefold battle of 18 yugas (periods): first, the *jīva* overcomes ancestral religious authority (the ancestor Bhīṣma is defeated on the 10th day), and reaches a direct contact with the divine (as shown in the 11th chapter of the *Gītā*); second, the *jīva* overcomes personal religious authority (the teacher Droṇa is defeated on the 15th day), and learns to discriminate by itself the differences between devil and divine (as shown in the 16th chapter of the *Gītā*); third, the *jīva* overcomes self-interest (the brother Karṇa is defeated on the 17th day and Duryodhana on the 18th), and ascends in the path of *saṅgyāsa* and *tyāga* (as shown in the 18th chapter of the *Gītā*), which leads to the state of a *jīvātman*.

territory where social-political interactions happen. Individual consciousness evolves through these mythological signs, which convey both a continuity and discontinuity of meaning, as ideological groups fight for hegemony. In the case of the *Gītā*, this fight is fought in the *Kurukṣetra*, around the concept of *dharma*. So, one can ask in Bakhtian terms, how can this concept of *dharma*, which in itself is transcendental and independent of the experience of the senses, relate to the subjective and unique time-space condition? How does the uniqueness of each time-space condition frame the character of each single action? Put in other words, how is the particular *jīva* (concrete living being), named Arjuna, supposed to relate to other *jīvas*, and reach that uniqueness of being which is the universal *ātman*? How is *ātman* being presented as the only real basis for any ethical action? How is the synthesis between sensibility and reason, as exemplified by Kṛṣṇa, possible?

The *Gītā*'s single answer seems to be that *dharma* relates to the uniqueness of one's experience of every single action through the ritual posture defined in terms of *śraddhā*. In other words, the *Gītā* stimulates the reflection over all of the above questions by suggesting *śraddhā* as the central mediating criteria. For, ultimately, *sattvic śraddhā* is nothing but an outcome of one's own *ātman*. That is why Kṛṣṇa's teaching of *Ātma-dharma* is contrasted with Arjuna's traditional sense of *kṣatriya-dharma*. For, when the act becomes a ritualistic deed and not a mere accident or product of social behavior, it is rooted in *ātman*. In Bakhtin's terms this dimension of the act is expressed as 'non-alibi in being' (*ne-alibi v bytii*) (1993, 42). The non-personal *ātman*, then, which is the cause of

Arjuna's transformation from non-active to active, is a model of perfection. On the other hand in the state of a *jīva* enslaved to *saṃsāra*, one has no awareness of the *ātmic* reality, which lies beyond all mortifying and flickering shadows.

An act 'taken without alibi' (*postupok*, the action intentionally performed) aims at freedom. It can be freedom from *saṃsāra* (the world of the performed act, Bakhtin's *mir postupka*), or freedom from Plato's Cave. For also in the *Gṛā* the body can be seen as the cave in which *ātman* remains hidden (BhG 13.21-3). If we recall that the *Gṛā*'s understanding of *ātman-dharma* transcends the *varṇāśrama* (caste and stage of life) *dharma*, then Bakhtin's notion of *the ought* (*dolzhensvovanie*) helps us recognize the way in which concepts such as *saṃnyāsa*, *pravṛtti*, and *nivṛtti* are defined in the *Gṛā*. Bakhtin says,

The irreproachable technical correctness of a performed act does not yet decide the matter of its moral value. Theoretical veridicality is technical or instrumental in relation to the ought. If the ought were a formal moment of a judgement, there would be no rupture between life and culture as creation, between act of judgement as a performed deed (a moment in the unity of the moment of my once-occurrent life) and the content/sense of a judgement (a moment in some objective theoretical unity of science), and this would mean that there would exist a unitary and unique context of both cognition and life, culture and life (which is not the case, of course). (4)

Similarly, in the *Gṛā*, Kṛṣṇa places the criteria for the moral evaluation not in the technical correctness of the action, but on its intention. Only a moral rupture in Arjuna's former understanding of *varṇāśrama dharma* duty as absolute respect to the ancestors allows him to go beyond his *kṣatriya dharma*, leading him to see that even the killing of beloved ancestors, could represent a duty of someone who is in charge of public affairs.

Arjuna has to shift from his old fashioned views on concepts such as *saṁnyāsa*, *pravṛtti*, and *nivṛtti*, in order to become able to make up his mind regarding the difficult task he was about to undertake. Put in Bakhtinian terms, the development of that awareness which is capable of developing one's *śraddhā*, means that one "will know what is marked by the moral ought and when" (6). The suggestion of the attitude of *śraddhā*, then, seems to be implied in Bakhtin's reference to "a certain attitude of consciousness," whose structure is to be disclosed. For in the *Gītā* Arjuna learns how to relate to the product of his actions, considering the unique context of life. *Saṁnyāsa*, then, is the answer that the *Gītā* provides for that practical orientation searched for by Bakhtin that fits within the theoretical world. For, being *ātman* oriented and not *ahaṁkāra* oriented, *saṁnyāsa* is what minimizes the danger of an 'absolute relativism'. The *Gītā*'s immediacy to experience provides an example of that knowledge, which, felt from within and rooted on reality, arises as *śraddhā*, and not as a cold theoretical system. Representing the consequence of a reflection on the relations between physical acts (*pravṛtti*) and those mental acts used to be seen as non-acting (*nivṛtti*, as sub-intended in the *Gītā*), *śraddhā* appears as that mediating function,²⁸¹ which Bakhtin had assigned to the relation between the order of signs and the order of things.

W.C. Smith when addressing the western use of the *rudrākṣa* (rosary), reopens the discussion about symbol and how it affects those engaged in religious activities. He soon

²⁸¹ This mediation is suggested also in the counting of beads of the rosary, as the *tatpuruṣa* compound *rudrākṣa*, 'the eye of Rudra' stands for a reminder of that polyphonic *praxis* through which one can achieve *śraddhā*. If nothing, the counting of beads is meant to allow us to develop our own soul force. For it emulates a kind of abstract feeling of trust in the ritual performance acknowledged even by the Christians who came to use the 'Hindu rosary' or '*rudrākṣa*', for counting their prayers.

realizes that ‘Hindu’ religious life can only be understood through analyzing the relations of the symbolic realm (1981, 23). Stating a kind of belief in a theological unity and coherence behind humankind’s religious history, he even sets forth a plan for attempting a demonstration of that coherence by speaking “theologically about the unity, the interrelation” that he can discern in the religious history (4). In doing so he finds himself “pushed to dropping the word ‘religion’ as a concrete term altogether, and also terms such as ‘Hinduism’ and ‘Christianity’” (4). He finds out that religions have something in common, but he does not quite know how to define it.

The ‘soul force’ which is responsible for putting love in action, even when acknowledged by some scholars as the essential part of the the religious phenomenon, is uncomfortably identified as a term coming out of a foreign scripture. Our preference, then, falls on a term such as ‘spirituality,’ which is used as a way to cut away the barriers among different ‘faiths’, and which now seems to be taking the place of what once we used to call ‘religion.’ It is with the help of this category ‘spirituality’ that we can draw together people with different expressions of faith, such as, Tolstoy, Thoreau, Emerson, Luther King, Gandhi, Joan of Arc, Socrates, Lao Tzu, The Buddha, and so on . . . In other words, the term ‘spirituality’ has brought people from different faiths closer, somehow acknowledging the fact that through many different faiths it is possible to manifest a sort of universal soul force, or religious fervour.

When one realizes that a term like ‘faith’ does not serve even the new Western demand for a more multicultural religious category, it is surprising that scholars would insist on translating *śraddhā* as ‘faith.’ The *Gītā* anticipates precisely this problem of

imposing an absolute sense on ‘faith’ or religious practice. What the *Gītā* shows is that anyone is able, subjectively, to ‘*experience with certitude*’ the transcendent *ātman* when they discover the highest forms of *śraddhā*. In conclusion, what the *Gītā* teaches is that no matter one’s dogma of faith, it is always possible to display through our deeds the universal soul force called *śraddhā*. For, when a sincere Christian, Hindu, Muslim, or even atheist, places their trust in that which transcends, what they all display is nothing but the *sattvic* or highest form of *śraddhā*. The next sections, besides considering *śraddhā* and the *Gītā* in the larger context of the *Mahābhārata*, will make this point clearer.

V.2. Death and Dying

Many voices speak in the *Mahābhārata*. Voices that tell us about human origins as well as about human essence. All starts with king Bharata, son of Śakuntalā and Duṣyanta. King Bharata gives preference to deeds over birth, and this fact frames the whole plot. Such a moral decision puts on check the idea of caste and privileges, and later, by the the time of the *Bhīṣmaparvan*, will trigger the final battle around the issue of moral duty. Because King Bharata does not know how to choose who should succeed him, he goes to Rṣi Kaṇva, who had brought Śakuntalā up. The Rṣi explains to him that he would know the answer only when he overcomes his egocentrism. Reentering the palace, the king makes up his mind. On the day of the official announcement, the Prime Minister reads the king’s speech. It starts by reminding all about the three duties of a

king – the protection of people, the promotion of justice, and the nomination of the successor. Because he could not find the first two qualities in his own sons he names a common citizen based on his deeds.

Śakuntalā's reaction is immediate. She blames him for depriving his sons of their rights. What kind of father could he possibly be? The King's answer is that he is not only a father; he is also a king. And as such, he should consider the whole kingdom to be his family. Generations go by fast in the *Mahābhārata*, and King Śantanu, the fourteenth descendent of Kuru, sets these values of Bharata aside, and once again birth gains preference over deeds. First, when he marries Gaṅgā, by whom he has the great Bhīṣma, King Śantanu places the future of Hastinapura in Ganga's hands, since he accepted her condition that he would never interfere, or question her decisions. As time will reveal, his marriage represents his stalking of the present for an unknown future, where he will become powerless even to stop his wife from drowning their sons. Later on he repeats a similar mistake, and marries Śatyavatī, by whom he has Citraṅgada and Vicitravīrya.

Speechless in front of the killings performed by Gaṅgā, he goes to a sage and hears from him that he had no right to give such a promise to Gaṅgā. For, such a word was nothing but a curse against his own kingdom. For a king who cannot protect his sons, how is he expected to protect his subjects? Even if as a king Śantanu was able to realize the nature of his injustice, as an individual he acknowledges that he cannot control his passions and egocentrism. And that was the reason why he had sought the sage's advice. The context makes it clear, however, that what he should know is that in the

search of a good wife he was supposed to look for three defining qualities: consciousness, inspiration, and compassion.

Śantanu is only capable of stopping Gaṅgā from killing their children by the time of the birth of their eighth son. They call the child Devavrata, who later will become known as Bhīṣma. Gaṅgā explains that she had not murdered the babies but had freed them from a curse dating back to the time she still lived with her father, the Lord Brahmā. Devavrata was a divine Vasu, who she said she failed to release from the curse. Because Śantanu had broken his word, she leaves him and takes with her their son. After Devavrata has grown, she brings him back to the king. She provided Devavrata with the best possible education, for she was aware of the tradition of choosing a king based on deeds, not birth.²⁸²

We cannot review here the many passages where the *Mahābhārata* anticipates, or prepares, for the *dharmic* unfolding of the *Bhīṣmaparvan*, but the passage how Devavrata becomes Bhīṣma will do for the purposes here established. This issue sends us to the circumstances around the second marriage of his father (MBh 1.94-6). The king had met Śatyavatī by the banks of the Yāmuna river, and immediately fell in love with her. However, her father, Daśaraja, would give his consent to their marriage only if Śantanu agreed that her son, rather than Bhīṣma, would ascend to the throne of Hastināpura. At

²⁸² Devavrata was ready to rule Hastināpura, the city founded by King Hastin. For, the virtuous doers, not the inheritors, are those who should always sit on the throne of Hastināpura. He had been instructed on the *Vedas* and on Politics by sages such as Paraśurāma, Vasiṣṭha and Bṛhaspati. From Paraśurāma, he is said to have learned that obeying one's father is the the only way to happiness. From Vasiṣṭha, that the Swan flies on two wings: the Wing of Knowledge and the Wing of Action. If it had only one wing, it would be of no use, flight would be impossible. And from Bṛhaspati, that when one decides to act, one should see the act to its completion or else the act would represent the end of oneself.

first the king refuses such an outrageous condition, for Devavrata, the most fit for the throne, had already been acclaimed the crown prince, and a good king would never disrespect such a decision. However, the king's state of sorrow makes Devavrata renounce his rights to the throne for the sake of his father's happiness. Furthermore, the smart Daśaraja reminds Devavrata that, even though he could speak for himself, he could not speak for his future offspring that could, at some point, make a claim for the throne. Devavrata, then, in order to fulfil Daśaraja demands, makes his terrible vow of remaining celibate and childless (MBh 1.94.85-90). His vow is said to be 'terrible', both because it represented a huge and scary display of willpower and detachment, and because it had been done for the wrong reasons.

That is how the Vasu born as the eighth son of Gaṅgā and Śantanu, which used to be called Devavrata (the one whose vow is divine), becomes Bhīṣma (the one of the terrible vow). Bhīṣma's non-reflected vow allows that birth takes priority over deeds once more. Bhīṣma had placed his father's happiness ahead of the interests of the people of Hastināpura.²⁸³ In a sense, he is the one responsible for the fact that a yet to be born blind child would get the rights to the throne. Yet, Bhīṣma is confident that through his

²⁸³ The 16 DVD Disc Set Mahabharat, produced and directed by B. R. Chopra and Ravi Chopra, gives us a nice account of how the king realizes that he was the cause of his son's misfortune: How could he forget that Devavrata had sacrificed his own happiness for the sake of his? His indulgences and lack of self-control had become not only the cause of his son's misfortune, but also of the uncertainties that the future had reserved for Hastināpura. The king tried to dissuade Bhīṣma from his oath by reminding him of the tradition that Worth not Birth should determine the heir to the throne. He asked Bhīṣma how to determine the Worth of an unconceived child, but Bhīṣma refuses to take his word back and remembers that the protection of the rights of his subjects was a kingly duty. He had the right to make such an oath, and it was the king's duty to respect it. At this moment Bhīṣma's value is acknowledged and he is granted the boon of choosing the day of his own death. Yet, his father's admonition caused him to become unsure about what he had just done. Bhīṣma goes to the Gaṅgā river to ask his mother if what he had done was right or wrong. He was told that, differently from his father, he could never do wrong, for he was born to do the right thing and lead by example.

oath and display of detachment he was doing the best: he would be bringing happiness to his father, and, as a consequence, to the whole kingdom.

Soon, however, his father died of disgust. Some years later, Śatyavatī loses her two sons. Then, in need of an heir, she asks her son of a previous relation, the sage Vyāsa, to produce children in her daughters in law and in a maid. And that is how Dhṛtarāṣṭra, Pāṇḍu, and Vidura were born. The three of them remained under the care of Bhīṣma, who had promised to remain alive for the time being to guarantee that, no matter who would be the new king, the kingdom would remain protected by him.

Moving on another couple of years, we get to the moment when, Devavrata, the great Bhīṣma, allows himself to be killed by Arjuna, his beloved nephew and son of Pāṇḍu. This brings us to the central point of the epic, which is the interplay between the realm of the psychological and the actual experiences around the idea of dying, and the symbolism of the death rites. For, the dilemmas of the *Mahābhārata* are mostly resolved in the rites of *śrāddha*, which eventually take one back to *śrāddhā*. In other words, the *Mahābhārata* is filled with transcendent images around death that help one to develop a symbolic understanding of fundamental truths which first reveal themselves in the form of *śrāddhā*.

If the pair Kṛṣṇa / Arjuna defines in the *Gītā* the arising of a new *dharma* which was indeed old, and if in the *Mahābhārata* as a whole the pair Kṛṣṇa / Bhīṣma can be said to define the different modes to be faithful to a true meaning of *dharma*, inside the *Bhīṣmaparvan* the divergences between the old and the new understanding of *dharma* is

represented by the clash in the battlefield of the pair Bhīṣma / Arjuna. The image of Bhīṣma's death is terrifying for Arjuna. Yet, besides being central to the whole episode, it favors Arjuna's developing of *śraddhā* for his later slaying of Bhīṣma – an image that reminds us of the trial of Job, as described in the Hebrew Tanakh.²⁸⁴

Arjuna is both the recipient of tradition, as represented by Bhīṣma, and also the recipient of Kṛṣṇa's new message. As a representative of the new generation of that big family, Arjuna is the vessel and the opportunity to bring to an end the decaying of *dharma*, which had started with Śantanu. Bhīṣma is there as the witness, the representative of the impotent older tradition. Arjuna is the hero, and as such he is required to develop the necessary *śraddhā* for undertaking the mission of restoring *dharma* in accordance to Kṛṣṇa's prescription – even if at the price of the death of the four commanders (*senāpatis*) of the Kaurava side: Bhīṣma, Droṇa, Karṇa, and Śalya.

²⁸⁴ If Biblical scholars have not fully succeeded in dialectally synthesizing the pairs of opposites as they appear in the Book of Job, where the problem of evil and suffering is addressed in contraposition to the existence of a transcendent principle beyond good and evil, perhaps they should make some use of the 'Book of Bhīṣma', which addresses the same question, but in a philosophically deeper fashion. Like Arjuna in the *Gītā*, Job was also confused, whining, and lamenting. The theological difference between both books, however, is exemplified in the difficulty that scholars have found to reconcile the idea of God with that of someone 'permitting' Satan to interfere with God's sons. Such a difficulty disappears in the Indian Epic, as the concept of *Brahman* includes the whole universe, 'Satan' included. Perhaps a good image for that in the *Gītā* would be the passage BhG 11.25, where Rudolf Otto has identified his '*mysterium tremendum*'. (Interesting that even the Bible acknowledges Satan as a former member of the divine council, as a kind of celestial examiner.) The kind of Job's endurance is precisely what Kṛṣṇa expects from a soul of Arjuna's dimension. Arjuna's experience, perhaps from the viewpoint of those living under the influence of the *triṣuṇic saṃsāra*, can be seen as one of misfortune. Yet, from the viewpoint of those awakened to the transcendent, Arjuna was nothing but blessed by his sanctifying experience with the divine. The same happened to Job, who is said to have had a dialogue with God, and heard from him, "Where was Job when God created the world?" What comfort can be bigger than God's revealing Himself? After such an experience, what is the big deal in any suffering during our transitory material life?

In the *Mahābhārata*, then, the real question becomes one on the meaning of *dharma yuddha*. Furthermore, while traditional rites, especially *śrāddha* rites, are important to the understanding of how this theological experience reflects the ritual link that joins one generation to another in the epic story of the *Mahābhārata*, *śrāddhā* is important to the understanding of what the *Gṛh* had qualified as *dharma-yuddha* (BhG 2.31), or just opposition to evil. Both sides, the *Kauravas* and the *Pāṇḍavas*, perform their *śrāddha* rites for the ancestors, but the heart of the *Kauravas*' leaders are hardly on their performance, whereas the *Pāṇḍavas* are role models of how rites are to be practiced. Yudhiṣṭira, for instance, as the oldest *Pāṇḍava*, keeps his noble heart even after the battle, mourning the death of enemies such as Bhīṣma and Droṇa (MBh 12.27, 4-17), or his brother Karṇa (MBh 18.3).

It is no wonder, then, that after the first half of the battle, on the ninth day, Yudhiṣṭira goes to Kṛṣṇa to get advice on *dharma yuddha* (MBh 6.103). Kṛṣṇa, then, helps Yudhiṣṭira to find a righteous way to accomplish his goals, without resorting to methods that could lead those bound by their sacred vows to break them. In other words, Kṛṣṇa teaches Yudhiṣṭira how to address, from his own depressed heart (*dṁātma*), Bhīṣma's heart. With this heart-to-heart *ātman*-based correlation, the son of *Dharma* gets from the great Bhīṣma the plan for his ritualistic death: it would be through Śikhaṇḍin (who had been Ambā in the previous life) that Bhīṣma would allow himself to be killed in that battle (MBh 6.103, 74-7).

Such an *ātmic* display of detachment as shown by Bhīṣma, which corresponds to what was being taught by Kṛṣṇa, proves difficult for Yudhiṣṭira to understand. Even after his painful mission is completed, he will show signs of suffering to the point of almost regretting his request to Bhīṣma. The *Bhīṣmaparvan* provides a context for linking this pair *śraddhā* / *śrāddha* through the drama of the war. The *Bhīṣmaparvan* shows that the pair *śraddhā* and *śrāddha* belong to an archetypical relation where death and dying are elevated to a sacred and transcendent context of reverence and homage. Suddenly we recognize the motive forces that move everyone in the wheel of *saṃsāra*. The elusive character and the ambiguity around *dharma* fade away when one is rooted in the *ātman* with *śraddhā*. With the teaching of the *Gītā* set at the center of the story, the divergences among the characters in the *Mahābhārata* is not so much in relation to their ‘beliefs’ on *dharma* and whatever those are to be labeled the ‘good’ guys or the ‘bad’ guys, but on how honestly and eagerly they try to enter into *śraddhā*.²⁸⁵

²⁸⁵ As we will see in the closing section of this chapter, Karṇa’s weaknesses, for instance, are a measure of his distance from *śraddhā* as being *ātman*-based, and, as a consequence, of the deeper meaning of *dharma yuddha*. Had Karṇa truly heard his heart (*ātman*), he would not remain overwhelmed by either his social rank and restrictions, or the *Pāṇḍavas*’s provocations. He would not lie to Paraśurāma to get from him a mere war discipline. He would not be cursed with losing his weapons when he needed them the most. Karṇa does perform some rites, as for instance to the representative of the god of fire, Sūrya. He does develop some *śraddhā*, but this is not sufficient to make him achieve the necessary willpower to change his mind and follow Kṛṣṇa’s advice to side with the *Pāṇḍavas*. He disregards even the plea of his mother Kuntī to not side with the *Kauravas*, even though he disapproves of Duryodhana’s methods and dislikes Bhīṣma. Karṇa’s behaviour toward his mother and brothers is oscillating, ambiguous. His rejection of Kṛṣṇa and of Kuntī’s advice does not mean he is making an altruistic rejection of power and fame. For what he is really demonstrating is that he could not fully forgive his mother and the *Pāṇḍavas*, which means that his reasons for fighting that war were very different from the reasons Kṛṣṇa provided to Arjuna. Lacking the necessary *śraddhā* for making up his mind, he refuses to change, and remains stuck to his ambiguous condition and state of confusion about who he truly is. Somehow, Karṇa knows that the *Kauravas* are wicked; he knows he is siding with evil, and yet he refuses to change – this refusal to change is his primary weakness, when compared to Arjuna.

In the previous chapters I have argued that *śrāddha* rites seem to work at the unconscious level, where *śraddhā* itself waits for an opportunity to find expression through consciousness. For, the pathway that allows one to manifest *śraddhā* in one's life is hindered by egocentrism. At the very moment one chooses not to follow what *ātman* indicates, one loses one's *śraddhā* and the ability to recognize *dharma*. The blind king loses sight of how to rule; Bhīṣma loses sight of what he needs to protect, and Karṇa loses sight of who it is to whom he really owes loyalty. These are the stories of the confusion about *dharma* in the *Mahābhārata*.²⁸⁶ What the *Gītā* adds to the story is the theological sense that when *śraddhā* is not manifest in a person's heart, the consequence is this deterioration of *dharma*.

The visit Vyāsa pays to his blind son seems to illustrate that, because the *śraddhā* of the Kaurava leaders did not develop to the full *sattvic* form taught to Arjuna, they were unfit for the renunciation or *saṁnyāsa* and *tyāga* as portrayed in the *Gītā*. More specifically, the blind king, although possessing some intellectual understanding of basic scriptural knowledge, was unable to advance in the spiritual path due to his strong egotism (*svārtha*). It is Saṁjaya, then, who, through the grace of Vyāsa, becomes able to lecture Dhṛtarāṣṭra on the causes of that war. The way Vyāsa found to provide some peace to his son was to allow Saṁjaya to lecture the king on kingly matters, pointing out

²⁸⁶ The *Mahābhārata* shows how the people who suffer from egocentrism, being devoid of the *ātmic* knowledge, begin to indulge in lawlessness; with the result there is soon confusion about the nature of the real *dharma* that one ought to practice. This vice of egocentrism is found throughout Bhīṣma's dynasty and involves increasing attachment to the fruit of action, mostly through the perpetuation of caste relations, and filial love. Had Bhīṣma truly renounced his desire for his father's happiness at any price, he would not have put the whole future of the dynasty at stake, and would not have given up his rights for the sake of the unborn children of his father. This mistake of filial loyalty will continue with the blind king, with the wicked Duryodhana, and even with Karṇa.

to him that the Kurus, led by Duryodhana, would be killed for the reason that nothing could stop the *karmic* law working itself out.

The whole *Gītā*, then, represents the answer of the half-*śūdra* Saṁjaya to Dhṛtarāṣṭra's question about the fate of his descendants and relatives in the war. So, while the *Mahābhārata* is framed in a context of conflicting *varṇāśrama-dharma*, the embedded *Gītā*'s narration of Saṁjaya to Dhṛtarāṣṭra is based on *ātma-dharma*, or the all inclusive *Yoga*. This *ātman*-based *Yoga* is defined in BhG 2.46-8 as *samatva*,²⁸⁷ or universal equanimity, and described in BhG 15.15 as that wholehearted mode of reasoning where the transcendent *ātman* is understood as a way to overcome the manifold world-processes of the *varṇāśrama* system.²⁸⁸

²⁸⁷ It is worth mentioning that in the *Mahābhārata* Kṛṣṇa had not counselled to wage the war, but that even in the waging of it one should not lose the peace, or *samatva*. That is why, in the *Gītā*, after war becomes a certainty, he stresses to Arjuna the importance of *samatva*.

²⁸⁸ BhG 2.46: As much value as there is in a water-tank when on all sides there is a flood of water, so much is there in all *Vedas* for a brahman who (truly) understands. BhG 15.15: I dwell in the heart of all beings. From me comes memory, knowledge and the dispelling of doubts. Through all the *Vedas* it is I that should be known, and 'I' indeed is the *Veda* knower and author of the *Veda*'s ends.

If the *Vedas* are a water-tank to be used by those who are thirsty, *ātman* is said to be like a flood with water on every side. Already by the 1920s there was controversy on the issue of Kṛṣṇa's critique of the *Vedas*. See F. O. Schrader, "Über Bhavavadgītā" (ZDMG 64, 1910), 336-340. According to Schrader, scholars like Pavolini, Belloni-Filippi, Jacobi, Garbe, Deussen and many others could not agree on the reasons why Kṛṣṇa seems to be rejecting the *Veda*'s teachings, or at least placing it second, in relation to the experience of the *ātman*. Schrader reminds us that the *ātmavidyā* nullifies one's dependency to the *Vedas* – a truth which is guaranteed by the *Upaniṣadic* tradition. Once we participate in the knowledge of *Brahman*, what good can we get from the books about this knowledge? No wonder, then, that the *saṁnyāsins*, believing to partake in such knowledge, do not make any use of the *Vedas*. Schrader is of the opinion that the *Gītā* is placing an emphasis on this experiential knowledge about the *ātman* of the *Upaniṣads* being more important than the 'Book-knowledge' of the *Vedas*. The *Vedas* teach the lower knowledge, and only those who leave their masters can expect to find salvation. For, by '*Vedānta*' is to be understood *Brahmavidyā*. And perhaps this fact is what explains Garbe's frustrated attempts to prove that the *Gītā* was a *Vedāntic* text not much older than the time of Śaṅkara. Much later, in his translation of the *Gītā*, Zaehner (1969) would come back to this issue of how to understand BhG 2.46 and BhG 15.15, but only to bring a polarized interpretation that fits the views of the *Vedānta* school, which sees 'work' in general as inferior to 'knowledge' – the first representing the *Vedic karma-khaṇḍa* and the second the

The problem presented in the *Gītā* through Arjuna’s dilemma, then, is how to interpret properly, at every moment and concrete situation, what *dharma* really is, despite all difficulties the concept presents. The *Mahābhārata* narrates the battle fought in *Kurukṣetra* by the sons of two brothers with different views of *dharma* as the moral, external, customary bases for determining the rights to the throne. In the *Gītā*, *dharma* is raised to the level of an inner ethics of motives overruling even family, gender, and caste values. Exploring the *Pāṇḍavas*’s dilemma and opposing family values, the *Gītā* brings to Arjuna the conflict between the personal values inherited from Bhīṣma and the new theological issues raised by Kṛṣṇa, who bases his system of ethics on the non-personal idea of *ātman*. The *Gītā* showcases in Arjuna’s struggle how these two orders are to be put together. The *Mahābhārata* presents a war-like situation in which the message of the *Gītā* provides a contrast between Arjuna’s process of *pravṛtti* – the 12 years in the forest, dedicating himself to the practice of *tapas* to get the necessary weapons for the fighting – with Arjuna’s process of *nivṛtti*, when he appears in the *Gītā* eager to step into the spiritual path. The synthesis that links that which originated in the forest, and that which is concerned with the political practices of the city, with spiritual insight, is unexpected. In other words, the *Gītā* is not a simple manual of ‘first communion teaching’, but is deeply embedded in the *Mahābhārata*’s complex plot around the concept of *dharma*, and is meant for grown-ups deeply involved in the world of action.²⁸⁹

Upaniṣadic jñāna-khaṇḍa. His explanation ignores the importance that the *Gītā* places on the theory of *niṣkāmakarmayoga*.

²⁸⁹ In the *Mahābhārata* *dharma* is said to range across all the duties of a man, demarcated by the *saṃskāras* (e.g. birth, death, marriage, house-warming etc.). *Dharma*, then, encompasses some of the ethical ideas of

The *Mahābhārata* seems to be making use of the *Kauravas*' commands with regard to *śraddhā* / *śrāddha*. Do the rites for the ancestors and you will enter into the realm of religious experience. In a sense, Kṛṣṇa represents the raising of the voice of conscience in Arjuna. What the *Gītā* does is raise this discussion to the world of *praxis*. It is this new dimension that introduces Arjuna's ritual need to finish Bhīṣma, and as a consequence, to finish the war. Despite his emotional confusion, he needs to accomplish this task for the sake of *dharma*. It is worth noticing that none of the four *Kaurava* commanders were able to fight for the sake of *dharma* alone because of their previous allegiances. This means that they were not able to fight out of pure *śraddhā*. This means, for instance, that had Karṇa succeeded in killing Arjuna, he would not have been able to perform Arjuna's *śrāddha* rites properly, out of *śraddhā*.

The *dharmic* correlation of *śraddhā* and *śrāddha*, then, are realized in a way that links *Vedic* rituals and the *Upaniṣadic* ideals of *mokṣa* now subsumed in the *Gītā*'s *ātma-dharma*. In this interpretation, paying homage to ancestors reflects a transformation of consciousness, where one acknowledges the historical process in the context of a beginningless and endless journey which is one's own. Ancestors become metaphors, symbols, and myths, and the rites we perform to them make us what we all are – *śraddhā*, according to the *Gītā*. Stating it another way, *sattvic śraddhā* is to be understood as of

the *Upaniṣads* as well as some of the ritual customs outlined in the *Brāhmaṇas*. It contains an elaboration of the orthodox social code, including the 4 *puruṣārthas* (*dharma*, *artha*, *kāma*, and *mokṣa*); the four stages of life (*brahmacarya*, *gṛhastha*, *vanaprastha*, and *saṃnyāsa*), and the duties of the four castes. The *Mahābhārata* raises the basic question, then, of how anyone should control their feelings and live in accordance to *dharma*. The *Gītā* represents a movement of this discussion of 'general' regulations to the particular situation when those regulations do not automatically work.

heroic dimension. For it requires a great deal of courage, and implies taking decisions which go against traditional views, norms, and so on. It involves setting out to unknown places, where one faces all kinds of challenges. It also involves a new view over old traditional values. Furthermore, beyond even the material heroic dimension, *śraddhā* involves commitment of a spiritual nature, which implies the understanding that participation in the world does not mean that one ‘belongs’ to this world.

What the pair *śraddhā* / *śrāddha* truly reveals, then, is that, when one performs all actions as ritual actions for the sake of the world, one becomes even more compassionate. For, *śraddhā* lies within and it is only its image that we represent as rites in general. Ultimately, rites are linked to our psychic dimension and they work as bridges to the sacred ground of being. This is precisely what the separate books on the deaths of the *Kaurava* commanders show: how the descendants of Kuru deal with those primordial processes that define their social history and psychic development. These death-stories do not seek to argue or to analyse in any pure theoretical sense; rather, they simply describe how the *praxis* of *karma* works itself out in the process of human experience.

Droṇa’s death presents some ritual elements of special interest, as his fighting was considered unrighteous even by the *Ṛṣis* (MBh 7.164). Otherwise, he should have been able to figure out that the truth about the killing of Aśvatthāman was linked with the elephant slain by Bhīma, and not with the slaughter of his son. The ritual advice offered by Kṛṣṇa to make Droṇa lay aside his weapons is successful mainly because of Droṇa’s own sins, as they make the sinner blind to the more subtle truths. Droṇa surely had hoped to get from Yudhiṣṭira a *friendly straight answer*, but what he got instead was just

a *straight answer*. Droṇa's assumption that Yudhiṣṭira's statement should convey the answer demanded by a friend was wrong. For Droṇa had come to him as someone from the Kaurava side. In that context Droṇa was an enemy, and it is a military duty to hide from the enemy any strategic truth. This means that Yudhiṣṭira was obliged to be truthful only in relation to the death of the elephant Aśvatthāman. Droṇa, however, was led to believe that his son had been slain. His answer is understandable, considering Yudhiṣṭira's pain in seeing his friend turned into an enemy. His action was not an easy one. Indeed, in some ways it involved the slaying of a guru by a disciple. It is only when it is seen as a ritual action to be performed out of *śraddhā* that Kṛṣṇa's solution to kill Droṇa becomes acceptable. It is only then that the *Pāṇḍavas* could possibly assist in Droṇa's *śrāddha* rites. The situation now is that Droṇa is killed during his peaceful *yogic* trance, and he ascends to the world of *Brahman* (MBh 7.165). His death, like that of Bhīṣma, is due to his misunderstanding of *dharma*, and his resultant siding with what was untruth.

Yudhiṣṭira, the son of *Dharma*, causes the *Kauravas*, who cannot accept nor understand the death of Droṇa, to reflect upon the meaning of the very *dharma* they have been dishonoring (MBh 7.166). Even among the *Pāṇḍavas* Droṇa's death causes grief, and second thoughts about the war they had failed to avoid. Arjuna's mourning of the death of their guru, Droṇa, becomes, then, part of the *śrāddha* ritual into which Kṛṣṇa had transformed the battle (MBh 7.167). The process of acquiring *śraddhā* which Kṛṣṇa had taught to Arjuna was now put to the test by the very contradictory reality of war. Even

the *Pāṇḍavas* give signs of losing sight of what Kṛṣṇa's *ātma-dharma* truly is. Yet, it is through Kṛṣṇa's guidance that they become able to reflect on the meaning of their own sovereignty.

In the next major event, the ritual death of Karṇa, the humane drama of the *Mahābhārata* will again focus on the realm of friendship, alliances, family matters, and common ancestors (MBh 8.27). Karṇa embodies one who has decided to put all his soul at the service of his *ahaṅkāric* need to display loyalty and friendship to those who do not deserve it. He is his own enemy, and also the enemy of the *ātman* in himself. Symbolically, this fact is expressed through his unfriendly relation with Śālyā, his charioteer. The charioteer is a symbol of one's own *ātman*, where the relation the two 'selves' develop should be one of *śraddhā*, as one is supposed to drive the other through the battles of life. However, there is no sign of *śraddhā* in this relation. As a consequence, even in situations when Karṇa may be said to be stronger than Arjuna, the antagonistic pair Karṇa/Śālyā could not ever be a match for the harmonious pair Arjuna/Kṛṣṇa. In other words, the death of Karṇa is due to his insistence on remaining as an *aśraddadhāna*, who is blind to the *ātmic* calls, and always fights for the wrong causes.²⁹⁰

Wrong causes to embrace and wrong reasons for friendship, thus seem to lead to those false friendships where one demands from, and plays with, the other *adharmic* roles. Karṇa's choices are never rooted in *ātman*; they are all based on his need to cope

²⁹⁰ This seems to be also Hildebeitel's understanding, as he points out: "If there is a lesson in these contrasts, it would seem to be that Arjuna and Krishna's success will be related to their true friendship, while Karṇa and Śālyā's failure will be related to their false friendship" (Hildebeitel, 1990, 257).

with his grief and humiliation. He had been humiliated by the five *Pāṇḍavas* at the military tournament, and by Draupadī twice, at her Svayaṃvara and at the Kaurava court. He could not, therefore, fight on their side, despite the *Pāṇḍavas* right reasons for fighting. His outer martial courage reveals a hint of inner weakness: he cannot control his anger, rooted in *ahaṅkāra*. Karṇa’s decision to ignore the counsels of both his mother and Kṛṣṇa indicate his inability to forgive and to develop the necessary *śraddhā* for the undertaking of the path of *karma yoga*. He bases his decision to side with the *Kauravas* on affection (*sneha*) and false notions of loyalty, or attachment to those who have accepted him as a friend simply to benefit from his strength.

Considered as an outcast (*pratiloma sūti jāti*), the son of a charioteer, Karṇa accepts the pernicious friendship of the *Kauravas*. However, his decision too is not a matter of altruism because he hopes selfishly to become a *kṣatriya*. It is in these terms that he builds the friendship with the *Kauravas* and thereby becomes enslaved by it.²⁹¹ Kṛṣṇa had previously told Karṇa that Arjuna was his brother (MBh 5.138), but, as Kṛṣṇa also acknowledges, he had failed to reach Karṇa’s heart (MBh 5.141). As a consequence, Karṇa prefers to ignore, for the wrong reasons, the fact that Arjuna is his brother, with both of them having Kuntī as common ancestor. At the moment of the fight with Arjuna, Karṇa prefers to ignore the fact that he is fighting against the throne he, indeed, is entitled to, and was indeed offered by Kṛṣṇa himself. In other words, this is the

²⁹¹ As Hildebeitel is quick to point out, “The fabric of “friendships” which holds this episode [described in the *Karṇaparvan*] together is thus further complicated. One might put Karṇa’s position into the following formula: for his own true friend [Duryodhana], he must fight against a pair of true friends [Arjuna and Kṛṣṇa] and thus face death by letting a false friend live [Śālyā]” (1990, 260).

price of his loyalty to Duryodhana and to what he represented; Karṇa becomes his own enemy – deaf even to words of his mother, Kuntī, and of his father, the god Sūrya, who had pleaded with him to join his brothers (MBh 5.144).

The ritual death of such a gentle and noble giant, though, has to be understood in the context in which *dharma* itself is being redefined by Kṛṣṇa. Kṛṣṇa’s teaching about engaged display of detachment overrides earlier understandings of what *dharma* is. The new world of *dharma* is a world in which one is supposed to nurture one’s reason to choose at every single moment what the best course of action is. Karṇa’s story exemplifies how the best *dharmic* course of action is difficult to figure out. His death symbolizes the contradictory nature of the different sources of *dharma*, among which, according to the second chapter of *Gītā, ātman*, as represented by Kṛṣṇa himself, is the most excellent source. As an expression of that proper order of things which brings about the best outcome, *dharma* is fluid and difficult to grasp. On the one side, Karṇa surely thought he was following *dharma* when he refused Kṛṣṇa’s advice. On the other side, he also knew Kṛṣṇa represented true *dharma*.

Kṛṣṇa’s *dharma*, understood as the sacrifice of *ahaṅkāra* for the sake of *ātman*, was not entirely new. It was already present in the *Vedic* claim that through the sacrifice to the gods humans were contributing to maintaining the world order, or *dharma*, as expressed in the different *varṇas*. The difficulty is that while *Vedic varṇa dharma* is static and believed to be natural, Kṛṣṇa’s *dharma* is fluid, and needs to be cultivated from the *ātmic* perspective, in accordance with the immediate circumstances. Karṇa shows

Kṛṣṇa he is not ready for such an ethereal form of wisdom. He prefers to stick to his own interpretation of the older code of moral values, which places friendship and loyalty above everything else.

Karṇa's choice, therefore, represents the choosing of a tradition that is dying,²⁹² as opposed to Kṛṣṇa's new revelation of *ātma-dharma*. Kṛṣṇa is careful to value Karṇa and his traditional way of thinking. Even the first seeds of *ātma-dharma* are there, as his courage to think on himself demonstrates. The problem is that even when he may have thought his decision was *ātman* based, the events of the *Mahābhārata* make it clear that Karṇa's choice was not *ātman*-based. Indeed, what Kṛṣṇa shows is that none of the *Kauravas'* choices are *ātman*-based. Their actions were stained by many different desires, and they were, therefore, not of the *niṣkāmakarma* type, which represents the essence of *yoga*. Even when high commanders such as Bhīṣma, Droṇa, and Karṇa believed they were giving full expression to their conscience, in reality they were fooled by their many different *ahaṅkāric* attachments to this world. As a consequence, they were constrained to side with Dhṛtarāṣṭra and Duryodhana – the two main archetypes of *ahaṅkāra's* role in the human domain. Furthermore, as we have seen, what legitimates one's activity and allows it to rise above *ahaṅkāra* is the attitude of *śraddhā*. It is *śraddhā* that puts one in touch with one's own conscience. That is to say, any legitimate reinterpretation of customs, traditions, and moral or ethical values must be rooted in the

²⁹² During the peace attempts of the *Udyogaparvan* Kṛṣṇa starts his dialogue with Karṇa by praising Karṇa's grasp of his *Vedic* knowledge (MBh 5.138).

ātman (BhG 2. 42-6). It is only under such a motivation that one develops *sattvic śraddhā*, which is the characteristic mark of behavior rooted in pure *ātman* (BhG 17).

The events related to the Kaurava commanders' *śrāddha* rites take up the *parvans* six to nine of the *Mahābhārata*. Throughout these stories one is constrained to reflect on the meaning of *dharma* and enquire what theology rests behind Kṛṣṇa's teaching on *dharma*. In a sense, the *Mahābhārata*'s account of the *śrāddha* rites represent a final attempt to help the descendents of Kuru (and all listeners) develop *śraddhā*, or a new *ātmic* perspective on the essence of reality itself, as taught by Kṛṣṇa in the *Gītā*. This teaching is not about blind devotion to Kṛṣṇa and the giving up of all individual choices. On the contrary, it means learning the process of awakening the *ātman* in oneself. In the end, Bhīṣma is close to Kṛṣṇa, as is Karṇa, Droṇa, and Śālyā.²⁹³

What we want to argue here is that it is only if we see *śraddhā* as the central religious experience linking one to *ātman* can we explain even the positions of giants such as Bhīṣma, Karṇa, Droṇa, Śālyā, Vidura, and many others who side with the *Kauravas* in spite of their deep respect for Kṛṣṇa. The *Mahābhārata* plot invites its

²⁹³ Despite the loyalty Karṇa feels he owns to Duryodhana, despite Bhīṣma's oath to protect the throne, one can hardly imagine either of them consulting Duryodhana or the blind king in order to gain a theological understanding of *dharma*. On the contrary, whenever Kṛṣṇa sets out his position, they are inclined to agree with him. The only reason for their refusal to side with Kṛṣṇa in the narrative framework is their need to please Duryodhana and the blind king. In the end, Kṛṣṇa praises and respects their choice and their knowledge of the *dharmaśāstras*, for, at the deepest level, *ātma-dharma* insists on the respect towards each individual's autonomous *ātman* and the path onto which it takes them. In this sense the homage to these *Kauravas*' at their *śrāddha* rites is the ultimate respect. If this way of understanding *ātma-dharma* has not always been clear, it is because sectarian views quickly become the vehicle through which the text was seen. The later *bhakti* Hinduism reinterpreted the *Mahābhārata*, and especially the *Gītā*, and imposed on it a reading where personal *bhakti* towards Kṛṣṇa becomes central. Krishna Sharma, as our earlier discussion showed leads the critique of this reinterpretation, but we want to argue here that our interpretation of the concepts of *śraddhā* and *bhakti* also shows that the *bhakti* sectarian view is not the most helpful understanding of Kṛṣṇa's teaching.

characters to explore the limiting situations for which the *śāstras* do not provide a clear answer. What the story is about is the discipline of relying on the approval of one's conscience. Because of the subtleties of such a discipline, the *Mahābhārata* has as its pivotal center the *Gītā*, which provides the theological clarification of this point. That is not to say the story stops as the *Gītā* unfolds theoretical knowledge. The teaching of the *Gītā* is an artistic masterpiece that teaches practical skills in the pursuit of wisdom. The core message of Kṛṣṇa to Arjuna is that *ātman dharma* demands engagement, but an engagement where one's eyes and ears are full of *śraddhā*.

V.3. A Gender and Caste Theological Perspective

Gender and caste perspectives have been portrayed with consummate skill in the *Mahābhārata*, and yet, their proper appraisal, as suggested in the *Gītā*, is often misunderstood. What happens as this narrative proceeds is that when gender and caste, which come from our material nature, take precedence over altruism and detachment, which come from our spiritual nature, what we get is an allegory of evil which leads toward war. What the narrator hopes is that the war story eventually turns on its head and the listener sees the role of *śraddhā* and how each character might have acted righteously.

The *Mahābhārata* uses characters of both sexes and of different castes with subtle psychological traits in order to describe all sorts of conflicts of interests. The text ultimately describes how ethical values are on the side of those who place gender and caste values second to the main goal of attaining *Brahman*. But the story starts with the

opposite perspective. Śantanu has a very male perspective and together with the very female perspectives of his two wives they put the kingdom at risk twice. Later on in the text, Karṇa's attachment to Duryodhana's *kṣatriya* rights, and Draupadī's anger and desire to revenge her humiliation as a woman, will drive the narrative and reinforce the idea that caste, ethnicity, and gender represent the blind motives of historical actors. Set to the side for the moment is the real goal of life in which they should have remained focused – achieving their *ātman*. Draupadī, for instance, wants revenge for her humiliation, and demands that her husbands go to war, despite Kṛṣṇa's attempts to make her change her mind. Whereas Arjuna is indeed not desirous of war due to his great deal of compassion (MBh 5.72.20-23), Draupadī, in anger, says to Kṛṣṇa that if the desolate Arjuna wants to make peace, then her father, along with his army, will go to war (MBh 5.80.37). Such imperative words, addressed to Kṛṣṇa, come straight from Draupadī's gender biased view. Answering Draupadī, Kṛṣṇa says that those postures, such as hers, make war inevitable (MBh 5.80.44).

Kuntī is another example of gender oriented bias. She watches in silence the humiliation of her son Karṇa in fear of the social humiliation she would face if she acknowledged Karṇa as her son. Deceitfulness, therefore, is often a complicating consequence of the gender and caste orientated bias, and is portrayed by the author as present, in some degree, in all characters. The one exception is the Kṛṣṇa of the *Gītā* who

is a true representative of the *ātmic* realm, even though he too is sometimes interpreted as murderous and deceitful²⁹⁴ in other parts of the narrative.

The *Gītā*'s argument is that *ātman* and its representative, Kṛṣṇa, are beyond the material frame for action based on gender and caste. If social rank in the form of gender and caste bothers everybody in the *Mahābhārata* narrative the *Gītā* argues that this kind of consideration ultimately is meaningless, as it belongs to that which dies – the material body. The soul is neither male nor female, and the soul is not marked by *varṇāśrama* hierarchical categories. Everybody's ultimate goal is the realization of the essence of the soul. Failing to understand this point leads to the rejection of Kṛṣṇa's advice, as we see in Draupadī and Karṇa, for instance – and the momentum toward war becomes overwhelming.

The symbolism behind Kṛṣṇa's diplomatic gesture toward all the descendents of the Kurus suggests that siding with the *Kauravas* means a view on *dharma* that confers legitimacy to almost any of the *ahaṃkāra*'s urges – as, for instance, the one which was embodied in Duryodhana's quest to become the 'crown prince' of the whole kingdom. Bhīṣma, who cannot change his mind and prefers to remain faithful to his family-oriented oath to protect the 'crown prince', and Karṇa, who also prefers to remain faithful to his urge to display gratitude toward the 'crown prince', left themselves with no other option

²⁹⁴ Yet, throughout the *Udyogaparvan* Kṛṣṇa is the Ambassador of Peace. Prior to the war, he had talked about peaceful solutions to all the main characters. Even after the war became inevitable, he still manages to help both sides understand what the real goal in life should be. He allows war to happen out of respect for everyone's personal choices, and uses that occasion to teach the descendents of Kuru the lesson they had refused to learn otherwise: to the *Kauravas*, who are worshippers of material powers, he gives his army; to the *Pāṇḍavas*, who are learning to seek *ātma-dharma*, he gives his guidance.

but to refuse Kṛṣṇa's advice²⁹⁵ and side with the *Kauravas*. Siding with the *Pāṇḍavas* means precisely the opposite view on *dharma*. Here Kṛṣṇa attempts to convince the real crown prince, Yudhiṣṭira, to accept his mission of reestablishing the *dharmic* order. Arjuna, who is open to changing his mind, represents the one who takes Kṛṣṇa's words to heart.

Deceitfulness is an attribute of those ruled by *ahaṅkāra*, and *ātman* encompasses *ahaṅkāra*. Hence the teacher of *ātman* sometimes appears to also operate in the realm of *ahaṅkāra*. Nevertheless to argue that *ātman*, or its true representative, Kṛṣṇa, is intentionally deceitful is to cross the line. That is, however, what Duryodhana and the blind king, for instance, do. In their selfish male oriented analysis, they attempt to argue that Kṛṣṇa is deceitful. One can hardly say that Kṛṣṇa has tried to *deceive* Karṇa, unless a call to wake up *ātman* in oneself can be called deceitful. Karṇa's heroism was not grounded on *ātman*. It was not based in a fervent struggle for the sake of world welfare or some sort of 'just war', but was really nothing but a kind of Mafia-oriented understanding of friendship and loyalty. It is not deceitful to help one to understand that difference, but it is difficult to break through the logic governed by *ahaṅkāra*.

The *Mahābhārata*'s characters are human beings, both males and females, from all the different social strata. Human beings express their material identity in terms of gender and social class. Our material identity (*ahaṅkāra*) is defined through these roles we play in society. However, our essential identity (*ātman*) is neither gender or class

²⁹⁵ Kṛṣṇa reminds Karṇa that if he joins his brothers, he will be the king, and also Draupadī's sixth husband (MBh 5.138, 12-5). Later on, even the great Bhīṣma, once on his bed of arrows, asks Karṇa to reunite with his brothers, putting an end to that war (MBh 6.117, 12).

oriented. This means that when a male or a female of any class or ethnicity is ruled by her or his essential identity, the gender and class perspectives she or he represents will express only the *ātmic* view, and will harmonize the different gender and caste views. Such is the meaning of the ‘ritual of the battle’: the overcoming of *ahaṅkāra*’s *triguṇic* influence, with the consequent surrender to the *ātman*’s demands. Stating it another way, the battle everyone has to fight is to free oneself from the material constraints, which come in all forms of biased views based on gender, caste, ethnicity, and so on.

One has to acknowledge that caste perspective, ethnic perspective, gender perspective, though limited and *ahaṅkāra*-oriented, are important to defining our identities in the world of *saṃsāra*. No one can express better how these views should be understood than Kṛṣṇa himself.²⁹⁶ As described by Kṛṣṇa in the *Gītā*, any ritual action, when performed to perfection, becomes practically the same as non-action – a fact that even the wise often fail to grasp.²⁹⁷ For instance, when Kṛṣṇa appears at Draupadī’s Svayaṃvara (one’s choosing [of a bridegroom]), Kṛṣṇa, not a suitor, seems to be a mere spectator (Hiltebeitel, 1990, 82). Yet his secret protection of the *Pāṇḍavas* turns the whole plot in their favour. Despite the voice of caste complaining that the Svayaṃvara was meant exclusively for *kṣatriyas*, Kṛṣṇa was in a position to assert that Draupadī had been won (by Arjuna disguised as a *brāhmin*) in accordance with *dharma* (83). Here his caste and gender oriented statement satisfies the audience’s superficial understanding of

²⁹⁶ See Alf Hiltebeitel, *The Ritual of the Battle: Krishna in the Mahābhārata* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1990).

²⁹⁷ It is no wonder, then, that some scholars will be tempted to envision an epic *without* such a *worthless* Kṛṣṇa, whose actions seem to mean nothing (Hiltebeitel, 1990, 79).

dharma, even as his *ātman*-based understanding protects the essential meaning of *dharma*. Later on, the resulting polyandric marriage would prove to be *dharmic*, because it had been performed with the best of intentions, and ended up being beneficial and fruitful in many ways.

In accordance to Kṛṣṇa’s analysis, *dharma* depends in a large measure on one’s altruistic attitude during the performance of one’s deeds, and *adharma*, on the other hand, represents the consequence of promiscuous endeavour. That is to say, what is *dharma*, and what is *adharma*, varies from case to case. In this analysis, Draupadī’s polyandric marriage could not be considered *adharmic*. The conditions which established the ceremony were not determined by any selfish trick on the part of those involved. As a consequence, Kṛṣṇa, whose task was to restore the true meaning of *dharma*, acknowledges that there was nothing wrong with their marriage, and bestows on them their wedding gifts.²⁹⁸

In the words of Hildebeitel, it is Kṛṣṇa’s role to preserve “the hidden structure of *dharma*” (1990, 85), even when it seems he is doing nothing. And he does so mostly through the *Pāṇḍavas*. He leads them to their new kingdom residence, Khāṇḍavaprastha, placed in the middle of a terrible forest, and helps them to transform the place into the heaven-like city of Indraprastha (MBh 1.199). Next, he wisely suggests the building of the magnificent hall (*sabhā*) (MBh 2.1), where later Duryodhana would be made a fool. Kṛṣṇa thus launches his campaign for Yudhiṣṭira’s performance of the Royal

²⁹⁸ Biardeau is of the same opinion, and argues for that in her “*Brāhmaṇes et potiers*,” Article liminaire, *Annuaire de l’Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes*, LXXXIX (1971-2).

Consecration Ceremony, Rājasūya (MBh 2.12), and makes sure nothing will disrupt Yudhishtira’s consecration (MBh 2.18-22 and MBh 2.37-42).

Kṛṣṇa’s ritual performance, acting for the sake of *dharma* as if he were not acting at all, continues in the events of the two dice games. For Kṛṣṇa is not present, and yet he impedes Draupadī’s disrobing (MBh 2.61). His geographic distancing from that evil performance of the concluding rites of the royal consecration only make more evident his spiritual closeness with those who are willing and deserving of his help. Then, in the episode at Kṛṣṇa’s bedside (MBh 5.7.17-31), when Duryodhana reminds Kṛṣṇa of his obligation to side with those who first come for help, Kṛṣṇa replies that, although Duryodhana had been the first to come, Arjuna was the first he had seen. Wisely demonstrating how his friendship and assistance were impartial, he granted to both of them the assistance they deserved, as if they had arrived together. Once more, acting as if not acting, he manages to protect *dharma* and to assist the humane needs: Duryodhana gets the armies and material weapons he values, and Arjuna gets the spiritual counselor he values – Kṛṣṇa.

Both Duryodhana and Arjuna were delighted with Kṛṣṇa’s solution, and yet, it was only *dharma* that had been served. This means that the only side Kṛṣṇa can take is that of *dharma*, which is something far beyond the reach of human preference which is usually defined in terms of genealogy, friendship, or any other characteristic ruled by the *guṇas* of *prakṛti*. For, while war happens in the *prakṛti*, peace is what one can get from

ātman, even if only that *inner peace while in an outer war*,²⁹⁹ which is what Kṛṣṇa has to offer to Arjuna. Kṛṣṇa’s inner peace makes it possible for him to maintain his stance of impartiality towards the world as a whole.

Again and again, while it seems that Kṛṣṇa is doing nothing, he is indeed actively revealing “the hidden structure of *dharma*,” which is always rooted in *ātman*. What Kṛṣṇa exemplifies is how *ātma-dharma* is difficult to grasp. This difficulty permeates the discourse of the whole *Mahābhārata*, and is marvelously represented in Duryodhana’s last words, right before his death, when he still finds enough energy to challenge Kṛṣṇa’s understanding of *dharma*. At that moment he reminds Kṛṣṇa that he had studied the *Vedas*; offered *dakṣiṇās* to the priests in accordance to the prescriptions; ruled his subjects in accordance to his *kṣatriya dharma*, and therefore, none could possibly have been more fortunate than himself (MBh 9.60).

Perhaps nowhere in the whole *Mahābhārata* does the tension between traditional gender and caste (*varṇāśrama*) understanding of *dharma*, and Kṛṣṇa’s *ātmic* understanding of *dharma* as dealt with in the *Gītā* become more evident. The clash is between these two ways of seeing the ancient order: *varṇāśrama dharma* and Kṛṣṇa

²⁹⁹ Kṛṣṇa represented also the very last attempt to find a peaceful solution for the conflict between the Kurus and the *Pāṇḍavas*. The fact that Kṛṣṇa as the last peace emissary is not heeded does not make the role unimportant. Advocating a peaceful solution is not to be understood as a sign of weakness or surrender, and does not involve compliance to all of the enemy’s demands (MBh 5.71). The final peace attempt means giving the *Kauravas* a last opportunity to review their biased position. Duryodhana and Dhṛtarāṣṭra, however, stick to their belief that it is possible to buy Duryodhana’s way to the throne, and try to seduce Kṛṣṇa by providing him with some fake hospitality (MBh 5.83-85). Kṛṣṇa, of course, refuses to be bought or bribed, and smartly steps away from the Kaurava’s caste-oriented entrapments. Ritual curtesies stained by selfish interests are not what Kṛṣṇa is looking for. Kṛṣṇa is open only to real hospitality, and for that reason he agrees to stay at the humble house of another Kaurava – the noble Vidura, who best represents among the *Kauravas* what *dharma* is (MBh 5.87-88).

dharma. For what Kṛṣṇa represents is a new understanding of that order which had put the *Kauravas* against the *Pāṇḍavas*. Kṛṣṇa chooses the *Pāṇḍavas* to modernize that practical science which was indeed really old: the essential discipline of purification, or *śuddha dharma*, which could not be anything but the ancient *ātman*-based discipline that sees all activities as ritual activities (BhG 5.10-1).

There is nothing enigmatic about Duryodhana's caste and gender biased position. His speech represents the dramatization of the sociological and metaphysical consequences of being under the influence, not of *ātman* in himself, but of *ahaṃkāra*. Duryodhana refuses to acknowledge whatever contradicts his *ahaṃkāric* demands. He stubbornly states that he had successfully avoided falling under Kṛṣṇa's influence (MBh 9.64). His personal vision or *śraddhā*, if any, when compared with that of Arjuna, only reveals his cold and stony heart, where there is no place for *ātmic* devotion of any kind.

Duryodhana represents the dead letter of tradition. Duryodhana's activities are mundane, rather than truly ritualistic and sacred. He does not consider properly why things are the way they are. He only wants things to be arranged so that they will favour his selfish goals. As a consequence, his actions are guided not by the sacred ideals of *lokasaṃgraha*. They are rather his own efforts (*puruṣakāras*) that are pre-determined (*niyati*) by those situations presented to him by destiny (*daiva*) in the course of time (*kāla*) from which he thinks he can profit. His outer struggles to succeed in the material world make him a perfect role model antagonist for the protagonist Arjuna, chosen by Kṛṣṇa to experience his highest *ātman*.

Differently from the *Kauravas*, the *Pāṇḍavas* in general are more keen to see their own fate in the larger context where all beings appear somehow vulnerable to certain bad and unpredictable events, which should be understood as opportunities for mastering oneself. Yudhiṣṭira, for instance, after the dice match, accepts his destiny without blaming *dharma*, and without considering the option of stepping out of its realm. He understands that *dharma* is what provides his every action with the character of a ritual and sacred action (MBh 3.32). Ritual action, then, becomes nothing but an action performed in accordance to *dharma*, expressing acceptance of both the fact that one is not supposed to control the events of the world, and that every occasion should be seen as a divine opportunity to reflect upon the meaning of *dharma*. For, as Yudhiṣṭira emphasized to Draupadī, it is through such efforts to reflect upon *dharma* that one can understand how human activity frames destiny.

Establishing the sovereignty of *ātman* over *ahaṅkāra* is the only war Kṛṣṇa has ever helped one to fight. For, such a sovereignty where either Viṣṇu or Kāla (BhG 11.30-2) can be understood as incarnated in everyone is the only meaning Kṛṣṇa wants for the idea of restoring *dharma* (MBh 13.11). Such a sovereignty, as explained in the *Gītā*, is born from *saṁnyāsa* and *tyāga* (in accordance to BhG 18.66), when in that strange moment described in the *Gītā*'s chapter 11, *śraddhā* leads one toward the revelations of the divine realm. For, as *Gītā*'s chapter 17 suggests, the virtues involved in overcoming *ahaṅkāric*'s gender and caste views entail a new understanding of the *Vedic* sacrifices

such as those related to Soma and Agni, where the *Vedic* goddess *Śraddhā* used to personify sovereignty and confidence.³⁰⁰

In the *Gītā*, as we have seen, it is *śraddhā* that helps Arjuna to restore his sense of royalty. In the *Mahābhārata* it is Draupadī's *total trust* (*paramapratīṇā*) on Kuntī's truthful word (MBh 1.182, 3) that makes her accept her polyandric marriage as *dharmic*, despite the traditional views of the time (MBh 1.188, 7-9). The *Mahābhārata* describes the contradictory nature of *dharma* as a gender and caste based display of the styles of royalty and the struggle for sovereignty, and the whole dialectics of the *Gītā* is meant to show how the themes of *dharma*, *artha*, *kāma*, and *mokṣa* are articulated through the structure of *ātma-dharma*. Kṛṣṇa's idea of sovereignty links the *Mahābhārata* and the *Gītā*, as he teaches the actors to give oneself in battle for the sake of what comes from the realm of *ātman*. This he explains to Yudhiṣṭira (MBh 5.29, 20) and even to Karṇa, who was tied to the caste status Duryodhana had given to him and blinded by his mother's prejudice (MBh 5.139, 20).

In the *Mahābhārata*, Karṇa fails to restore the real sense of royalty, for he lacks the necessary *śraddhā* to overcome his disabilities. He knows Yudhiṣṭira is a good king, and he is not naïve enough to believe that Duryodhana could be a good king. He even knows that his every move in the battle is also ritualistic in nature (MBh 5.139, 45), but he cannot change sides in that battle, because placing his material dissatisfactions second to the spiritual goal is not something he is looking for. All he wants is to live up to his

³⁰⁰ In the *Taittirīya Saṃhitā* VII, 1, 8, 2, for instance, it is said that the great Ṛṣi Atri had *Śraddhā* for divinity.

personal commitment, something that places his courage on the same plane as that of Duryodhana. His courage is different in nature from the non-personal courage required from Arjuna in the *Gītā*. Karṇa's outer courage is indeed nothing but inner cowardice – a cowardice of the very same kind Arjuna had shown to Kṛṣṇa prior to the battle. Inner cowardice, in a sense, is nothing but the weak resolution of an *aśraddadhāna* who prefers to flee from the real battle inside oneself.

Such an inner battle is so terrible that even the awesome Bhīṣma was able to face it only after having allowed himself to be killed to favour the *Pāṇḍavas*. Bhīṣma's death, then, happens in a very specific situation, where gender plays a decisive role. The gender of Śikhaṇḍin is crucial to Bhīṣma's death and the consequent victory of the *Pāṇḍavas*. That is to say, Bhīṣma kills his residual prejudice by allowing himself to be killed in a confrontation with that ghost which had bothered him all his life. Bhīṣma's final courageous choice is one full of *śraddhā* attuned with Kṛṣṇa's *dharma*. After Bhīṣma's defeat, the other *Kaurava* heroes also have the opportunity to follow suite and overcome their prejudice and perform the battle as a sacred ritual, out of *sattvic śraddhā*. Yet, none of them can match Bhīṣma's example, who from his bed of arrows, is given divine eyes (*cakṣur divyam*) by Kṛṣṇa, so that he was able to watch the aftermath of the war (MBh 12.46-7). For, over and above all, according to Kṛṣṇa, Bhīṣma represents the ancient and still valid (*pramāna*) uttering of the Veda (*vedappravāda*) (MBh 12.54). For, Bhīṣma, as his final words from his bed of arrows acknowledges, Arjuna and Kṛṣṇa are Nara and Nārāyaṇa. After such a statement, out of a miraculous process, he leaves the body and

ascends to heaven (MBh 13.153-4). The cremation of his body, his *śrāddha*, is the very last lesson on ritual activity or *śraddhā* for all of his dynasty.

V.4. The Role of *Śraddhā* in Solving Moral Dilemmas

It is not only in the character of Arjuna that *śraddhā* plays an important role. *Śraddhā* is essential also to understand King Yudhiṣṭira.³⁰¹ Perhaps the role *śraddhā* plays in Arjuna's solving his dilemma will be even clearer, if we describe first how *śraddhā* is essential also to the Dharma King. Yudhiṣṭira hardly feels disheartened for siding with *dharma*, and he is always desiring to know about *dharma*. Even in extreme situations where one cannot recognize *dharma*, Yudhiṣṭira is resilient enough to endure the hardships, in spite of everything else. His character suggests that every moral dilemma presents from a higher viewpoint an agreeable solution, which means that ambiguity is only due to the material framework from where we see things.

Yudhiṣṭira always displays faith or trust in *dharma*, or that which provides sustenance for the universe, even at those moments where *adharma* seems to rule. He holds, for instance, that it would be *dharma* for Draupadī to marry all the five brothers, and is reassured on that by Vyāsa and Kṛṣṇa (MBh 1.180-191). Then, in the course of the battle, even when he shows signs of being disheartened, as for instance when grieving over Gaṭotkaca's death, he still remains willing to hear the words of those, like Vyāsa, who represent *dharma* (MBh 7.158). As a consequence, from his one-pointed focus on

³⁰¹ See Alf Hiltebeitel, *Rethinking the Mahabharata: A Readers' Guide to the Education of the Dharma King* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2001).

dharma, which represents his *yoga*, he gains *divyaṃ cakṣur* (divine eyes), which enables him to understand the postwar consequences, and, out of his *śraddhā*, to endure the *śrāddha* rites of thousands of slain kings (MBh 11.26-7).

Then, in the peace section which follows those *śrāddha* rites, known as *Śāntiparvan*, Nārada and Vyāsa come to Yudhiṣṭira, who is disheartened. Grieving over the many deaths, and failing to find peace, he has decided to renounce his duties toward his kingdom (MBh 12.1). Yet once again he is able to compose himself and reflect on that state of depression due to his guilty feelings (MBh 12.33). He accepts Vyāsa's counsel to perform the horse sacrifice as a way to reconcile *dharma* with the political events, which had made him feel responsible for those deaths. Despite all the weeping women who are blaming Yudhiṣṭira for their family members lost in the war, the elders tell him to find peace in himself (MBh 12.34-8).

According to Vyāsa, all events up to the performance of Bhīṣma's last rites, should be seen as the final steps of Yudhiṣṭira's training for the throne (MBh 13.153). While Bhīṣma lays on his bed of arrows, Yudhiṣṭira had been encouraged by a *Ṛṣi* to repeat the long mantra Bhīṣma had sung (MBh 13.18). Throughout the *Aṅuśāsanaparvan*, Yudhiṣṭira was learning how honorable the dying patriarch was. Bhīṣma, before becoming silent on his bed of arrows (MB 13.152), had explained to his pupil, Yudhiṣṭira, the supreme discipline for the removal of one's faults, and he had given his assent for Yudhiṣṭira to return to Hastināpura as a king. (MBh 13.151). Bhīṣma even

relates to Yudhiṣṭira the episode of Naciketas and Yama, when Yama enables him to see some people who had given away cows to the sacrificer priests (MBh 13.71).

By the beginning of the *Āśvamedhikaparvan*, however, Yudhiṣṭira was showing signs of being discouraged once again. For that reason he is reprimanded by Kṛṣṇa, Vyāsa, and others (MBh 14.2). Once more, the text discusses how difficult it is to purify one's mind, and indicates that the failure to do so appears as a state of confusion (*mūḍha*). Yudhiṣṭira is blamed by Vyāsa for having fallen once again, into the state of an *aśraddadhāna*, even after he had been given the opportunity to hear the entire *mokṣadharmā* (MBh 14.2.18). Once more, in order to achieve the necessary *śraddhā*, Yudhiṣṭira is presented with a number of ritual solutions. Among the possibilities such as the performance of the *Rājasūya* (Royal Consecration), the *Āśvamedha* (Horse Sacrifice), and the *Sarvamedha* (Universal Sacrifice), Vyāsa insists on the performance of the Horse Sacrifice (MBh 14.3). Yudhiṣṭira's final learning, then, is that devotion alone means nothing, for real devotion always comes in the form of *yogic* engagement in ritual activity. And that is why he accepts Vyāsa's advice to perform a ritual and recover from that miserable state of depression.

The ritual he was about to perform was intended to cheer him up so that he could move on with the royal task he was assigned to. The rite had not been assigned for expiatory reasons, and Yudhiṣṭira was not charged as a war criminal. He was not considered guilty of any crime, nor had he been asked to repent from any sin. On the contrary, the ritual he was told to perform was meant to recover his *śraddhā*.

The implication, then, is that Yudhiṣṭira’s situation shows a clear parallel with that of Arjuna in the *Gñā*.³⁰² Furthermore, the display of such *sattvic* good will, or *śraddhā*, is what differentiates Arjuna and Yudhiṣṭira from their brother Karṇa, who stubbornly refuses to move from his *ahaṅkāric* concerns.³⁰³

In the fight scene between Arjuna and Karṇa, *śraddhā* is present in the loving and trusting relation of the pair constituted by Arjuna and his charioteer, Kṛṣṇa;³⁰⁴ whereas, *aśraddhā* is what best represent the relation of Karṇa with his charioteer, Śālyā. In a sense, the killing of Karṇa by Arjuna can be understood in ritual terms, where *śraddhā* is the central determinant. The theological meaning of Karṇa’s death is stated by Kṛṣṇa himself when he identifies Karṇa’s death with that of Vṛtra, the *Rgvedic* demon (MBh 8:91, 4798 of the Calcutta Edition).³⁰⁵

³⁰² Even Kṛṣṇa’s statement to Yudhiṣṭira is worded in a similar way to the one he had made to Arjuna. Kṛṣṇa blames Yudhiṣṭira for being his own worst enemy, incapable of fighting the inner battle (MBh 14.11). Through the performance of the *Āśvamedha* ceremony, Yudhiṣṭira recovers his capacity to adhere to dharma so as to put love in action, with every single deed (MBh 14.70). This is a capacity that the *Gñā* discusses as the interplay of *śraddhā* and *karma yoga*, where one appears as an outcome of the other. *Śraddhā* – or his soul force and zealous disposition to cling to the truth –, helps Yudhiṣṭira to endure the hardships of his mission, just as it had helped Arjuna to endure the hardships of his mission.

³⁰³ As we have seen, Karṇa is unable to change his mind even when faced with evidence that prove him to be wrong. Just before the battle, for instance, Karṇa tells Kṛṣṇa that he would not do anything unpleasant to Duryodhana (MBh 6.41). We have already discussed how Karṇa, due to his anger toward the *Pāṇḍavas* and his loyalty toward Duryodhana, misses at least two opportunities to engage in righteousness – one with the invitation of his mother Kuntī to join the *Pāṇḍavas*, and the other when Kṛṣṇa offers to lead him to the throne.

³⁰⁴ As Vidura explains to Dhṛtarāṣṭra, Arjuna is as dear to Kṛṣṇa as his own life and that Kṛṣṇa will never abandon him (MB 5.85.12).

³⁰⁵ For more details on this passage, see Hildebeitel, who discusses this point thoroughly. He explains that in the *Rg Veda* Viṣṇu is *Indra*’s ally against Vṛtra (1990, 264).

Even when Arjuna and Karṇa both perform their ritual duty, it is Arjuna who does it properly, out of a real sense of duty and full *śraddhā*.³⁰⁶ For, as opposed to Arjuna's method of solving his dilemma, Karṇa had made his choice during a state of anxiety where the whole universe appeared to him as meaningless. Karṇa is a victim of his own material, or human condition, built upon his *ahaṅkāric* feelings of anger about his fate and unknown origin. In this state of unhappiness, he incarnates a permanent state of disillusion toward that which could possibly be permanent. He feels confused about who he truly is. Karṇa sees life only as a place to experience and endure pain. His attitude is life-denying; it is *ātman*-denying. And as a consequence his 'self-affirmation' is nothing but *ahaṅkāra*-affirmation. His 'self-affirmation' means the opposite of freedom; it means to be enslaved by false notions of friendship and loyalty. His compassion is directed toward the wrong objects. He always forgives Duryodhana's misdeeds, but he is incapable of forgiving those with whom he does not share shallow notions of complicity.

Karṇa is driven exclusively by his material *duḥkha* (pain), and as such, he completely loses sight of *ātman* – the source of all *sukha* (happiness) in oneself. That is why he had rejected Kṛṣṇa's offer. He sees no meaning in the *ātmic* reality represented by Kṛṣṇa. He wants a world where his 'snake arrows' can reach any target he chooses to hit. He does not want to bow to a higher order which might control the way things are.

³⁰⁶ Karṇa's ritual action is stained by his preoccupation with personal goals, whereas Arjuna's fighting is less personal, as demonstrated by his confession to Kṛṣṇa that he did not want to fight. This means that Arjuna is constrained to kill Karṇa as a way to perform his necessary ritual action, but without any personal interest to benefit from that action or enjoy its fruits. Hildebeitel, in his analysis of this passage seems to point in this same direction. His analysis of how Śalya destroys Karṇa's energy (1990, 265), points to the centrality of the issue of 'energy' in defining the difference between Arjuna's and Karṇa's activity. The implication seems to be that Arjuna's 'energy' (soul force, *śraddhā*) remains 'pure' (*sattvic*) and determines Karṇa's fall (265-6).

He cannot even face the reality that he is the son of Kuntī. For truly acknowledging this fact would lead him to review his beliefs and ethical values. When a truth becomes too hard to bear, we all tend to look for comfort in the worlds of lies and illusions. That is why Karṇa's character is so fascinating. He represents us all in our cowardice about facing up to the wrong dogmas we have embraced. We feel compassion toward him, because we want life to be compassionate toward our own poor choices. Above all, the truth of our origin, like that of Karṇa, remains an untouchable topic for all eternity. He is really the son of God, as we all are, but we hesitate to acknowledge that. He has somehow fallen, as we all also have. He managed to keep the gates of heaven open to him, as we all expect also to do, yet he remained deaf to the calls of his Father (Sūrya), of Kṛṣṇa, and even of his mother. His contradictory nature, being a son of god and a sinner at the same time, bring us all hope, because we know he will find *mokṣa* someday, and so may we.

Karṇa's fate makes him see reality as the place where meaningless wars take place, and worse, in the logic of predestination, where our struggles do not help to change the final outcome. Karṇa's existential appeal, then, bring us to the crux of the *Mahābhārata*: how is one supposed to deal with reality, after one has contemplated some revelations about its inner structure? Are we ready to move out of Plato's cave to see what Sūrya, the father-sun, has to show us? Karṇa was not. For he lacked the necessary *śraddhā*. And that is why he turned back to his world of shadows, and decided to fight to

the death those who had had some glimpse from the outside of the painful cave of *saṃsāra*.³⁰⁷

Karṇa does understand that gender, caste, and ethnicity do not determine one's value; yet, being blind to *ātman*, which represents the transcendence of gender, caste, and ethnic bias, he allows his judgement to be enslaved by Duryodhana's bias against the pure soul. Karṇa has knowledge of moral values, but he has no determination to face those, like Duryodhana, who sin against those same values. By placing himself in the position of never contradicting Duryodhana, he allowed himself to be equated to him. That was his mistake: He chose never to hear his father Sūrya, his mother Kuntī, or even Kṛṣṇa. Brainwashed by the wicked Duryodhana, he would pay attention only to him, blindly following him and obeying all of his orders as if he were in a state of deep hypnosis.

³⁰⁷ From the *Pāṇḍavas'* viewpoint Karṇa, out of his blind faith, enters into the battle as a fanatic, one who wishes to defend the evil Duryodhana, and is determined to obey his command at any price. However, from the Kaurava *ahaṅkāric* viewpoint no one could ever have displayed higher courage in battle than Karṇa himself. In other words, Karṇa gets from the *Kauravas* the acknowledgment he needed in order to legitimate his deeds. Such is the nature of Karṇa's choice, which finally leads him to falsely believe that he could, against all odds, defeat Arjuna. The *Mahābhārata's* author seems to use Karṇa to show us that 'for everything there is a season', and that for everyone the day to be harvested as a mature fruit will come. Karṇa's blind faith in his loyalty, somehow also reveals the seeds of the higher types of virtues we all are destined to find in ourselves. For, as Kṛṣṇa had explained to Arjuna, we all make of ourselves what we are in accordance to our *śraddhā* (BhG 17.2-3). Even if we cannot say that Karṇa's *śraddhā* is *sattvic*, one can say that he does display a lower type of *śraddhā*, which takes the form of mere 'faith' in his loyalty.

VI. CONCLUSION

I have shown that the term *śraddhā* means ‘zeal, soul force, or religious enthusiasm’ in the *Gītā*, and that *śraddhā* is what leads Arjuna to accept engagement in the war as the solution for his moral dilemma. I have also discussed some theological implications of this view and considered how *śraddhā* relates to other key concepts, like *saṃnyāsa* and *bhakti* and so on. *Śraddhā*, as we have interpreted it, links the *Gītā* to the *Mahābhārata*, and reveals the centrality of *dharma* in both texts. Next, I establish the *ātma-yoga-mārga*, which expresses my thesis on *śraddhā*, and shows how *śraddhā* is made manifest through a person’s heart.

VI.1. *Ātma-Yoga Mārga: the Gītā in the Light of Śraddhā*

Like Gandhi, Aurobindo, and the Transcendentalists, I also understand the *Gītā* as a theologically coherent text. My reading, therefore, is similar to theirs. While they simply assign unity to the text, I propose to translate *śraddhā* as ‘zealous soul force’ or ‘religious enthusiasm’, and place *śraddhā* as the candidate for explaining the theological unity.³⁰⁸

³⁰⁸ Gandhi argued that the text of the *Gītā* provided him with the know-how to develop his ‘practical wisdom’ – a statement which echoes the text itself, as shown in BhG 18.71. Gandhi failed, however, to point out where in the text one could find a discussion which resembled what he defined as *satyāgraha*. It has been my contention that the soul force and loving action that Gandhi associates with the term *satyāgraha* is represented in the text of the *Gītā* through the term *śraddhā*, which he learnt with the meaning of ‘faith’. For, the *Gītā* seems to place *śraddhā* as a foundational attitude or experience that is crucial no matter one’s religious faith. BhG 7.21, BhG 7.22, and BhG 9.23, which we have already exegeted, show this point.

Because *śraddhā* is foundational to different religious practices, even those who translate *śraddhā* as faith are not completely comfortable with their choice. Rao, for instance, starts his investigation on *śraddhā* in the *Gṝh̄* by warning us of the difficulties of using the word ‘faith’ to translate *śraddhā*: “The usage of the Sanskrit term *śraddhā* in the *Bhavavadgṝh̄* and the Western conception of ‘faith’ present close parallels in certain respects; but there are also certain fundamental differences which are enormously important. These differences are altogether missed by rendering *śraddhā* by the word ‘faith’ without qualification” (1971, 125). In the Foreword to Rao’s study D. B. Harned already laid out the reasons why ‘faith’ was not a good translation:

It [*śraddhā*] designates not a creed but what lies beyond every creed: it does not define a “religion” but tells of what might be more important, the different paths that men can follow within a single tradition and remain *homines religiosi* still. *Śraddhā* has volitional, emotional and intellectual elements, personal and impersonal connotations, ascetic and acquisitive implications, ritual and mystical aspects. Despite the temptation to equate it with what the Christians describe as “faith”, such translation obscures and diminishes the multifoliate and yet distinctive genius of the tradition that, more than any other in the world, properly deserves the label “catholic.” (1971, ix-x)

Harned here almost anticipates what we have argued, except that he does not draw out all the theological implications of his insight. Unlike Harned Rao himself tended to carelessly equate ‘faith’ and ‘*śraddhā*’ in the *Gṝh̄* largely because he relied on Louis Renou’s theory that religious terminology is almost completely transformed between the *Veda* and the Epic periods.

As we have shown in Chapter Two, there is certainly room for seeing a continuity of meaning from one period to the other in the use of the term *śraddhā*. The *Gṝh̄* fills out the earlier thought about *śraddhā* when it defines it as born from a latent human

disposition (*svabhāva*), and argues that humans are nothing but *triguṇic* embodiments of this *śraddhā* (BhG 17.2-3). Furthermore, *śraddhā* appears already associated with *ātmic* ontology at least since the early *Upaniṣads*. This means that the understanding of ritual action in a context where action becomes non-action, as discussed in the *Gītā*, is not something strange to the previous period. On the contrary, the *Upaniṣads* in general represent this understanding of sacrifice as self-sacrifice, with the concrete instances of the *Vedic* ritual sacrifice being the media to display *śraddhā*, which appears, then, as the very essence of sacrifice in any form.

The *Gītā* redefines the traditional negative meaning of the term *saṁnyāsa* (renunciation), by presenting it with an entirely new and positive aspect. The *Gītā*'s view on *saṁnyāsa* is anything but negative. Arjuna's *saṁnyāsa* is not the negative refusal to fight, but the positive life-enriching determination to both fulfil his duties and approach the highest goals. As such, it is beyond any kind of sectarianism, which can be amply demonstrated through its influence and acceptance as an authoritative Scripture³⁰⁹ by different religious movements. That is to say, *saṁnyāsa* (renouncing) and *tyāga* (relinquishment) in the *Gītā* are the terms used by Kṛṣṇa as a means of teaching Arjuna how to achieve success in this inner battle of the soul and conquer himself thus leading others to salvation, while at the same time approaching salvation himself. Action

³⁰⁹ Even its colophon as the *Bhavavadgītā Upaniṣad* suggests the thesis that the *Gītā* is to be placed at the same level of importance as the *Upaniṣads*. The colophon, which describes the *Gītā* as an *Upaniṣad*, however, is probably much later than the text. It does not appear in the *Mahābhārata*; it appears only in the editions of the text of the *Gītā* alone, at the end of each chapter. It says: *ity śrīmad bhavavadgītāsūpaniṣatsū brahmavidyāyām yogasāstre*. That is to say, the knowledge of *Brahman* as well as the *yogic* discipline which leads one toward *Brahman*, and which are the purports of the *Upaniṣads*, are also present in the *Gītā*.

(*karma*), therefore, is to be undertaken as a ritual sacrifice (*yajña*) where *Brahman* is the offering (*arpaṇa*) and the oblation (*havis*), poured out (*huta*) by *Brahman* and into the fire (*agni*) of *Brahman*. It is with this sacrifice, which is kindled by the knowledge (*jñānadīpita*) that allows one to see all beings in *ātman* (in oneself and also in him, Kṛṣṇa), that one is fulfilled with *śraddhā* and attains supreme peace (BhG 4.22-39). Such a ritualistic interpretation of the *Gītā*, where one is supposed to transcend the pairs of opposites born from the qualities (*guṇas*) of matter (*prakṛti*), and remain indifferent to success and failure, is what explains why Arjuna decides to fight – which is the the core issue in the *Gītā*.

We are now in a position to conclude the larger picture, and explain why, despite the two hundred years of scholarship on the *Gītā*, the centrality of *śraddhā* had not been discussed before. For, the understanding of *śraddhā* which arises from a couple of crucial verses of the *Gītā* impact us all in a truly universal religious sense, as the following sections will show next.

VI.2. *Pratijñā*, or the hypotheses to be proved

I have argued that the concept of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* plays a central role in the process of Arjuna's transformation from an inactive to an active person. I have also argued that *śraddhā* is more central in the argument than *bhakti* (devotion, longing, faith), and represents the immediate cause that moves Arjuna to fight. Furthermore, I have argued that when translated as 'zealous soul force or religious enthusiasm', *śraddhā*

explains Arjuna’s final choice to engage in *dharmayuddha* – a fact which reveals the *Gītā*’s theology as the synthesis of the *Vedic* and *Upaniṣadic* periods.

Orientalists who insist on working along the lines of the ‘Documentary hypothesis’ are all wrong in their evaluation of the *Gītā*. In my view, I find that the *Gītā* does present semantic consistency, as Indians who have studied the text with *śraddhā* have always assumed. It seemed, in fact, that this could be easily shown, once one does not assume as a dogma, or *a priori*, that parts of the *Gītā* center on theistic devotion.

Western Sanskritists failed to find agreement on how to read this text precisely because their method more or less forbids them to take a foreign text as a Scripture in the proper sense of the term. The consequence is that they had to disregard those, like Gandhi, who, not only took that approach toward the text, but also dared to compare it in ethical terms with Western equivalents such as those of the Sermon on the Mount. Gandhi’s intuitive method was based on an allegorical sense of Arjuna’s life, but it was also experimentally worked out through his own dedication to a life of transcultural *orthopraxis*, strictly understood as terms of *niṣkāmakarmayoga*.

VI.3. *Hetu*, or the logical arguments

I have discussed how the *Gītā* shows Arjuna’s shift from an initial state where he appears as a devotee (*bhakta*) without *śraddhā*, to a final state where he appears as a devotee filled with *śraddhā*. Furthermore I have shown that scholars have pointed out that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* are different. We have seen that it is not by coincidence that

between the first and the last occurrences (BhG 3.31 and 18.71) of the term *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* Arjuna is shown changing from his initial whinning and ill-will into an attitude of joy and a willingness to stand firm against everything that is *adharmā*. Kṛṣṇa's *niṣkāmakarma* thesis is that if the suffering of Arjuna ends the suffering of the kingdom, then Arjuna, who has compassion for the subjects of the kingdom, should cause that suffering and do so with joy.³¹⁰ For, as Kṛṣṇa had also argued, if on the one side all those who suffer in the world do so because of their *ahaṅkāric* desire for their own happiness, on the other side all those truly happy in the world are so because of their *ātmic* desire for the happiness of others.³¹¹

Orthopraxis, understood as *niṣkāmakarmayoga* and considered as the result of one being motivated and full of religious enthusiasm (*sattvic śraddhā*), is presented in the *Gītā* as a way to end suffering – both one's own and that of the others. There must be a continuous search for *orthopraxis* or right action at every single moment. It is something that must be constantly redefined in the light and authority of *ātman*. For, as the context of the *Mahābhārata* shows with so many examples, concrete instances that at one time may be said to represent *dharma*, in a different cultural environment may be said to represent the opposite, *adharmā*. The subtle difficulty this subjectivity entails is set out in the *Gītā* through Arjuna's honest process of doubt.

The fact that Arjuna was religiously free to address all his doubts (*saṁśaya*) concerning what would constitute *dharma* in his particular situation represented the key

³¹⁰ A similar thesis is present in Śāntideva, in the passage *Bodhicaryāvatāra* 8.105.

³¹¹ A similar thesis is present in Śāntideva, in the passage *Bodhicaryāvatāra* 8.129.

to his recovering of *śraddhā*. For, as Kṛṣṇa reminds him, only a fool would believe to be wise enough to always know *a priori* the best course of action to take. For, the wise one is he who is always cautious,³¹² and understands that certainty only arises in *sattvic śraddhā*. For it is only when one’s heart expands and bathes oneself in divine love that one knows one is under the guidance of *ātman*.³¹³ According to Kṛṣṇa, when this process happens in oneself, one becomes wise and learns to see “nonaction in action and action in nonaction.” For, when the heart motivates one’s actions, one rests in *ātman* possessed of *sattvic śraddhā*, acting for the sake of all religious paths and different cultural truths as if not acting. Such is the meaning of the universal *śraddhā*, found in all religious paths, and in all worth-doing activities.³¹⁴

The *Gṝā*, then, represents a Scripture on *ātman*. It proposes *mokṣa* as the capacity to free oneself (through *ātman*) from *saṃsāra* and its constraints (including the blind reliance on Scriptures themselves, since they are also by-products of *saṃsāra*).³¹⁵ It is only in this sense, then, that the text of the *Gṝā* can be seen as a unified and mystical text, capable of revealing its theological beauty and coherence. This concrete feeling in oneself of *śraddhā* is what legitimates the translation of the term as ‘zeal’, ‘soul force’,

³¹² “The fool doth think he is wise, but the wise man knows himself to be a fool.” William Shakespeare

³¹³ We find a similar statement in St. Jean-Baptiste-Marie Vianney’s *Catechism on The Holy Spirit*: “When we have the Holy Spirit, the heart expands; it bathes itself in divine love.

³¹⁴ *Śraddhā*, then, being universal, works nicely in the *Gṝā* – a text which intends to be an amalgam of the *Vedas*, and the *Upaniṣads*. For, *śraddhā* is that which provides the amalgam of the many and different *ārya* and *anārya* theories and models of *doxas*. Considered by some to be *hetero-* or *ortho-* *doxas*, if they represent that which is described in the *Gṝā* as the experience of anyone who listens to the divine song of the universal reality known as *ātman* they experience *śraddhā*. It does not matter which name one chooses to designate this experience (or to negate it, as the Buddhists do); or which kind of symbolism one’s intuition uses to represent the transcendental reality it points to.

³¹⁵ As, we have seen, Aldous Huxley touched on this point when he argued that religion and philosophy are part of the same human realm. For in his view life becomes a poor imitation when the higher forms of humanism give place to simple scriptural creeds.

and ‘religious enthusiasm’, since it captures the joy which is triggered by the awareness of ‘being inhabited by God’. Furthermore, ‘soul force and religious enthusiasm’ make better sense of the religious attitude which covers so many different moments, from the *Vedic* to the Epic period, which are expressed through concepts, such as, *ṛta* (cosmic law), *vrata* (solemn vow) *yajñā* (act of worship or sacrifice), *tapas* (the heat of religious austerity), and even the funeral rites, *śrāddha*.

We have seen how *śraddhā* is deified and addressed as deity in the *Ṛgveda*, and we have also seen how in the funeral rites or *śrāddha* one finds *śraddhā*. The importance of death in ritual terms is clear in each of the different periods, with the relation of *śraddhā* and *śrāddha* particularly explored in the *Mahābhārata* with its different *parvans* celebrating commanders deaths.³¹⁶

With *śraddhā* being the essential component of the *śrāddha* rites it is no wonder that the *Mahābhārata* relates *śrāddha* to *śraddhā* and to the doctrine of *karma* and *punarjanma*. Each death of a family member represents in the *Mahābhārata* an occasion for discussing *dharma*, and for bringing the theological link of *śrāddha* and *śraddhā* to the attention of the reader. Ancestor-worship is for the sake of the memory of the deceased ancestors, but it also allows the worshipper to reach into the beyond with *agape* love. In this sense, *śraddhā* in the *Mahābhārata* is the receptacle of truth. That is also why *śraddhā* is said to constitute the essence of *dharma*. For, as we have seen, where

³¹⁶ In the *Aṅgīśāsanaparvan*, for instance, Yudhiṣṭhira acknowledges that it is through those *śrāddhas* that the *pitṛs* have their desires fulfilled (MBh 13.115). That is to say, those ancient *Vedic* death rituals, including the fire (*Agni*) that burns the deceased, continue in the *Mahābhārata* to trigger ‘fervent’ emotions, and ethical discussions.

there is no *śraddhā*, there is no *dharma*. It was for this reason that in a visionary way Urqhart saw the *śrāddha* rites as a universal which stands beyond the scope of any particular race or creed, and in his words represents the starting point of history, metaphysics, and other inquiries on the mysteries of life and love. His conclusion was that the rites of *śrāddha*, being concrete, open up their equivalent universal, or abstract, idea of *śraddhā*.

A block of wood taken from the *Ficus Religiosa* is used for kindling (*araṇi*) and is drilled till it flames in the sacred funeral rites. As it ignites emotional stimuli they create a righteous path. *Śrāddha* in this sense provides the ritual foundations of religion or *śraddhā*. That is how the allegory of the ritual fire places one in relation to the social and cosmic order.

In the case of the *Gṛ̥ā*, Kṛ̥ṣṇa's teaching on *āma-yoga* represents this igneous link up, and redefines the previous understanding of *pravṛ̥tti* and *nivṛ̥tti* in such a way that the magical rituals of the outer world become the inward attitude of *niṣkāma* (non-desire). Agni, the personal deity – or the fire, the sun and the light coming from the sun, the heat that rises from the sacrificial fire, the light of knowledge, and so on – together with the symbolism of casting sacrificial materials into the fire, is present also in the *Gṛ̥ā*, through the *yogic* symbolism of the fire and Vivasvat, the primal ancestor.

In the *Gṛ̥ā* Arjuna acknowledges Kṛ̥ṣṇa in the form of Agni, the god of fire, and also of Yama, the god of death. Whatever the concepts of the popular personal gods, even those understood at that time as separated from and opposed to the idea of the

higher and philosophically more sophisticated non-personal *Brahman*,³¹⁷ they all appear harmonized in the *Gṛ̥ā*. Kṛ̥ṣṇa, is nothing but a personal god, as he acknowledges he had had many births before. Yet, as he also acknowledges, he had achieved the status of a true representative of the never-born *Brahman*, the *Puruṣottama*, who is *nirguṇa* in character. The consequence of such a view is the establishment of the *Gṛ̥ā* at the very center of the religious and theological phenomena. For, it explains human activity in terms of the humane interaction (of Arjuna) with the transcendent (*ātman*) through the divine (Kṛ̥ṣṇa).

VI.4. *Udāharaṇa*, or some concrete examples

I have provided examples that explain how the term *śraddhā* evolved from the *Vedic* to the Epic periods. Its continuity of meaning between the different periods is made especially evident through the link of *śraddhā* with the rites of *śrāddha*. In the *Ṛgvedic* occurrences of the term, *śraddhā* already had the meaning of ‘enthusiasm and trust’ (*Ṛg Veda* VIII, 1, 31 and I, 108, 6), ‘being loyally devoted at heart’ (*Ṛg Veda* II, 26, 3), ‘confidence’ (*Ṛg Veda* VII, 6, 3), ‘enthusiastic engagement’ (*Ṛg Veda* IX, 113,4), and so on.³¹⁸ In the *Ṛg Veda* *śraddhā* is also related to an attitude of trust in the sense of

³¹⁷ Kṛ̥ṣṇa stresses he is Viṣṇu among the many sons of Āditi (BhG 10.21), but he also associates the entire rite of fire with the eternal and non-personal *Brahman* (BhG 4.24-7). For, the worship is *Brahman*; the fire in which the action is performed is *Brahman*, and so, the worshipper himself becomes *Brahman*. This idea is not strange to the *Upaniṣads*, where, as we have already seen, those who worship with *śraddhā* are said to merge into the flame, moving northwards towards *Brahman* (ChU. 5.10 1-2 = BU. 6.2.14).

³¹⁸ Many *Ṛg Vedic* occurrences show how being endowed with *śraddhā* was crucial for the performance of ritual activity (*yajña*). Köhler even argued the impossibility of *yajña* or sacrifice existing in the absence of *śraddhā*. For, when the *Yajamāna* or sacrificer is not himself fulfilled with *śraddhā* the hymns and rituals

self-confidence (*R̥g Veda* I, 103, 3 and I, 104, 6). The personification of this force of the heart becomes even stronger when *śraddhā* becomes the goddess *Śraddhā* (*R̥g Veda* X, 151). The sentiment of conviction in the performance of any deed, personified as a deity, is said to reside in the heart of every living being, and serves as an innate quality which functions as a symbol of illumination and revealer of truth. *Śraddhā* is the daughter of Sūrya, the sun, and she is said to bring the state of *ānanda* or bliss.

As an ‘asceticism of the soul’, *śraddhā* is closely related to *tapas* (fervor, ardor), representing an ‘enthusiastic engagement and will power of the heart’ that compels one to sacrifice oneself for the sake of *dharma* and of the divine. As such, *śraddhā* is what prepares one for any heroic deed. For, when one is possessed by *śraddhā* one’s whole being is invested in the performance of the sacrificial act. This fact was already made clear by a whole tradition of scholarship on the pre-*Gṛ̥ā* occurrences of the term *śraddhā*. What I have done is to show that the *Vedic* concept of *śraddhā* keeps much of its meaning in the *Gṛ̥ā*.

Having removed the veils of prejudice which had overshadowed the importance of *śraddhā* in the *Gṛ̥ā* by translating it as ‘faith’, we were able to freshly re-evaluate all the occurrences of the term as they appear in the text. Once we were able to see that *śraddhā* could be dealt with as the idea of trust and confidence in one’s own *ātmic* inclinations, it became easy to apprehend its centrality in the text itself. For, in the *Gṛ̥ā* *śraddhā* seemed to mean mostly a kind of vigorous disposition of the soul to give of

that the priest directs to him become meaningless. This means that the attitude of *śraddhā* is more powerful than the speech and the sacrifice themselves.

itself. The task, then, became to verify if a sense of *śraddhā* as ‘a desire to perform holy work’ or ‘the willingness to sacrifice’ would work into the plot of the *Gṛh̄ā*. For it would be only in this sense of ‘a cordial desire to sacrifice and to give’, and not of ‘dogmatic faith’, that *śraddhā* could become a candidate to explain Arjuna’s final decision to fight.³¹⁹

Hara’s main conclusion is that *śraddhā* is a ‘more fundamental principle’, and I agree with that, even though I do not place *bhakti* as a special sub-set of *śraddhā*, as he suggested. I do not really think *śraddhā* can be said to be ‘a grace accorded by God’, as *bhakti* has been taken to be. Having proved that *śraddhā* and *bhakti* are different in the *Gṛh̄ā*, therefore, also implies that the personal deity Kṛṣṇa and the non-personal *ātman* are quite different. The conception of *śraddhā* as *āstikya-buddhi* – a Vedic ritualistic state of mind, is totally different from a later theistic *bhakti*. The understanding of *śraddhā* in the *Gṛh̄ā* as *āstikya-buddhi* implies that whatever the *śraddhāka* does, he does it as an offering for the benefit of the whole world (including oneself); he is entering the sphere of *ātman*.

Smith’s view of *śraddhā* as *āstikya buddhi* makes it an orientation of yes-ness, an ‘awakeness to transcendence’ that belongs to *buddhi*, the higher visionary self or the

³¹⁹ The etymology of *śrad-dhā* suggested the general meaning of ‘to place one’s heart on’, but that need not to be taken to mean in the devotional sense of *bhakti*. For, as we have seen, Das Gupta’s conclusion was that the meaning of *śraddhā* in the Vedic *Saṃhitās* cannot be said to be very close to that of *bhakti*. We have also seen Minoru Hara’s conclusion that in the *Gṛh̄ā bhakti* might be seen as related to dependence on a theistic god, this is not the case with *śraddhā*. In his view it preserves a more traditional concept of religion, quite independent of theism. As Das Gupta sees it, *bhakti* has a personal connotation and implies a human relation, whereas *śraddhā* is a more impersonal and neutral principle, resulting from a ritual context. That is to say, the contrast between the experiential concepts of *śraddhā* and *bhakti* actually corresponds to the contrast between what one believes the terms *ātman* and Kṛṣṇa designate as objects. Those who propose *śraddhā* as a synonym of *bhakti* could only do so if they held the complete identity of *ātman* and Kṛṣṇa.

‘heart’, and not to *manas* or the rational mind. *Manas* is the category responsible for the state of doctrinal assent or ‘believing’, and therefore it relates to *bhakti*, not *śraddhā*. The equating of *bhakti* and *śraddhā*, then, would never be proper. *Bhakti* in this sense is a form of faith, but *śraddhā* is not. Even when Smith accepts the statement that ‘*śraddhā* is faith’, he does not accept the reverse that ‘faith is *śraddhā*’. In other words, as anyone can see, ‘zeal’, ‘soul force’, and ‘enthusiasm’ work better than ‘faith’ when translating *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* because these translations work both ways, ‘zealous and enthusiastic soul force’ means *śraddhā* and *śraddhā* means ‘zealous and enthusiastic soul force’.³²⁰

Gandhi’s ‘allegorical’ method linked the Arjuna story with his own experiments. Gandhi’s *satyāgraha* (or *śraddhā*) represents his intuitive method, but he based it in the *Gītā* which he took to be a consistent scriptural treatise, whose main topic was the method he was learning to apply. Through his reading he believed he came to understand a way to decide on how to perform any deed. For, once one has *śraddhā*, one is ready to undertake with confidence that course of action one believes to best represent what is truth (*satyam*) and in accordance to *dharma*. For, *dharma* is never an *a priori* as moral commandments want to be. On the contrary, as demonstrated in the *Gītā* and exemplified

³²⁰ The exegesis of the twenty-one occurrences of the term *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* provides numerous examples of the different roles of *manas* and *buddhi* in the experience involved. The mediation between reason and heart that the *śraddhāka* is compelled to undertake has been consistently explained by a tradition of Indian scholars and commentators descending from Śāṅkara and Rāmānuja. What we now divide into the two different categories of philosophy and religion, were in the *Gītā* a bold synthesis which was the source of intuitions in general. It is *śraddhā* which gives us enough certainty about our intuitions in order to lead us into action. The *Gītā*, then, names *yoga* as the science of the intuitive (*ātmic*) mastering of how to function in this world. It is this intuitive capacity that leads one to decide about the best course of action to undertake at every moment. Beyond the fact that the *Gītā* can be seen as a source of *śraddhā*, representing an *ātmic* (intuitive) treatise on the nature and role of *ātman* (intuition), it also unfolds ethical and philosophical issues. For, it is precisely this inner intuitive certainty, which is described allegorically that is visible as *śraddhā*. It is the subjective universality of this link between *ātman* and *prakṛti* (non-*ātman*), which makes of human activity an opportunity to go beyond the humane realm.

by Gandhi, *dharma* is to be approached in terms of “experiments with truth,” where *śraddhā* works as a certificate of methodological accuracy.³²¹

The real *saṁnyāsīn* is the yogin who ritually performs all his actions, without attachment to their fruits. Real *saṁnyāsa* is the display of a mastery over actions; it is *yoga*. One raises oneself by focusing on the *ātman* in oneself alone. *Ātman* is the friend of the seekers, but the enemy of the non-seekers. We have seen how Kṛṣṇa explains the *ātman* (real self) as birthless and imperishable. Those who understand the intuitive process of the divine *ātmic* awakening in the person [which means to subordinate the *ahaṁkāra* personality to *ātman*] also manage to recognize that it functions on practical grounds (BhG 4.5-6). This point is made clear in the exegesis of the verse BhG 6.37, where *śraddhā* cannot in any possible sense be understood as an attitude directed toward the personal god Kṛṣṇa. *Śraddhā* can never be understood as a mere component of *bhakti*, or a theistic adoration toward Kṛṣṇa.

Kṛṣṇa admits that these conceptions are difficult to grasp by those who have not yet cultivated the *ātman*. However, he argues, those who cultivate the *ātman* can overcome all difficulties through practice (*abhyāsa*) and the discipline of detachment from worldly desires (*vairāgya*). One should never avoid righteous activities, even when

³²¹ The allegorical method, then, is the key element for finding in the text what the text demands from the reader: *śraddhā*. It is not a matter of *believing* that the content of the *Gītā* should be about *śraddhā*. It is a matter of possessing some *śraddhā* in order to be able to identify it in the text. For, as the blind can never identify the colour blue, the one who is dispossessed of *śraddhā* can never identify *śraddhā* anywhere. In other words, *śraddhā* is a very particular quality in the sense that it can only be grasped as a concept if one already has it. To understand the importance of *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* one needs to free oneself from the pretentious belief that the content of the *Gītā* corresponds to one’s narrow views. Ideologies which have postulated a special theological content exclusive of an Ur-*Gītā* result from a refusal to read carefully the *Gītā* as we have it now. Otherwise, they also would see the quite obvious point that *śraddhā*, understood as soul-force, explains Arjuna’s final decision to fight.

one cannot completely control oneself through *yoga*. Such is the context around the occurrence of the term *śraddhā* in BhG 6.37, where Kṛṣṇa associates the existence of *śraddhā* with the generic performance of good deeds. *Śraddhā* does not represent, therefore, an act of grace of any Lord. For, one has to earn any grace-like state through *yogic* practice (*abhyāsa*). And that is why Kṛṣṇa ends the chapter asking Arjuna to become such a *yogin*. One established in the inner *ātman* and filled with the highest *śraddhā* is ready for the *yogic* deed.³²²

For, it is not ‘faith’ in the person of Kṛṣṇa that is said to lead to the highest goal (BhG 9.3). It is faith, trust, confidence, religious fervour, soul force, and enthusiasm in regards to what one understands to constitute (*ātma-*) *dharma*. Such a regard or *śraddhā* for the *Ātma-dharma*, is what is partially expressed in the worship of all kinds of different deities. This is what chapter 11 demonstrates, when it shows them as lower forms of the Supreme *ātman*. As Kṛṣṇa explains, those without *śraddhā* cannot understand this secret of *Rājavidyā*. The fate of the *aśraddadhāna* is to be reborn, until he learns to develop the freeing *śraddhā*.³²³

³²² For, all different (religious) paths are subsumed in *ātman*. It is due to the influence of the three *guṇas* of *prakṛti* that the highest (*ātmic*) path is only partially perceived in the many (religious) paths. It is as if the *guṇas* of *prakṛti* protects the higher mysteries of *ātman* from the evildoers (*duṣ-kṛti*) by helping define human pathways.. But when one is willing to become a *mahātmā* (great expression of *ātman*), all one has to do, no matter his previous beliefs, is to develop the good-will to become a good-doer (*su-kṛti*) and to learn to abide in the *ātman*. For, all previous popular religious beliefs, representing the many different people’s material constitutions, work as preliminaries of the final *ātmic* discipline. Different kinds of devotees (*bhakta*) are rewarded in accordance with their *śraddhā*. As one’s *śraddhā* improves, one starts to have intuitive glimpses of the *ātmic* beyond, and from there one learns to move on along the path.

³²³ The secret, therefore, in dealing with all the situations life presents to us, is to surrender to that inner divine *ātman*, from where one can access the ocean of *śraddhā*, as shown by Arjuna in chapter 12. *Śraddhā* appears here in relation to the experience Arjuna has just had with the divine realm. The experience made his devotion one pointed, and the togetherness of the universe he experienced reflected the partially contradictory nature of the manifold conditions of beings. All beings arise from *ātman*, dwell in *ātman*, and

Kṛṣṇa holds *śraddhā* to constitute the characteristic mark of those who are perfect in *yoga* (BhG 12.2), and that is why he says that those endowed with *śraddhā* are dearest to him (BhG 12.20). The philosophical and theological import is made clear in the very first verse of chapter 17, for it implies the possibility of a worship with *śraddhā* being conducted along with the neglect of the Scriptures. If we were to understand *śraddhā* as ‘faith’, of course, this verse would become contradictory. However, once one understands the absolute impossibility of breaking the bond which exists between philosophy and theology, then one is able to see the argument. *Śraddhā* is one’s true will to live up to what one sees as *dharma* in each particular circumstance, including those cases in which Scriptures do not seem to be of much help.

Śraddhā, for instance, compels Arjuna to kill Bhīṣma, even when Scriptures point out that the killing of elders and gurus is a terrible sin. *Śraddhā* provides a higher authority on matters of what really constitutes a sin. For, beyond the narrow and mediated Scriptural tradition, *sattvic śraddhā* raises up an immediate interaction with *ātman* in oneself. The question the *Gītā* wants to answer, then, becomes how to differentiate among different kinds of *śraddhā*. One could argue, for instance, that Arjuna is a fanatic who was brainwashed by the evil Kṛṣṇa and that led him to kill innocents. Such a misinterpretation of the text is easily clarified once one sees the impossibility of designating *śraddhā* as ‘faith in Kṛṣṇa’, as BhG 17.2 makes clear. *Śraddhā* does not have Kṛṣṇa as its object, as we have seen. Given that one is defined in

yet are born partially ignorant (*ajñāna*) of the reality of *ātman* and its excellences (*ātmavibhūti*). Such a one pointed devotion has nothing to do with the kind of devotion Arjuna had shown before. For, now its mark is *śraddhā*.

terms of one's *śraddhā*, *śraddhā* represents then nothing but one's eager setting out upon that path. The next section recapitulates the evidence that demonstrates that Kṛṣṇa is not evil, and that what leads Arjuna to engage in the fight is the fact that he has become endowed with *sattvic śraddhā*.

VI.5. *Upanaya*, or the bringing near to the master-conclusion

I have shown that, being a privileged mode of self-expression, *śraddhā* governs participation and active engagement in life, and represents striving after self-realization. The highest type of *śraddhā* characterizes those who are unattached to the fruits of their actions, and live in terms of cosmic purposes (BhG 17.17). I have also shown the centrality of *śraddhā* as the ruling principle of existence and as the criteria for any ritual performance (BhG 17.28). Because salvation depends essentially on one's *śraddhā*, one recognizes that the salvation path made of *saṁnyāsa* and *tyāga* is a path built upon *śraddhā*.

When Arjuna decides to fight, there is no doubt that he does not take pleasure in that. He does so because his renewed *śraddhā* allows him to act out of an attitude of *saṁnyāsa* (renouncing) and *tyāga* (self-surrender) as redefined in the *Gītā*. If, as stated by Tilak, *saṁnyāsa* refers to the renunciation of *kāmya* (desire-prompted) action and *tyāga* to the abandonment of hope for the fruit of the required *niṣkāma* (desireless) action, or if, as stated by Aurobindo, *saṁnyāsa* is outer renunciation, and *tyāga* is inner renunciation, the fact is that both terms appear in relation to *śraddhā*. Whether we follow

Tilak or Aurobindo, Arjuna's *saṅgyāsa* and *tyāga* reminds us of the trial of Job, where the problem of evil and suffering is addressed in contraposition to the existence of a transcendent principle beyond good and evil. In other words, the kind of endurance Job possesses is what can be expected from someone filled with *śraddhā*. This is the meaning of the *niṣkāmakarmayoga*, which Arjuna is required to perform, and which represents the doing of what goes precisely against Arjuna's attachments. *Niṣkāmakarmayoga*, then, in Arjuna's case, unfolded itself into a philosophy of social and political action (*dharmayuddha*) on the battlefield of righteousness (*dharmakṣetra*). For, even political activism can be seen as being ritualistic in nature and dependent upon one's attitude of *śraddhā*. *Yoga*, or the display of skill in the performance of action, is what defines the *sthitaprajñā*, or the one who is steady in the right or transcendental way. Such a capacity is what the *Gītā* calls *naiṣkarmya siddhi*, carrying out actions through the senses, mind, and reason, without desire (*kāma*), or selfish interest. This is possible through the surrender to *ātman*, which represents the eternal principle behind the phenomenal universe.

Arjuna is taught to reinterpret *dharma* and *svadharma* because they are concepts that obey historical circumstances, and as such, they also should be evaluated under the higher authority of *ātman*. Whatever one's *concrete* historical circumstance, what is to be affirmed is what we *feel* arising from *ātman*. And we *feel* through *śraddhā*. So, when it *felt* right to him, Arjuna engaged in the battle.

Kṛṣṇa's definition of selfishless action is what frames and defines the real meaning of *ahiṃsā*. For, as in Rāmānuja's medical metaphor, killing is not always an act of violence. For, where the killing is beneficial to both the winning and losing sides, there is neither real injury in thought, word nor deed at all. It can be justice that is served through war (*dharmayuddha*). Arjuna understands he should act as just such a physician, one who does not avoid the procedures of a healing surgery out of fear that the killing of the malign tumour could be interpreted as an act of violence. Fighting injustice (*adharma*) by means of 'soul-force' means non-cooperation with evil regimes. It also means an attitude of non-harm (*ahiṃsā*) to the process of being that leads to the eternal soul. Soul-force requires an attitude of love for that soul which is also present in the enemy's body. This attitude of love transforms Arjuna's killing of Bhīṣma into a sacred act.

The understanding of the *Gītā* as a manual on *orthopraxis* allows us to accept that when one is filled with *sattvic śraddhā* one may kill without incurring real sin. Arjuna was brought face to face with that very crucial ethical dilemma whose solution demonstrates one's spiritual stature. For he had to understand that as a necessary consequence of his inner struggle to overcome the enemies within (in the form of desire, ignorance, and egoism), he would bring the outer world back into the control of the powers of *dharma*. Such is the nature of his final urge to struggle for victory in the outer realm for the sake of others. The *Gītā* portrays the world as the theatre where one has to act, full of *śraddhā*, out of an attitude of *saṃnyāsa* and *tyāga*, and for the sake of *lokasaṃgraha*. One may want to name the inner struggle *tyāga* and the outer struggle

saṃnyāsa, but unified they only express the attitude of *niṣkāmakarma*, which is the characteristic mark of those filled with *sattvic śraddhā*.

VI.6. *Nigamana*, or the final summing up

It is my contention that *śraddhā* as dealt with in this thesis, leads to the understanding of *karmayoga*, as a pure and selfishless expression of one's own *ātman* (BhG 18.61). That is to say, Arjuna is led to act as a result of his own *śraddhā* and desire to reach *mokṣa*. This view is in agreement with Rāmānuja's understanding that the dedication of all actions to *Brahman*, together with the disinterestedness in the fruit of those actions, lead one to realize that all actions are indeed non-actions (*naiṣkarmya*).³²⁴ For, renouncing means the renouncing of agency for the sake of becoming an instrument and channel of God's will.

The conclusion is that *śraddhā*, being the element that is common to people of different faiths, represents the main category for the understanding of the theology of the *Gītā*. In the *Gītā śraddhā* is an outcome of standing firm in *ātman*. With the movement from *aśraddhā* to *śraddhā* there is a gradual shift from the sphere of *ahaṅkāra* to that of *ātman*, and it becomes clear that *śraddhā* is an altruistic 'placing of the heart' on

³²⁴ Rāmānuja's treatment of the the 32 verses of the *Gītārtha-saṅgraha* of Yāmuna makes it clear that, as opposed to what Śāṅkara had defended, the *Jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada* is central, and both *jñāna* and *karma* are necessary for the development of *prapatti*. *Prapatti*, or the active exertion of the devotee, becomes, then, the culmination of what is called in *Vedānta* provisional (*viśama*) *jñānakarmasamuccaya-vada*. In Rāmānuja's scheme, the *saṃnyāsa* of the *jñāna yogin* together with the 'renunciation in action' of the *karma yogin* are not independent of the *tyāga* of the *bhakti yogin*. This is made clear in the paradigmatic BhG 18.66, where surrendering oneself integrates *jñāna*, *karma*, and *bhakti* within the path toward *mokṣa*.

righteous action. *Śraddhā* comes about when one puts one's heart in what one knows to be one's real mission (*svadharmā*), a mission (*dharma*) which is to be fulfilled without any selfish interest in the mission's fruits.³²⁵

The centrality and complexity of *dharma* in all its varieties is made evident both in the *Gītā* and in the *Mahābhārata* as a whole. In the *Anu-Gītā*, for instance, Kṛṣṇa blames Arjuna for his residual condition of *aśraddadhāna* because in the course of the war Arjuna fails in part in the discipline of *ātma-dharma*, and fights as a mere *kṣatriya*. Kṛṣṇa's disappointment reveals that it was not the mere fulfilment of the *kṣatriya dharma* that he was expecting from Arjuna. In other words, he expected Arjuna to perform by the *Gītā*'s code, which is *ātma*-based,³²⁶ rather than caste-based.

The *Gītā*'s *ātma-dharma* both fulfills and overcomes *varṇāśrama-dharma*, because submission to *ātman* frees external actions to be performed in their own context, as long as they fulfill the requirements of being free from selfish motives rooted in *ahaṅkāra*. In other words, the *yogic* discipline of *ātman* taught by Kṛṣṇa leads Arjuna to solve the dichotomy between the duties of the warrior in the *pravṛtti* process and those of the disciple seeking spiritual instruction in the *nivṛtti* path. For, both paths are made one through *śraddhā*, which empowers *ātman* in everyone as the *kṣetra-jñā*, the *Īśvara*, or the

³²⁵ We have seen how among *Pāṇḍavas* and *Kauravas* the common dilemma is how to decide about what best represents one's own mission, or *svadharmā*. If in the *Gītā* Arjuna's mission is not stained by any selfish goal, in the *Mahābhārata*, Bhīṣma's mission (*svadharmā*) is stained by his attachment to pleasing his father. Bhīṣma and Karṇa choose personal loyalty as that for which they should fight. Arjuna and his brothers see the placing of social duty over personal matters as that which best represents their *svadharmā*.

³²⁶ In the *Gītā* Arjuna is led by his own *śraddhā* to acknowledge that the Scriptural *dharma* is ephemeral when compared to *ātma-dharma*. That is to say, he acknowledges that *karma mārga* and *jñāna mārga*, *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti*, *saṁnyāsa* and *tyāga*, and so on, are Scriptural concepts that get deeper meanings when reevaluated in the light of *ātman*. The *Gītā* appears, then, as a new and original Scripture, because it provides a solution for the ethical question of what constitutes an *orthopraxis*.

inner intuitive ruler of the world of *prakṛti*. Because in the *Gītā*, spirit and matter, *ātman* and *prakṛti*, are the two aspects of the Godhead, *saṁnyāsa* is redefined in intimate relation to *śraddhā* in terms of the processes of *pravṛtti* and *nivṛtti*. It represents the overcoming of *kāṛpanya doṣa*, or the evil egocentrism, which makes one lose proper sight of the immutable *dharma* due to its ever changing nature as part of the world of *prakṛti*.

Both the *Gītā* and the *Mahābhārata*, then, legitimate through their main characters the view which establishes *śraddhā* as the characteristic mark which defines and ranks everyone. For, besides the complex of philosophical and mythological elements and the ritual theory which frames the *Gītā* in the context of the *Mahābhārata*, one cannot disregard the fact that what explains how the different characters respond differently to the same ethical dilemmas is *śraddhā*. This perspective provides the underlying unity of the two texts. For, since *sanātana dharma* can never be fully turned into written codes, one can only hint as to what constitutes its practice. Facing these dilemmas on what constitutes *dharma* at each particular moment, eventually we come to trust our own ability to identify that voice which represents our *śraddhā*.³²⁷

³²⁷ Many voices speak inside ourselves. Voices that tell us about the moral decisions we all relate to, but which, being contradictory in nature, makes us battle over what constitutes our moral duty. In the *Mahābhārata*, Rṣi Kaṇva, who had brought Śakuntalā up, tells King Bharata that in order to learn how to answer these questions one should overcome egocentrism. In the *Gītā*, Kṛṣṇa tells Arjuna that he should overcome egocentrism, as well. In both cases the novelty of the suggestion is that a spiritual discipline is the solution for a problem of the material realm. In the *Mahābhārata* the context determines whether the act is right or wrong, but in general, the main characters accept the relative truth that the sage's right is more than the teachers'; the father's right is more than the sage's, and the mother's right is more than the father. In the case of Arjuna, he is both the recipient of the traditional values, as discussed in the *Mahābhārata*, and the recipient of Kṛṣṇa's new message, as discussed in the *Gītā*. The voices who speak inside Arjuna, then, are those of tradition and the new.

Differently from Karṇa, whose egocentrism is a measure of his distance from *ātman*, inside Arjuna the real issue is on the meaning of *dharma yuddha*, or the standing for what best represents *dharma*. Karṇa knows the *Kauravas* are wicked and sides with them, anyway. Arjuna does not want to commit the same mistake. His recovery of *śraddhā* reveals *dharma-yuddha*, or the sticking to the truth to be of the very essence of *śraddhā*. For, whereas both the *Kauravas* and the *Pāṇḍavas* would follow the Scriptural prescriptions, the hearts of the *Kauravas* were hardly on their performance for the sake of *lokasaṃgraha*. The *Pāṇḍavas*, on the other side, were truly reflecting the meaning of *dharma yuddha*. That is how Yudhiṣṭira, for instance, talking heart-to-heart with Bhīṣma, gets from him the secret for his ritual killing – a fact which reveals the pair *śraddhā* and *śrāddha* operating in conjunction for the sake of overcoming *adharma* and ending that war. With the *śrāddha* rites working as a healing process where one gets a new opportunity to learn how to develop *śraddhā*, the cycle is closed.

In a sentence, *śraddhā* in the *Gītā* is also a *feeling*. For, it represents both experiential *ātmic* knowledge and that very *feeling* arising from the heart, which triggers intuitive jumpings into what leads towards the Supreme *Ātman*.

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